
Seismic Investigations of Solar and Stellar Magnetic Activity

DISSERTATION

zur
Erlangung des Doktorgrades
der
Fakultät für Mathematik und Physik
der
Albert-Ludwigs-Universität
Freiburg im Breisgau

vorgelegt von

René Kiefer

Freiburg, 2018

Dekan:	Prof. Dr. Gregor Herten
Betreuer:	PD Dr. Markus Roth
Referent:	PD Dr. Markus Roth
Korreferent:	Prof. Dr. Oliver Waldmann
Zweiter Korreferent:	Prof. Dr. Markus Schumacher
Vorsitzender der Prüfungskommission:	Prof. Dr. Gregor Herten
Prüfer Theorie:	Prof. Dr. Thomas Filk
Prüfer Experiment:	Prof. Dr. Bernd von Issendorff
Datum der Disputation:	16. Mai 2018

To Lena.

Contents

Abstract	V
Kurzfassung	VII
Preface	IX

Basic Matters

1 Introduction	3
2 Helio- and Asteroseismology	9
2.1 Introductory Remarks	9
2.2 The Governing Equations	10
2.3 Separation of Variables and Solutions	12
2.4 Asymptotic Theory of Stellar Oscillations	15
2.5 The Modes and Their Properties	16
2.5.1 p Modes	16
2.5.2 g Modes	18
2.5.3 f Modes	20
2.5.4 Mixed Modes	20
2.6 What Do We See?	21
2.6.1 Data from the <i>Kepler</i> Mission	21
2.6.2 Data from the GONG Network	23
2.6.3 Global Seismic Parameters	24
2.7 The Stars from Their Sound	27
2.7.1 Properties and Interior Structure of the Sun	27
2.7.2 Model S and Its Eigenmodes	31
2.8 Asteroseismic Inference of Stellar Structure	31
2.8.1 Asteroseismic Scaling Relations	32
2.9 Where Can We Do Better?	33
3 Solar and Stellar Activity	35
3.1 The Solar Cycle	35
3.1.1 Sunspots	35
3.1.2 The Ups and Downs	37
3.1.3 The Helioseismic Solar Cycle	38
3.2 Stellar Activity Cycles	39
3.2.1 Starspots	42
3.3 Dynamo Models	42
4 Scientific Contributions of This Thesis	47

Developments

5	Stellar Activity and Oscillation Parameters	53
5.1	Introduction	54
5.2	Methodology	55
5.2.1	Data and Computation of Periodograms	55
5.2.2	Measuring the Frequency Shifts	56
5.2.3	Consistency Check with BiSON Data	59
5.2.4	Height of the Mode Envelope	60
5.3	Results	61
5.3.1	Frequency Shifts and Background Parameters	61
5.3.2	Results for the Ensemble	63
5.3.3	KIC 8006161	65
5.3.4	KIC 10644253	68
5.4	Summary and Conclusion	69
6	Mode Parameters from GONG	73
6.1	Data and Methodology	73
6.1.1	Data Sets	73
6.1.2	Azimuthal Averaging and Correction for Spatial Masking	73
6.1.3	Correction for Window Function	75
6.1.4	Correction for Jumps in Sensitivity	76
6.1.5	Proxy for Solar Activity	77
6.2	Temporal Variation of Mode Parameters	77
6.3	Results for Physical Quantities	85
6.4	Summary and Discussion	88
7	Essentials of Perturbation Theory	93
7.1	From Observation to Theory	93
7.2	Basic Ideas of Perturbation Theory	94
7.3	Non-Degenerate Perturbation Theory	96
7.4	Quasi-Degenerate Perturbation Theory	96
7.4.1	The Supermatrix \mathbf{Z}	97
7.5	Frequency Shifts	100
7.6	Perturbation of Eigenfunctions	101
7.7	Review and Preview	101
8	The General Matrix Element for the Direct Effect	103
8.1	Introduction	103
8.2	The Equilibrium Model	105
8.3	Essentials of Quasi-Degenerate Perturbation Theory	107
8.4	The General Matrix Element for a Magnetic Field	109
8.4.1	Modeling the Toroidal Magnetic Field	109
8.4.2	The Matrix Element of a Toroidal Magnetic Field	110
8.5	The Analytical Form of the General Matrix Element	110
8.5.1	Selection Rules	111
8.6	Discussion and Conclusion	111
9	Toroidal Magnetic Fields and Solar Oscillation Frequencies	115
9.1	Introduction	115
9.2	Perturbation Theory	117
9.3	The Indirect Effect	119
9.4	Disturbing the Sun	121
9.5	Discussion	126

9.6 Conclusion	131
--------------------------	-----

Concluding Remarks

10 Summary	135
11 Conclusion	141
12 Outlook	145

Appendix

A Appendices to Chapter 5	151
A.1 Tables of Stellar Parameters	151
A.2 Plots of Frequency Shifts and Variations of the Height of the p-Mode Envelope, Correlation Coefficients of the Background Model Parameters and the Measured Frequency Shifts	153
A.3 Plot of Frequency Shifts as a Function of Height of the p-Mode Envelope for KIC 5184732	165
B Appendices to Chapter 6	167
B.1 Correction for Jumps in Mode Amplitudes	167
B.2 Results for Normalized Mode Parameter Variation	169
B.3 Supplemental Information	171
C Appendices to Chapter 8	175
C.1 The Eulerian Perturbation of the Magnetic Field	175
C.2 Mathematical Supplements	175
C.3 Calculation of the General Matrix Element	176
C.4 The Generalized Spherical Harmonics and Their Properties	178
C.4.1 Elimination of Trigonometric Functions	179
C.5 The Wigner $3j$ Symbol	180
C.6 Integral of the Products of Generalized Spherical Harmonics on the Unit Sphere . .	181
C.7 The Angular Kernels for Toroidal Magnetic Fields	182
D Appendices to Chapter 9	191
D.1 Decomposition of a Real-Valued Vector Field	191
D.2 Expansion of the Lorentz Force	192
D.2.1 The Radial Component	192
D.2.2 The Azimuthal and Colatitudinal Components	193
D.3 The Sensitivity Kernels	194
D.4 Perturbations in Structural Quantities	195
D.5 Additional Figures	197
References	201
Publications and Scientific Contributions	219

Abstract

Context. Understanding the solar activity cycle — its origin, the mechanisms that drive it, and its relation to stellar activity cycles — is an outstanding open issue in solar and stellar astrophysics. Helio- and asteroseismology have developed into powerful tools to gain insight into the interior conditions of the Sun and the stars. The properties of stellar acoustic oscillation eigenmodes (p modes) change with the level of magnetic activity. However, seismic techniques to infer the location and configuration of the magnetic field inside the Sun or the stars from observations are few and far between.

Aims. With this thesis, I contribute to the development of seismic diagnostics and tools with which solar and stellar magnetic activity can be studied. Additionally, I aim to further the seismic exploration of stellar activity cycles as well as the investigation of the change of the parameters of the Sun’s acoustic oscillations over the solar cycle.

Methods and Data. I analyze photometric data of a sample of 24 solar-like stars from the *Kepler* satellite looking for signatures of stellar magnetic activity in the parameters of their acoustic oscillations: the temporal evolution of mode frequencies, the height of the p-mode envelope, as well as granulation time scales are explored. Furthermore, I use data from the ground-based GONG network to examine the solar cycle dependence of the damping widths, amplitudes, as well as several physical quantities of solar p modes as functions of the level of solar activity. Finally, I employ techniques from quasi-degenerate perturbation theory to derive the analytical expression for the coupling strengths of oscillation eigenmodes under the influence of a superposition of zonal toroidal magnetic fields. These coupling strengths are then used to compute the effect of six magnetic field models on p-mode multiplet frequencies.

Results and Conclusions. I detect significant frequency shifts in time for 23 of the 24 investigated solar-like stars. For six of them, I link these shifts to magnetic activity. I also find that the amplitude of the frequency shifts decreases with stellar age and rotation period. These results show that magnetic activity can be routinely observed in the oscillation parameters for solar-like stars. This opens up the possibility of placing the solar activity cycle in the context of other stars by asteroseismology. From my analysis of 22 years of GONG data, I find that the amplitude of the parameter variation changes with mode frequency and harmonic degree. Damping widths are correlated with the level of solar activity, mode energy and mean square velocity are anti-correlated with it. Generally, I can confirm previous measurements of the variation of mode parameters with the solar cycle. Two main results of this thesis are the general matrix elements for a superposition of zonal toroidal fields: first, the general matrix element for the direct effect — that is the coupling of modes conveyed by the magnetic field — and second, the indirect effect — that is the coupling of modes due to a change in the stellar structural quantities due to the introduced perturbation. From forward calculations with these matrix elements, it can be seen that the magnetic field affects the multiplet frequencies in a way that depends on its location and the geometry inside the Sun. By comparison of my theoretical results and observed shifts, I conclude that strong tachocline fields cannot be responsible for the observed frequency shifts of p modes over the solar cycle. I also find that part of the surface effect in helioseismic oscillation frequencies might be attributed to magnetic fields in the outer layers of the Sun.

Kurzfassung

Kontext. Den Aktivitätszyklus der Sonne zu verstehen — seinen Ursprung, die Mechanismen, die ihn antreiben, und seine Beziehung zu Zyklen anderer Sterne — das ist noch immer ein offenes Thema in der Sonnen- und Astrophysik. Helio- und Asteroseismologie haben sich zu mächtigen Instrumenten entwickelt, mit welchen man Erkenntnisse über die Bedingungen im Inneren der Sonne und der Sterne gewinnen kann. Die Eigenschaften der Eigenmoden von akustischen Oszillationen (p Moden) von Sternen ändern sich mit der Stärke der magnetischen Aktivität eines Sterns. Die Methoden zur seismischen Bestimmung der Tiefe und der Konfiguration des Magnetfeldes innerhalb der Sonne oder gar von Sternen sind jedoch nur unzureichend entwickelt.

Ziele. In der vorliegenden Arbeit werden seismische Verfahren und Methoden entwickelt, mit welchen solare und stellare magnetische Aktivität untersucht werden kann. Des Weiteren soll hierin auch die seismische Erkundung von stellaren Aktivitätszyklen und auch die Untersuchung der Veränderung der Parameter der akustischen Oszillationen der Sonne während ihres Zyklus weiterentwickelt werden.

Methoden und Daten. Ich analysiere photometrische Daten von 24 sonnenähnlichen Sternen, welche vom *Kepler* Weltraumteleskop gewonnen wurden. Dabei suche ich nach Signaturen von stellarer magnetischer Aktivität in den Oszillationsparametern. Ich untersuche die zeitliche Entwicklung der Modenfrequenzen, der Amplitude der Einhüllenden der p-Moden, sowie der Zeitskalen der Granulation. Des Weiteren benutze ich Daten vom bodengebundenen GONG Netzwerk, um die Dämpfungsbreiten, die Amplituden, sowie weitere abgeleitete Parameter solarer p Modi in Abhängigkeit der Stärke der Sonnenaktivität zu untersuchen. Schließlich nutze ich Methoden der quasi-entarteten Störungstheorie, um den analytischen Ausdruck für die Kopplungsstärke von Oszillationsmodi unter dem Einfluss der Überlagerung von zonalen toroidalen Magnetfeldern herzuleiten. Diese Kopplungsstärken benutze ich dann, um den Effekt von sechs verschiedenen Magnetfeldmodellen auf die Multipletfrequenzen von p Modi zu berechnen.

Resultate und Fazit. In meiner Analyse der stellaren Daten stelle ich signifikante Frequenzverschiebungen bei 23 der 24 untersuchten Sterne fest. Bei sechs dieser Sterne ist es mir darüber hinaus möglich, diese Verschiebungen in Verbindung mit magnetischer Aktivität zu bringen. Ich finde außerdem, dass die Amplitude der Frequenzverschiebungen mit dem Alter der Sterne und deren Rotationsperiode abnimmt. Diese Resultate zeigen, dass magnetische Aktivität routinemäßig in den Oszillationsparametern von sonnenähnlichen Sternen nachgewiesen werden kann. Dies eröffnet die Möglichkeit, den Sonnenzyklus mit Hilfe asteroseismischer Methoden im Kontext anderer Sterne zu betrachten. Durch meine Analyse von 22 Jahren an GONG Daten stelle ich fest, dass die Amplitude der Parametervariationen von der Modenfrequenz und dem harmonischen Grad abhängt. Die Dämpfungsbreiten der Moden sind korreliert mit der Stärke der Sonnenaktivität, wohingegen die Energie in den Moden und deren mittlere quadratische Geschwindigkeit anti-korreliert damit sind. Dies bestätigt vorherige Messungen der Veränderung der p-Modenparameter über den Sonnenzyklus. Zwei weitere Hauptresultate dieser Arbeit sind die allgemeinen Matrixelemente für die Überlagerung von zonalen toroidalen Magnetfeldkomponenten: zum einen für den direkten Effekt — dieser beschreibt die direkte Kopplung von Oszillationsmodi durch das Magnetfeld — und zum anderen für den indirekten Effekt — dies ist die durch Änderungen der Strukturgrößen des Sterns bedingte Störung von Oszillationsmodi.

In Vorwärtsrechnungen mit Hilfe dieser Matrixelemente finde ich, dass das Magnetfeld die Multipletfrequenzen in Abhängigkeit von dessen Tiefe und geometrischer Beschaffenheit beeinflusst. Durch den Vergleich meiner theoretischen Resultate mit Beobachtungsdaten kann ich zeigen, dass starke Magnetfelder in der solaren Tachocline nicht für die beobachteten Frequenzverschiebungen über den Sonnenzyklus verantwortlich sein können. Des Weiteren finde ich, dass ein Teil des sogenannten Oberflächeneffektes Magnetfeldern in den äußeren Schichten der Sonne zugeschrieben werden kann.

Preface

Motivation The Sun’s activity cycle is a fascinating and very differentiated topic of research. The physical mechanisms that govern solar and stellar activity, and the dynamo that drives the periodic changes of the face of the Sun and the plethora of phenomena these changes encompass — to understand these is at the heart of solar physics and is of major importance for stellar astrophysics. Over the last decades, seismology of the Sun and the stars has emerged as a powerful tool to learn about the interior structure of stars. In this thesis, I advance seismic methods to learn about seismic signatures of solar and stellar magnetic activity and develop novel techniques to infer the subsurface magnetic field in the Sun and stars. I aimed to write a self-consistent thesis, which provides the reader with all the necessary background knowledge to follow my explanations and derivations, even though this thesis is presented in a cumulative way. This led to the following layout.

Outline This thesis is structured in four parts. In the first part — **Basic Matters** — I present information which is fundamental to several aspects of this work. In Chapter 1, a general introduction to the science questions, which drove the research for this thesis, is given. The theory of linear adiabatic stellar oscillations and the properties of the modes of stellar oscillations are presented in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 is dedicated to an overview of the field of solar and stellar magnetic activity, with focus on the solar and stellar cycles, as well as a short overview of the theory of flux transport dynamos. The scientific contributions of this thesis with respect to the topics presented in the first three chapters are briefly outlined in Chapter 4.

In the second part, named **Developments**, the results of this thesis are presented. Three chapters of this part are reprints of publications, which contain the main results of this thesis. I detail them in the next section. Chapter 5 treats the analysis of photometric short cadence *Kepler* time series, with the aim of finding signatures of magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters of solar-like stars. In Chapter 6, I present results on the temporal variation of solar oscillation parameters observed by the GONG network (Global Oscillation Network Group). The essentials of perturbation theory are reviewed in Chapter 7. After that, in Chapter 8, the general matrix element for the direct effect of toroidal magnetic fields is derived. This quantity is important for forward calculations of perturbed solar and stellar eigenfunctions and frequency perturbations. Finally, in Chapter 9, I present my results on forward calculations of the effect of toroidal magnetic fields on solar oscillation frequencies.

I give a summary of my results (Chapter 10), discuss the entailing conclusions (Chapter 11) and give a final outlook (Chapter 12) in the **third part** of this thesis. In the last part — the **Appendix** — I include the appendices of the reprinted papers and add some useful supplementary information and plots to Chapter 6.

Publications Included in This Thesis This thesis is presented as a *cumulative thesis*, as outlined by the Doctoral Degree Regulations for the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics of the

University of Freiburg (Promotionsordnung für die Fakultät für Mathematik und Physik der Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg vom 06.06.2016, §8, Abs. (3)), consisting of the following refereed publications:

(Paper I) René Kiefer, Ariane Schad, Guy Davies, and Markus Roth: “*Stellar magnetic activity and variability of oscillation parameters: An investigation of 24 solar-like stars observed by Kepler.*” [Astronomy & Astrophysics, Volume 598, Article A77, 2017.](#)

(Paper II) René Kiefer, Ariane Schad, and Markus Roth: “*The Direct Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Stellar Oscillations: An Analytical Expression for the General Matrix Element.*” [The Astrophysical Journal, Volume 846, Number 2, Article 162, 2017.](#)

(Paper III) René Kiefer and Markus Roth: “*The Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Solar Oscillations Frequencies.*” [The Astrophysical Journal, Volume 854, Number 1, Article 74, 2018.](#)

These publications are included in Chapter 5, Chapter 8, and Chapter 9. Their accompanying appendices are presented in Appendix A, Appendix C, and Appendix D.

Contributions of the Author to the Included Publications Here, I detail the contributions of me and my coauthors to the publications, which are included in this thesis.

(Paper I) The research leading to the results presented in this paper was largely carried out by me. I wrote the paper, with Ariane Schad substantially contributing to writing Section 5.2.2 and Guy Davies substantially contributing to writing Section 5.2.4. I selected the targets and wrote the code for the measurement of the frequency shifts and the calculation of the correlation coefficients between frequency shifts and mode heights. Guy Davies supplied the mode heights, which he obtained by fitting background profiles to periodograms calculated by me. Ariane Schad made contributions to the development of the resampling approach by which the error bars on the frequency shifts are calculated. Markus Roth supplied general supervision and provided important feedback during the drafting of the paper. I generated all plots and tables presented in this paper. I performed the submission and handled the review process of this paper. Helpful comments which led to an improvement of the paper were given by Ariane Schad, Guy Davies, Markus Roth, our institute’s internal referee for this paper Volkmar Holzwarth, as well as the anonymous referee.

(Paper II) I derived the necessary equations and carried out the calculation of the general matrix element, which is the main result of this publication. Ariane Schad and Markus Roth provided supervision in the development of the theory and the drafting of the paper. I wrote the paper, performed the submission, and handled the review process of this paper. Helpful comments which led to an improvement of the paper were given by Ariane Schad, Markus Roth, our institute’s internal referee for this paper Oskar Steiner, as well as the anonymous referee.

(Paper III) The results presented in this paper were primarily obtained by me. I derived the necessary equations for the calculation of the indirect effect of a superposition of toroidal magnetic fields. I wrote the code for the forward calculations and selected the magnetic field models. I wrote the paper and made all the plots and calculations of this publication. I executed the submission and took care of the review process. Markus Roth provided supervision in the development of the theory and the drafting of the paper. Helpful comments which led to an

improvement of the paper were given by our institute's internal referee for this paper Wolfgang Schmidt as well as the anonymous referee.

Funding The research leading to the results presented in this thesis has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union's Seventh Framework Program (FP/2007-2013)/ERC Grant Agreement no. 307117 (ORIGIN). The research leading to the results presented in Chapter 6 has received funding from the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under Grant Agreement no. 312495 (SOLARNET).

Copyright Notice This work is licensed under the Creative Commons license (CC BY 4.0). This license applies to the entire work, including Chapter 5, and Appendix A. Chapters 8, 9, as well as Appendices C, and D were originally published under the (CC BY 3.0) license. The license of this thesis does not apply to Figures 1.2, 1.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10, 2.11, 2.12, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.5, and 3.7. This material is reproduced here with permission of the respective rights owners. Sources and authors are credited. For reproductions of these figures, the licenses of the respective rights owners apply.

Data Acknowledgements This work includes data collected by the *Kepler* mission. Funding for the *Kepler* mission is provided by the NASA Science Mission Directorate. This research has made use of the SIMBAD database, operated at CDS, Strasbourg, France. This work utilizes data obtained by the Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG) program, managed by the National Solar Observatory, which is operated by AURA, Inc. under a cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation. The data were acquired by instruments operated by the Big Bear Solar Observatory, High Altitude Observatory, Learmonth Solar Observatory, Udaipur Solar Observatory, Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias, and Cerro Tololo Interamerican Observatory.

Personal Acknowledgements To Markus. My gratitude goes to you for supporting me during the last years. You created an environment, where I could pursue my own ideas, encouraged me to do so, and aided me in becoming a scientist. The weekly Sunquaks created an atmosphere where ideas and problems could be exchanged and the group could grow together. It was a pleasure to be part of the group of young, motivated scientists you put together.

To Ariane Schad, who acted as co-supervisor of this thesis for most of the time. Your attention to detail and your clear, scientific way of writing shaped my work over the last years. Thank you for this.

To Prof. von der Lühe and Prof. Berdyugina. I want to thank you for providing young scientist with the possibility to go to summer schools, conferences, and also to participate actively in the development of the Kiepenheuer Institute.

To all people at KIS. The institute has been a really nice place to work and develop over the last years. The administration, the secretariat, and all the other personnel create a very friendly and productive environment to work. Thank you, Tanja, Silvi, Frau Barkowski, Roland, Christiane, Melli, and Bettina for keeping the place running and for the organization of travels.

To Rudi Komm, Frank Hill, and the whole GONG and NSO crews I owe a big thank you for giving me such a warm welcome. I had a really good time in Tucson. I learned a lot and met so

many friendly people. Even though it has been a while, I will live up to my promise and publish those results. First thing on the agenda after finishing this thesis.

To Kolja Glowgowski for calculating the set of solar oscillation eigenfunctions from Solar Model S and for your dedication in giving answers to pretty much every science or programming question I asked.

To all the other colleagues and friends at KIS, who made these past four years so enjoyable: Vigeesh, Irina, Wiebke, Johannes, Christoph, René S., Manu, Morten, Hanna, Rolf, JuanMa, Aneta, Wolfgang, Volkmar, Matthias, and all who I forgot to mention (Sorry about that!).

To the proofreaders of this thesis and the included publications: Volkmar Holzwarth, Vigeesh Gangadharan, Oskar Steiner, Wolfgang Schmidt, Ariane Schad, Vincent Böning, Anne-Marie Broomhall, and Markus Roth. Thank you for the helpful advice and the suggested corrections, additions, and deletions. Sometimes one really can't see the forest for the trees.

To sharing an office. Special thanks go to my long-time office mates and friends Vincent Böning and Sebastian Hoch. For the helpful discussions about science, for the motivation and drive, and the occasional view on life, the universe, and everything. We had fun together and shared the hardships that are part of one's journey as a PhD student.

To teachers. I want to acknowledge my teacher from primary school Herr Kärcher. I remember the awe I felt when you told us that all the stars in the sky are not so different from our own Sun. Who knows, maybe I would not have become an astrophysicist if it wasn't for you. Thank you, Herr Kärcher!

To all my friends, to the members of hopfenbetont., and all the lost companions. Thank you for all the pub quizzes, all the fun, and listening to me when I was babbling about work. Even though I believe that I am in a similar situation as Chandler Bing. No one really knows what I do for a living. ;-)

An meine Eltern. Mama, Papa, euch möchte ich ganz besonders danken. Dafür, dass ihr mich stets ermutigt habt meinen Interessen und Leidenschaften zu folgen. Als sei es gestern gewesen, so erinnere ich mich daran, wie ich mit meinem ersten Teleskop den Kometen Hale-Bopp bestaunt habe. Danke für alles! Und auch an dich Aaron, danke und Heja BVB!

And to Lena, my love. You make me better. Every day.

To our future.

Basic Matters

Introduction

With the seismology of the Sun and the stars, we have at hand appliances which “*can pierce through the outer layers of a star and test the conditions within*” (Eddington 1926). The analysis of a star’s normal modes grants insight into its fundamental properties such as its mass, radius, age, and rotation. In this thesis, I develop methods for the seismic investigation of solar and stellar magnetic activity (hence the title) and I do this by approaching the following questions:

- Can we detect signatures of magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters of stars?
- How does a large-scale magnetic field affect a star’s oscillations?
- Where in the solar interior is the location of the dynamo?

I tackle these questions from different angles: On the one hand, I analyze data from the *Kepler* spacecraft and from the ground-based GONG network to learn about the variation of the properties of acoustic solar and stellar oscillations with a changing level of magnetic activity. On the other hand, I carry out theoretical calculations which yield a formalism that can be used to compute the effect of magnetic fields on stellar oscillations.

Here, I give a brief introduction to the two topics which this thesis is concerned with: the seismology of stars, and solar and stellar magnetic activity. I will dwell on them in more detail in the following chapters.

Sounding the Stars

The Sun and stars oscillate in their normal modes. The Sun is observed to oscillate in millions of these eigenmodes simultaneously. These modes are resonant global or pseudo-global standing acoustic waves – that is to say, the entire stellar body serves as a cavity. The properties of the modes are thus determined by the stellar structure. As these modes penetrate into the stellar interior, their observed properties can be used to infer the conditions within the Sun and the stars (see Chapter 2 for a detailed overview). In stars like the Sun which have an outer convection zone the modes are nominally acoustic. For these acoustic modes, the pressure gradient acts as the dominant restoring force. They are thus called p modes.

In Figure 1.1, a full-disk Dopplergram of the Sun taken by the MDI (Michelson Doppler Imager), which is aboard the SOHO (Solar and Heliospheric Observatory) spacecraft, is shown. Here, darker colors indicate motion towards the observer and brighter colors indicate motion away from the observer. In the left panel, the solar rotation is apparent as a gradient in the observed velocity from the western to the eastern limb with a value of about 2 km s^{-1} . The grainy structure in this panel is made up out of so-called supergranules, which are cells of convective motion with

Figure 1.1: *Left panel:* full-disk Dopplergram from the MDI instrument. *Right panel:* same as left panel but after subtraction of a 45 min average of Dopplergrams to remove the signals of rotation and supergranulation. Figure courtesy of Ariane Schad.

sizes between 20–50 Mm. In the right panel, an average of 45 min of consecutive Dopplergrams is subtracted to remove the signal of the solar rotation and the supergranules. The remaining velocities are a superposition of the Sun’s oscillations. Dopplergrams like this serve as the basis of modern helioseismology. The Dopplergrams can be projected onto the spherical harmonic functions (see Section 2.3 for an explanation for their use). This assigns a harmonic degree l , an azimuthal order m , and a radial order n to each oscillation eigenmode (see Figure 2.1). The frequencies of the individual modes can then be measured from the time series of the respective spherical harmonic coefficients (e.g., Hill et al. 1996). From knowledge about the physics of the modes and the Sun, as well as through comparison of measured and computed mode parameters, conclusions about the actual physical conditions within the Sun can be drawn.

For stars, such analyses are limited to fewer oscillation modes because they cannot be spatially resolved. The oscillations lead to subtle changes in a star’s brightness as a whole. These changes can be detected in high-precision photometric time series, which have become available thanks to space missions *Kepler* (Borucki et al. 2010; Koch et al. 2010) and *CoRoT* (Baglin et al. 2006; Auvergne et al. 2009). This has helped asteroseismology to grow into a powerful tool with which we can learn about the interior structure of stars. In this thesis, data from both resolved ground-based observations as well as space photometry is used.

The Ever-Changing Sun

The Sun’s magnetic field undergoes a cyclic regeneration with a period of approximately eleven years. The physical mechanisms and the exact location of the dynamo that is causing this cyclic regeneration are still a matter of debate (see Chapter 3 for details about the solar and stellar cycles, dynamo theory, and the relevant literature on these topics). So far, the main benchmarks for dynamo simulations are the correct cycle lengths as well as the properties and distribution of active regions over a cycle. Mapping magnetic field concentrations inside the Sun would put

Figure 1.2: The Sun over 20 years as seen by EIT/SOHO instrument in the Fe XV line at 284 \AA . This line samples the lower solar corona. Image: SOHO (ESA & NASA).

important constraints on any dynamo theory. Our best hope to learn about the conditions within the Sun and the stars is through the methods of helio- and asteroseismology. With this thesis, I aim to develop seismic methods to exclude or confirm possible candidates of dynamo simulations and to learn more about the magnetic cycles of stars through asteroseismology.

The most prominent features of the solar activity cycle are sunspots and the associated active regions (see Section 3.1). Figure 1.2 shows a sequence of images of the Sun at intervals of one year. The entire sequence covers the years 1996–2015, which are almost two solar cycles. This time period largely overlaps with that of the data that I will use in Chapter 6 for my investigation of the change of solar p-mode parameters over the solar cycle. The images in Figure 1.2 were taken by the EIT (Extreme ultraviolet Imaging Telescope) instrument, which is aboard the SOHO spacecraft. The Fe XV line at 284 \AA , in which these images are taken, forms in the lower corona of the Sun. It can be seen that the brightness of the corona changes considerably during these 20 years. During times of high magnetic activity, e.g., in 2001, there is a large number of magnetically active regions and sunspots on the Sun. These regions are connected to the bright structures in the corona which distinctly stand out in Figure 1.2.

The phenomena that are caused by the magnetic field on the Sun and are thus connected to the solar cycle are plentiful. The aim of simulations of the solar dynamo is to reproduce the properties of the observed magnetic structures and the temporal evolution of the global solar magnetic field. The result of a three-dimensional Babcock–Leighton solar dynamo simulation by Miesch and Teweldebirhan (2016) is shown in Figure 1.3 (see Section 3.3 for an overview of the ideas of a Babcock–Leighton solar dynamo). The top left panel shows the average radial magnetic

Figure 1.3: Results from a three-dimensional Babcock–Leighton solar dynamo model by [Miesch and Teweldebirhan \(2016\)](#)¹. *Top left panel:* average radial magnetic field strength at the surface as a function of latitude and time. Color table is clipped at ± 100 G. *Bottom left panel:* average azimuthal magnetic field strength at a depth of $0.71 R_{\odot}$ as a function of latitude and time. Color table is clipped at ± 50 kG. *Top right panel:* averaged strength of the radial magnetic field over the north (blue) and south (red) polar regions, for latitudes higher than 85° . Vertical dotted lines in all panels mark the reversals of the polar field in the northern hemisphere (blue) and in the southern hemisphere (red). *Bottom right panel:* same as top right panel but for the azimuthal field of the entire respective hemisphere.

field strength at the surface and the bottom left panel shows the average azimuthal magnetic field strength at a depth of $0.71 R_{\odot}$ as functions of latitude and time. The strength and distribution of the surface magnetic field can be measured from observations. In contrast to this, we have no direct observational information about the subsurface magnetic field distribution in the Sun with which results of dynamo simulation can be excluded or constrained. Some constraints are of course imposed by physical principles as well as the solar structure.

Perturbed Sounds

Helioseismology found that the frequencies of solar p modes are correlated with solar magnetic activity (e.g., [Woodard and Noyes 1985](#); [Libbrecht and Woodard 1990](#); [Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998](#)), whereas mode amplitudes are anti-correlated with it (e.g., [Pallé et al. 1990](#); [Komm et al. 2000b](#); [Broomhall et al. 2015](#)). Activity-related frequency shifts are larger for modes of higher frequency ([Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998](#)) because these modes have their maximum sensitivity to structural changes in the solar interior in shallower layers than modes of low frequency ([Basu et al. 2012](#)). This was recently used by [Salabert et al. \(2015\)](#) to study the change of sub-surface solar activity as a function of time and for different depths.

It has been shown that the frequencies of acoustic oscillations of solar-like stars undergo changes similar to those observed on the Sun. The first time that such changes were reported for a star

¹Reprinted from *Advances in Space Research*, 58, Miesch, M. and Teweldebirhan, K., *A three-dimensional Babcock–Leighton solar dynamo model: Initial results with axisymmetric flows*, 1571-1588, 2016, with permission from Elsevier.

other than the Sun was done by [García et al. \(2010\)](#). They also showed that these changes are correlated with stellar magnetic activity. Gaining insight into the underlying magnetic field causing these changes in stars would supplement the simulation of solar and stellar dynamos greatly.

There has been a number of attempts to measure the magnetic field inside the Sun with helioseismic methods in the past. [Gough and Thompson \(1990\)](#) presented a formalism that is based on perturbation theory. They calculated the eigenfrequency perturbations and splitting coefficients of modes of low harmonic degree of a stellar model with a magnetic field and rotation. [Antia et al. \(2000\)](#) refined the approach of [Gough and Thompson \(1990\)](#) by also including effects from general relativity and second-order effects of rotation. They could limit the strength of a toroidal magnetic field near the Sun's tachocline to 300 kG. [Baldner et al. \(2009\)](#) used this formalism to analyze one solar cycle's worth of MDI data to probe the solar interior for magnetic field concentrations by comparing the calculated splitting coefficients with the observed values. Their results included two very shallow toroidal field distributions and a poloidal field. However, due to the shallowness of the inferred field components, they could not draw conclusions regarding dynamo models, which mostly rely on deeper seated field concentrations (e.g., [Charbonneau 2014](#)). [Dziembowski and Goode \(2005\)](#) analyzed the behavior of centroid multiplet frequencies between the minimum and maximum of cycle 23. They found that the frequency increase can be explained by a less than 2% decrease in the radial component of the turbulent velocity in the convection zone. They explain the p-mode frequency increase with rising levels of activity by the inhibiting effect of the magnetic field on convection.

In this thesis, I analyze solar and stellar seismic data with the aim to understand how exactly the changing magnetic field affects the oscillation parameters (Chapters 5–6). In the theoretical part (Chapters 7–9) I develop a formalism that allows calculating the perturbation of a toroidal magnetic field to solar and stellar p-mode eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies. The approach that I use here is novel in its application to magnetic fields. In this approach, I utilize methods from perturbation theory. The strength of the perturbation that is induced by the magnetic field is quantified in a matrix element, which expresses the coupling of modes. Here, I build on the work of [Lively and Ritzwoller \(1992\)](#), [Roth \(2002\)](#), and [Schad et al. \(2011\)](#) and extend their formalism to toroidal magnetic fields.

In the next two chapters, I will give a more detailed overview of the methods and observational quantities of helio- and asteroseismology as well as the topic of solar and stellar magnetic activity. After that, I will present my findings and the techniques which I developed. These shall help to learn more about the solar interior magnetic field configuration and the relation of the Sun's activity cycle to that of other stars.

Helio- and Asteroseismology: An Overview

2.1 Introductory Remarks

Waves, which travel through an object, can be utilized to learn about the object's composition and properties. For the Earth, for example, traveling waves, which are induced by earthquakes, can be used to map the density stratification down to the core (Fowler 1990; Romanowicz 2008). For the Sun, it was first discovered by Leighton et al. (1962) that velocity fields on the solar surface oscillate with an approximate five-minute period. The field of *helioseismology* was born. Since then, the investigation of the oscillations in, on, and over the Sun by observation, modeling, and inversions has developed into a powerful tool to learn about the solar interior and atmosphere. The accuracy to which the solar structure has been determined is very high. For example, the discrepancy between the sound speed as inferred by helioseismic inversions and standard solar models is of the order of 0.5% (Basu 2016, and references therein). The Sun can now be considered a test-bed for asteroseismic techniques that can be applied in investigations of stars with solar-like oscillations.

Stellar oscillations are generally detected with one of two methods. The first one uses Doppler shifts of spectral lines caused by the oscillatory motion of stellar plasma. Since velocity amplitudes of stellar oscillations are only of the order of cm s^{-1} to m s^{-1} (see, e.g., Kjeldsen and Bedding 1995; Komm et al. 2000b), observational conditions have to be excellent and the instrument has to have high accuracy to detect the Doppler signal in stellar measurements. For the Sun, measurement of Doppler shift is the standard method to observe oscillations and motions on a large range of length scales, from solar rotation down to small-scale convective motion. The second method utilizes luminosity variations caused by stellar oscillations, which can be measured by stellar photometry. Variations in density caused by oscillations slightly change opacity and thereby the energy flux through the material. Due to the huge distance to the stars, a spatial resolution of their surface is not possible. Any detectable luminosity variations can only occur on length scales of the order of stellar radii. The planet-hunting satellite missions *Kepler* (Borucki et al. 2010; Koch et al. 2010) and *CoRoT* (Baglin et al. 2006; Auvergne et al. 2009) detected stellar oscillations this way. The photometry-based detection of stellar oscillations is however limited to the lowest orders due to their disk integrated nature, see Section 2.6. See Harvey (1988) for an overview of the Doppler and photometric methods to detect stellar oscillations.

In this chapter, I first briefly review the equations which govern stellar oscillations, with focus on solar-like oscillations (Sections 2.2–2.3). The Sun and stars similar to it have an outer convective layer. Convection is a source of acoustic noise which can stochastically excite normal modes. The physical conditions of the cavities for acoustic oscillations and other kinds of modes are derived

in Sections 2.4–2.5. I will then introduce global seismic parameters and discuss some results from seismic inference on solar and stellar structure in Section 2.6–2.7. Asteroseismic methods to infer stellar structure and fundamental stellar parameters are briefly reviewed in Section 2.8. Finally, I collect some open issues in helio- and asteroseismology and topics, which this thesis addresses, in Section 2.9.

2.2 The Governing Equations

Solving the perturbed stellar structure equations yields oscillatory solutions, which describe stellar oscillations. I will not reproduce the entire derivation of the stellar oscillation equations here, as it can be found in many sources, e.g., [Unno et al. \(1989\)](#), [Aerts et al. \(2010\)](#), [Roth \(2002\)](#), to name but a few. Throughout this thesis, velocity fields, like rotation and meridional circulation, are neglected. Magnetic fields are also not included in the derivation of the oscillation equations. Hence, any magnetic field in the star is a perturbation to the state for which the solutions of the oscillation equations are found, see Chapters 8 and 9.

Observed solar-like stellar oscillations have small amplitudes compared to the stellar radius. Therefore, one can treat them as small perturbations of the equilibrium state. Stars are in hydrostatic equilibrium, i.e., gravity is balanced by the pressure gradient. The equilibrium state of a star without a magnetic field is thus defined by the equations of stellar structure

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}_0) = 0, \quad (2.1a)$$

$$\rho \frac{d\mathbf{v}_0}{dt} = -\nabla p + \rho \mathbf{g}, \quad (2.1b)$$

$$\nabla^2 \Phi = 4\pi G \rho, \quad (2.1c)$$

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = \frac{\Gamma_1 p}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dt}, \quad (2.1d)$$

which are the continuity equation (Equation (2.1a)), the equation of motion (Equation (2.1b)), the Poisson equation (Equation (2.1c)), and the energy equation in the adiabatic approximation (Equation (2.1d)). The terms which include the velocity field \mathbf{v}_0 are kept here for the purpose of deriving the linear oscillation equations of the star. However, for the cases considered in this thesis $\mathbf{v}_0 = 0$, i.e., the equilibrium star is without any velocity fields. This complete set of partial differential equations describes adiabatic motion of matter with pressure and gravity as the only forces acting on it. For a detailed discussion of stellar structure and evolution, see, e.g., [Prialnik \(2009\)](#), [Kippenhahn et al. \(2012\)](#), or [Iben \(2013\)](#). The assumption of adiabaticity is justified for most of the stellar radius. An inspection of the heating term in the full energy equation, see [Aerts et al. \(2010\)](#), leads to a separation into two important contributions: Nuclear energy production and radiation. The time scales for these two contributions are of the order of the nuclear ($\sim 10^{10}$ yr) and the Kelvin-Helmholtz time scales ($\sim 10^7$ yr, see Chapters 2–4 in [Kippenhahn et al. 2012](#)). The time scale of stellar oscillations is of the order of the dynamical time scale (minutes to hours). Therefore, physical conditions, especially temperature, do not change considerably over many periods of oscillations: the motion occurs adiabatically. However, in near-surface layers the characteristic length scale for radiation becomes large and the assumption of adiabaticity is no longer valid ([Ando and Osaki 1975](#)). A detailed treatment of radiation transfer has to be carried out in these regions in order to improve agreement between theoretically derived and observed oscillation frequencies. Modern stellar oscillation codes take non-adiabaticity into account ([Townsend and Teitler 2013](#)).

There are two reference frames when dealing with motions in a continuum. The *Eulerian* description is fixed to a given point in space, corresponding to a stationary observer. In the *Lagrangian* description, the observer is following the material along its path of motion. When considering temporal derivatives, one has to distinguish between these two descriptions. In the *Lagrangian* picture, the temporal derivative of a physical quantity Q is given by

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla Q, \quad (2.2)$$

where the velocity is given by

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} \quad (2.3)$$

in Lagrangian form. Equation (2.2) is called the *advective* or *substantial* time derivative. The partial derivative $\partial/\partial t$, taken at a fixed point, is called the *local* time derivative.

In the Eulerian picture, a perturbation to a physical quantity Q is introduced through

$$Q(\mathbf{r}, t) = Q_0(\mathbf{r}_0) + Q'(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \quad (2.4)$$

where Q' is a small perturbation at a *fixed* position \mathbf{r}_0 . Henceforth, equilibrium quantities are labeled with a subscript 0. In the Lagrangian frame, the material is moved from \mathbf{r}_0 to $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_0 + \boldsymbol{\xi}$. The displacement vector $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ describes the excursion from the equilibrium position \mathbf{r}_0 . The Lagrangian perturbation of the quantity Q is given by

$$Q(\mathbf{r}, t) = Q_0(\mathbf{r}_0) + \Delta Q(\mathbf{r}, t). \quad (2.5)$$

To first order, the two descriptions are related by

$$\Delta Q(\mathbf{r}, t) = Q'(\mathbf{r}_0, t) + \boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla Q_0(\mathbf{r}_0). \quad (2.6)$$

The velocity introduced by the perturbation, i.e., the temporal change of the displacement vector around the equilibrium position, is given by the time derivative of $\boldsymbol{\xi}$:

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial t}. \quad (2.7)$$

The notions of Eulerian and Lagrangian frames are also used in Chapter 8.

Introducing a perturbation into the stellar structure equations (2.1), subtracting the equilibrium equations, and retaining only terms linear in the perturbations yields the following set of equations:

$$\frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad (2.8a)$$

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial^2 \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial t^2} = -\nabla p' + \rho_0 \mathbf{g}' + \rho' \mathbf{g}_0, \quad (2.8b)$$

$$\nabla^2 \Phi' = 4\pi G \rho', \quad (2.8c)$$

$$p' + \boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla p_0 = \frac{\Gamma_1 p_0}{\rho_0} (\rho' + \boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla \rho_0). \quad (2.8d)$$

2.3 Separation of Variables and Solutions

The equilibrium quantities are static compared to the perturbations. In addition, spherical symmetry of the system assures that equilibrium quantities depend only on the radial coordinate. In the spherical polar coordinate system — the use of which is expedient due to the symmetry of the system — the vector of a displacement $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ from the equilibrium position can be decomposed into its radial and horizontal component

$$\boldsymbol{\xi} = \xi_r \mathbf{e}_r + \boldsymbol{\xi}_h \quad (2.9)$$

with

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_h = \xi_\theta \mathbf{e}_\theta + \xi_\phi \mathbf{e}_\phi, \quad (2.10)$$

where \mathbf{e}_r , \mathbf{e}_θ , and \mathbf{e}_ϕ are the unit vectors in the respective directions.

The oscillation equations (2.8) will now be simplified such that they only depend on the perturbations p' , Φ' , $d\Phi'/dr$, and ξ_r (Aerts et al. 2010). The perturbation to any physical quantity can be decomposed into a radial dependent amplitude function \tilde{Q} , a function f which solely depends on the angles, and a temporal function:

$$Q'(r, \theta, \phi) = \tilde{Q}(r) \cdot f(\theta, \phi) \cdot e^{-i\omega t}. \quad (2.11)$$

The angular frequency ω in the harmonic time factor $e^{-i\omega t}$ can, in general, be complex. The radial and angular functions of the solution are yet to be determined from the solutions to the oscillation equations.

The radial function of the horizontal part of the displacement can be calculated by (see Aerts et al. 2010)

$$\tilde{\xi}_h = \frac{1}{\omega^2 r} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_0} \tilde{p}(r) + \tilde{\Phi}(r) \right). \quad (2.12)$$

With this, the horizontal displacement is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_h = \tilde{\xi}_h \cdot \nabla_h f(\theta, \phi) \cdot e^{-i\omega t}, \quad (2.13)$$

where ∇_h is the horizontal part of the gradient operator $\nabla_h = \mathbf{e}_\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + \mathbf{e}_\phi \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi}$. In the case of the solution to the perturbed stellar structure equations, the analytical expression for $f(\theta, \phi)$ is found to be the solution to the horizontal Laplace operator

$$\nabla_h^2 f(\theta, \phi) = -\frac{1}{r^2} \Lambda f(\theta, \phi). \quad (2.14)$$

A complete set of solutions to Equation (2.14) is given by the spherical harmonic functions:

$$f(\theta, \phi) = (-1^m) \sqrt{\frac{2l+1}{2\pi} \frac{(l-m)!}{(l+m)!}} P_l^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\phi} \equiv Y_l^m(\theta, \phi). \quad (2.15)$$

Here, P_l^m are the associated Legendre functions, the *harmonic degree* l is a non-negative integer, and the *azimuthal order* m is limited by $|m| \leq l$. Also, the spherical harmonics are only regular solutions to Equation (2.14) if the eigenvalue is given by $\Lambda = l(l+1)$. The spherical harmonics

Figure 2.1: The real part of six spherical harmonic functions with varying harmonic degree l and azimuthal order m . The polar axis is inclined 30° towards the observer.

are orthonormal with

$$\int_{\Omega} \overline{Y_l^{m'}}(\theta, \phi) Y_l^m(\theta, \phi) d\Omega = \delta_{ll'} \delta_{m'm}, \quad (2.16)$$

where the first spherical harmonic is complex conjugated and the integral extends over the unit sphere.

In Figure 2.1, the real part of six spherical harmonics with different harmonic degrees l and azimuthal orders m are shown. It can be seen that the harmonic degree is equal to the total number of nodal lines on the sphere, while the azimuthal order gives the number of nodal lines through the poles.

The radial amplitude function $\tilde{Q}(r)$ must be obtained by solving the linear adiabatic oscillation equations, which are the result of perturbing the stellar structure equations. After factoring out the time factor and the spherical harmonics, these equations can be reduced to the following system of ordinary differential equations (Unno et al. 1989; Aerts et al. 2010):

$$\frac{d\xi_r}{dr} = - \left(\frac{2}{r} + \frac{1}{\Gamma_1 p} \frac{dp}{dr} \right) \xi_r + \frac{1}{\rho c^2} \left(\frac{S_1^2}{\omega^2} - 1 \right) p' + \frac{l(l+1)}{\omega^2 r^2} \Phi', \quad (2.17a)$$

$$\frac{dp'}{dr} = \rho(\omega^2 - N^2) \xi_r + \frac{1}{\Gamma_1 p} \frac{dp}{dr} p' - \rho \frac{d\Phi'}{dr}, \quad (2.17b)$$

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{d\Phi'}{dr} \right) = 4\pi G \left(\frac{p'}{c^2} + \frac{\rho \xi_r}{g} N^2 \right) + \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} \Phi', \quad (2.17c)$$

where the subscripts 0, which indicate equilibrium quantities, have been discarded and tildes, which indicate the amplitude functions, were replaced by primes. The use of the characteristic

frequencies

$$S_1^2 = \frac{l(l+1)c^2}{r^2}, \quad (2.18)$$

$$N^2 = g \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma_1 p} \frac{dp}{dr} - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dr} \right), \quad (2.19)$$

enhances clarity of this set of equations. S_1 is the *characteristic acoustic frequency* or *Lamb frequency*; N is the *buoyancy frequency*, also called *Brunt-Väisälä frequency*. Additionally, use of the squared adiabatic speed of sound

$$c^2 = \frac{\Gamma_1 p}{\rho} \quad (2.20)$$

is made. The Lamb frequency is the local characteristic frequency of horizontally propagating sound waves and the Brunt-Väisälä frequency is the local frequency of internal gravity waves (Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard 2017). N^2 is negative in convectively unstable regions (Aerts et al. 2010; Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard 2017).

The displacement vector ξ can be written as

$$\xi(r, \theta, \phi, t) = [\xi_r(r)Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)\mathbf{e}_r + \xi_h(r)\nabla_h Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)] e^{-i\omega t}, \quad (2.21)$$

where Equations (2.9)-(2.15) were used.

The set of equations (2.17) is a complete set of ordinary differential equations dependent on the variables ξ_r , p' , Φ' , and $d\Phi'/dr$. It has to be supplemented by appropriate boundary conditions to be solvable. Since (2.17) is a system of four first-order ordinary differential equations, four boundary conditions are required. These are discussed extensively in, e.g., Unno et al. (1989) and Aerts et al. (2010). It is worthy of mention that the solutions to Equations (2.17) are not only the displacement eigenfunctions ξ_r but also the eigenfunctions to the gravitational potential Φ' and $d\Phi'/dr$. In Chapter 9 they are utilized in the calculation of the effect of magnetic field on the stellar structure.

The system of oscillations equations (2.17), together with the appropriate boundary conditions, only has solutions for specific discrete frequencies. These frequencies are the eigenvalues of the system and are in fact squared angular frequencies ω_{nl}^2 . Each eigenvalue can be assigned to a radial perturbation eigenfunction ξ_r , p' , Φ' , and $d\Phi'/dr$. For each frequency ω_{nl} the index n denotes the radial order, i.e., the number of zero crossings of the corresponding eigenfunction, and the index l denotes the harmonic degree of the corresponding spherical harmonic.

The system (2.17) is not solvable analytically. Solutions can either be obtained by making simplifications (see Section 2.4 and references therein) or with numerical codes. Two of the most widely used stellar oscillation codes are ADIPLS (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2008) and GYRE (Townsend and Teitler 2013). A model of the star for which the oscillation frequencies and eigenfunctions are sought has to be supplied to these oscillation codes. Such a model can be obtained from stellar evolution codes like ASTEC (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2007) or MESA (Paxton et al. 2011).

The displacement eigenfunction, Equation (2.21), and the equivalent solutions for the perturbations p' , Φ' , and $d\Phi'/dr$ involve the azimuthal order m in the spherical harmonics Y_l^m . However, due to the spherical symmetry that was imposed on the star at the beginning (no external forces, no rotation or any other velocity fields), the azimuthal order does not appear in the oscillation equations or the boundary conditions. As there are $2l + 1$ values for the azimuthal order for each

harmonic degree l , each eigenfrequency ω_{nl}^2 is $2l + 1$ -fold degenerate. The entirety of these $2l + 1$ modes for each value of (n, l) is called a multiplet.

The spherical symmetry is broken in real stars, as all stars rotate to a certain extent or have magnetic fields, which act as additional external forces. The degeneracy in each multiplet is lifted. The magnitude of the splitting of the azimuthal components can be used for inference of the underlying perturbation which causes it. The inversion of splitting coefficients is a standard method to measure the internal solar rotation profile, see Section 2.7.1 (Howe 2009 and references therein).

2.4 Asymptotic Theory of Stellar Oscillations

The oscillation Equations (2.17) do not allow for general analytical solutions (Cox 1980). In an asymptotic approach, the equations are simplified considerably. The outcome of this reproduces the observed parameters to a good degree of accuracy.

The first simplification of this approach is to neglect the perturbation to the gravitational potential Φ' . This is certainly justified for modes of high radial order n or high degree l , for which perturbations in Φ from different regions in the star average out. This approximation was first studied by Cowling (1941) and is thus called the *Cowling approximation*. A discussion of the effect of the Cowling approximation on the solution of the oscillation equations and its validity can be found in Christensen-Dalsgaard (1991).

For the modes of high radial order, the eigenfunctions vary much more rapidly than equilibrium quantities. Therefore, in a second approximation, all derivatives of equilibrium quantities can be neglected. Also, in a crude approximation, the term $2/r$ in Equation (2.17a) is neglected. These approximations reduce the set of oscillation equations (2.17) to

$$\frac{d\xi_r}{dr} = \frac{1}{\rho c^2} \left(\frac{S_1^2}{\omega^2} - 1 \right) p', \quad (2.22a)$$

$$\frac{dp'}{dr} = \rho(\omega^2 - N^2)\xi_r. \quad (2.22b)$$

By differentiating Equation (2.22a) with respect to r and neglecting derivatives of equilibrium quantities, dp'/dr can be substituted by Equation (2.22b), yielding

$$\frac{d^2\xi_r}{dr^2} = -K(r)\xi_r, \quad (2.23)$$

where

$$K(r) = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \left(\frac{N^2}{\omega^2} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{S_1^2}{\omega^2} - 1 \right). \quad (2.24)$$

Equation (2.23) is a crude approximation to the full set of oscillation equations. Nevertheless, the overall properties of the modes of oscillation are reasonably well reproduced by it and a discussion of its solutions can be carried out in a straightforward manner.

Whether the eigenfunction ξ_r is locally oscillating or exponentially increasing or decreasing depends on the sign of K . The oscillating case is realized if either

$$|\omega| > |N| \quad \text{and} \quad |\omega| > S_1 \quad (\text{p modes}) \quad (2.25)$$

Figure 2.2: Mode frequencies of Model S as a function of harmonic degree. Colors indicate where the modes have their lower turning point according to Equation (2.31). The radial extent of these regions is discussed in Section 2.7.1.

$$\text{or } |\omega| < |N| \quad \text{and} \quad |\omega| < S_1 \quad (\text{g modes}) \quad (2.26)$$

are satisfied. The eigenfunction is decreasing exponentially if

$$|N| < |\omega| < S_1 \quad \text{or} \quad S_1 < |\omega| < |N|. \quad (2.27)$$

In a region where Equation (2.27) is satisfied the mode is called *evanescent*. Due to the exponential decrease in amplitude it does not propagate inside this given region.

2.5 The Modes and Their Properties

Solutions of the oscillation equations can, in general, be categorized into p, g, and f modes. With Equations (2.25) and (2.26) regions in which pressure acts as the restoring force if a parcel of gas is displaced from its equilibrium position can be distinguished from regions where gravity acts as the restoring force. In the former regions, acoustic p modes (*p* for pressure) can propagate. In the latter region, g modes, which are buoyancy driven oscillations, can propagate. Buoyancy is proportional to gravitational acceleration \mathbf{g} , which gives these modes their name.

2.5.1 p Modes

These are standing acoustic waves, which are stochastically excited through noise generated by convection. For p modes, the dispersion relation

$$\omega^2 = c^2 |\vec{k}|^2 \quad (2.28)$$

can be established (see, e.g., Aerts et al. 2010). The horizontal and radial parts of the wave vector are given by

$$k_h^2 = \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2}, \quad (2.29)$$

$$k_r^2 = \frac{1}{c^2}(\omega^2 - S_l^2). \quad (2.30)$$

This follows from Equation (2.24) in the limit $\omega \gg N$. The right-hand side of Equation (2.30) can be identified as $K_p(r)$, i.e., the approximation for Equation (2.24) for p modes. $K_p(r)$ can be used to define the propagation path of a p mode. A p mode can be considered as a plane wave with non-vanishing horizontal wave vector. As the wave propagates into the star, temperature and sound speed increase. Thus, deeper parts of the plane wave experience a greater sound speed, see Equation (2.30). The plane wave gets refracted away from the radial direction as the radial part of the wave vector decreases and the horizontal part increases. At a certain point, the radial part of the wave vector is equal to zero. According to Equation (2.30), this is equivalent to $S_l = \omega$. The radial point r_t where this happens is called the *lower turning point*

$$\frac{c^2(r_t)}{r_t^2} = \frac{\omega^2}{l(l+1)}, \quad (2.31)$$

which corresponds to an internal reflection of the oscillations. The region in which a certain p mode can oscillate, also known as the p-mode cavity, extends from the surface to a distance r_t from the center.

In Figure 2.2, mode frequencies of the standard solar model ‘Model S’ (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996, see Section 2.7.2 for a description) are shown as a function of harmonic degree and the region of the lower turning point of each mode is indicated by the color of the points. The extent of the respective region in the Sun is given in Section 2.7.1. It can be seen that only modes of $l \lesssim 10$ have cavities which reach down to the solar core (red dots). The tachocline region is probed by modes of up to $l \lesssim 70$. In Figure 2.3, the lower turning point is plotted as a function of harmonic degree and color-coded according to their radial order. Modes of higher radial order probe deeper parts of the Sun as the lower turning point moves outside with increasing radial order. Also, for higher harmonic degrees a lower number of radial orders exist.

It is largely due to the behavior of p modes manifested in Equation (2.31) that helioseismology can be used to accurately determine the solar structure, e.g., the sound speed profile (Kosovichev et al. 1997), throughout the Sun with inversion techniques, see Section 2.7.1. This is not possible in the same way for stars as stellar observations cannot be spatially resolved. Hence, only low degree modes $l \leq 3$ can be detected in photometric time series (Harvey 1988; Appourchaux et al. 2012). Inference of the internal structure of stars is much coarser than for the Sun (e.g., Mathur et al. 2012, Metcalfe et al. 2014) and mostly restricted to global parameters like mass, radius, age, and composition.

Reflection of the waves at the stellar surface is due to the rapid decrease in density. Only waves with a frequency higher than

$$\omega_a = \frac{c}{2H_p} \quad (2.32)$$

can propagate into the stellar atmosphere (Lamb 1909), where

$$H_p = -\frac{dr}{d \ln p} \quad (2.33)$$

is the pressure scale height. Modes with $\omega < \omega_a$ are trapped inside the star, while modes with higher frequency cannot develop standing waves inside the star. ω_a is called the *acoustic cut-off frequency*. For the Sun $\omega_a \approx 5.3$ mHz (Balmforth and Gough 1990; Fossat et al. 1992).

Figure 2.3: Lower turning point of p modes from Model S as a function of harmonic degree. Colors indicate the radial order of the modes.

According to the conditions (2.25), p modes are trapped in regions where their frequencies are higher than the buoyancy frequency N and the acoustic frequency S_1 . The acoustic cut-off frequency puts an outer boundary on the cavity for p-mode oscillations. Modes are not able to propagate when their vertical wavelength is longer than the scale of the density variation in the equilibrium structure. This leads to reflection of the waves. See Wiśniewska et al. (2016) and references therein for a description of the detailed physics involved and an analysis of the change of the solar acoustic cut-off frequency with height in the solar atmosphere. In Figure 2.4, the Lamb frequency is shown for different harmonic degrees (dashed lines) and the Brunt-Väisälä frequency is plotted as a solid line for the case of the present Sun. As indicated by a horizontal red line, a p mode of degree $l = 20$ with $\nu = 2000 \mu\text{Hz}$ is trapped between the surface and $r = 0.61 R_\odot$ in the Sun. In Figure 2.5 the same is plotted for a more evolved solar-like star with an age of 11.67 Gyr. Here, N is shown as a solid blue line, and red lines indicate the Lamb frequency of modes of different harmonic degrees. Comparison with Figure 2.4 shows that the mode cavities have changed considerably. The cavity of a p mode with $l = 20$ and $\nu = 2000 \mu\text{Hz}$ now extends down to $r \approx 0.4 R_\odot$. Of course, also the radius of the star has changed over the course of the star’s evolution (Prialnik 2009).

2.5.2 g Modes

In stars with a radiative core and convective outer layers, e.g., the Sun, g modes are hard to detect. They are only oscillating in regions where the conditions (2.26) are met. g modes propagate in the radiative parts of stellar interiors. They are evanescent in convective regions, see Equation (2.27), and their surface amplitudes on solar-like stars are below the current limits of detection (Appourchaux et al. 2000). For the Sun, no unambiguous detection of g modes has been reported so far (Appourchaux et al. 2010, and references therein). However, there are reports of the detection of the period spacing of solar dipole ($l = 1$) g modes in agreement with the value predicted by theory (García et al. 2007) and their asymptotic period equidistance and rotational splitting (Fossat et al. 2017). These results point to a rotation of the solar core, which is about

Figure 2.4: Propagation diagram of Model S. The black dashed lines indicate the Lamb frequency S_l for different harmonic degrees. The solid black line is the Brunt-Väisälä frequency N . The solid red line marks the propagation region of a p mode with $l = 20$ and $\nu = 2000 \mu\text{Hz}$. The solid green line shows where a g mode with $l = 1$ and $\nu = 100 \mu\text{Hz}$ would propagate. Figure adapted from [Christensen-Dalsgaard \(2014\)](#).

three times faster than that of the radiation zone, see Section 2.7.1. In frequency spectra of more massive main sequence stars, like γ Doradus and δ Scuti stars, which have radiative outer layers or only a thin convective shell ([Iben 2013](#)), g-mode oscillations can readily be detected, see, e.g., [Van Reeth et al. \(2015\)](#). Formally, g modes are assigned negative radial orders n .

In asymptotic analysis of high order g modes, for which $\omega^2 \ll S_1^2$, Equation (2.24) can be approximated by

$$K_g(r) \simeq \left(\frac{N^2}{\omega^2} - 1 \right) \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2}. \quad (2.34)$$

Therefore, the cavities and the dynamics of g modes are determined by the radial profile of N . In Figure 2.4 the profile of N is plotted as a solid line and the cavity of a g mode with $l = 1$ and a frequency of $\nu = 100 \mu\text{Hz}$ is shown as a green horizontal line. The inner turning point of this g mode, at $N = \nu$, is very near the center of the solar model used for this diagram. For low-frequency g modes, the base of the convection zone at $r \approx 0.71 R_\odot$ marks the outer turning point. g modes of higher frequency are confined to even deeper regions. Thus, the search for individual g modes is concentrated to the frequency domain below $\lesssim 200 \mu\text{Hz}$.

In the asymptotic approximation, the turning points of g modes are independent of the harmonic degree of the modes. g-mode periods are equally spaced in radial order and the spacing decreases with increasing l ([Appourchaux et al. 2010](#)). This is in contrast to p modes, which are equally spaced in the frequency domain, see Section 2.6.3.

Figure 2.5: Propagation diagram for a model of a star with a mass of $1 M_{\odot}$. The star is at the subgiant stage with an age of 11.67 Gyr. The dark blue line indicates the Brunt-Väisälä frequency. The red lines show the Lamb frequency for the indicated harmonic degrees. The horizontal cyan line shows the propagation cavity for an $l = 1$ mode with a frequency of $\nu = 1$ mHz. The horizontal dotted magenta line shows the cavity for an $l = 1$ mode with a frequency of $\nu = 0.5$ mHz. Figure from Basu (2016).

2.5.3 f Modes

The f modes or *fundamental* modes are surface gravity waves with radial order $n = 0$ (Gizon and Birch 2005). These f modes propagate only horizontally. Hence, their wave vector is determined by Equation (2.29). They (almost) follow the dispersion relation for waves on a deep ocean $\omega^2 = \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{g}$. Thus, their frequencies can be calculated by

$$\omega_1^2 \approx g_s \frac{\sqrt{l(l+1)}}{R}, \quad (2.35)$$

where g_s is the gravitational acceleration at the surface and R is the surface radius. Because f modes do not propagate in the radial direction, their radial displacement can be assumed to decay exponentially inwards. According to this and Equation (2.35), f modes are only sensitive to surface gravity and are confined to near-surface layers. Therefore, they cannot provide information on the deep stellar interior. However, they can be used to probe the outer layers of the Sun for near-surface structures such as near-surface flows (Gizon and Birch 2005; Jackiewicz et al. 2007). In stellar observations, they cannot be detected as they are of intermediate degree $l \gtrsim 20$ (Aerts et al. 2010).

2.5.4 Mixed Modes

If the cavities of a p mode and a g mode of like harmonic degree overlap or have only a narrow evanescent region between them, the two modes can couple. Figure 2.5 illustrates the characteristic frequencies and mode cavities for a stellar model of a star with one solar mass at the

subgiant stage with an age of 11.67 Gyr. As can be seen here, the cavities of a p mode with $l = 1$ and $\nu = 1$ mHz and a g mode with the same parameters, shown by the horizontal cyan line, are only separated by a small fraction of the stellar radius. The resulting modes are called *mixed modes*, as buoyancy acts as the restoring force in the one cavity and pressure in the other cavity. A mixed mode is a single mode with different physical mechanisms in different regions of a star. Their frequencies are shifted compared with pure acoustic or gravity modes. The magnitude of the shift depends on the separation of the two cavities and hence the coupling strength between the two oscillation cavities (e.g., [Deheuvels and Michel 2010](#)).

[Deheuvels and Michel \(2011\)](#) showed that the study of coupling strengths of mixed modes in subgiant stars can provide insight into questions such as core overshooting, the efficiency of convection, and the abundances of heavy elements in stars. A review on the seismology of giant stars, for which the understanding of mixed modes is essential, is given by [Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard \(2017\)](#).

2.6 What Do We See?

The power of modern helioseismology is rooted in the fact that we have highly resolved, long baseline observations of the Sun, thanks to space-borne missions like SOHO (Solar and Heliospheric Observatory, [Domingo et al. 1995](#)) and SDO (Solar Dynamics Observatory, [Pesnell et al. 2012](#)) and the ground-based GONG network (Global Oscillation Network Group, [Harvey et al. 1996](#)).

These data enable us to measure mode parameters up to high harmonic degree. Mode frequencies, damping widths, and amplitudes (e.g., [Hill et al. 1996](#)), mode splittings (e.g., [Schou et al. 1998](#)), peak asymmetries (e.g., [Nigam et al. 1998](#)), amplitude ratios ([Schad et al. 2011](#)), travel times (e.g., [Duvall Jr. et al. 1993](#)), are but a few of the helioseismic quantities, which can be measured and used to map out the inner workings of our star (see Section 2.7.1). I will give more details about some of these parameters in Chapter 6.

In Figure 2.7, a power spectrum of solar full-disk data from the HMI instrument ([Schou et al. 2012](#)) aboard the SDO spacecraft is shown. As can be seen by comparison with Figure 2.2, the ridge structure predicted by the theoretical model frequencies can indeed be observed for the Sun. Thanks to the high spatial resolution of HMI, oscillations of harmonic degrees up to 1000 and higher can be detected.

Asteroseismology inference is limited by the fact that only modes of degree $l \leq 3$ can be observed in photometric stellar observations. This corresponds to the leftmost three columns of the power spectrum in Figure 2.7. Hence, the resolution of stellar structure inferred by asteroseismology is far from what can be reached with helioseismology. For the work that is presented in this thesis, I used data from the NASA *Kepler* spacecraft (Chapter 5) and from the ground-based GONG network (Chapter 6).

2.6.1 Data from the Kepler Mission

Figure 2.6 illustrates the reduction of photometric data from the *Kepler* spacecraft as used in Chapter 5. In panel (a), the pixel mask for the star KIC 8006161 is shown (left half). Such masks are defined for all $\approx 156\,000$ observed stars within the field of view of *Kepler*. The flux that is accumulated within the white pixels of this mask over the exposure time of 6.02s is

Figure 2.6: Reduction of *Kepler* short cadence data at a glance. *Panel (a)*: pixel mask for the star KIC 8006161 (left) and raw data within the mask for one short cadence datum. The white pixels in the optimal photometric aperture of the star and are considered to contribute to the flux of the star. Gray pixels are halo pixels, which can be added to the aperture to allow for a margin of error in the position of the star. Black pixels are outside the mask and are not considered. The coloring of the pixels in the right panel ranges from dark orange (few counts) to white (many counts or saturated pixel). *Panel (b)*: raw time series of the short cadence flux (black data points). The red line is a spline fit with a width of 1000 data points. *Panel (c)*: time series corrected for jumps, drifts, and outliers. *Panel (d)*: periodogram of the full short cadence data set of KIC 8006161 (black) and smoothed over 30 frequency bins (red).

then added over nine exposures to give a short cadence datum every 58.85 s.¹ The right half of panel (a) shows one of these summed short cadence datums of KIC 8006161. (see [Borucki et al. 2010](#), and references therein for further information on the acquisition, preparation, and reduction of *Kepler* data). For the long cadence data, which is primarily used in the search for exoplanets, 270 exposures are added, giving a data point every 29.43 min. The long cadence data is also sufficiently temporally sampled for asteroseismic investigations of stars with low-frequency eigenmodes, e.g., red giants ([Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard 2017](#)). As this is a particularly

¹The CCD read-out time is 0.52 s.

Figure 2.7: Power spectrum computed from data of the HMI instrument aboard the Solar Dynamics Observatory spacecraft. Courtesy of Kolja Glogowski, using data provided by the HMI science team.

bright star, flux is leaking into neighboring pixels in the direction of CCD read-out.

Panel (b) of Figure 2.6 shows a one month long segment of the uncorrected short cadence time series of KIC 8006161 (black data points) and a spline (solid red line) fitted to the data, that is subtracted from the time series to account for long-term drifts in the data, which are, for example, caused by CCD degradation or satellite maneuvers. Panel (c) shows the same data as (b) after the corrections for jumps, drifts, and outliers have been applied (García et al. 2011). A Lomb-Scargle periodogram (Lomb 1976; Scargle 1982) of the full short cadence data set (1147 days) of KIC 8006161 is shown in panel (d) in black and smoothed over 30 frequency bins in red. Clear peaks can be identified between 2.5 – 4.2 mHz. *Kepler* short cadence data has a Nyquist frequency of 8.5 mHz and is thus ideally suited for the asteroseismic investigation of solar-like oscillators.² However, due to a limited download bandwidth from *Kepler*³ only 512 stars were continually observed in the short cadence mode.

2.6.2 Data from the GONG Network

For the investigation of the solar magnetic activity presented in Chapter 6, data from the ground-based network GONG was used. GONG started taking data in 1995 and is still in operation. It consists of six identical observing stations distributed across the globe in such a way to minimize diurnal gaps in the data. The observing sites are located at the Observatorio del Teide on Tenerife, the Udaipur Solar Observatory in India, the Learmonth Solar Observatory in Australia, the High Altitude Observatory on Mauna Loa in Hawaii, the Big Bear Solar Observatory in California, and the Cerro Tololo Interamerican Observatory in Chile. This distribution allows an average of 1.8 telescopes to observe the Sun at any time of the day (Harvey et al. 1996). The high duty cycle (see the third column of Table B.3) that can be achieved by multi-site networks reduces the side lobes in the frequency power spectrum considerably (see Fig. 2 in Harvey et al. 1996).

²As these stars have eigenfrequencies in the mHz regime, see Sections 2.6.3 and 2.8.

³*Kepler* is in an Earth-trailing heliocentric orbit. Its distance to Earth is slowly increasing. As its prime mission goal was the search for exoplanets, most of the bandwidth was reserved for the long cadence data.

An advantage of ground-based telescopes, compared to satellite missions, is that they can be upgraded and maintained.

The GONG instruments obtain Doppler velocity maps (Dopplergrams) for the full disk of the Sun every minute. The Doppler shift is measured in the Ni I absorption line at 676.8 nm. A Dopplergram recorded by the MDI instrument aboard SOHO, which is similar to the instruments used in GONG, is shown in Figure 1.1. The left part shows the surface velocity field with a clear velocity gradient from the eastern to western limb, which is due to the rotation of the Sun. Solar rotation and residual velocities from Earth's orbit around the Sun are removed from the Dopplergrams before they are further used for helioseismic studies. The time series of full disk Dopplergrams are then decomposed into spherical harmonic coefficient time series (see, e.g., Fig. 1 in Harvey et al. 1996) for each harmonic degree l and azimuthal order m . The power spectra of such time series are then fitted to obtain the mode parameters (mode frequency, mode damping width, mode amplitude, and parameters of the background of the spectrum) of each mode (see Fig. 4 in Hill et al. 1996). Figure 2.7 shows a power spectrum for $m = 0$ modes which was computed from data of the HMI instrument. Each column of such an l - ν diagram corresponds to the power spectrum of a spherical harmonic time series of one mode with $(l, m = 0)$. Results of the GONG fitting pipeline are used in Chapter 6 to investigate the temporal variation of parameters of modes up to $l = 150$.

2.6.3 Global Seismic Parameters

I will highlight some global seismic parameters which enable us to make assessments of stellar parameters like mass, radius, and age in the following. These parameters can be extracted from stellar photometric time series and are of great diagnostic potential for asteroseismic studies.

A standing wave in radial order inside a cavity can only form if its phase changes along the radial extension by $n\pi$ with integer n . For the radial part of the wave vector, see Equation (2.30), this can be written as

$$\int_{r_t}^R k_r dr = \int_{r_t}^R \sqrt{\omega^2 - S_1^2} \frac{dr}{c} = \pi(n + \alpha), \quad (2.36)$$

where use of Equation (2.24) was made and α accounts for phase changes at the boundaries. This relation was first found by Duvall Jr. (1982) and is known as the *Duvall law* of helioseismology. It is an integral relation in Abel form: the left-hand side is a function of speed of sound (Equation (2.18)) and values for the right-hand side can be obtained from observation. Hence, the Duvall law can be inverted analytically to get the sound speed profile as a function of radius without computing a stellar model in the first place, e.g., Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (1985).

Frequency Separations

As already discussed in Section 2.5.1, the turning points of low-degree p modes are very close to the stellar core. By rewriting the Duvall law (2.36) to

$$\int_{r_t}^R \sqrt{1 - \frac{S_1^2}{\omega^2}} \frac{dr}{c} = \frac{\pi(n + \alpha)}{\omega}, \quad (2.37)$$

Figure 2.8: Small section of an acoustic frequency spectrum computed from data of the VIRGO instrument aboard SOHO. Modes are labeled by their order and degree (n, l) . Two large and two small frequency separations are indicated. Figure by [Bedding and Kjeldsen \(2003\)](#)⁴.

it can be seen that the second term under the square root is much smaller than unity for most of the range of integration for low degree modes, see [Figure 2.4](#), and can be neglected to a high degree of precision. By using this approximation, asymptotic p-mode frequencies can be calculated to leading order, yielding the simple relation

$$\nu_{nl} = \frac{\omega_{nl}}{2\pi} \simeq \left(n + \frac{l}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \alpha \right) \Delta\nu, \quad (2.38)$$

where the *large frequency separation* is defined by

$$\Delta\nu = \left[2 \int_0^R \frac{dr}{c} \right]^{-1} \quad (2.39)$$

and α is a constant term ([Aerts et al. 2010](#)). A more rigorous derivation of Equation (2.38) can be found in [Tassoul \(1980\)](#). The large frequency separation is the inverse of the time it takes an acoustic wave to travel once throughout the star. It is sensitive to the mean density of the star. The large frequency separation of the Sun is $\Delta\nu_{\odot} \approx 135 \mu\text{Hz}$ (e.g., [Kiefer et al. 2015](#)). Equation (2.38) predicts a uniform spacing in mode order n . Also, in this approximation, modes with equal values of $n + l/2$ almost have the same frequency:

$$\nu_{nl} \simeq \nu_{n-1, l+2}. \quad (2.40)$$

In [Figure 2.8](#), a section of the solar power spectrum is shown. The large separation is indicated for the modes $(n, l) = (19, 1)$ and $(20, 1)$ as well as for the separation between the modes $(20, 0)$ and $(21, 0)$. It can be seen that from observations one finds the degeneracy (2.40) lifted by a

⁴This figure is reproduced with permission from the publication Timothy R. Bedding and Hans Kjeldsen, *Solar-like Oscillations*, Publications of the Astronomical Society of Australia, 20, 203-212.

Figure 2.9: Section of the smoothed power spectrum of HD 49385 computed from 137 days of CoRoT data. The green curve is a fit to the background. The blue dashed curve is the Gaussian fit to the envelope of the oscillations in the raw power spectrum. The resulting frequency of maximum power is indicated by a vertical dotted line. Figure from [Deheuvels et al. \(2010\)](#)⁵.

small difference in frequency in Figure 2.8:

$$\delta\nu_{nl} = \nu_{nl} - \nu_{n-1,l+2}. \quad (2.41)$$

This frequency separation, called the *small frequency separation*, can be calculated if the expansion of Equation (2.38) is carried out up to second order ([Tassoul 1980](#)):

$$\delta\nu_{nl} = \nu_{nl} - \nu_{n-1,l+2} \simeq -(4l + 6) \frac{\Delta\nu}{4\pi^2\nu_{nl}} \int_0^R \frac{dc}{dr} \frac{dr}{r}. \quad (2.42)$$

Inspecting the integral in this equation, it can be seen that $\delta\nu_{nl}$ is strongly sensitive to a gradient in the sound speed if r is small, i.e., in the core region. In turn, the speed of sound is strongly dependent on chemical composition, which changes during stellar evolution. Therefore, the small frequency separation contains information on stellar age and composition in the core region. Ratios of the small to large separations and ratios of small separations are approximately independent of the structure of the outer layers of a star and can, therefore, be used as diagnostics of the stellar interior structure ([Roxburgh and Vorontsov 2003](#); [Roxburgh 2005](#)). This is used in asteroseismic inference to better constrain stellar models ([Silva Aguirre et al. 2015](#)).

Frequency of Maximum Power

The section of the power spectrum which contains the p-modes of the G-type star HD 49385 is shown with the fits to the background⁶ and the mode envelope in Figure 2.9. As can be seen here,

⁵Credit: Deheuvels et al., A&A, 515, A87, 2010, reproduced with permission © ESO.

⁶See [Kallinger et al. \(2014\)](#) on the effect of granulation to the background signal for stars of different spectral type.

the amplitudes of the modes in a power spectrum of a solar-like star are modulated by an almost symmetric envelope, which is generally assumed to be a Gaussian, around a central frequency of maximum power. The width and shape of the mode envelope are influenced by excitation and dampening of the standing waves inside the star. A characteristic parameter of this envelope is the frequency of maximum power ν_{\max} , which generally does not coincide with a mode frequency. There is no rigorous derivation for this asteroseismic parameter.

As stated in Section 2.5.1, the acoustic cut-off frequency is the fundamental upper bound for p modes. Therefore, the frequency of maximum power should scale with the acoustic cut-off frequency (Brown et al. 1991)

$$\nu_{\max} \propto \frac{c}{H_p}, \quad (2.43)$$

see Equation (2.32). This was confirmed by Belkacem et al. (2011), who found a linear relation between ν_{\max} and ν_a . Assuming a constant adiabatic exponent Γ_1 and an equation of state for an ideal gas $p \propto \rho T$ yields

$$\nu_{\max} \propto \frac{g}{\sqrt{T}}, \quad (2.44)$$

where Equations (2.20) and (2.33) were substituted (Kjeldsen and Bedding 1995). Therefore, ν_{\max} connects the two important stellar quantities surface gravity g and effective temperature T . The frequency of maximum power of the Sun is $\nu_{\max} \approx 3120 \mu\text{Hz}$ (Kallinger et al. 2010).

2.7 The Stars from Their Sound

In this section, I want to highlight some of the results of helio- and asteroseismology. Helioseismology is a unique tool to determine the interior structure of the Sun and has significantly contributed to our current understanding of our nearest star. With the photometric data that has become available thanks to the CoRoT and *Kepler* missions, asteroseismology has developed significantly over the last one and a half decades. It can now be used to infer stellar structure and bulk stellar parameters, as I will describe in Section 2.8.

2.7.1 Properties and Interior Structure of the Sun

The Sun is a G2 dwarf star with an effective temperature of $T_{\text{eff}} = 5777 \text{ K}$ and an absolute magnitude of $M_V = +4.83$. It has a radius of $R_{\odot} = 696 \text{ Mm}$ and a mass of $M_{\odot} = 1.989 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$. Its main constituents are hydrogen and helium with mass fractions of about 73.5% and 24.8%, respectively. The remaining 1.7% is a mixture of many heavier elements, where oxygen is the most abundant, with $\approx 0.8\%$ of the Sun's mass (see Grevesse and Sauval 1998 for the determination of this *Standard Solar Composition* or Asplund et al. (2009) for a composition slightly deviating from this). The current value of the age of the Sun from helioseismic measurements is $t_{\text{Sun}} = 4.57 \text{ Gyr}$ (Bonanno et al. 2002; Bonanno and Fröhlich 2015).

Our current picture of the interior radial structure of the Sun is depicted in Figure 2.10. The layers that are commonly distinguished are

Core		$r/R_{\odot} \leq 0.2,$
Radiation zone	$0.2 <$	$r/R_{\odot} \leq 0.65,$
Tachocline	$0.65 <$	$r/R_{\odot} \leq 0.713,$
Convection zone	$0.713 <$	$r/R_{\odot} \leq 0.95,$
Near-surface shear layer	$0.95 <$	$r/R_{\odot} \leq 1,$
Atmosphere		$r/R_{\odot} > 1.$

These layers differ regarding their energy generation, the dominant mode of energy transport, and their rotation.

The *core* is where the temperature and pressure are high enough for fusion to take place. Hence, it is only the inner 20% of the Sun, where its energy output of 3.828×10^{26} W is produced by fusion of hydrogen to helium⁷. The understanding of the conditions in the core is one of the major contributions of helioseismology to physics in general. By confirming the solar core temperature of $T_{\text{core}} = 15.6 \times 10^6$ K, the radial profile of temperature, density, and sound speed (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996) and by determining the solar composition, it was settled that the apparent lack of neutrinos coming from the Sun was not rooted in an incorrect understanding of the Sun but in a problem in particle physics. This led to the solution of the neutrino problem by the discovery of neutrino oscillations⁸. The rotation rate of the core has so far eluded measurement. Only few modes have cavities that reach down to this region (see Figures 2.2 and 2.3) and hence the rotation profile is difficult to constrain in this region of the Sun. However, there have been reports that the solar core rotates with a shorter period than the layers above it (García et al. 2007; Fossat et al. 2017).

In the *radiation zone*, the energy that is produced in the core is transported outward by radiation. This transport can be seen as a diffusion process, where the mean free path of the photons is 9×10^{-4} m and a diffusion time scale of 170000 yr⁹ (Mitalas and Sills 1992). In Figure 2.11 the mean rotation profile of the Sun is shown. In the left panel, contours of constant rotation are plotted as a function of radius. The right panel shows cuts through the rotation profile at constant latitude as a function of radius. As can be seen in the right panel, the Sun is rotating as a solid body in the radiation zone.

The *tachocline*¹⁰ separates the radiation zone from the convection zone. In the tachocline, the differential rotation profile of the convection zone is converted into the solid body rotation of the radiative zone, see right panel of Figure 2.11. This layer of strong radial shear in the rotation is hypothesized to be critical to the solar dynamo: The shear of plasma that occurs in the tachocline is assumed to be the main agent for the cyclical transformation of large-scale poloidal magnetic field into large-scale toroidal magnetic field, see Chapter 3. The tachocline is also the region where the dominant mode of energy transport outwards changes from radiation to convection. The depth where convection sets in — the base of the convection zone — was first determined by inversions of the sound-speed by Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (1991) to be at $0.713 R_{\odot}$. Due to

⁷This an approximation: The energy production within this region accounts for $\approx 90\%$ of the total. However, the energy production rate above $0.2 R_{\odot}$ drops quickly, as the temperature decreases. Also, the pp-chain is the dominant energy production process in the core accounting for about 98.8% of the energy production, but not the only process. The CNO-cycle provides the remaining 1.2%. See Stix (2002) for a detailed account of physics and processes of and in the Sun and the observation of them.

⁸See Section 1 in Gough (2012) for a detailed discussion of the helioseismic research concerning the solar neutrino problem.

⁹These values refer to the average step length of a photon until it reaches the convection zone and the time it takes for it to reach this point in the Sun.

¹⁰The term *tachocline* was introduced by Spiegel and Zahn (1992). It is coined to resemble the name of the thin layer in Earth's oceans which features a strong gradient in temperature – the thermocline.

Figure 2.10: The structure of the Sun. The interior is separated into four regions: The core, the radiative zone, the tachocline, and the convection zone. The atmosphere is composed of the photosphere, the chromosphere, a transition region and the corona. Image from [NASA](#).

the change of the mode of dominant energy transport, the steep radial gradient in rotation, and its role for the dynamo, the tachocline is of special interest for solar modelers, dynamo theorists, and helioseismologists. For a collection of treatises on different topics concerning the tachocline see [Hughes et al. \(2007\)](#). Pinpointing the exact depth and determining the width of the tachocline was a major contribution of helioseismology to solar physics, see Chapter 6 of [Howe \(2009\)](#). I will come back to the tachocline in Section 3.3 and test the effect of magnetic field in the tachocline region on solar oscillation frequencies in Chapter 9.

In the *convection zone*, the Sun rotates differentially and the energy transport outwards is largely conducted by turbulent upward motion of plasma, i.e., *convection*. As can be seen in Figure 2.11, different latitudes rotate at different periods. While the equator has a rotation period of only 24.47 days, it takes higher latitudes and the poles up to 38 days to rotate once¹¹. The rotation rate is only weakly dependent on radius in the convection zone. It is nearly constant on contours at about a 25° angle to the rotation axis ([Howe et al. 2005](#)). This differential rotation profile of the Sun is in stark contrast to what it was expected to be before helioseismic measurements of it. It was predicted that the rotation rate is constant on cylinders parallel to the axis of rotation. For dynamo theory, this posed a new problem, as a radial gradient in rotation in the convection zone

¹¹These are sidereal rotation periods. See [Roša et al. \(1995\)](#) for formulae to convert them to synodic rotation rates.

Figure 2.11: Mean rotation profile of the Sun from GONG data. *Left panel:* contours of constant rotation, dashed lines show lines of near-constant rotation in the convection zone with an inclination of 25° to the rotation axis. *Right panel:* cuts through the rotation profile at constant latitude as a function of radius. Figure from [Howe \(2009\)](#).

was assumed to be necessary to drive the solar cycle, see Chapter 3 for more details. The polar rotation rate is still somewhat undetermined, as the polar regions are subject to projection effects when observed from the ecliptic of the solar system. This will soon be remedied with observations from the upcoming ESA Solar Orbiter mission ([Mueller et al. 2012](#)), which will leave the ecliptic and be able to observe high solar latitudes with much weaker projection effects.

In the *near-surface shear layer* — the upper $\approx 5\%$ of the solar interior — the rotation rate increases inward at all latitudes. It had been theorized that such a layer must exist in the Sun (e.g., [Gilman and Foukal 1979](#)), as the observed rotation of the solar photosphere in Doppler measurements differed from the rotation period of surface features like sunspots, i.e., the surface features rotate faster (see [Howe 2009](#), and references therein). Hence, the surface features must be rooted or originate in some deeper lying, faster rotating region of the Sun. The near-surface shear layer, with its radial gradient in rotation, is also a possible location of the solar dynamo ([Brandenburg 2005](#)).

The solar *atmosphere* is partitioned into four layers: The *photosphere*, the *chromosphere*, a *transition region*, and the *corona*. I will not go into detail about all of them here and refer to the textbooks of [Priest \(2014\)](#) for a more theoretical overview of magnetohydrodynamics and many phenomena in the solar atmosphere and to [Stix \(2002\)](#) for a more observation driven approach. The lower boundary of the atmosphere is called the *photosphere*. This is where opacity and density become low enough for radiative transport to become dominant again. The mean free path of photons becomes large; the majority of photons we receive from the Sun come from this layer and thus the Sun is perceived as a sphere with a rather well-defined limb. Physically, the photosphere is located at an optical depth of $\tau = 1$, i.e., one mean free path of a photon into the star. This defines the radius of a star, which is usually located at the photosphere, thus aptly named the *photospheric radius*. However, the solar photosphere is actually a thin layer of a few hundred kilometers in thickness. Most of the information, i.e., most photons, we have about the Sun and the stars come from this thin layer and the layers above it. The photosphere is dominated by convective cells, called granules, which are blobs of ascending hot material. Their life-times are of the order of minutes; the granular pattern can be seen in the region outside the

sunspot in Figure 3.6. The “flickering” of starlight due to granulation can be used to estimate surface gravities, as shown by Bastien et al. (2013).

2.7.2 Model S and Its Eigenmodes

The solution to the stellar structure equations and the appropriate energy equation, as outlined in Section 2.2, is referred to as a standard model.¹² How solutions to the stellar structure equations can be obtained and calculated can be found in, e.g., Kippenhahn et al. (2012). A model of the Sun is needed to obtain the oscillation eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies.

I use Model S by Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (1996) as a model for the Sun throughout this thesis. It is well established in helioseismology. The model contains the equilibrium quantities, e.g., temperature, density, pressure, and the first adiabatic exponent as functions of radius¹³. These quantities are obtained by solving the stellar structure equations for the Sun. Convection is modeled with a mixing length approach (Böhm-Vitense 1969). The OPAL equation of state (Rogers et al. 1996) and the OPAL opacities (Iglesias and Rogers 1991) are used in the calculation of this model. Also included is the gravitational settling of helium and heavy-elements. The input parameters of the model are optimized such that the resulting model reproduces the global solar parameters as luminosity, radius, and surface composition¹⁴.

The eigenfunctions of the model — ξ_r , ξ_h , Φ' , and $d\Phi'/dr$ — were calculated with the ADIPLS (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2008) code¹⁵. The mode set I used in this thesis includes the solar f-mode eigenfunctions (harmonic degrees from $l = 2$ to 2716) and p-mode eigenfunctions (harmonic degrees up to $l = 1669$ for radial order $n = 1$) below the acoustic cut-off frequency. Due to the thick outer convection zone, g modes and mixed modes are not observed on the Sun, as discussed in Section 2.5.

2.8 Asteroseismic Inference of Stellar Structure

Asteroseismic techniques can be used to estimate global stellar parameters, like mass, radius, and age, as well as to infer the stellar structure, regions of abrupt changes thereof, and the rotational profile. In this section, I want to highlight some of the astounding possibilities and results of asteroseismology, which help advance stellar astrophysics. Detailed overviews can be found in the review of Chaplin and Miglio (2013) on “Asteroseismology of Solar-Type and Red-Giant Stars” and in the review entitled “Giant star seismology” by Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard (2017).

There are two approaches to infer stellar parameters from asteroseismic measurements: Grid-based modeling and detailed modeling (see Chapter 11 of Basu 2016 for a brief discussion of

¹²As Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (1996) point out: “The notion of ‘standard’ models is an evolving concept; in a loose sense, such models should incorporate the physics that is generally recognized as relevant and for which an adequate theoretical description exists.” In this sense, Model S is still a standard model.

¹³The full model file contains up to 36 physical quantities as functions of radius, depending on the version number. A description of the model file can be found in this document: astro.phys.au.dk/~jcd/solar_models/file-format.pdf. The model is freely available and can be downloaded here: astro.phys.au.dk/~jcd/solar_models/

¹⁴From Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (1996): “The correct values of the radius and luminosity can be obtained by adjusting the initial helium abundance and a parameter characterizing the near-surface convection. Also, the initial heavy-element abundance is generally chosen to obtain the observed surface value in the model of the present sun.”

¹⁵The set of eigenfunctions was computed and kindly provided by K. Glogowski

these two approaches). In grid-based modeling, large grids of stellar models are computed and their global parameters are searched for the best fit to the observed values. For example, the method by [Stello et al. \(2009\)](#) uses the surface gravity $\log g$, effective temperature T_{eff} , luminosity, and mean large frequency separation $\Delta\nu$ to find the optimal model in a grid of models which are computed with the ASTEC code ([Christensen-Dalsgaard 2007](#)). In detailed modeling, first a stellar model is generated, then the frequencies of this model are computed. By optimizing the agreement between model and observed frequencies, the best model is found ([Metcalf et al. 2009](#)). This approach yields a higher precision on stellar parameters than the grid-based approach. A comparison of the results of three grid-based methods and one detailed modeling pipeline of a set of solar-type stars can be found in [Mathur et al. \(2012\)](#).

The asymptotic theory of stellar oscillations (see Section 2.4) leads to a regular pattern in the mode frequencies, see also Equation (2.38) and [Tassoul \(1980\)](#) for a derivation. Sharp changes in stellar structure, as, for example, the thin tachocline of the Sun, introduce so-called *glitches* in the frequency separations. These glitches can be measured as an oscillatory component in the separation of the star's eigenfrequencies (e.g., [Mazumdar et al. 2014](#), and references in the introduction thereof). This can be used to determine the location of the bottom of the convection zone and the layer of ionization of helium.

The visibility of rotationally split multiplet components can indicate the inclination of the star's rotational axis towards the observer ([Gizon and Solanki 2003](#)). For example, for a star with an inclination of 90° , the $m = 0$ component of a dipole multiplet is not visible and only the $m = \pm 1$ components can be detected. If the investigated system has a transiting exoplanet, the obliquity of the system (the tilt between the rotation axis of the host star and the planetary orbit) can be determined ([Huber et al. 2013a](#)). This can help to learn about the formation history of planetary systems.

The rotation rate can be routinely detected in periodic variations of stellar photometric time series. These variations can be caused by surface features, like long-living starspots. Several studies on a large number of stars found surface rotation periods, which largely agree with one another (e.g., [McQuillan et al. 2014](#); [Reinhold et al. 2013](#)). Also, the internal rotation profile and differential rotation can be measured in the splitting of multiplets, as was shown by, e.g., [Gizon et al. \(2013\)](#), [Davies et al. \(2015\)](#), and [Nielsen et al. \(2015\)](#). As I will discuss in Chapter 3, knowledge of the stellar rotational properties is important for the theory of stellar dynamos.

2.8.1 Asteroseismic Scaling Relations

Scaling relations are used to estimate unknown parameters by simply scaling the sought-for physical quantity of an object that is well known, like the Sun, to the value of the investigated object. This often works remarkably well, for example with the mass-luminosity-relation ([Kuijper 1938](#)), which connects the solar mass and luminosity to the mass and luminosity of a different star, see [Weigert et al. \(2009\)](#), Chapter 5.5.3. From the properties of the global seismic parameters presented in Section 2.6, the following scaling relations for stellar mass and radius can be established ([Kjeldsen and Bedding 1995](#)):

$$\frac{M}{M_\odot} = \left(\frac{\nu_{\text{max}}}{\nu_{\text{max}\odot}} \right)^3 \left(\frac{\Delta\nu_\odot}{\Delta\nu} \right)^4 \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff}\odot}} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}, \quad (2.45)$$

$$\frac{R}{R_\odot} = \left(\frac{\nu_{\text{max}}}{\nu_{\text{max}\odot}} \right) \left(\frac{\Delta\nu_\odot}{\Delta\nu} \right)^2 \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff}\odot}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (2.46)$$

where the subscript \odot indicates solar values. $\Delta\nu$ and ν_{\max} can be determined from the frequency spectrum of stellar photometric time series and the stellar effective temperature T_{eff} has to be supplied from other sources, e.g., from a spectroscopic analysis of the star as in [Molenda-Żakowicz et al. \(2013\)](#). These scaling relations give good results for solar-like stars. When compared with radii determined with other methods, the values obtained with Equation (2.46) are within 5% for subgiants, dwarf stars, and giants (see [Viani et al. 2017](#) and references therein). Masses estimated with Equation (2.45) are correct to about 10%. The masses can, for example, be cross-checked for binary systems, where an independent value of the mass of each component can be obtained from the analysis of their orbital parameters. The accuracy of the asteroseismic scaling relations can be improved by adding a mean molecular weight term ([Viani et al. 2017](#)) and a correction of the observed value of the large separation to include second order effects ([Mosser et al. 2013](#)).

There are several methods to extract the large frequency separation from stellar photometric time series described in the literature. Two of them include simply fitting the individual modes and calculating their frequency separation ([Roxburgh and Vorontsov 2006](#); [Mosser and Appourchaux 2009](#)) and to fit the auto-correlation function of the periodogram of the time series (e.g., [Appourchaux et al. 2012](#)).

In [Kiefer et al. \(2015\)](#), I developed a robust method to determine the large frequency separation. I used the analytic signal¹⁶ of filtered stellar oscillation time series to compute the signal envelope. Spectral analysis of the signal envelope then reveals frequency differences of dominant modes. I could show that with this method, the large frequency separation $\Delta\nu$ can be extracted from the envelope spectrum¹⁷ even for data of poor signal-to-noise ratio. The result, together with a measurement of ν_{\max} , can then be used for an estimation of the stellar mass and radius with Equations (2.45) and (2.46).

2.9 Where Can We Do Better?

Are we done? Are the mysteries of the Sun and the stars solved? Not by far. A lot is left to explain and the journey has just begun. Here, I will briefly list some of the open questions and issues which are connected to the topics of this thesis and will have to be addressed by helio- and asteroseismic research in the future¹⁸.

As is shown in [Figure 2.12](#), the oscillation eigenfrequencies of Model S and the measured frequencies disagree to a certain extent depending on mode frequency, radial order, and harmonic degree. This disagreement between model frequencies and observed frequencies is commonly referred to as the *surface term*. It subsumes all missing physics in the stellar models, most of which are important in near-surface layers, and are called in their collectivity the *surface effect*. This includes the incomplete modeling of non-adiabaticity in near-surface layers and the turbulent pressure due to the vigorous convection close to the stellar surface.

Magnetic fields are also not included in the stellar models for which the eigenfrequencies are computed. Hence, if a magnetic field is present in the near-surface regions of a star, they may contribute significantly to the surface effect. As the strength of magnetic fields varies over stellar activity cycles (see [Chapter 3](#)), the variation of the surface term as a function of time may hold

¹⁶The analytic signal $x_a(t)$ of a real-valued signal $x(t)$ is defined by $x_a(t) = x(t) + i\text{H}[x](t)$ where $\text{H}[x](t)$ is the Hilbert transform of $x(t)$. The modulus of $x_a(t)$ is then the envelope of the signal.

¹⁷This term describes the power spectral density of the signal envelope, thus *envelope spectrum*.

¹⁸This is by far not an exhaustive list. Some more open topics are discussed by ([Gough 2012](#)).

Figure 2.12: *Left panel:* differences of frequencies between solar Model S and observed frequencies in the sense observation – model. *Right panel:* same as left panel, but scaled by mode inertia (see Section 6.3). This accounts for the fact that modes with less inertia change more for a given perturbation compared to modes with larger inertia. Figure from Basu (2016).

information on the behavior of the near-surface magnetic fields. This was recently investigated by Howe et al. (2017). The results presented in this thesis may be used in the investigation of this, see Chapter 12.

Another issue which demands attention is the mapping of the unknown regions of the solar rotation profile: As can be seen from Figure 2.11, the rotation rate of the polar regions and of the inner half of the Sun have still not been measured. As mentioned before, the upcoming ESA Solar Orbiter mission will help to ascertain rotation rates in the polar regions in the next years. The dynamics of the core may be unveiled by direct measurement of solar g modes frequencies and their rotational splittings (Appourchaux et al. 2010). However, due to their intrinsic low amplitude in the photosphere, very long time series are necessary to detect them unambiguously and directly.

Due to its importance for models of stellar dynamos, the meridional circulation, which is the transport of matter from the equator to the poles, has to be measured. I postpone the discussion of this to Section 3.3.

Another question which can be addressed with seismic techniques is how the solar activity cycle relates to the cycles of other stars. I will discuss this in Chapters 3 and 5.

Solar and Stellar Magnetic Activity

3.1 The Solar Cycle

One of the central questions in solar physics is: *What is the origin of the solar cycle?*¹ As I have outlined in the [Introduction](#), the magnetic field in the Sun is undergoing a cyclic regeneration. In this section, I briefly review some essential observational quantities and phenomena which are connected to the solar cycle and solar magnetic activity. A detailed review on this is given by [Hathaway \(2015\)](#).

3.1.1 Sunspots

One of the first to systematically observe sunspots was Galileo Galilei. One of his sunspot drawings is shown in [Figure 3.1](#). In his drawings, the dark core of larger spots, the so-called *umbra*, can be discerned from the less dark, filamentary *penumbra*. His conclusion that these spots are objects on the solar surface (see the quote in [Figure 3.1](#)) was met with suspicion and contempt at the time, as the heavens were thought to be perfect and free of any blemish. Thanks to Galilei's detailed drawings and records, the temporal evolution of the number of sunspots can be reconstructed back to his time.

[Schwabe \(1844\)](#) was the first to notice a periodicity in the number of sunspots. In his communication, Schwabe wrote: “*By comparing the number of groups with the number of days without spots, one finds that the sunspots had a period of about 10 years [...]*”² Today, the solar cycle is called *Schwabe cycle* and its period is determined to approximately eleven years. We are currently in Schwabe cycle 24 and the first cycle lasted from 1755 to 1766, see [Figure 3.2](#). In 1908, [Hale](#) found that sunspots are regions of strong magnetic fields. After [Hale et al. \(1919\)](#) had discovered that the polarities of leading and trailing sunspots in bipolar sunspot groups change from Schwabe cycle to Schwabe cycle, it was established that a complete magnetic solar cycle is in fact 22 years, now known as a *Hale cycle*.

¹This question is being tackled on many fronts, which is mirrored in the large number of review articles, each concerned with a specific part of the overall problem. Review articles include [Broomhall et al. \(2014\)](#) on “The Sun’s Interior Structure and Dynamics, and the Solar Cycle”, [Fan \(2009\)](#) on “Magnetic Fields in the Solar Convection Zone”, [Charbonneau \(2010\)](#) on “Dynamo models of the solar cycle”, [Usoskin \(2017\)](#) on “A history of solar activity over millennia”, [Miesch \(2005\)](#) on “Large-Scale Dynamics of the Convection Zone and Tachocline”, to name but a few.

²Translated from the German original: “Vergleicht man nun die Zahl der Gruppen und der fleckenfreien Tage mit einander, so findet man, daß die Sonnenflecken eine Periode von ungefähr 10 Jahren hatten [...].”

“HAVING MADE REPEATED OBSERVATIONS I AM AT LAST CONVINCED THAT THE SPOTS ARE OBJECTS CLOSE TO THE SURFACE OF THE SOLAR GLOBE, WHERE THEY ARE CONTINUALLY BEING PRODUCED AND THEN DISSOLVED, SOME QUICKLY AND SOME MORE SLOWLY.”

— Galileo Galilei, *Lettere solari* (1612)

Figure 3.1: Sunspot drawing by Galileo Galilei from June 23, 1613.³

A high-resolution image of a sunspot taken with the Vacuum Tower Telescope on Tenerife is shown in Figure 3.6, see image caption for a detailed description. The sunspot imaged there has a diameter of about 20 000 km. The largest sunspots can have umbrae with diameters of up to 50 000 km. The magnetic field that penetrates the solar surface at the locations of spots can have strengths of up to 6 kG (Livingston et al. 2006). In the region of the strong magnetic field, convective energy transport is impeded. This results in a lower temperature within the spot with a difference in temperature compared to the surrounding quiet Sun⁴ of 500–2000 K. Thus, sunspots appear darker than the surrounding photospheric plasma. The lifetime of a sunspot strongly depends on the size of the spot. Smaller spots tend to have shorter lifetimes, of the order of hours to a few days, whereas the largest sunspots can exist up to four months (see, e.g., Chapter 6 of Solanki et al. 2006 and references therein for a more detailed discussion of sunspot properties). Sunspots rotate faster around the solar rotation axis than the surrounding photospheric plasma of the quiet Sun. This is taken as indication that the magnetic flux tubes, which cause the spots, are anchored in a deeper, faster-rotating layer.⁵

³A collection of sunspot drawings can be found on this website: <http://galileo.rice.edu/>

⁴The term *quiet Sun* refers to regions on the Sun without strong magnetic activity, i.e., outside of sunspots or pores.

⁵See the paragraph on the near-surface shear layer in Section 2.7.1 and the references which are given there.

SILSO graphics (<http://sidc.be/silso>) Royal Observatory of Belgium 2017 October 2

Figure 3.2: The international sunspot number S_n over the last 317 years. The gray data points before 1749 are yearly mean values. The blue data are 13-month smoothed values. Image source: SILSO, Royal Observatory of Belgium, Brussels.

3.1.2 The Ups and Downs

In Figure 3.2, the international sunspot number is shown as a function of time. With over 400 years' worth of sunspot data available⁶, the length of the Schwabe cycle can be determined to about 11 years with a standard deviation of about 14 months (Hathaway 2015).

The total solar irradiance (TSI), which is measured as the power of solar radiation per square meter that reaches the Earth, is correlated with the solar activity cycle (Kopp 2016). Sunspots on the solar disk lower the TSI. However, this decrease is outweighed by the increase of irradiance caused by *faculae*. These structures are bright regions with stronger magnetic field than in the quiet Sun. Their magnetic field is not strong enough to hinder convective energy transport from below. The plasma density in faculae is slightly decreased and, as a result, radiation from deeper and hotter layers can escape (Solanki et al. 2006).

The regular 11-year pattern of solar activity sometimes goes through extended periods with only few or even no observable sunspots. The period between 1800 and 1820 is known as the Dalton minimum, see Figure 3.2. Even though the Sun was already observed regularly between 1645 and 1715 (not shown in this plot), the number of recorded sunspots within these 70 years totaled to only a handful per decade (Maunder 1894). This period, now known as the Maunder Minimum phase of solar activity, is one of several Grand Minima, which occurred over the last millennia (Usoskin 2017). Levels of solar activity before the invention of the telescope and the systematic recording of sunspots can be reconstructed with indirect methods. One of these methods compares the cosmogenic isotope production rate in the Earth's atmosphere from model calculations and from measurements in, e.g., polar ice cores (Usoskin 2017).

Another striking feature of the solar cycle is illustrated in Figure 3.3. Here, the areas covered by sunspots are shown as a function of time and latitude. The coverage of spots in strips of equal

⁶For sunspot number time series which reach back to Galilei, see, e.g., Kopp et al. (2016) and references therein.

Figure 3.3: Sunspot area between 1874 and 2015 as a function of latitude. Color coding indicates coverage of spots in the latitude strips of equal area. Image from [Hathaway \(2015\)](#).⁷

area is indicated by the color of the individual latitude strip. In this spatio-temporal diagram, commonly called a *butterfly diagram*, it can be seen that the first spots of each cycle appear in mid-latitudes around 25° north and south of the equator. As the cycle progresses, the spots appear closer to the equator. Two consecutive sunspot cycles can overlap during the activity minimum between them.⁸ In magnetic butterfly diagrams, i.e., if the magnetic polarity were encoded in Figure 3.3, the mean polarity of each wing of the butterfly changes from Schwabe cycle to Schwabe cycle (see, e.g., Figure 17 of [Hathaway 2015](#)).

3.1.3 The Helioseismic Solar Cycle

The properties of the Sun's p modes are also affected by its magnetic activity cycle. Investigating activity-related changes of p-mode parameters can thus yield insight into the processes that occur in the solar interior over the solar cycle. Mode frequencies and lifetimes vary in phase with the level of solar activity, while mode amplitudes vary in anti-phase with it. Mode frequencies are affected in two ways by the magnetic field associated with the solar cycle: First, the additional restoring force exerted by the magnetic field changes the frequencies *directly*. Second, the physical properties of the p-mode cavities are changed by the magnetic field, which affects mode frequencies *indirectly*. Turbulent convection, through which p modes are excited, is also affected by the presence of a magnetic field ([Muller 1988](#)) and regions of strong magnetic field are known to suppress acoustic waves ([Braun et al. 1987](#)). The exact mechanisms that cause the variation of damping and excitation of acoustic modes are still under debate.⁹ Previous studies which aimed to learn about the subsurface structure and strength of the global solar magnetic field with seismic techniques are referenced and briefly discussed in Sections 8.1 and 9.1.

The differential rotation profile of the Sun is slightly changing over the course of the solar cycle. This is depicted in Figure 3.4, where the so-called torsional oscillations can be seen as bands of slower (colored green to black) and faster-rotation (colored red to orange), which migrate from mid-latitudes towards the equator and towards the poles. The mean of the rotation profile was subtracted. This pattern exists in at least the outer half of the convection zone, probably all the way down to the tachocline ([Howe 2009](#), and references therein). The slower branch of the torsional oscillations is connected to the activity belt, as can be seen from the black contours in

⁷The upper half of Figure 9 of [Hathaway \(2015\)](#) is used here.

⁸During these times, there are sunspots from cycle N at high latitudes and sunspots from cycle number $N - 1$ close to the equator.

⁹See Section 5.1, Chapter 6, Section 8.1, and Section 9.1 for more detailed discussions and references for the variation of p-mode parameters over the solar cycle. A concise review on the topic is given by [Broomhall et al. \(2014\)](#).

Figure 3.4: Residual rotation rate at $0.99 R_{\odot}$ as a function of time and latitude after subtraction of the temporal mean at each latitude. The rotation rate is obtained by merging inversions of HMI, MDI, and GONG data. Regions of strong photospheric magnetic field are shown in black contours. Figure from Broomhall et al. (2014).¹⁰

Figure 3.4 which indicate photospheric magnetic fields (compare these to the butterfly diagram in Figure 3.3). A branch of faster than average rotation can be seen at the equatorward edge of the activity belt. It appears several years before the first active regions of the next solar cycle.

The high latitude regions with magnetic field are associated with the faster-rotating branch of the torsional oscillations. Rempel (2006) was able to reproduce this pattern in simulations of the solar dynamo by additional surface cooling in the active region belt and the back-reaction of the magnetic field on the differential rotation. The variation of the meridional circulation¹¹ with the solar cycle (e.g., Hathaway and Rightmire 2010) seems to be due to the back-reaction of magnetic field on it as well (Hazra and Choudhuri 2017).

The phenomena and quantities I mentioned in the last two sections are merely a small sample of all those which are varying with the solar activity cycle. Extensive lists and discussions of them can be found in the reviews listed in footnote 1 on page 35. Any theory which tries to explain the mechanisms that drive the solar cycle and its cyclic regeneration of the magnetic field must be able to reproduce these observations reasonably well. The case of the solar activity cycle serves as a testbed for dynamo theory and dynamo simulations. In a broader picture, the questions “*Is the Sun special?*” and “*How does the solar cycle relate to stellar counterparts?*” arise.

3.2 Stellar Activity Cycles

Observing stellar activity cycles from the ground is hindered by the Earth’s atmosphere and the trivial fact that stars, compared to the Sun, have a low apparent brightness and cannot be

¹⁰Reprinted by permission from Springer Customer Service Centre GmbH: Springer Nature, Space Science Reviews, Volume 186, 191, “The Sun’s Interior Structure and Dynamics, and the Solar Cycle”, by A.-M. Broomhall, P. Chatterjee, R. Howe et al., 2014, doi.org/10.1007/s11214-014-0101-3

¹¹See Section 3.3 for details on the meridional circulation and its role in the solar dynamo.

Figure 3.5: Four time series of the Mt. Wilson Ca II H & K long-term observation program. The ordinate in all plots is the dimensionless S index. Figure adapted from Baliunas et al. (1995). © AAS. Reproduced with permission.¹⁴

spatially resolved.¹² Hence, observing and counting starspots is not practical.¹³ Spectroscopic proxies can be used to ascertain the level of stellar magnetic activity.

The two prominent Fraunhofer absorption lines of singly ionized calcium, namely Ca II H with a wavelength of 3968 Å and Ca II K with a wavelength of 3934 Å, can be observed from the ground. For the Sun and solar-like stars, they originate in the chromosphere.¹⁵ Due to departures from radiative equilibrium, these lines go into emission in active regions. The intensity of the emission in Ca II H & K can be used as a spectroscopic indicator of the level of magnetic activity of a star (Skumanich et al. 1975; Schrijver et al. 1989).¹⁶

The long-term stellar Ca II H & K emission monitoring program by the Mount Wilson Observatory in California (started in 1966, see Wilson 1968) yielded the largest sample of confirmed stellar cycles to date. Baliunas et al. (1995) reported on the results of 111 stars of spectral types F2–M2 V on or near the main-sequence. Four of their time series are shown in Figure 3.5 with the dimensionless S index on the ordinate.¹⁷ In each panel, the catalog number of the star, its color index $B - V$, the cycle length in years (if detected), and a grade for the false alarm probability of the cycle are given. In the top left panel, the time series for the Sun is shown. The solar cycle is clearly visible. In the top right panel, the time series of the G2 V star HD 81809 with a cycle of 8.2 years is shown. The lower left, a 7.0 year cycle of the K2 V star HD 160346 can be clearly identified. The G2 V star HD 143761 in the lower right panel did not show a cyclic behavior over

¹²Bar the interferometric observations of a few nearby giant stars, e.g., Haubois et al. (2009) or Ohnaka et al. (2017)

¹³However, as I will briefly discuss in Section 3.2.1, the variation of stellar luminosity due to starspots is imprinted in photometric time series.

¹⁴Panels are extracted from Fig. 1 of Baliunas et al., “Chromospheric variations in main-sequence stars”, The Astrophysical Journal, 438, 269-287, 1995. [dx.doi.org/10.1086/175072](https://doi.org/10.1086/175072)

¹⁵For an in-depth discussion of “Stellar Chromospheric Activity” and details about proxies of stellar activity calculated from Ca II H & K measurements, see Hall (2008) and references therein.

¹⁶Or as Wilson (1968) put it in the introduction of his paper: “At maximum, as compared with minimum, the whole calcium network is notably more intense, and plages are more numerous and brighter. Since all this radiation is concentrated into narrow bands of the order of 0.5 Å width at the centers of the photospheric H and K absorption lines, it is quite reasonable to suppose that suitable measures of the strengths of these chromospheric emissions in stars should provide information on the stellar analogues of the solar cycle.”

¹⁷See Section 2.2 in Baliunas et al. (1995) for more information on the S index.

Figure 3.6: An active region observed at the Vacuum Tower Telescope. The resolution is 0.03 arcsec/pixel which corresponds to 22 km/pixel. The observed area has an approximate size of $45 \cdot 10^3$ km \times $53 \cdot 10^3$ km on the solar surface. In the dark *umbra* of the sunspot, the magnetic field is strongest and approximately vertical to the solar surface. In the *penumbra* of the spot, the magnetic field lines are more inclined. The dark features in the center of the image are called *pores*, concentrations of magnetic field without a penumbra. Outside the spots and pores, granulation can be seen. Granules are generally brighter in the center and darker on their edges. They are formed when hot material is ascending due to convection. When the material reaches the photosphere, energy is radiated away. The cooler material descends in the darker regions between the granules. Image courtesy of Sebastian Hoch.

the observed time period. Only little variation of the S index can be seen for this star. It may currently be in a phase similar to the Maunder Minimum of the Sun.

As Skumanich (1972) showed, the level of emission in the H and K lines as well as the rotational velocity decrease as the square root of the age of the star. Meibom et al. (2015) and Saders et al. (2016) showed that the stellar rotation rate can indeed be used as a reliable determinant of stellar age if proper calibration is applied. The technique of determining stellar ages from the stars' rotation rates bears the name *gyrochronology*. The rotation rate can be derived from stellar photometric time series (e.g., McQuillan et al. 2014) or from stellar spectra (e.g., Molenda-Żakowicz et al. 2013).

Metcalf and Saders (2017) found that the Rossby number (i.e., rotation period divided by convective turnover time $Ro = P_{\text{rot}}/\tau_c$) of a star may be crucial for the length of its activity cycle. They found that once stars reach $Ro \approx 2$, the surface rotation rate changes more slowly with age and the period of the activity cycle gradually grows before the cycle disappears eventually. The slowed change of the rotation period at a certain stellar age was attributed by Saders et al. (2016) to weakened magnetic braking. As I will discuss in the next section, rotation and the transport of angular momentum are key ingredients in most theories of stellar dynamos.

3.2.1 Starspots

Sunspots cover only a small fraction of the solar surface; the unit for the size of a sunspot is the microhemisphere (MHS), which corresponds to parts per million of the visible hemisphere. The largest sunspots have umbrae which are of the order of a few hundred MHS. Thus, they cover about a tenth of a percent of the visible surface (Bogdan et al. 1988; Kiess et al. 2014). Figure 3.6 shows a sunspot with a diameter of $\approx 20\,000$ km and several smaller regions of magnetic field which are called pores. Starspots can reach much larger sizes. Measured amplitudes of the modulation in the optical brightness of cool stars imply the existence of starspots which cover up to 40% of the visible stellar hemisphere (see Berdyugina 2005, and references therein). Starspots can produce a signal similar to that of a transiting planet in photometric time series. The effect of their passage over the stellar disk on radial velocity measurements and on stellar brightness variations can be modeled (e.g., Dumusque et al. 2014). The signal of starspots in photometric time series can also be used to infer differential rotation and their latitudinal distribution (Roettenbacher et al. 2013; Reinhold and Arlt 2015; Santos et al. 2016). The variability of stellar photometric time series itself, called S_{ph} to reflect its connection to the chromospheric S index, can be used as a proxy for stellar magnetic activity (García et al. 2010; Mathur et al. 2014b). At a stellar age of about 2 Gyr magnetic-activity-induced stellar brightness variations switch from being spot-dominated to faculae-dominated (e.g., Radick et al. 1998).

3.3 Dynamo Models

The objective of dynamo models is to explain the cyclic regeneration of the solar magnetic field and the associated phenomena. Such models must include simplifications of the complex physics that governs the magnetized, high-density plasma in the solar interior. Over the last half-century, several mechanisms have been considered to be responsible for the solar dynamo. Here, I will focus on the most widely used mechanisms and the most important ingredients of solar dynamo models.¹⁸

Dynamo models must include processes that explain the observed polarity reversal of the global magnetic field and the sequential generation of its components: Over the course of the solar cycle, the components of the observed global solar magnetic field vary in strength. The global magnetic field can be decomposed into a toroidal and a poloidal component. While at solar maximum, the toroidal component of the magnetic field in the solar interior is strongest, its poloidal component is strongest during times of low activity. The toroidal component is manifested in sunspots, where ropes of magnetic flux pierce through the photosphere. In the polar regions, the poloidal component is observed to be strongest. Both the toroidal and the poloidal components of the global solar magnetic field undergo a reversal of polarity every eleven years.¹⁹ A full magnetic cycle is thus a sequence

$$P(+) \rightarrow T(-) \rightarrow P(-) \rightarrow T(+) \rightarrow P(+) \rightarrow \dots, \quad (3.1)$$

where P and T denote the poloidal and toroidal component of the magnetic field, and $(+)$ and $(-)$ denote opposite polarities.²⁰ The mechanisms which are responsible for the generation of a

¹⁸The information presented in this section is gathered from the reviews Dikpati and Gilman (2007), Charbonneau (2010), and Cameron et al. (2016) on this topic.

¹⁹The reversals of the toroidal and the poloidal field are not in phase.

²⁰This notation is borrowed from Charbonneau 2010, Equation (9).

toroidal from a poloidal field and vice versa are the main differentiators between models of the solar dynamo. Here, I focus on a class of dynamo models called flux-transport dynamos.

In Figure 3.7, a flux-transport dynamo is depicted for one sequence $P \rightarrow T \rightarrow P$, which corresponds to the solar Schwabe cycle. These types of dynamo models can reproduce many of the observed features of the solar cycle. Differential rotation is essential for the generation of the toroidal field component from a poloidal field in these models. The radially and latitudinally dependent rotation in the Sun (see Section 2.7.1) bodily drags (advects) a given poloidal field. Due to the high conductivity of the plasma in the solar interior, the magnetic field is forced to follow the plasma's motion (see, e.g., Priest 2014). Thus, the radial and latitudinal gradients in the rotation profile lead to shearing of the poloidal field (see Panel (a) of Figure 3.7). The radial gradient in the solar differential rotation is strongest in the tachocline region and the near-surface shear layer. Hence, in these two layers the Ω -effect — the winding up of poloidal into toroidal field $P \rightarrow T$ — can take place. It appears to be consensus that the Ω -effect is mainly responsible for the cyclic regeneration of the toroidal field (see, e.g., Charbonneau 2010; Cameron and Schüssler 2015; Cameron and Schüssler 2017).

There are two primary theories of how the latitudinal migration of active regions over the course of the 11-year cycle (see Figure 3.3) is generated. In the first proposed theory, radial shear due to the gradient in the rotation profile causes toroidal flux to propagate latitudinally. Whether the migration occurs equatorward or poleward depends on the mechanism which generates the poloidal field from the toroidal field and on the sign of the radial gradient of the differential rotation profile (Yoshimura 1975). Precise knowledge of the profile of differential rotation is thus indispensable. In the second theory, the meridional circulation, which is thought to be equatorward in the tachocline region, advects the toroidal flux after it has been created by the Ω -effect. This leads to an equatorward migration of active regions over the solar cycle.

No consensus has been reached yet on what the generating mechanism(s) of the poloidal magnetic field from the toroidal field $T \rightarrow P$ is (are). One of these proposed mechanisms operates on toroidal magnetic flux rising from the bottom of the convection zone to its top. During the ascent, the element of magnetic flux is subject to the Coriolis force, which tilts the rising flux tubes which results in a poloidal component (see panel (c)-(d) in Figure 3.7). Integrated over the length of the solar cycle and over many elements of rising toroidal flux, this can lead to the generation of a large-scale poloidal magnetic field (Parker 1955). Mechanisms of this type are commonly referred to as α -effects, due to the notation of a parameter or tensor in the mathematical formulation of them (see Section 3.2 of Charbonneau 2010). Another $T \rightarrow P$ mechanism (depicted in panels (d)-(i) of Figure 3.7), proposed by Babcock (1961), Leighton (1964), and Leighton (1969), puts more weight on the individual active regions in the photosphere: The leading spots of bipolar magnetic regions generally appear closer to the equator than the trailing spot which is of opposite polarity. Thus, the flux of the leading spots gets canceled with the flux of opposite sign from leading spots in the other hemisphere more efficiently than the flux of the trailing spots. It is known, that there is a poleward meridional flow at the photosphere (Duvall Jr. 1979). This flow then transports the remaining magnetic flux from decayed active regions towards the poles and thus contributes to the generation of poloidal magnetic field (e.g., Cameron and Schüssler 2017). This process is depicted in panel (g) of Figure 3.7. Flux-transport dynamo models²¹, where mainly the near-surface meridional flow is responsible for the regeneration of the poloidal field, and the toroidal field is created through the Ω -effect, are called Babcock-Leighton dynamo models.

²¹See the introduction of Cameron and Schüssler (2017) or Charbonneau (2010) for concise descriptions of different types of dynamo models.

Figure 3.7: Schematic depiction of a flux-transport dynamo model in a solar-like star. The orange inner sphere represents the radiative core and the outer blue mesh symbolizes the stellar surface. The convection zone is in between these two. *Panel (a)*: the sense of rotation is indicated by the arrow at the pole. A solar-like rotation profile is assumed (see Figure 2.11). The poloidal magnetic field (black lines, polarity indicated by arrows) is sheared by the strong gradient in the rotation profile at the base of the convection zone (Ω -effect). *Panel (b)*: toroidal magnetic field at the base of the convection zone. Note the opposite polarity in the northern and southern hemispheres. *Panel (c)*: at a certain magnetic field strength, the toroidal field becomes buoyant. Flux tubes start to rise to the surface. The flux gets twisted due to the Coriolis force. Spots form where the tubes pierce the surface. *Panels (d)–(f)*: more flux emerges. It gets spread in latitude as well as longitude as the spots decay. Note the polarities of the bipolar groups and the polar magnetic field indicated in (f). *Panel (g)*: the meridional circulation is indicated by yellow loops. Surface flux of decayed sunspots is transported poleward. Polar fields reverse polarity due to this. *Panel (h)*: magnetic flux is transported downward and equatorward. The poloidal field has opposite polarity compared to panel (a). *Panel (i)*: configuration as in panel (a) but with opposite sign. The sequence is complete. Figure from Dikpati and Gilman (2007).²²

²²Figure from M. Dikpati and P. A. Gilman, *Global solar dynamo models: simulations and predictions of cyclic photospheric fields and long-term non-reversing interior fields*, *New Journal of Physics*, 2007, Vol. 9, 297. doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/9/8/297

The sub-surface configuration and amplitude of the meridional circulation are still a matter of debate. There are measurements of the meridional circulation with only one cell in each hemisphere (e.g., Giles et al. 1997; Braun and Fan 1998; Hathaway 2012), with multiple cells in depth (Zhao et al. 2013), and with multiple flow cells in latitude as well as depth (Schad et al. 2013). Böning (2017) could show that both the single-cell flow profiles and the multi-cell flow profiles are consistent within the measurement errors. The strength of the meridional circulation controls the length of the activity cycle (Dikpati and Charbonneau 1999) and its precise determination would help advance models of the solar dynamo and their predictive capabilities.

It should be noted that other types of stellar dynamo models, e.g., without storage of toroidal magnetic flux in a tachocline, are investigated. This is motivated by the fact that a large fraction of fully convective stars is also exhibiting magnetic activity (Brun and Browning 2017, and references therein). These models include flux generating mechanisms which operate in the bulk of the convection zone or a near-surface shear layer (e.g., Brandenburg 2005)

To close this chapter, I quote from the abstract of Metcalfe and Saders (2017): “*After decades of effort, the solar activity cycle is exceptionally well characterized, but it remains poorly understood.*”

Scientific Contributions of This Thesis

To put the research and results of this thesis into context to the science questions that motivate them, I want to quote two researchers, who have greatly advanced (or even developed parts of) helio- and asteroseismology with their work over the last decades. In her review on “Solar Interior Rotation and its Variation” Rachel Howe wrote (Howe 2009):

“[...] a complete numerical model of the solar dynamo — vital for any long-term predictive capability — is still lacking, and helioseismic observations still have an important part to play in constraining such models as they develop.”

Furthermore, Douglas Gough wrote the following sentences in the conclusion of his review entitled “What Have We Learned from Helioseismology, What Have We Really Learned, and What Do We Aspire to Learn?” (Gough 2012), which go nicely with the developments presented in this thesis:

“It must be appreciated that the Sun is an important benchmark for the whole of stellar physics, and helioseismology for asteroseismology. Finding answers to many of these questions is likely to be assisted by new helioseismological findings, although seismology alone will not be enough. Answers will not come easily – the easy questions were answered quickly (although not necessarily easily) in the early days. But the rewards from answering the new questions – designing subtle, hardly detectable, seismic diagnostics and developing techniques to analyse them – are potentially great.”

In this thesis, I develop “subtle [...] seismic diagnostics” which help in “constraining [...] models” of solar and stellar dynamos. These developments shall help answer questions as “Can we detect magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters of stars?” and “Where in the solar interior is the location of the dynamo?”

The research that I conducted uses methods from helio- and asteroseismology (see Chapter 2) to learn about the activity related changes of properties of stellar acoustic oscillations and the magnetic fields which cause them (see Chapter 3). In the following remarks, I briefly summarize the main findings and developments of this thesis and they should be understood in the context of the topics, open problems, and the relevant scientific literature, which were discussed in the previous two chapters.

Stellar Activity and Oscillation Parameters

Chapter 5 – Stars In this chapter I present my work on the search for signatures of stellar activity in the oscillation parameters of solar-like stars in the *Kepler* time series of a set of 24

solar-like stars. As [García et al. \(2010\)](#) showed, it is possible to detect activity-related changes of p-mode parameters in stars. However, more detections of this kind have been sparse, at best, after [García et al.](#)'s discovery. Increasing the number of stars with seismically detected activity (cycles) may help to learn about the dependence of p-mode parameters on the strength of stellar activity and about the dependence of their variational amplitude as a function of fundamental stellar parameters as mass, rotation rate, and age. This is instrumental for gaining insight about the fundamental ingredients of stellar dynamos.

Here, I devise a method to determine the average shift of the p-mode frequencies of these stars via the cross-correlation of periodograms of segments of the entire time series. The uncertainties of the frequency shifts are then calculated via an approach in which the time series are resampled. There are other methods of measuring the frequency shifts and calculation of the associated uncertainties which are found in the literature: [Régulo et al. \(2016\)](#) used a similar cross-correlation technique but a different approach on the estimation of the uncertainties. [García et al. \(2010\)](#) used both a cross-correlation technique and fitting of the individual mode peaks in the periodogram to estimate the frequency shifts. However, with the method of calculating the uncertainty of the measured frequency shift which I present here, the uncertainties are not underestimated, as effects of the correlation structure of the fitted cross-correlation functions are circumvented. By checking the adequacy and reliability of the method on solar data, I show that it returns the correct temporal variation of mode frequencies and the associated uncertainties. Both were in line with previously published results (see, e.g., the results of [Chaplin et al. 2007b](#)). The temporal variation of mode amplitudes is determined by computing a proxy for them by measuring the excess of the p-mode peaks over the background in the periodogram.

I detect significant frequency shifts in time for all but one of the 24 stars. For six of them, I show that the changes in their oscillation frequencies and amplitudes are indeed related to variation in the level of stellar magnetic activity. The changes of these two quantities are strongly anti-correlated for these six stars, which is a telltale sign of stellar magnetic activity (see references in [Section 5.1](#)). These six stars increase the number of stars with seismically detected magnetic activity by more than a factor of two. Finally, I show that the amplitude of the temporal frequency shift is decreasing with stellar age and rotation period. This is expected from stellar dynamo theory, because rotation, which is a key ingredient in the cyclic regeneration of stellar magnetic fields (see [Section 3.3](#)), slows down with age.

The major scientific contribution of this chapter is thus the development of a robust method to detect temporal changes in the parameters of acoustic oscillations of stars and the detection of signatures of stellar magnetic activity in six stars. Adding more detections of this kind will allow understanding the solar activity cycle in the context of other stars with asteroseismology. There are a number of upcoming satellite missions¹ that will produce data comparable to that of *Kepler*. Hence, the results presented in [Chapter 5](#) can be used in the future to establish a database of seismically measured stellar activity cycles, which will help to identify those fundamental stellar parameters that are crucial for the operation of stellar dynamos.

Chapter 6 – The Sun The main result of this chapter is the extension, refinement, and confirmation of previous measurements of the temporal variation of p-mode parameters over the solar cycle. I use two cycles (22 years) worth of data from the ground-based GONG network,

¹The NASA-led mission TESS (**T**ransiting **E**xoplanet **S**urvey **S**atellite, [Ricker et al. \(2014\)](#)), set to launch in March 2018, and the ESA-led mission PLATO (**P**LAnetary **T**ransits and **O**scillations of stars, [Rauer et al. \(2013\)](#)), aimed to launch in 2026, are the two most prominent examples. Both will produce data for asteroseismology.

which makes this the study of solar p-mode parameters of intermediate harmonic degree with the longest data baseline to date. The last in-depth studies of this kind were carried out by [Komm et al. \(2000a\)](#) and [Komm et al. \(2000b\)](#). By expanding their analysis to a longer time series and investigating different dependencies of the mode parameters, we can hope to learn more about the response of solar oscillations to the changing level of solar magnetic activity. This is the major contribution of this chapter.

I investigate the fractional change of mode parameters, with focus on mode damping rates (mode widths) and mode amplitudes, for mode sets of different ranges of frequencies and harmonic degrees. I demonstrate that the fractional change of mode parameters is largest for modes with frequencies of 2400–3300 μHz . This is in contrast to the observed shifts of mode frequencies along the solar cycle, which are largest for modes with highest frequencies (see [Section 3.1.3](#) as well as [Broomhall et al. \(2014\)](#) and references therein). This indicates that the respective underlying mechanisms, which change mode frequencies, on the one hand and affect the excitation and damping of modes, on the other hand, are somewhat different. I also show that mode widths and amplitudes saturate at a certain level of solar magnetic activity. This is also in contrast to mode frequencies for which such behavior is not observed (e.g., [Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998](#)).

Furthermore, I find the frequency distribution of the mode amplitudes is best fitted by an asymmetric Voigt profile. This result is of particular interest to modelers of the excitation and damping of acoustic stellar oscillations (see, e.g., [Houdek et al. \(1999\)](#)).

Finally, I confirm that the physical parameters of the oscillations — mode damping rate, mean squared velocity, and mode energy — change along the solar cycle and the energy supply rate to the modes does not change. This confirms the earlier results of, e.g., [Komm et al. \(2000b\)](#), and [Chaplin et al. \(2000\)](#). This also highlights the impact of magnetic activity on the detectability of stellar oscillations: As the level of magnetic activity increases, the amplitudes of the oscillations decrease and their damping increases ([Chaplin et al. 2011](#)).

Magnetic Field Concentrations in Stellar Interiors

Chapter 8 – Calculation of the General Matrix Element The central contribution of this chapter is an analytical expression of the general matrix element (see [Section 7.3](#) for the formal definition), which can be used to calculate the effect of large-scale toroidal magnetic fields on solar and stellar global oscillation eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies. This is one of those “subtle [...] seismic diagnostics” [Gough](#) wrote about.

Due to the Lorentz force that is added to the stellar structure equations by the inclusion of a magnetic field, stellar eigenmodes of the equilibrium model (see [Section 2.7.2](#)) can couple. The strength of this coupling, also known as the direct effect, is quantified by the general matrix element. The analytical expression of the general matrix element is calculated in the convenient basis of generalized spherical harmonics, which helps to separate the radial from the angular dependencies. The angular integrals that appear in the calculation of the general matrix element can thus be expressed as a sum of products of Wigner $3j$ symbols. This facilitates the efficient numerical calculation of the general matrix element. Selection rules, which are imposed by properties of the generalized spherical harmonics and the analytical expression of the general matrix element, are found. These are used to limit the number of terms of the general matrix element and determine the set of coupling modes.

The general matrix element may be used to assess the perturbation of mode frequencies and eigenfunctions by sub-surface toroidal zonal magnetic field configurations. The result of this chapter is thus a prerequisite for forward calculation of solar and stellar large-scale subsurface magnetic fields of arbitrary toroidal configuration and strength. The magnetic fields can be chosen such as to model their change over the course of the activity cycle. Such forward calculations are presented in Chapter 9. In an analogous approach, [Schad et al. \(2011\)](#) showed that it is possible to measure the solar meridional circulation with an inversion scheme that utilizes the general matrix element. Thus, the main result of this chapter represents an important first step in the development of a seismic inversion technique which will let us learn about the subsurface solar magnetic field.

Chapter 9 – Forward Calculations In this chapter, first, the general matrix element for the indirect effect is calculated in the basis of generalized spherical harmonics. The indirect effect that is acting on the eigenmodes is due to the change of the stellar structural quantities that is caused by the added magnetic field. Then, the complete general matrix element, comprising both the direct and indirect effect, is used to compute the frequency shifts of eigenmodes of a solar model for six models of toroidal subsurface magnetic field concentrations. The ansatz from quasi-degenerate perturbation theory ([Lavelly and Ritzwoller 1992](#)) that is used here allows for the calculation of the general matrix element of both self-coupling and cross-coupling of modes. However, as the self-coupling is dominant, cross-coupling is neglected here.

As mentioned in Section 2.9 and shown in Figure 2.12, the computed and observed frequencies of solar p modes disagree by several μHz . From my forward calculations, I find that this *surface effect* may be caused (at least partially) by toroidal magnetic fields in the outer $\approx 10\%$ of the Sun.

I demonstrate that a strong magnetic field located at the solar tachocline cannot be responsible for the observed shifts of p-mode frequencies over the solar cycle. Even for the strong magnetic field located at the tachocline, which I model here, the resulting frequency shifts are orders of magnitudes smaller than the observed values. However, this does not exclude the existence of such a magnetic field concentration in this part of the Sun.

As another major result of this chapter, I find that the difference of the calculated frequency shifts for two differently strong magnetic field configurations that are located around $0.9R_{\odot}$ produces a pattern in the frequency shifts and amplitudes thereof which strongly resembles the observed values. This shows that the formalism I present here can indeed be used for “constraining [...] models“ of the solar dynamo with seismic techniques.

Developments

Stellar Magnetic Activity and Variability of Oscillation Parameters

This chapter and Appendix A were originally published as

“Stellar magnetic activity and variability of oscillation parameters:
An investigation of 24 solar-like stars observed by *Kepler*”,
Astronomy & Astrophysics, Volume 598, A77, February 2017,

by René Kiefer, Ariane Schad, Guy Davies, and Markus Roth.

Abstract

Context. The Sun and solar-like stars undergo activity cycles for which the underlying mechanisms are not well understood. The oscillations of the Sun are known to vary with its activity cycle and these changes provide diagnostics on the conditions below the photosphere. *Kepler* has detected oscillations in hundreds of solar-like stars but as of yet, no widespread detection of signatures of magnetic activity cycles in the oscillation parameters of these stars have been reported.

Aims. We analyse the photometric short cadence *Kepler* time series of a set of 24 solar-like stars, which were observed for at least 960 days each, with the aim to find signatures of stellar magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters.

Methods. We analyse the temporal evolution of oscillation parameters by measuring mode frequency shifts, changes in the height of the p-mode envelope, as well as granulation time scales.

Results. For 23 of the 24 investigated stars, we find significant frequency shifts in time. We present evidence for magnetic activity in six of them. We find that the amplitude of the frequency shifts decreases with stellar age and rotation period. For the most prominent example, KIC 8006161, we find that, similar to the solar case, frequency shifts are smallest for the lowest and largest for the highest p-mode frequencies.

Conclusions. These findings show that magnetic activity can be routinely observed in the oscillation parameters for solar-like stars, which opens up the possibility to place the solar activity cycle in the context of other stars by asteroseismology.

5.1 Introduction

Understanding the solar dynamo, exactly how and where it operates within the Sun, is a major open task in modern astrophysics. Helio- and asteroseismology are outstanding tools to probe the interiors of the Sun and other stars. The vast amount of data which has become available thanks to satellite missions like *CoRoT* (Baglin et al. 2006; Auvergne et al. 2009) and *Kepler* (Borucki et al. 2010; Koch et al. 2010) enables us to investigate stellar cycles for a wide range of stellar types. By putting the Sun and its magnetic activity cycle into context to similar stars, we can widen our perspective on the basic processes at work in dynamos in different physical environments and may be able to decide between opposing dynamo theories.

The better part of known activity cycles of main-sequence stars was detected from Mount Wilson Observatory (Wilson 1978; Baliunas et al. 1995). Their measurements of fluxes in the line cores of Ca II H and K, which can be used as proxies for stellar activity (Hall 2008, and references therein), suggest a relation between the age, the rotation, and the activity of stars. For a subset of solar-type stars Baliunas et al. (1995) found that younger stars exhibit higher average levels of activity and rapid rotation rates, while older stars with a slower rotation usually have cycles with lower levels of magnetic activity. A relation of this kind was already proposed by Skumanich (1972), who found that stellar Ca II emissions decay as the inverse square root of the age. Brandenburg et al. (1998) and Saar and Brandenburg (1999) made an empirical classification of stars from the Mount Wilson Observatory sample in a rotation-activity scheme. They found that most stars fall into one of three distinct branches when examining the ratio of cycle and rotation periods as a function of chromospheric activity. Karoff et al. (2013) used ground-based observations in combination with data from the *Kepler* satellite to test age-rotation-activity relations.

Helioseismology found that the frequencies of solar acoustic oscillations (p modes) are positively correlated with solar magnetic activity (e.g. Woodard and Noyes 1985; Libbrecht and Woodard 1990; Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998), whereas mode amplitudes are anti-correlated with it (e.g. Pallé et al. 1990; Komm et al. 2000b; Broomhall et al. 2015). Activity-related frequency shifts are larger for modes of higher frequency (Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998), because these modes have their maximum sensitivity to structural changes in the solar interior in shallower layers than modes of low frequency (Basu et al. 2012). This was recently used by Salabert et al. (2015) to study the change of sub-surface solar activity as a function of time and for different depths.

In an analysis of photometric data of the *CoRoT* satellite, García et al. (2010) found evidence for an activity cycle with $P_{\text{cyc}} > 120$ d in the F5V star HD 49933. They found shifts in the frequencies of the star's p modes which showed a cycle-like behaviour and, in addition, changes in mode amplitudes which were anti-correlated to the frequency shifts. Later, Salabert et al. (2011) found the frequency shifts of HD 49933 to be dependent on mode frequency. The *Kepler* satellite produced a huge data set on solar-like stars with asteroseismic import, which shows great promise for many more detections of the kind García et al. made. Vida et al. (2014) found hints of cyclic activity in the *Kepler* data of nine fast-rotating late-type stars. Recently, Salabert et al. (2016b) investigated *Kepler* and spectroscopic data from the young solar analog KIC 10644253. They found variability in the p-mode frequencies of this star with a modulation of about 1.5 years.

In this paper, we describe our efforts to find signatures of stellar magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters of solar-like stars, focussing on the shifts of p-mode frequencies and the variation of the height of the p-mode envelope. In Section 5.2 we describe our approach to measure these quantities and to estimate the errors on them. Section 5.3 is dedicated to a presentation of the

results and a more detailed discussion of two stars from our sample. Section 5.4 gives a conclusion of our findings.

5.2 Methodology

5.2.1 Data and Computation of Periodograms

We analysed *Kepler* data from 24 stars, which were observed in the satellite’s short cadence mode. Only data from the *Kepler* data release 25 was used in this work. In this data release, the scrambling of the short-cadence collateral smear data, which was reported in the Global Erratum for *Kepler* Q0-Q17 & K2 C0-C5 Short-Cadence Data, and the Dynablock calibration problem, which was reported in the Data Release 24 Notes Q0–Q17 Erratum, are corrected. These 24 stars were selected because they are known to exhibit solar-like oscillations (e.g. Mathur et al. 2012; Appourchaux et al. 2012; Huber et al. 2013b) and are known to be similar to the Sun regarding fundamental parameters like mass, radius, and effective temperature (see Table A.1 and Table A.2 and references therein). No strict criteria were applied to define this special sample of stars. It is therefore just a first assessment of the variability of stellar p mode parameters in the *Kepler* short cadence sample. The full set of stars, which were observed in *Kepler*’s short cadence mode over extended periods of time, is considerably larger and is a worthwhile subject for future investigation.

The coverage of data for these stars ranges from 10 to 13 *Kepler* quarters of observation (960 to 1147 days). A list of the *Kepler* input catalogue (KIC) numbers of the stars and the available quarters of data is given in the first two columns of Table 5.1. Missing quarters are listed in a footnote to Table 5.1. The third column gives the number of days the data for each star spans, counting from the first day of observation to the last. The light curves were cleaned of jumps, drifts, and outliers similar to the method described by García et al. (2011).

To investigate the temporal variation of p-mode parameters, the time series were divided into consecutive, overlapping segments of equal length. To compromise between frequency resolution and number of independent segments, we chose a typical length of 150 days for the segments. From one segment to the next, the starting point was shifted by 50 days, resulting in a three-time overlap for 150 days long segments. If the errors on the eventually measured frequency shifts allowed a decrease in segment length and hence frequency resolution of the periodograms, we reduced it to 100 days. The shift of the starting point remained at 50 days, resulting in a two-time overlap. The lengths of the segments are given in the fourth column of Table 5.1.

Since the time series are slightly unevenly sampled and are affected by observational gaps, we used the Lomb-Scargle method (Lomb 1976; Scargle 1982) in the fast implementation of Press et al. (2007) to calculate the periodograms (LS-periodogram). The resulting periodograms are scaled to comply with Parseval’s theorem.

The observational gaps lead to spectral leakage of mode power. To study the effect of the gaps in the *Kepler* time series on our analysis, we used the inpainting software of Pires et al. (2015) to fill gaps up to a length of 20 days (García et al. 2014b). For none of our targets did the high frequency noise level decrease significantly. Also, the results described in the subsequent sections, frequency shifts and mode heights, do not change in a way that would make necessary the inpainting of the time series. This is because the *Kepler* gap structure does not have a large effect on the periodograms of solar-like stars as long as the stars are no fast rotators (García et al.

Table 5.1: Overview of the basic data of the investigated time series and their periodograms.

KIC	Data coverage*	Length of data (d)	Length of segment (d)	Frequency range (μHz)
3632418	5-17.2	1147	150	700-1700
3656476	7-17.2 ^a	960	150	1500-2500
4914923	7-17.2	960	150	1350-2300
5184732	7-17.2	960	100	1400-2700
6106415	6-16 ^b	1018	150	1550-3100
6116048	5-17.2	1147	150	1550-2600
6603624	5-17.2	1147	100	1900-3000
6933899	5-17.2	1147	150	1000-1800
7680114	7-17.2 ^c	960	150	1350-2100
7976303	5-17.2	1147	150	550-1300
8006161	5-17.2	1147	100	2800-4400
8228742	5-17.2	1147	100	800-1600
8379927	5-17.2	1147	150	2100-3700
8760414	5-17.2	1147	150	1950-3000
9025370	5-17.2	1147	100	2550-3450
9955598	5-17.2	1147	150	3000-4100
10018963	5-17.2	1147	100	650-1500
10516096	7-17.2 ^d	960	100	1200-1900
10644253	5-17.2	1147	150	2450-3350
10963065	5-15 ^e	1027	150	1700-2700
11244118	5-17.2	1147	100	1000-1800
11295426	5-17.2	1147	150	1800-2400
12009504	5-17.2	1147	100	1400-2300
12258514	5-17.2	1147	150	1050-2100

Notes. (*) Data coverage indicated in *Kepler* quarters. Missing quarters: ^(a) Q10, Q14; ^(b) Q9, Q13 ^(c) Q6, Q7.2, Q10; ^(d) Q10.1; ^(e) Q8, Q9, Q12

2014b) and the periodograms are computed from time series segments with a length of only 100 or 150 days.

To get the same frequency axis for the LS-periodogram of each data segment of a given star, the LS-periodograms were interpolated onto the frequency grid of the segment with the lowest fill factor. This way, the LS-periodograms can later be correlated with each other. The minimum fill factor of segments was set to 50%. Thereby, we ensured a reasonable frequency resolution for the LS-periodograms of all the segments of a star. In Figure 5.1, the $0.81 \mu\text{Hz}$ (7 bins) boxcar smoothed segments between $3570 - 3610 \mu\text{Hz}$ of the LS-periodograms of the first and the nineteenth segment of the time series of KIC 8006161 are shown in black and red colour, respectively. Even by visual inspection of the peak at $\sim 3590 \mu\text{Hz}$, a shift towards higher frequency can be spotted for the red peak.

5.2.2 Measuring the Frequency Shifts

The first segment of each star was used as the reference for defining zero frequency shift. Due to this, the level of zero frequency shift can be at any level of a stellar activity cycle, e.g., its

Figure 5.1: Section of the LS-periodograms of the first and nineteenth segment of KIC 8006161 in black and red colour, respectively. The LS-periodograms are boxcar smoothed over $0.81 \mu\text{Hz}$.

maximum. We computed the shift relative to the reference segment by calculation of the cross-correlation of that frequency range of the LS-periodograms which contains the p modes and fitting a Lorentzian to the cross-correlation. We selected this frequency range by visually determining the lower and upper boundaries between which p-mode peaks can be spotted in the smoothed LS-periodogram of the entire time series of each star (see the last column of Table 5.1). Recently, a cross-correlation technique for measuring mode frequency shifts was presented by Régulo et al. (2016). Their method to measure the frequency shifts is very similar to the approach presented here. However, our approach to estimate the error on the frequency shifts, which is described in the following section, is different in several aspects from that of Régulo et al. (2016).

In the top panel of Figure 5.2, the part between $\pm 5 \mu\text{Hz}$ of the cross-correlation between the p-mode region of two realisations (see Sect. 5.2.2) of the first segment of KIC 8006161 is shown in black. The Lorentzian fit to the data is shown as a continuous red curve. The dotted black line marks zero frequency lag, the dashed red line marks the center of the fitted Lorentzian. The bottom panel of Figure 5.2 depicts the same as the top panel, but for the cross-correlation between the first and the nineteenth segment of the time series from KIC 8006161. Here, the maximum of the cross-correlation is clearly shifted towards positive values. Peaks of stochastically excited solar and stellar p-mode oscillations appear to be of Lorentzian shape. The Lorentzian is invariant under convolution with a Lorentzian, hence the cross-correlation of two of them can be fitted with a Lorentzian. In our analysis, we used a symmetric Lorentzian profile. We found that the extra parameter introduced by a skewness does not decrease the error on the frequency shift or increase the stability of the fits.

Resampling Approach

Since the correlation structure of the estimated cross-correlation function depends on the true unknown cross- and auto-correlation function in a complicated manner, we use a resampling approach to estimate the error on the frequency shift (see Bartlett 1978 and, e.g., Chaplin et al. 2007b). We generate a sample of new LS-periodograms, which follow the statistical properties of

Figure 5.2: *Top panel:* cross-correlation between the part of interest of the LS-periodograms of two realisations of the first segment of KIC 8006161 (black). The Lorentzian fit to the cross-correlation is shown in red. The dotted black vertical line marks zero frequency lag, the dashed red line marks the centre of the fitted Lorentzian. *Bottom panel:* same as in the top panel, but for the cross-correlation between a realisation of the first and one of the nineteenth segment.

the original periodogram, and from which we compute the sample mean and sample error. In our resampling approach, we neglect effects from uneven sampling, since it is small for *Kepler* data. The largest effects on our analysis are assumed to result from gaps in the data.

For each data segment i , we draw $B = 200$ complex random series $F_i^*(\nu_k)$ for $\{\pm\nu_k\}_{k=1,\dots,N}$ from a zero mean normal distribution $N(0,1)$ weighted by the estimated spectral power $\hat{S}_i(\nu_k)$, such that:

$$\Re\{F_i^*(\nu_k)\} \sim \sqrt{\hat{S}_i(\nu_k)} \times N(0,1) \quad (5.1)$$

$$\Im\{F_i^*(\nu_k)\} \sim \sqrt{\hat{S}_i(\nu_k)} \times N(0,1), \quad (5.2)$$

and $F_i^*(-\nu_k) = \overline{F_i^*(\nu_k)}$. For $\nu = 0$, we set $F_i^*(\nu = 0) = 0$, reflecting a zero mean time series. An estimate \hat{S}_i of the true unknown spectral density S_i is obtained by smoothing the

LS-periodogram with a boxcar window. The width of the boxcar varies from star to star, ranging from 0.38–1.52 μHz (5–12 bins). We chose the width of the boxcar depending on the frequency resolution of the periodograms and the width of the p modes of each individual star. The complex random series $\{F_i^*(\nu_k)\}_i$ may be considered as realisations of Fourier transforms that would be obtained in the ideal case of evenly sampled data without observational gaps but with the same spectral density underlying the respective original data. Note that the real and the imaginary part of $\{F_i^*(\nu_k)\}$ are by construction independent of each other and with respect to ν_k . In order to take into account the effect of gaps in the original data, we generate new time series $\{x_i^*(t_k)\}$ on an evenly sampled grid $\{t_n\}_{n=1,\dots,N}$ by the inverse Fourier transform of $\{F_i^*(\nu_k)\}$. The grid in time approximates the one for the original data. Data points at the respective grid points with observation gaps are removed. These new time series $\{x_i^*(t_n)\}$ are treated as described above to compute frequency shifts from the cross-correlation function of LS-periodograms. We further note that these resampled time series have no physical meaning, since the phases between real- and imaginary part of the Fourier transforms are random. However, the described procedure conserves the linear spectral properties of the original data.

We emphasise that the LS-periodogram is computed with oversampling factor 1. In case of evenly sampled data without gaps, the LS-periodogram is then equivalent to the classical Fourier based periodogram and follows the same statistical distribution (Scargle 1982). An oversampling factor greater than 1 corresponds to an interpolation of the periodogram along frequency bins and gives correlated values at adjacent frequency bins. In this study, we aim to suppress such additional correlations since they lead to an unwanted complex correlation structure in the error analysis and result in a systematic underestimation of the error on the frequency shifts.

Each realisation of the LS-periodogram of a given segment is cross-correlated with a realisation of the LS-periodogram of the reference segment. For the reference segment, two samples of 200 realisations are drawn. The cross-correlation analysis between these two sets yields the error bar on the zero level of the frequency shifts. The standard deviation of the centroid values of the Lorentzian profile of the 200 fits is used as the error for the shift of the p modes, while their mean is used as the value of the shift. The value $B = 200$ was chosen, because it is a conservative number of realisations for which the variance of the estimator of the error is small compared to the variance of the distribution of the centroid values of the frequency shifts. Hence, the standard deviation of the 200 centroid values is a reliable estimate for the error on the measured frequency shifts.

5.2.3 Consistency Check with BiSON Data

For a consistency check of our method, we analysed data from the BiSON network (Davies et al. 2014). The time series encompasses the period from 1985–2014, covering about two and a half solar cycles. Figure 5.3 depicts the frequency shifts and the associated $1\text{-}\sigma$ error bars as black data points. The monthly sunspot number is shown as a continuous red line (boxcar smoothed over seven months). It is scaled to match the amplitude of the variation of the p-mode frequencies in this figure. In this case, we set the length of the segments to 200 days and the step length to 100 days in order to increase the clarity of the plot by reducing the number of data points. We selected the frequency range between 1800–3800 μHz for the cross-correlation of the periodograms. The frequency shift closely follows the sunspot number, a proxy of solar magnetic activity.

For the amplitude of the solar p-mode frequency shift, we find a value of $0.62 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{Hz}$. This is in agreement with previous investigations of the p-mode frequency shifts obtained with the

Figure 5.3: Frequency shifts of solar p modes from BiSON data with $1\text{-}\sigma$ error bars (black). The seven-month boxcar smoothed monthly sunspot number is shown in red. Source of the sunspot number: WDC-SILSO, Royal Observatory of Belgium, Brussels.

cross-correlation method using BiSON data (Chaplin et al. 2007b).

5.2.4 Height of the Mode Envelope

As we are considering the temporal evolution of the frequencies of all p modes in the periodogram, we compute a proxy for the amplitudes of the p modes by measuring their excess over the background in the periodogram.

For this, we have fitted a background to each of the segments and recorded the summary statistics. We used a variant of “model F” as described in and recommended by Kallinger et al. (2014), which consists of two Harvey-like profiles (Harvey 1985), a Gaussian p-mode envelope, and an instrumental noise component. Following Kallinger et al., we restricted the exponents of the Harvey-like profiles to a value of 4.

Here our purpose was to study the impact of stellar activity. So, in order to isolate the activity signal of the p modes from the low-frequency activity signal due to surface modulation, we restricted the fitting range to frequencies above $400\ \mu\text{Hz}$. This lower limit excludes regions of the periodogram that can also contain activity signals, but mitigates problems caused by a *Kepler* noise feature found at $374\ \mu\text{Hz}$. As the surface activity signal is excluded, we did not include a power-law to account for surface activity in the model.

To fit the model, we used the affine invariant Markov Chain Monte Carlo code *emcee* (Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013). From the resulting Markov Chains we quote the summary statistics of the posterior probability distributions, which are normally distributed, as the median value and the 15.9th and 84.1th percentile to define the highest posterior density interval, i.e., the credible interval. We used the standard Gaussian form for the mode envelope:

$$N(\nu) = a \exp\left(-\frac{(\nu - b)^2}{2c^2}\right) \quad (5.3)$$

where a is the height of the Gaussian, b is the frequency of maximum height, and c is the width of the Gaussian. In the subsequent sections, we will refer to a as the height of the p-mode envelope, or simply height.

To exclude contamination of the measured mode heights with a temporally varying instrumental noise component, which might, for example, arise from the quarterly satellite rolls performed by *Kepler* during its nominal mission phase, we checked its temporal variation for all our targets. We found that there are no considerable jumps in the instrumental noise component at the quarter boundaries of the time series we used for the analyses.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Frequency Shifts and Background Parameters

In Table 5.2 the peak-to-valley amplitudes of the frequency shifts of all 24 stars are listed. The amplitude A was calculated as the difference between the minimum and maximum values of the frequency shifts. With the propagated error σ_A , we also calculated the significance of the observed shift amplitude A/σ_A , see Table 5.2. The observed frequency shifts in our sample range from $\approx 0.17 \mu\text{Hz}$ for KIC 4914923 to $\approx 0.95 \mu\text{Hz}$ for KIC 8006161. Only one star from our sample, KIC 9955598, does not exhibit a frequency shift amplitude which is larger than the error and is therefore compatible with zero for all the segments. In the top panels of Figures A.1-A.23 the frequency shifts are plotted as a function of starting time of the segments, while in the bottom panels the temporal variation of the mode heights are depicted.

As described in Section 5.1, the temporal variation of p-mode frequencies can be a proxy for stellar magnetic activity. For some stars, the frequency shifts follow a cycle-like pattern, e.g., KIC 8379927, KIC 8760414, KIC 10644253. Yet, the available time series are not sufficiently long to draw the conclusion that we found clear evidence for a complete cycle in any of the stars of this sample.

We calculated the Spearman rank correlation coefficients ρ between the variation of the mode frequency shifts, mode heights, the granulation time scales of the background Harvey profiles, and the noise level, as well as the corresponding p-values p for independent segments of all 24 stars. The values are listed in Tables A.3-A.26. The correlation coefficients of the frequency shifts and the mode height variations and their p-values are also given in Table 5.3.

For the Sun (e.g. Pallé et al. 1990; Komm et al. 2000b; Broomhall et al. 2015) and one more star, the solar-like CoRoT star HD 49933 (García et al. 2010), the shifts in mode frequency and the variation of p-mode amplitudes are anti-correlated over the course of their magnetic cycle. For six stars from our sample, the correlation coefficient between the frequency shifts and the variation of the height of the p-mode envelope is less than -0.5 and the amplitude of the frequency shift is significant: KIC 6933899, KIC 8006161, KIC 8760414, KIC 9955598, KIC 10644253, KIC 11244118, and KIC 12258514. For these stars, the evidence for magnetic activity influencing the p-mode parameters is strongest.

There is no clear consensus in the literature, on whether the granulation and super-granulation properties are correlated with the solar activity cycle. Lefebvre et al. (2008) find no correlation between the activity level and granulation velocities or time scales in GOLF data, Muller et al. (2007) show that there is an in-phase variation of the contrast of solar granulation with the

Table 5.2: Amplitudes of frequency shifts and their significance.

KIC	A (10^{-7} Hz)	σ_A (10^{-7} Hz)	A/σ_A	KIC	A (10^{-7} Hz)	σ_A (10^{-7} Hz)	A/σ_A
3632418	3.99	1.81	2.20	8228742	5.72	2.24	2.56
3656476	1.75	1.51	1.16	8379927	4.38	1.88	2.32
4914923	1.74	1.40	1.25	8760414	2.06	1.41	1.46
5184732	3.67	1.85	1.98	9025370	6.27	5.62	1.12
6106415	2.41	1.79	1.35	9955598	3.00	3.52	0.85
6116048	3.70	1.52	2.43	10018963	4.36	2.37	1.84
6603624	1.94	1.51	1.28	10516096	3.43	2.47	1.39
6933899	1.84	1.37	1.34	10644253	8.66	5.73	1.51
7680114	4.80	2.61	1.84	10963065	1.84	1.39	1.32
7976303	2.49	1.28	1.95	11244118	3.21	1.60	2.00
8006161	9.53	2.25	4.23	11295426	2.26	1.53	1.48
low	5.65	2.77	2.04	12009504	6.19	3.45	1.79
mid	10.81	2.96	3.65	12258514	2.66	1.29	2.06
high	12.61	4.81	2.62				

activity cycle but no such correlation for granulation length scales, [Meunier et al. \(2008\)](#) find smaller supergranules at cycle maximum. Since granulation has different properties for different stellar parameters (e.g. [Beeck et al. 2013](#)), we expect different responses by the granulation to magnetic cycles for different stars. In the case of HD 49933, [García et al. \(2010\)](#) showed that the variation of the granulation time scale, the photon noise, and the mode amplitudes are uncorrelated.

The correlation coefficients we present in Tables [A.3-A.26](#) do not present any systematic correlation between the oscillation and background parameters across the sample of stars. For the two stars, which we will discuss in detail in the subsequent sections, KIC 8006161 and KIC 10644253, both of which show evident signs of magnetic activity, we find very different correlations between the investigated parameters.

For KIC 10644253, which was shown to exhibit magnetic activity by [Salabert et al. \(2016b\)](#), we find that the frequency shifts are anti-correlated with the first granulation time scale with $\rho = -0.71$ and $p = 0.07$, but correlated with the second time scale with $\rho = 0.86$ and $p = 0.01$, see Table [A.21](#). The measured mode heights show the opposite behavior. It is noteworthy that for this evidentially active star ([Mathur et al. 2014a](#); [Salabert et al. 2016b](#)) the frequency shifts are correlated with changes in the high frequency noise with $\rho = 0.50$, while the mode heights are anti-correlated to these changes with $\rho = -0.75$.

In contrast to this, KIC 8006161, which exhibits the strongest frequency shifts of the investigated sample, shows virtually no significant correlations or anti-correlations between any of the background parameters, see Table [A.13](#), where the only exception is a correlation between the two granulation time scales with $\rho = 0.74$ and $p = 0.01$.

For four stars, KIC 6106415, KIC 6116048, KIC 6603624 and KIC 7680114, the shifts in p-mode frequency are strongly correlated with the variation in mode height, with correlation coefficients greater than 0.5. For magnetic activity, which is comparable to that observed on the Sun, this is not expected. As some of these stars show significant temporal variability in their p-mode frequencies as well as their mode heights, e.g., KIC 6116048, this might either be due to a dynamo in these stars, which is working differently than in the solar case, or to another mechanism influencing the oscillation parameters, e.g., temporally varying flows ([Roth and Stix 2003](#)). Whether

Table 5.3: Correlation coefficients of frequency shifts and p-mode envelope height variations and their p-values

KIC	correlation	p	KIC	correlation	p
3632418	-0.14	0.76	8228742	-0.29	0.39
3656476	0.30	0.62	8379927	0.43	0.34
4914923	0.49	0.33	8760414	-0.54	0.22
5184732	-0.44	0.20	9025370	-0.25	0.45
6106415	0.60	0.21	9955598	-0.75	0.05
6116048	0.75	0.05	10018963	0.46	0.15
6603624	0.52	0.10	10516096	-0.26	0.47
6933899	-0.57	0.18	10644253	-0.93	$3 \cdot 10^{-3}$
7680114	0.60	0.21	10963065	-0.26	0.62
7976303	-0.29	0.53	11244118	-0.61	0.05
8006161	-0.93	$4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	11295426	0.36	0.43
low	-0.92	$7 \cdot 10^{-5}$	12009504	-0.13	0.71
mid	-0.93	$4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	12258514	-0.50	0.25
high	-0.87	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$			

there is relationship between basic stellar parameters (e.g., mass, effective temperature, or thickness of the convection zone) and the correlation of seismic activity proxies as well as granulation parameters, will be investigated in a future study of an expanded sample of *Kepler* stars.

Stellar magnetic activity need not be necessarily cyclic in the solar sense and it might be that the variation of frequency shifts and mode heights is correlated in physical settings which are different from the solar reference case regarding, e.g., differential rotation. The frequency shifts and mode heights of KIC 10018963 for example, see Fig A.17, are moderately correlated with a correlation coefficient of 0.46. Both, frequencies and mode heights, exhibit significant temporal variations which might be caused by non-cyclic sporadic stellar magnetic activity.

5.3.2 Results for the Ensemble

With this systematic investigation of the frequency shifts for a larger sample of stars at hand, we try to find relationships between the measured shift amplitudes and fundamental stellar parameters. We assume here that the observed shifts are solely due to magnetic activity. The available values for stellar radius, mass, and age are listed in Table A.1. The spectral types, effective temperatures, rotation periods, and special features, e.g., binarity, are presented in Table A.2. The references for all values we used are given below these two tables.

In Figure 5.4 the measured frequency shift amplitudes are plotted as a function of effective temperature. The age of the stars is given by the colour and type of symbol: black diamonds represent stars younger than 4 Gyr, red triangles are stars between 4–5 Gyr, orange circles between 5–6 Gyr, blue squares between 6–7 Gyr, and purple asterisks are stars older than 7 Gyr.

There are two proposed scaling models for the frequency shifts over a stellar activity cycle: Chaplin et al. (2007a) come to the conclusion that the frequency shifts are directly proportional to the strength of the activity cycle given by $\Delta R_{\text{HK}'}$, which is given by the average fraction of the stellar luminosity that is emitted in the Ca II H and K line cores. The second model, presented by Metcalfe et al. (2007), assumes that the frequency shifts are proportional to $D/I \cdot \Delta R_{\text{HK}'}$, where D is the depth of the perturbations and I is the mode inertia. In Figure 9 of Karoff et al.

Figure 5.4: Measured shift amplitudes as a function of effective temperature. Colour and symbol coding: black diamonds represent stars younger than 4 Gyr, red triangles are stars between 4–5 Gyr, orange circles between 5–6 Gyr, blue squares between 6–7 Gyr, and purple asterisks are stars older than 7 Gyr.

Figure 5.5: Measured shift amplitudes as a function of stellar age.

(2009), these two models are compared as a function of effective temperature and for different stellar ages.

The here presented sample of stars does not allow us to decide between the two models. The errors on the frequency shift amplitudes are too large and the sample of 24 stars is too small. However, there appears to be a slight tendency towards greater shift amplitudes for hotter stars. This would support the scaling model by Metcalfe et al. (2007). The outstanding exception from this is KIC 8006161, located at $T_{\text{eff}} = 5258$ K and a shift amplitude of $0.95 \mu\text{Hz}$. That KIC 8006161 shows out-of-the-ordinary activity was also noticed by Karoff et al. (2013). An expansion of our study to all stars with *Kepler* short cadence data of sufficient length and a reduction of the uncertainty on the frequency shifts, e.g., by peak-bagging of the periodograms of all segments, will help to shed light on the question which of the two models is the correct one.

Figure 5.6: Measured shift amplitudes as a function of rotation period.

Figure 5.5 shows the frequency shift amplitudes as a function of the stellar ages, which are available in the literature, see Table A.1. As shown by, e.g., Skumanich (1972) and recently by Salabert et al. (2016a), the strength of stellar activity is declining over time. Both scaling models for the cycle frequency shifts include the strength of the activity cycle via the quantity $\Delta R_{\text{HK}'}$. It is the youngest star of the investigated sample, KIC 10644253, which shows the second greatest shift amplitude. Stars between 1.07–2.88 Gyr are missing from our sample. We excluded KIC 9025370 from this plot, as its age is only poorly determined. From Figure 5.5, it can be seen that the amplitude of the frequency shifts is decreasing with stellar age. Again, KIC 8006161, at an age of 5.04 Gyr and a shift amplitude of $0.95 \mu\text{Hz}$, is the exception.

In Figure 5.6 the shift amplitudes are plotted as a function of rotation period. Only 15 stars of the sample have measured rotation periods. As the rotation period is linked to the strength of stellar activity (e.g. Skumanich 1972; Wright et al. 2011), it is straightforward to assume that also the frequency shift amplitudes decrease with increasing rotation period. We note that once more KIC 8006161, found at $P_{\text{rot}} = 29.79$ days and a shift amplitude of $0.95 \mu\text{Hz}$, appears to deviate from the behaviour of the remaining sample. Indeed, even though the sample now consists of only 15 stars, there is a trend towards smaller shift amplitudes for longer rotation periods.

5.3.3 KIC 8006161

KIC 8006161 is a solar-like star with a mass of $1.04 \pm 0.02 M_{\odot}$, a radius of $0.947 \pm 0.007 R_{\odot}$, and an age of 5.04 ± 0.17 Gyr (model values from Metcalfe et al. 2014). It is a G8V star (Molenda-Żakowicz et al. 2013) and its rotation period is 29.79 ± 3.09 d (García et al. 2014a). This star shows the most significant and greatest frequency shifts of our sample with $A/\sigma_A = 4.23$. The variation of the p-mode frequencies in the range between 2800–4400 μHz is shown in the top half of the top panel of Figure 5.7. From the zero level at the beginning of the time series, the mode frequencies increase by $\approx 0.95 \mu\text{Hz}$ until the end of the time series. The error bars on the frequency shifts, which result from our resampling approach described in Section 5.2.2, are only of the order of $\approx 0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$. This small error is due to the narrow width of the p modes in the LS-periodogram of KIC 8006161 and the broad frequency range where modes can be detected. The shifts reach a local maximum at around day 350, followed by a brief decrease. The shifts then increase again

Figure 5.7: *Top panel:* frequency shifts for KIC 8006161 for the frequency range between 2800–4400 μHz (top half) and height of the p-mode envelope of KIC 8006161 (bottom half) as a function of time. *Bottom panel:* frequency shift as a function of height of the p-mode envelope.

towards the end of the time series. This behaviour is reminiscent of the double maximum of the Sun’s activity cycle. Unfortunately, the available time series does not cover a full activity cycle of KIC 8006161. Therefore, we can only limit the cycle length to $P_{\text{cyc}} > 1147\text{d}$.

The variation of the mode heights are depicted in the bottom half of the top panel of Figure 5.7. We find a clear anti-correlation between the shift of mode frequencies and the variation of mode heights with a correlation value of $\rho = -0.93$ with a p value of $4 \cdot 10^{-5}$. This linear anti-correlation is clearly seen in the bottom panel of Figure 5.7, where the frequency shifts are plotted as a function of height of the mode envelope. There is a slight departure from the linear relationship towards higher values of height, which correspond to a state of lower magnetic activity. This behaviour, albeit less pronounced, is also observed for KIC 5184732, see Figure A.25. As discussed before, the other parameters of the background fit show no correlations or anti-correlations, see Table A.13, where the only exception is a correlation between the two granulation time scales with $\rho = 0.74$ and $p = 0.01$. We therefore conclude that the observed variations in mode frequencies and mode heights are due to magnetic activity on KIC 8006161.

Figure 5.8: Frequency shifts of KIC 8006161 for three frequency ranges as a function of time: 2800–3300 μHz (*left panel*), 3300–3800 μHz (*middle panel*), and 3800–4400 μHz (*right panel*).

Karoff et al. (2013) found that the S index of KIC 8006161, a measure for stellar chromospheric activity, is comparable to that of the Sun. They also found that, at the same time, KIC 8006161 exhibits an unusually low excess flux. This flux is associated with magnetic sources on the stellar surface. They argue that due to this odd combination of activity indices, KIC 8006161 might be in a minimum state of activity. Their measurements were taken between 2010 and 2012, which corresponds to *Kepler* quarters 4 through 15, and therefore largely overlap with the time series we used for our analyses, which encompasses Q5–17.2.¹ In the study of García et al. (2014a), KIC 8006161 was found to be more active than the Sun. García et al. used the standard deviation of the time series, a measure of photospheric activity, to determine the activity level.

Since this star is very similar to the Sun regarding its fundamental parameters, our findings for the activity-related shift of its p-mode frequencies, and especially the strong anti-correlation between mode frequencies and heights of the p-mode envelope, suggest that the magnetic activity on KIC 8006161 is somewhat stronger than on the Sun, following the results presented by García et al. (2014a).

For the Sun, it was shown that the amplitude of frequency shifts over the solar cycle are larger for higher frequencies (e.g. Libbrecht and Woodard 1990; Jiménez-Reyes et al. 2001; Chaplin et al. 2007b; Salabert et al. 2015). We looked for a similar behaviour for KIC 8006161 by dividing the frequency range where p modes are visible in the periodogram into three smaller sections: a low-frequency range between 2800–3300 μHz , an intermediate range with frequencies 3300–3800 μHz , and high frequency range between 3800–4400 μHz . The results are shown in the three panels of Figure 5.8. As in the solar case, the frequency shifts increase with increasing mode frequency: the modes in the low-frequency range vary by only $\approx 0.6 \mu\text{Hz}$, while the modes in the intermediate range shift $\approx 1.1 \mu\text{Hz}$. The modes in the high frequency range even shift by as much as $\approx 1.2 \mu\text{Hz}$. The measuring of the frequency shifts via the cross-correlation and the estimation of the error bars on them are sensitive to the mode widths and amplitudes. Due to the fact that mode widths increase with frequency and mode amplitudes follow a Gaussian envelope centred around the frequency of maximum power, the estimated error bars on the frequency shifts are smallest in the intermediate range and largest in the high frequency range (see Figure 5.8, Table 5.2, and Régulo et al. (2016)) The overall course of the variation of the frequencies is similar for all three frequency ranges. The characteristics of the variation for the entire frequency range are dominated by the variation of the modes in the intermediate frequency range, since these modes have the largest

¹*Kepler* quarter 4 started December 19, 2009; quarter 15 ended January 11, 2013.

amplitudes and thus contribute strongest to the cross-correlation. As for the entire frequency range, the frequency shifts of these sub-ranges are strongly anti-correlated to the variation of the mode heights with correlation coefficients of -0.92 (low frequency range), -0.93 (intermediate frequency range), and -0.87 (high frequency range). This is only the fourth star for which a frequency dependence of the activity-related shift of p-mode frequencies has been detected after the Sun, HD 49933 (Salabert et al. 2011), and KIC 10644253 (Salabert et al. 2016b).

5.3.4 KIC 10644253

This star has a mass of $1.13 \pm 0.05 M_{\odot}$, a radius of $1.108 \pm 0.016 R_{\odot}$ (Mathur et al. 2014a), and an age of 1.07 ± 0.25 Gyr (model values from Metcalfe et al. 2014). It is a G0V star (Molenda-Żakowicz et al. 2013) with a surface rotation rate of 10.91 ± 0.87 d (García et al. 2014a).

The frequency shifts we found for this star follow a cycle-like pattern, see top half of the top panel of Figure 5.9, and have the second greatest peak-to-valley amplitude in our sample of stars with a value of $\approx 0.87 \mu\text{Hz}$. The heights of the mode envelope, see bottom half of the top panel of Figure 5.9, are strongly anti-correlated to the frequency shifts with a correlation coefficient of $\rho = -0.93$ and a p value of $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$. This linear anti-correlation is seen in the bottom panel of Figure 5.9, where the frequency shifts of KIC 10644253 are plotted as a function of height of the mode envelope.

In their study of 22 F stars Mathur et al. investigated the long cadence *Kepler* time series of KIC 10644253 regarding signs of magnetic activity and activity cycles. In their magnetic proxy for this star, they found indications of two activity cycles during the first 16 quarters of *Kepler* data. They use the scale average variance, which is a projection of the wavelet power spectrum in a small region around the stellar rotation period onto the time axis, as a magnetic proxy. The overall magnetic activity of this star was among the highest from their sample of stars. Mathur et al. spotted the strongest peak in their cycle proxy of KIC 10644253 during Quarter 10, which corresponds to a time during day ≈ 400 -450 for our data set. This was recently confirmed by Salabert et al. (2016b) who find a positive shift in p-mode frequencies and a large stellar magnetic variability in this time period. Indeed, in our analysis, the frequency shifts are at a local maximum and the mode heights are at a local minimum during this period. The local minima found in the frequency shifts before and after this maximum are also reflected in the magnetic proxy of Mathur et al. (2014a) and the frequency shifts and stellar magnetic variability of Salabert et al. (2016b).

Interestingly, we find strong positive frequency shifts and small mode heights, which indicates strong magnetic activity, during the last 250 days of the time series. This is not reflected in the proxy of Mathur et al. (2014a) or in the stellar magnetic variability of Salabert et al. (2016b). During the same time period, there is a discrepancy between the mode frequency shifts and the photometric activity proxy presented by Salabert et al. (2016b).

There are different values for the inclination angle of KIC 10644253 in the literature. Mathur et al. (2014a) state $i = 43.44 \pm 14.48^{\circ}$, whereas Salabert et al. (2016b) find values of $i \approx 11^{\circ}$ derived from spectroscopic measurements², $i = 7_{-9}^{+9^{\circ}}$ derived from the stellar radius, rotation period and the asteroseismic $v \sin i$, and $i = 48_{-9}^{+11^{\circ}}$ derived with another value of the spectroscopic $v \sin i$. Therefore, the inclination of the rotation axis of KIC 10644253 to the line of sight seems to be rather low, with a weighted average value of $i = 23 \pm 6^{\circ}$.

²For the weighted average of the inclination angle, we estimated the error on this value to be $\pm 11^{\circ}$

Figure 5.9: *Top panel:* frequency shifts for KIC 10644253 for the frequency range between 2450–3350 μHz (top half) and height of the p-mode envelope of KIC 10644253 as a function of time (bottom half). *Bottom panel:* frequency shift as a function of height of the p-mode envelope.

Due to this low inclination, it is conceivable that the regions of high activity are largely confined to the nearly out-of-sight hemisphere of the star during the last 250 days of the time series, where the discrepancy between the activity proxies is found. The global, low degree modes we use for our analyses are susceptible to magnetic activity throughout the star. Therefore, the frequency shifts and variation of the mode heights might reveal signatures of magnetic activity which are hidden to photometry based techniques like that of Mathur et al. (2014a).

5.4 Summary and Conclusion

We investigated the *Kepler* data of 24 solar-like stars for the temporal variation of p-mode frequencies and height of the p-mode envelope. For this, we split the stars' time series into shorter segments. The shifts of p-mode frequencies were measured by using a cross-correlation analysis of the segments' periodograms. The errors on the frequency shifts were estimated with

a resampling approach. This approach will be further investigated and compared to similar approaches used in helio- and asteroseismology in a future study. The temporal variation of the heights of the p-mode envelope, the high frequency noise, and two granulation time scales were measured by fitting the segments' periodograms.

We found significant variation of p-mode frequencies (above $1\text{-}\sigma$), which can be signatures of stellar magnetic activity, during the observed period for 23 of the 24 stars of our sample. A cycle-like behaviour could be spotted in the frequency shifts of several stars (e.g., KIC 3632418, KIC 6933899, KIC 8760414, KIC 10644253). The correlation between the frequency shifts and the variation of mode heights was found to be strongly negative (below -0.5) for six stars (KIC 6933899, KIC 8006161, KIC 8760414, KIC 9955598, KIC 10644253, KIC 11244118, and KIC 12258514). Together, the significant shift in p-mode frequencies and this anti-correlation strongly supports asteroseismic detection of solar-like magnetic activity on these stars. Due to the limited length of the time series, we refrain from assigning cycle periods to any of these stars. However, we can limit the cycle period of KIC 8006161 to $P_{\text{cyc}} > 1147\text{ d}$ and state that more detailed and longer observations of the respective stars with evidence for cyclic activity could shed light on the period lengths of their magnetic activity cycles. Moreover, there are hints of sporadic activity on some of the investigated stars. The frequency shifts and mode heights of KIC 10018963 and KIC 11295426 exhibit significant temporal variations which might be caused by such non-cyclic sporadic stellar magnetic activity. It is also noteworthy that the correlation of frequency shifts and mode heights is strongly negative, following the solar reference case, for only 7 out of 24 stars, and even strongly positive for a couple of stars. Whether there is something to be learned from this about the connection of stellar magnetic activity or the dynamos at work in stars slightly different than the Sun to the temporal evolution of the mode frequency shifts and the mode heights is currently subject of further investigations.

The background parameters – specifically mode heights, granulation time scales, and high frequency noise level – and the frequency shifts do not show any systematic correlation across the sample of stars. We found very different correlations between the investigated parameters for the two stars, which we discussed in detail, KIC 8006161 and KIC 10644253, both of which show clear signs of magnetic activity. It will need an expanded sample of stars with a broader range of fundamental parameters, optimally all available *Kepler* stars with long enough short cadence coverage, to find the cause for this varying behaviour of the oscillation and background parameters.

The star KIC 10644253 exhibited shifts in p-mode frequencies and changes of the mode heights which might be caused by two stellar cycles during the available data set, as was also recently discovered by Salabert et al. (2016b). When compared to the activity indices of Mathur et al. (2014a) and Salabert et al. (2016b), we conclude that we found indications of stellar activity on the nearly out-of-sight hemisphere of this star during the last 250 days of *Kepler* observations.

For the solar-like star KIC 8006161 we were able to investigate the frequency dependence of the mode frequency shifts. We found that the shifts are larger for p modes of higher frequencies, just like in the solar case (Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998), for HD 49933 (Salabert et al. 2011), and for KIC 10644253 (Salabert et al. 2016b). It is only the fourth star for which this frequency dependence of the activity-related frequency shifts could be measured. KIC 8006161 is very similar to the Sun regarding its mass, age, and rotation period. It is therefore noteworthy that the frequency shifts are larger than for the Sun, even though the time series does clearly not cover a full cycle. This raises the question what sets this star's magnetic cycle apart from the Sun's cycle. Further investigation of KIC 8006161 and its magnetic activity cycle is therefore worthwhile.

When examining the frequency shifts as a function of mode height, there is a departure from the negative linear relationship between these two quantities for higher values of mode height. This is also observed for KIC 5184732 and raises the question whether this observed pattern is part of a hysteresis curve of the frequency shifts over a stellar cycle, similar as observed for the Sun (Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998).

We found that the frequency shift amplitude decreases with stellar age and rotation period. The results for our sample did not enable us to reject one of the two opposing scaling models for cycle frequency shift amplitudes by Chaplin et al. (2007a) and Metcalfe et al. (2007), while the data seems to show a slight tendency towards the scaling of Metcalfe et al. (2007).

Acknowledgments The research leading to these results received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union’s Seventh Framework Program (FP/2007–2013)/ERC Grant Agreement No. 307117. G.R.D. acknowledges the support of the UK Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC). This research has made use of the SIMBAD database, operated at CDS, Strasbourg, France.

Variation of Solar Oscillation Parameters Over Two Solar Cycles Observed by GONG¹

6.1 Data and Methodology

6.1.1 Data Sets

In the present analysis, I used mode parameter data² which were produced by the standard GONG pipeline (Hill et al. 1996; Hill and Howe 1998) from solar full-disk Dopplergrams as described in Section 2.6.2. The mode parameters are obtained by fitting Lorentzian profiles to the power spectra of 108-day long data sets, where every third data set is independent, i.e., they overlap by 72 days. These time series are concatenations of three GONG months, with one GONG month being 36 days. This ensures a reasonable frequency resolution of the fitted power spectra and number of independent data points. The power spectra are computed and fitted for all harmonic degrees l and azimuthal orders $-l \leq m \leq l$ up to $l = 150$. The GONG peak-fitting algorithm fits symmetric Lorentzian profiles to the spectra (Hill et al. 1996). Since the mode peaks are known to be asymmetric (Nigam et al. 1998), this might introduce small, temporally varying systematics to the mode parameter analyzed here, as the asymmetry changes over the solar cycle (Jiménez-Reyes et al. 2007; Korzennik 2013; Howe et al. 2015). The fitted Lorentzians include the parameters mode width Γ , amplitude A , and two background parameters, which are not considered in the following.

6.1.2 Azimuthal Averaging and Correction for Spatial Masking

Pixels close to the solar limb (see Section 2.6.2 and the full-disk HMI Dopplergrams shown in Figure 1.1) are subject to several unwanted effects. First, because GONG measures line-of-sight velocities, projection effects increase towards the solar limb. Second, the resolution of each pixel, measured in distance on the solar surface, increases towards the limb. A spatial mask is applied to cut away these unwanted pixels. This leads to a suppression of mode amplitude depending on the ratio of azimuthal order and harmonic degree $|m/l|$.

¹The work presented in this chapter is unpublished as of the time of writing this thesis. However, I included it as it adds results from helioseismic analyses of the solar cycle to the asteroseismic perspective presented in Chapter 5. The results presented here were largely achieved in collaboration with Rudi Komm and Frank Hill during a research stay at the NSO (National Solar Observatory) in Tucson, Arizona.

²The data is publicly available online and can be downloaded here: <ftp://gong2.nso.edu/TSERIES/>

Figure 6.1: Correction for the effects of the spatial masking for the mode $(n, l) = (10, 50)$ in GONG month 5. Black data points are measurement values. Solid black lines are fits to the data to remove the effect of the masking. Red data points are the corrected values. Solid red lines indicate the weighted mean of the corrected data. Mode widths are not affected by the spatial mask.

In Figure 2.1 the geometries of six spherical harmonic functions, which are used to decompose the wavefield on the solar surface, are depicted. In the upper row, three spherical harmonic functions with harmonic degree $l = 4$ and $m = 0, 2, 4$ are shown. While the spherical harmonic with $m = 0$ is oscillating over all latitudes (with a temporal dependence of $e^{-i\omega t}$, where ω is the angular frequency), spherical harmonics with azimuthal order $m \neq 0$ are confined to latitudes closer to the equator. This can best be seen for the spherical harmonic with $l = 10$ and $m = 10$, shown in the middle panel of the lower row in Figure 2.1. The confinement to low latitudes becomes more pronounced for higher harmonic degree and higher $|m/l|$. Therefore, by masking out regions near the solar limb, more mode power is cut away from modes with low $|m/l|$ than from those with higher $|m/l|$. In contrast to this, the damping width of a mode in a power spectrum, representing the lifetime of the mode, is negligibly affected by the masking.

Some of the outputs of the GONG pipeline for the mode $(n, l) = (10, 50)$ from month 5 are shown in Figure 6.1. In the top left panel, the mode widths Γ of the azimuthal components are shown as a function of m/l but no visible dependence is observed. The solid red line is the mean of the data weighted by the error. In the top right panel, the black data points are the measured values of the mode amplitude. As discussed above, mode amplitude and all parameters derived from it (mode area, which is mode width times mode amplitude, $\Gamma \cdot A$, and width times mode area, $\Gamma^2 \cdot A$) show a dependence on m/l , which is introduced by the spatial mask. It is accounted for by fitting a polynomial proportional to $(m/l)^{2k}$ with $k = 0, 1, 2$ to the data.³ This fit is shown as a solid black line in the top right and two lower panels of Figure 6.1. The dependence is then removed, where the values at $|m/l| = 1$ are kept constant. The weighted mean of the corrected data points

³This polynomial function is empirically determined.

Figure 6.2: Correction of the effect of the temporal window function on mode parameters of mode $(n, l) = (10, 50)$. Parameter values are shown as a function of the temporal fill factor of the individual GONG months. Linear fits to the data are shown in red lines. Data are normalized to the value of the linear fit at fill = 1.

is then adopted as the representative value of the mode parameter (shown as a solid red line). Later in this chapter, these adopted values will be investigated as a function of time. In order to obtain meaningful weighted mean values, only those multiplets are included for which at least one third of the azimuthal components are fitted by the GONG pipeline. The minimum of fitted components is set to two thirds for modes with low harmonic degree $l \leq 10$, to account for their small number of azimuthal components. This ensures a well-defined weighted mean parameter value. In the following, I avoid the term multiplet, as only azimuthal averages are considered, and use the term *modes* instead.

6.1.3 Correction for Window Function

A temporal fill factor lower than 1 is equivalent to a convolution of the ideal power spectrum with the Fourier transform of the window function of the time series. This leads to a redistribution of the power from the mode peak to neighboring frequency bins and into side lobes of the main peak⁴, which, in turn, results in a diminished mode amplitude and an increased mode width. To account for this, I adopted the approach described in Komm et al. (2000b), who showed that a linear regression is sufficient to correct for the effect of the temporal window function. The specific structure of the gaps does not have to be taken into account as the fill factor is rather high with values between 69% and 93%⁵. The strongest contribution to the gap structure comes

⁴The side lobes are caused by repeating gaps in the data. These side lobes, especially those caused by daily gaps, are considerably suppressed for a network distributed around the globe as GONG (Hill et al. 1996; Leibacher 1999).

⁵A machine-readable table with the fill factor of each 36-day GONG month is available at <https://gong2.nso.edu/fill.txt>

from diurnal gaps in the data. The parameters of each mode (n, l) are corrected for the effect of the temporal window function by performing a linear regression of the available data points as a function of fill factor.

In Figure 6.3, the mode width Γ , mode amplitude A , mode area $\Gamma \cdot A$, and mode width times mode area $\Gamma^2 \cdot A$ of the mode $(n, l) = (10, 50)$ are shown as a function of fill factor. The products $\Gamma \cdot A$ and $\Gamma^2 \cdot A$ will be utilized in Section 6.3 to calculate the quantities of mean squared velocity, mode energy, and energy supply rate of the modes. The data are normalized to the value of the linear regression at fill = 1. To obtain the corrected value, the resulting linear function, shown as a red line, is then subtracted from the data and its value at fill = 1 is added. As expected, mode widths increase and amplitudes decrease with decreasing fill factor. The background amplitude and slope are also included in the output of the GONG pipeline but are of no interest for the subsequent discussions. It should, however, be noted that the background amplitude increases with decreasing fill factor. This indicates that some power from the mode peaks is distributed into the background.

6.1.4 Correction for Jumps in Sensitivity

The cameras of the GONG network were upgraded from 256×256 rectangular pixels to 1024×1024 square pixels after GONG month 60⁶ (Harvey et al. 1998). Care was taken to minimize the effect of the transition between the two sets of instrumentation on the measured mode parameters by updating the data reduction and peak finding pipeline (Toner et al. 2003; Hughes et al. 2016). However, there appears a clear jump in the mode amplitudes at the time of the network upgrade. The fractional variation of mean uncorrected mode amplitudes as a function of time is shown in Figure B.1. As a complete reprocessing of the original data is not feasible, I removed this jump by matching the mode parameters on either side of the jump using a correction factor C given in Equation B.1. This factor is dependent on the frequency and the harmonic degree of the mode.

There is another jump at month 100, which only affects mode amplitudes and derivative parameters and not mode widths (see Figure B.1). I was not able to relate this jump to a change in the instrumentation or the processing pipeline⁷. Therefore, this jump was also patched by multiplying mode amplitudes after month 100 with a correction factor (Equation (B.1)). As can be seen in Figure B.1, the magnitudes of the jumps are dependent on mode frequency (at month 60) and on harmonic degree (both at month 60 and at month 100). I included a linear term in mode frequency and a term linear in harmonic degree to the correction factor given in Equation (B.1). After applying the correction for the jump at month 60 there is strong temporal variation in mode amplitudes around this time (± 3 months). This variation does not follow a simple step-like function and is not further corrected for. Its cause is probably the incremental switch to the upgraded cameras across the network over several months.

No correction factor was applied to the mode widths. There is no clear jump visible around months 60 or 100 for mode widths. As can be seen in the fourth panel of the first column of Figure 6.7, which shows the fractional change of widths of modes with frequencies 1500–2400 μHz

⁶For a table with the exact dates of the GONG months see gong.nso.edu/data/DMAC_documentation/gongmonths.html

⁷Technicians and software experts of GONG were not able to find a documented change of the instrumentation or the processing pipeline which could affect the data in this way. As the hardware was definitely not changed at this time, the jump is probably due to an undocumented and/or unwanted change in the data processing, possibly due to an update of a software library. As the magnitude of the jump is clearly dependent on harmonic degree, one possibility is that the spherical harmonic functions, which are used to calculate the spherical harmonic time series, changed in an unnoticed way.

Figure 6.3: Normalized mode widths averaged over all modes as a function of time (*left column*), fill factor (*middle column*), and of the magnetic activity proxy $F_{10.7}$ (*right column*). The top row shows the raw data, the middle row is normalized for the effects of the fill factor, and the bottom row is corrected for fill and for change in apparent radius of the Sun.

and harmonic degrees 100–150, around month 45 there is a rapid change in mode widths. As this is only seen for mode widths in this small sub-set of modes, I chose not to apply a correction factor in this case.

6.1.5 Proxy for Solar Activity

As discussed in Chapter 3, many quantities connected to the Sun are known to vary with the solar activity cycle, e.g., the sunspot number and the emission in the Ca II H & K lines. Here, I use the solar radio flux $F_{10.7}$ as a proxy for the level of solar activity⁸. The $F_{10.7}$ is the total emission on the solar disk at a wavelength of 10.7 cm integrated over one hour. $F_{10.7}$ is measured in *solar flux units* sfu, where $1 \text{ sfu} = 10^{-22} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ Hz}^{-1}$. It is a proxy for the level of activity in the upper chromosphere and the lower corona (Tapping 2013). A comparison of different proxies of solar magnetic activity and their correlation to the activity related frequency shifts of solar p modes over the last 3 solar cycles can be found in Broomhall and Nakariakov (2015).

6.2 Temporal Variation of Mode Parameters

Mode Widths To obtain clear results on the temporal variation of mode parameters they have to be averaged over many modes. From here on, only modes which are present at all time samples are considered. The analysis is restricted to modes with $1500 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 4500 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $0 \leq l \leq 150$ for mode widths as well as mode amplitudes. As mode widths and amplitudes are

⁸ $F_{10.7}$ data can be downloaded from this website: spaceweather.gc.ca/solarflux/sx-5-en.php

Figure 6.4: Same as Figure 6.3 but for mode amplitudes.

dependent on mode frequency and harmonic degree, the values are normalized to the mean value over all time samples for each mode individually. Next, the parameters of all included modes are averaged. The result for observed mode widths $\Gamma_{\text{obs, mean}}$ is shown in the first panel of the top row of Figure 6.3. Here, the correction for the effect of the fill factor has not yet been applied. This can be seen from the middle panel of the top row, where the same data are plotted as a function of fill factor. The linear dependence on fill is apparent. In the right panel, the mode widths are shown as a function of the $F_{10.7}$ solar radio flux. The red data points in all panels of Figure 6.3 indicate time samples with higher than median level of activity as computed from the $F_{10.7}$ flux.

In the middle row of Figure 6.3, the mode widths $\Gamma_{\text{fill}=1, \text{mean}}$ are shown after the correction for the temporal window function. The apparent radius of the Sun changes along the year. This affects the measured values of oscillation parameters as the spatial resolution of the Dopplergrams changes with it. I applied a linear correction to the mode parameters as a function of apparent solar radius to correct for this. The bottom row shows the mode widths $\Gamma_{\text{fill}=1, \text{radius, mean}}$ after both, the effect of the fill factor and the change of the apparent solar radius, have been removed.

For better visibility, the left panel of the bottom row of Figure 6.3 is shown again in the top panel of Figure 6.5. As can be seen, the uncertainties on the normalized variation of the mode widths are of the order of a few tenth of a percent. The error bars given here are computed as the standard error of the mean. The solid black line is the one-year running average. The red line is the $F_{10.7}$ solar radio flux. It is boxcar smoothed over one year and scaled to match the extrema of the one-year boxcar smoothed variation of the mode widths. The correlation coefficient (Spearman's rank correlation coefficient) between the variation of the widths and the $F_{10.7}$ index (both unsmoothed) is $\rho = 0.62$ with $p = 2 \cdot 10^{-9}$. Only independent data points were used to calculate this. The number of independent data points is 74, i.e., every third 108-day GONG data set. I used Spearman's ρ for the assessment of the level of correlation of the two quantities as the relation between mode widths and activity is not strictly linear⁹: As can be

⁹In contrast to the Pearson correlation coefficient, which is used to measure linear correlations, Spearman's rank correlation can evaluate two quantities for any monotonic relation.

seen from the right panel in the bottom row in Figure 6.3, the variation of mode widths increases with the level of the $F_{10.7}$ index. However, for values of $F_{10.7} \gtrsim 130$ mode widths appear to be in saturation. The largest discrepancy between the $F_{10.7}$ index and the mode widths can be seen during the time of the camera upgrade in the GONG network around month 60. Averaged over all modes, the min-to-max amplitude of the variation of mode widths is $11.5 \pm 0.2\%$.

In Figure 6.6, the normalized variation of averages of mode widths (after the corrections for fill and apparent solar radius variation have been applied) for modes of different frequency and harmonic degree ranges are shown as a function of time. The number of modes which enter the averaging of each panel is listed in the fifth column of Table B.1. The first four columns of this table give the ranges of mode frequency and harmonic degree of the panels in Figure 6.6. In the sixth and seventh column, the minimum and maximum of the one-year boxcar smoothed variation of the individual mode subsets and their uncertainties are given. The eighth column gives the mean error of the unsmoothed data points for the mode subsets, which is calculated as the standard error of the mean.

The min-to-max variation of the mode widths over the two observed solar cycles is dependent on mode frequency and harmonic degree. The largest fractional variation is found for modes with $2400 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 3300 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $31 \leq l \leq 60$ with a min-to-max amplitude of $26.6 \pm 0.3\%$. The smallest variation of mode widths is found for the modes in the $1500 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 2400 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $101 \leq l \leq 150$ parameter regime with a min-to-max amplitude of $5.5 \pm 0.2\%$ ¹⁰. Of the three frequency ranges for each subset of modes of the same range of harmonic degrees, the middle range with $2400 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 3300 \mu\text{Hz}$ shows the largest min-to-max amplitudes over the solar cycle. The exception to this is the subset of modes with $101 \leq l \leq 150$, for which the variation over the solar cycle is largest for modes in the high frequency range.

The last two columns of Table B.1 give the correlation between the variation of mode widths and the $F_{10.7}$ index as well as the associated two-sided significance value. The highest level of correlation is found for modes with $1500 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 2400 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $0 \leq l \leq 30$ with a Spearman's rank correlation coefficient of $\rho = 0.84$ and a two-sided significance of $p < 10^{-10}$. The lowest correlation is found for modes with $1500 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 2400 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $31 \leq l \leq 60$ with $\rho = 0.31$ and $p \approx 0.01$. Within each range of harmonic degrees, the correlation coefficient increases with mode frequency. The exception to this are modes with $0 \leq l \leq 30$, where modes in the middle frequency range show the highest level of correlation to the $F_{10.7}$ index.

Mode Amplitudes In Figure 6.4, the mode amplitudes A are shown as functions of time, fill, and $F_{10.7}$ index (columns) and for three levels of correction (rows) as I previously described for the mode widths (Figure 6.3). The effect of the correction for the change in apparent size of the Sun is more pronounced for mode amplitudes than it is for mode widths. As can be seen in the left panel of the middle row, there is a pronounced yearly variation in the mode amplitudes $A_{\text{fill}=1, \text{mean}}$ after the fill correction has been applied. This is largely removed in the left panel of the bottom row. This correction is most obvious through months 110–150, which corresponds to the activity minimum between cycles 23 and 24. In the right panel of the bottom row of Figure 6.4, mode amplitudes $A_{\text{fill}=1, \text{radius}, \text{mean}}$ are shown as a function of the $F_{10.7}$ index. A clear anti-correlation between the two quantities is visible. For levels of activity up to $F_{10.7} \approx 130$,

¹⁰To suppress the impact of outliers on these amplitudes, they are calculated for the one-year boxcar smoothed values of the mode widths. The same will be applied for the variational amplitudes of the mode amplitudes below.

Figure 6.5: *Top panel:* normalized mode widths averaged over all modes (black data points). Error bars indicate the error of the mean. The solid black line is the one-year average of the mode widths. The red line is the $F_{10.7}$ solar radio flux as a function of time smoothed by boxcar with a width of one year. It is scaled to match the variation of the mode widths. *Bottom panel:* same as top panel but for mode amplitudes. The $F_{10.7}$ radio flux was flipped for better appreciation of the anti-correlation of the change in mode amplitudes and the level of activity.

Figure 6.6: Temporal variation of mode widths for different ranges of harmonic degrees (rows, harmonic degree range indicated to the right of the fourth column) and mode frequencies (columns, frequency range indicated above the first row). Widths are normalized to the mean for each mode and then averaged over all modes in the respective range of frequency and degree. Months with higher than median $F_{10.7}$ solar radio flux are highlighted by red points. The one-year average is shown by the solid black line. Levels of 1.1 and 0.9 of the mean are indicated by grey dashed lines.

Figure 6.7: Same as Figure 6.6 but for mode amplitudes.

the relation appears linear. For higher levels of activity, there is little to no change in mode amplitudes, similar to the behavior seen for mode widths.

The normalized, averaged, and corrected temporal variation for mode amplitudes is shown in the lower panel of Figure 6.5. The error bars are computed as the standard error of the mean¹¹. The solid black line is the data smoothed with a 10-bin boxcar (one year). The solid red line is the one-year-smoothed $F_{10.7}$ index. It is scaled to match the min-to-max variation of the mode amplitudes and flipped for better appreciation of the anti-correlation of the two quantities. Averaged over all modes, the min-to-max amplitude of the variation of amplitudes is $17.3 \pm 0.2\%$. The correlation coefficient (Spearman's rank correlation coefficient) between the variation of amplitudes and the $F_{10.7}$ index (both unsmoothed) is $\rho = -0.91$ with $p < 10^{-10}$. Only independent data points were used in the computation of the correlation.

The equivalent of Figure 6.6, where the normalized variation of mode widths is shown for different mode parameter regimes, is presented in Figure 6.7 for mode amplitudes. Detailed information on the individual panels is given in Table B.2. The largest variation is found for modes with $2400 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 3300 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $61 \leq l \leq 100$ with a min-to-max amplitude of $27.4 \pm 0.4\%$. Modes with frequencies $1500 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 2400 \mu\text{Hz}$ and harmonic degrees $0 \leq l \leq 30$ exhibit the smallest variation over the 22 years of data with a fractional change of $11.6\% \pm 0.5$. I find that the anti-correlation between the level of activity and the change in mode amplitudes is highest for modes with $2400 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 3300 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $0 \leq l \leq 30$ with a rank correlation of $\rho = -0.94$ and $p < 10^{-10}$. For the three ranges of harmonic degrees (l between 0–30, 31–60, and 61–100) the largest variation is found in the middle frequency range (2400–3300 μHz). For modes with $101 \leq l \leq 150$, this is observed for the high frequency modes.

Frequency Distribution of Mode Amplitudes In Figure 6.8, the amplitudes of all modes included in the analysis are shown as a function of mode frequency. Here, the amplitude values interpolated to fill = 1 are used. Any parameter variation due to residual change in apparent solar radius is averaged out as the data cover 22 years.

The solid red line in Figure 6.8 is the fit of an asymmetric Voigt profile to the mode amplitudes. This profile is described by

$$V(\nu) = \mathcal{A} \cdot \left(b + a \cdot \int G(x)L(\nu - x)dx \right) \quad (6.1)$$

where b is an offset, a is a factor to adjust the height of the profile, and the Gaussian function $G(\nu)$ and the Lorentz function $L(\nu)$ are given by

$$G(\nu) = \frac{\exp(-\nu/2\sigma^2)}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}}, \quad (6.2)$$

$$L(\nu) = \frac{\gamma}{\pi(\nu^2 + \gamma^2)}, \quad (6.3)$$

with the standard deviation of the Gaussian σ and the half-width at half maximum of the Lorentzian γ . The asymmetry is introduced with the function

$$\mathcal{A} = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\tan^{-1} (S \cdot (\nu - \nu_{\max}) / \Sigma) + 0.5 \right), \quad (6.4)$$

¹¹Consult last row of Table B.2 for more detailed information about the number of modes and the error bars presented in this plot.

Figure 6.8: Mode amplitudes as a function of mode frequency. Amplitudes are averaged over all GONG months after correction for fill factor. The red curve is an asymmetric Voigt profile fitted to the data.

where S is the asymmetry parameter, ν_{\max} is the frequency of the maximum of the symmetric Voigt profile, and the full-width-at-half-maximum of the Voigt profile, Σ , can be approximated by (Whiting 1968; Olivero and Longbothum 1977)

$$\Sigma = 1.0692\gamma + \sqrt{0.86639\gamma^2 + 8\ln(2)\sigma^2}. \quad (6.5)$$

The resulting fit parameters are given in Table 6.1. For the frequency of maximum amplitude, I find $\nu_{\max} = 3073.59 \pm 0.18 \mu\text{Hz}$. The width of the Voigt profile is $\Sigma = 612.3 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{Hz}$. The parameter $S = -0.072 \pm 0.002$ indicates a slight asymmetry towards lower frequencies. It should be noted that the maximum of the mode amplitudes ν_{\max} presented here is not exactly what is often referred to as ν_{\max} in the literature. It is usually measured from Sun-as-a-star data which only include low harmonic degrees up to $l \lesssim 4$ (Broomhall et al. 2009). Here, ν_{\max} is the maximum of the mode amplitudes in the frequency spectrum of the spherical harmonic transform of the GONG Doppler velocity data for all harmonic degrees up to $l = 150$. There are different values for the value of ν_{\max} in the literature: $3050 \mu\text{Hz}$ by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995), $3090 \mu\text{Hz}$ by Viani et al. (2017), $3104 \mu\text{Hz}$ as a calibrated value to obtain better results from asteroseismic scaling relations by Mosser et al. (2013), $3120 \mu\text{Hz}$ from SOHO/Virgo data by Kallinger et al. (2010). If ν_{\max} is measured from the velocity of the modes (as will be discussed in Section 6.3, the mean velocity of the modes is proportional to mode width Γ times mode amplitude A), the damping widths Γ are included in the measured quantity. As mode widths change with mode frequency and harmonic degree (see next section), the maxima in mode amplitude A and mean velocity of the modes (proportional to $\Gamma \cdot A$) occur for different frequencies.

The χ_{red}^2 of the fit is 29.2. This rather high χ_{red}^2 value is due to the spread in the distribution of the mode amplitudes, the small error bars on them, and the outliers under the curve. Interestingly, these outliers are all of low harmonic degree $l \lesssim 50$. Other profiles were tested (pure Gaussian, pure Lorentzian, both Gaussian and Lorentzian with asymmetry included), but the resulting χ_{red}^2 was considerably larger for all of them.

Table 6.1: Parameters of the fit to the frequency distribution of mode amplitudes.

ν_{\max} (μHz)	σ (μHz)	γ (μHz)	Σ (μHz)
3073.59 ± 0.18	184.9 ± 0.3	146.1 ± 0.2	612.3 ± 0.7
a ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2} \text{Hz}^{-1}$)	b ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2} \text{Hz}^{-1}$)	S	χ_{red}^2
33423896 ± 15229	-561 ± 1	-0.072 ± 0.002	29.2

6.3 Results for Physical Quantities

The mode widths and mode amplitudes can be combined to give further physical parameters of the oscillation modes. The amplitude A is given as power per frequency bin $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2} \text{Hz}^{-1}$. Hence, calculating the product of mode width and mode amplitude $\Gamma_{nl} \cdot A_{nl}$ has the unit of squared velocity. The quantity $\Gamma_{nl} \cdot A_{nl}$ is referred to as the *mode area*, i.e., the area under the fitted peak in the spectrum (Komm et al. 2000b). The mean squared velocity of the modes can be calculated as (Goldreich et al. 1994)

$$\langle v_{nl}^2 \rangle = \frac{\pi}{2} C_{\text{vis}} A_{nl} \Gamma_{nl}. \quad (6.6)$$

Symmetric Lorentzian profiles are fitted to the peaks in the power spectrum by the GONG pipeline. This is taken into account by the factor $\pi/2$. The factor $C_{\text{vis}} = 3.33$ corrects for the reduced visibility of modes due to leakage effects (Hill and Howe 1998).

Due to the different cavities in which modes of different harmonic degree and frequency propagate (see Section 2.5.1), the fraction of the mass of the Sun that is affected by different modes varies. The *mode mass* M_{nl} is given by

$$M_{nl} = M_{\odot} I_{nl}, \quad (6.7)$$

where M_{\odot} is the solar mass and the *mode inertia* I_{nl} is calculated as

$$I_{nl} = \frac{4\pi \int_0^{R_{\odot}} \rho(r) \left(\xi_{nl}^r(r)^2 + l(l+1) \xi_{nl}^h(r)^2 \right) r^2 dr}{M_{\odot} \left(\xi_{nl}^r(R_{\odot})^2 + l(l+1) \xi_{nl}^h(R_{\odot})^2 \right)}. \quad (6.8)$$

Here, $\xi_{nl}^r(r)$ and $\xi_{nl}^h(r)$ are the radial and horizontal displacement eigenfunctions, $\xi_{nl}^r(R_{\odot})$ and $\xi_{nl}^h(R_{\odot})$ are their values at the photospheric radius, and $\rho(r)$ is mass density.

The mode inertias of the eigenmodes of the standard solar model ‘Model S’ (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996), as calculated with Equation (6.8), are shown as a function of frequency in Figure 6.9. The harmonic degree of the modes is indicated by the color of the circles. It can be seen that mode inertia of solar acoustic oscillations decreases by two orders of magnitude between modes with frequencies of $1500 \mu\text{Hz}$ and those with frequencies of $3000 \mu\text{Hz}$. Mode inertia decreases along ridges of modes with same radial order n with increasing harmonic degree (connected by thin grey lines). This reflects the depth of the lower turning point of each mode, which is moving

Figure 6.9: Mode inertia of the solar model ‘Model S’ (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996) as a function of mode frequency as calculated with Equation (6.8). Harmonic degrees of the modes are indicated by the color of the points. Modes of same radial order are joined by grey lines.

outward with increasing harmonic degree: Less mass of the Sun is affected by the mode. Hence, the mode inertia is lower.

The energy that is stored in the modes can be calculated as the product of mode mass (6.7) and mean squared velocity (6.6):

$$E_{nl} = M_{nl} \langle v_{nl}^2 \rangle. \quad (6.9)$$

This is the total mode energy, i.e., the sum of kinetic and potential energy (Goldreich et al. 1994). The rate at which energy is supplied to the modes can be calculated by the product of the energy in the modes and the radian damping rate of the modes $2\pi\Gamma_{nl}$ (Kumar et al. 1988; Goldreich et al. 1994):

$$\frac{dE_{nl}}{dt} = 2\pi E_{nl} \Gamma_{nl} = \pi^2 C_{\text{vis}} M_{nl} A_{nl} \Gamma_{nl}^2, \quad (6.10)$$

which is proportional to the product of squared mode width Γ_{nl}^2 and mode amplitude A_{nl} .

In Figure 6.10, the mode width (damping rate) Γ , mean squared velocity $\langle v_{nl}^2 \rangle$, mode energy E , and energy supply rate dE/dt of modes with harmonic degree $l > 10$ are shown on logarithmic scales as functions of mode frequency¹². For each mode, the values for Γ , A , $\Gamma \cdot A$, and $\Gamma^2 \cdot A$ are calculated as the mean over all time samples after correction for the fill factor. Any effects from the activity cycle or residual yearly variations are averaged out as the data set spans two complete Schwabe cycles. The conversion of these quantities to physical units is then done according to Equations (6.6), (6.9), and (6.10).

The mode widths (upper left panel in Figure 6.10) increase from 0.3–0.5 μHz at low mode frequencies $\approx 1500 \mu\text{Hz}$ to values between 1–2 μHz for mode frequencies between 2400–3000 μHz .

¹²Modes with $l \leq 10$ are excluded here to reduce the scatter in these plots. The parameters of these modes are less well-defined due to their small number of azimuthal components, see Section 6.1.2.

Figure 6.10: Mode widths Γ , mean squared velocity $\langle v^2 \rangle$, mode energies E , and energy supply rates dE/dt as functions of frequency. Averaged over all GONG months.

For higher mode frequencies, mode widths increase again, reaching $\Gamma \approx 10 \mu\text{Hz}$ for the highest included mode frequencies. The mean squared velocity (upper right panel) increases monotonically with mode frequency until it reaches its maximum for modes with frequencies of $\approx 3200 \mu\text{Hz}$. The maximum mean velocity value is $v \approx 37 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. The mode widths, mean squared velocity, as well as the energy supply rate (lower right panel) show ridges of modes with equal radial order. Different ridges are slightly offset from one another but show the same behavior with frequency. The ridge structure is not apparent in the mode energies (lower left panel). The difference between mode energy E and the other three quantities is the inclusion of mode inertia, see Equations (6.6), (6.9), and (6.10).

A normalized mode inertia can be calculated by computing the ratio of the mode inertia I_{nl} to the inertia of radial modes $\overline{I_{n0}}$ interpolated to the frequency of the mode ν_{nl} (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996; Aerts et al. 2010):

$$Q_{nl} = \frac{I_{nl}}{\overline{I_{n0}}(\nu_{nl})}. \quad (6.11)$$

The result of multiplying mode widths, mean squared velocity, and energy supply rates with Q_{nl} is shown in Figure 6.11. The overall frequency dependence of the quantities is unchanged. However, ridges of different radial orders are now largely collapsed into one. This can best be observed for $\langle v_{nl}^2 \rangle$ (top left panel), which is only composed of one thin line of data points without any residual ridge structure. The steep gradient in mode inertia at low frequencies is not perfectly represented by scaling Q_{nl} with $\overline{I_{n0}}$. Some of the residual scatter in mode widths, energies, and energy supply rate at low mode frequencies is due to this. Different scalings, e.g., with the interpolated inertia of $l = 50$ modes, give somewhat different results (Komm et al. 2000b). However, the scatter in the scaled quantities is never completely removed. The remaining dependence observed in mode widths across all frequencies may hold information on a degree dependence of the involved damping mechanisms.

To be able to appreciate the temporal change of the four quantities (mode widths, mean squared

Figure 6.11: Same as Figure 6.10 but normalized for mode inertia with Equation (6.11). Mode energy E is unchanged.

velocity, mode energy, mode energy supply rate), the parameters of many modes have to be averaged. As the quantities cover two to three orders of magnitude for the investigated set of modes, the frequency range of averaging has to be restricted. Otherwise, values which differ by orders of magnitude would contribute to the average. In Table 6.2, the frequency ranges of the modes which are taken for the averaging of the four quantities, and the number of modes within these frequency ranges are given. The frequency ranges are chosen to select as many modes as possible with similar parameter values (within about a factor of two).

The result of this averaging is presented in Figure 6.12 as a function of time. The red data points indicate times of higher than median level of activity and the solid black lines are the data smoothed with a one-year boxcar. The last two rows of Table 6.2 give the rank correlation of independent data points between the four quantities and the $F_{10.7}$ index as well as the two-sided significance value. As before, the mode widths are correlated with the level of magnetic activity with $\rho = 0.69$. Both, the temporal variation in mean squared velocity and mode energy are highly anti-correlated with the level of solar activity with a value of $\rho = -0.88$. The energy supply rate is not correlated with solar activity for the here investigated set of modes as $\rho = -0.01$ and $p = 0.88$.

6.4 Summary and Discussion

In this chapter, I analyzed mode parameter data from the ground-based GONG network spanning two complete solar cycles. Systematic effects due to the spatial masking of the GONG full-disk solar images, the imperfect temporal sampling, and a yearly modulation due to changes in the apparent radius of the Sun were corrected for. Measurements of mode widths and mode amplitudes are generally less robust than measurements of mode frequencies. Thus, averages over azimuthal orders as well as modes of different ranges of frequencies and harmonic degrees have to be performed in order to reach meaningful results for the temporal variation of these mode

Figure 6.12: Mode widths Γ , mean squared velocity $\langle v^2 \rangle$, mode energies E , and energy supply rates dE/dt as functions of time. Averaged over all modes in the frequency ranges given in Table 6.2.

parameters. For the mode widths, which were averaged over 1275 modes, a variation of $11.5 \pm 0.2\%$ was found between the minimum and maximum level of activity in the investigated time period. Mode amplitudes varied by $17.3 \pm 0.2\%$ over the same time (averaged over 1272 modes). Overall, the results from previous analyses of the variation of mode widths and amplitudes with the level of solar activity by, e.g., Komm et al. (2000a), Komm et al. (2000b), and Broomhall et al. (2015) could be confirmed.

Little attention has been given to mode widths and amplitudes (for resolved solar data that is, Komm et al. 2000b; Korzennik et al. 2013; Korzennik 2017 being the most notable exceptions), let alone their temporal variation over the solar cycle, as damping widths and amplitudes cannot be accurately calculated with the existing theory of convection and mode excitation (see, e.g., Houdek et al. 1999; Houdek and Dupret 2015; Basu 2016). Thanks to the long, uninterrupted GONG time series that is now available, the dependence of the variation of the mode widths and amplitudes could be investigated for subsets of modes and as functions of the level of solar activity. The amplitude of the shifts of mode frequencies with the level of solar activity is known to increase with mode frequency (Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998; Salabert et al. 2015). In stark contrast to this, this behavior is neither observed for mode widths nor mode amplitudes. For these two parameters, the largest variation over the solar cycle is observed around the frequency of maximum power ν_{\max} , see Tables B.1 and B.2. This indicates that the mechanisms through which the frequencies are changed by the presence of the magnetic field associated with the solar cycle differ from those physical mechanisms which perturbs the mode damping widths and the mode amplitudes. Mode widths and amplitudes are determined by the excitation and damping of the acoustic oscillations in very shallow layers, where convection is most vigorous (Balmforth 1992; Rimmele et al. 1995; Houdek and Dupret 2015). Hence, this is where the changing magnetic field over the solar cycle affects mode widths and amplitudes the most. In contrast to this, mode frequencies are also perturbed by magnetic fields which are seated much deeper, as I will show in Chapter 9. An analysis of the timing of the changes in mode frequencies, amplitudes, and

Table 6.2: Frequency ranges for averaging of quantities, number of modes in this frequency range.

	Γ	$\langle v^2 \rangle$	E	dE/dt
Frequency range (μHz)	2400–3000	2900–3300	2900–3300	3000–3600
Number of modes	358	237	237	385
Correlation ρ	0.69	-0.88	-0.88	-0.01
p value	$< 10^{-10}$	$< 10^{-10}$	$< 10^{-10}$	0.88

widths may yield information on the evolution and possibly the gradual ascending of magnetic field concentrations in the outer part of the convection zone.

The mode amplitudes as a function of mode frequency were fitted with an asymmetric Voigt profile. From this, I found a frequency of maximum amplitude at $\nu_{\max} = 3073.93 \pm 0.18 \mu\text{Hz}$. The frequency of maximum power ν_{\max} is of great interest to asteroseismic studies due to its use in asteroseismic scaling relations (see Section 2.8.1). This value found here compares well to those found in the literature (see page 84). I found that the mode amplitudes are a function of radial order and frequency, as can be seen in Figure 6.8. The spread in the distribution of the mode amplitudes as a function of mode frequency (see Figure 6.8) could not be removed by multiplication with mode inertia as for, e.g., mean squared velocity of the modes. This indicates that the excitation of modes is intrinsically not only a function of mode frequency.

The physical parameters of mean squared velocity, mode energy, and energy supply rate were calculated from the mode widths and amplitudes. Ridges of the same radial order of the modes are evident in the mode widths, mean squared velocity, and the energy supply rates (Figure 6.10). This is removed by scaling them with their mode inertia Q_{nl} (Figure 6.11), indicating that Q_{nl} is the correct scaling for mode widths, mean squared velocity, and energy supply rates (Komm et al. 2000b; Aerts et al. 2010). The maximum of the velocity of the modes is approximately 37 cm s^{-1} . This value is somewhat higher than the value of $\approx 27 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ found by Chaplin et al. (1998) for radial modes from BiSON data. As modes of very low harmonic degree (below $l = 10$) are not included in my investigation, it may well be that their velocity measured by GONG is closer to the value of Chaplin et al. (1998) than that of modes for higher degree. This is supported by the fact that, at closer inspection, I found that modes of lower harmonic degree are found on the lower edge of the distribution shown in the top right panel of Figure 6.12.

To obtain the temporal variation of these quantities (i.e., mean squared velocity, energy, and energy supply rate; in physical units, not normalized to their temporal mean), an average over modes within a frequency range specific to each quantity (see Table 6.2) was calculated for the inertia corrected parameter values. The average of the mode widths was found to vary by $12.9 \pm 1.0\%$ ¹³, with a maximum width of $1.36 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{Hz}$ at the maximum of solar cycle 23 and a minimum of $1.19 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{Hz}$ during the activity minimum between cycles 23 and 24. The mean squared velocity varied by $14.7 \pm 0.3\%$ with extrema of $1065 \pm 2 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $1249 \pm 4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. The mean mode energy exhibits variation between $1.64 \pm 0.01 \times 10^{28} \text{ erg}$ and $2.06 \pm 0.01 \times 10^{28} \text{ erg}$ which corresponds to a variation by $18.4 \pm 0.3\%$. This highlights that detectability of solar-like oscillation is reduced in stars with high levels of magnetic activity, as has been investigated and

¹³The fractional changes in this paragraph are calculated as $1 - \min(\text{parameter})/\max(\text{parameter})$. All values given in this paragraph are calculated from the data smoothed over one year.

shown by Chaplin et al. (2011). These fractional changes are considerably different for modes of different frequencies, as can be seen from Figures 6.6 and 6.7. The variation of the mean energy supply rate, shown in the lower right panel of Figure 6.12 is not correlated with the level of solar activity for the investigated set of modes. This confirms the results of, e.g., Chaplin et al. (2000) and Broomhall et al. (2015), who also found that the energy supply rate to the solar p modes does not change with the level of activity. Overall there is a decrease in supply rates over the observed time period of about 8%. However, this decrease happened entirely before GONG month 60, hence before the upgrade of the GONG network. Since then, it has remained at a rather constant level. A dedicated study of energy supply rates, focusing on mode sets from different frequency ranges and harmonic degree ranges, as was done here for mode widths and amplitudes, will give further insight into whether the energy supply rates are truly constant over the solar cycle.

Essentials of Perturbation Theory

7.1 From Observation to Theory

This chapter shall connect the preceding chapters, which are more data-oriented, and the following chapters, which are more theory-oriented. In Chapter 5, we have seen how magnetic activity can be detected in the oscillation parameters of solar-like stars. This research was focused on mode frequencies. In Chapter 6, I then showed how solar p-mode parameters (mode widths, mode amplitudes, and derivative parameters) change along the solar cycle. In this chapter, I derive a method with which we can calculate the effect of a magnetic field on solar and stellar oscillation frequencies.

Seismic forward modeling, as presented in Chapters 8 and Chapter 9, aims to reproduce observed phenomena or quantities with reasonable input values of, e.g., the magnetic field strength. The observed frequency shifts of solar p modes over the solar cycle are the observational quantities which I aim to reproduce here. The physics and parameters of a star which determine its eigenfrequencies are well understood, as I described in Chapter 2: Solving the perturbed stellar structure equations numerically yields the star's eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies.

Solar-like acoustic oscillations are excited by turbulent convection. As can be seen best in the extreme example of Sunspots, see Figure 3.6, a magnetic field suppresses the convective energy transport and hence the excitation of acoustic waves. Measurements of frequencies, damping widths, and amplitudes of acoustic oscillations within Sunspots and in their surroundings have shown that they are all strongly influenced by the magnetic field. As Braun et al. (1987) have shown, sunspots can absorb a large fraction of the incoming acoustic wave power. It has been shown in theoretical calculation by, e.g., Bogdan et al. (1996) that thin magnetic flux tubes can dampen acoustic oscillations in the Sun. Calculation of the global modal amplitudes and mode damping rates requires the solution of the oscillation equations (see Chapter 2) for the non-adiabatic case (see Section 4.3 of Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard 2017 and references therein). The perturbation of the energy transport and the energy equation by the magnetic field needs to be modeled¹. This, however, is beyond the scope of this thesis. I focus on the calculation of perturbed mode frequencies in the following. I employ concepts from perturbation theory to calculate the effect of a magnetic field on stellar oscillation frequencies.

In the Introduction, I posed the question “*How does a magnetic field affect a star's oscillations?*”. The goal is now to develop a formalism with which this question can be answered. The formalism

¹Equations for the calculation of the effect of an axisymmetric magnetic field on the angular momentum transport and the chemical mixing in stars were presented by Mathis and Zahn (2005).

shall allow to numerically calculate the eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies of a star with a large-scale magnetic field from its previously obtained set of eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies without the magnetic field. This shall be done in such a way that solar as well as stellar models can be investigated. The observed frequency shifts, such as those presented for stars observed by *Kepler* in Chapter 5, shall be reproducible with the formalism. This may help to rule out certain magnetic field configurations that lead to frequency shifts that cannot be reconciled with the observations. The results will be helpful in guiding dynamo simulations of the Sun and the stars and also help answer the question “*Where in the solar interior is the location of the dynamo?*”.

In this chapter, I introduce the concepts of perturbation theory, on which the explanations and derivations in Chapters 8 and 9 are based. I present the essentials of perturbation theory more detailed² than this is done in the publications which are included in Chapters 8 and 9. Much of the content of this chapter is inspired by the work of [Lavelly and Ritzwoller \(1992\)](#) and can also be found in the theses of [Roth \(2002\)](#), [Schad \(2013\)](#), and [Herzberg \(2016\)](#).

7.2 Basic Ideas of Perturbation Theory

The theory that is relevant to this thesis is time-independent perturbation theory, i.e., the Rayleigh-Schrödinger perturbation theory. The magnetic field, which is the perturbation under investigation in this thesis, does, of course, depend on time, as we have seen in the preceding chapters. However, the relevant time scale for changes of the large-scale magnetic field is the stellar cycle length, which is eleven years for the Sun. It is, therefore, reasonable to consider a specific magnetic field configuration to be stationary compared to the oscillation time scale of five minutes³ and examine the effect of this configuration on the unperturbed system. Different configurations, which correspond to the large-scale magnetic field at different times in the stellar cycle can thus be investigated independently.

The operator of a perturbed system \mathcal{L} can be decomposed into two parts⁴:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_1, \quad (7.1)$$

where \mathcal{L}_0 is the operator of the unperturbed system and \mathcal{L}_1 describes the perturbation. Solving the eigenvalue problem

$$\mathcal{L}_0 \boldsymbol{\xi}^0 = \omega^2 \boldsymbol{\xi}^0 \quad (7.2)$$

yields the eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions of the problem. Here, $\boldsymbol{\xi}^0$ is an eigenfunction of the unperturbed system and ω^2 is the squared eigenfrequency of this eigenfunction. By introducing the perturbation \mathcal{L}_1 into the system, the eigenvalue equation

$$(\mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_1) \boldsymbol{\xi} = \tilde{\omega}^2 \boldsymbol{\xi} \quad (7.3)$$

has to be solved. Here, $\tilde{\omega}^2$ is the eigenfrequency of the perturbed system.

²Some duplicity of equations and explanations here and in the included publications cannot be avoided.

³This corresponds to the solar p modes, which have frequencies of the order of 3 mHz.

⁴I change the notation from what is usually used in quantum mechanics textbooks on perturbation theory. The Hamilton operator of the unperturbed system is usually denoted by H in quantum mechanics, e.g., [Sakurai and Napolitano \(2014\)](#). However, in this thesis, H is used to denote the general matrix. The term *general matrix* is used in astrophysical literature, introduced by [Lavelly and Ritzwoller \(1992\)](#), to describe the perturbation matrix in the basis of the eigenfunctions of the star, see Equation 7.9.

It can be shown (see Section 8.2) that for a star without flows or a magnetic field the equivalent of Equation (7.2) is given by⁵

$$-\rho_0\omega^2\xi^0 = \mathcal{L}_0(\xi^0), \quad (7.4)$$

where the Hermitian operator of the unperturbed system (star) is given by

$$\mathcal{L}_0(\xi^0) = -\Delta(\nabla p) + \mathbf{g}_0\Delta\rho + \rho_0\Delta\mathbf{g}. \quad (7.5)$$

Here, ρ is density, Δ is the Lagrangian perturbation operator (see Equation (8.2)), ∇p is the pressure gradient, \mathbf{g} is gravitational acceleration, and the sub- and superscript 0 indicate equilibrium quantities of the system⁶. As demonstrated in Appendix B of Lively and Ritzwoller (1992), $\mathcal{L}_0(\xi^0)$ can be transformed into a form where its linear dependence on ξ^0 is apparent. The eigenfunctions in Equation (7.4), which can be identified with the eigenfunctions of stellar oscillations as discussed in Section 2.3, form an orthonormal basis with the orthogonality relation⁷

$$\int_V \rho_0 \bar{\xi}_{k'} \cdot \xi_k dV = N_k \delta_{k'k}, \quad (7.6)$$

where the first eigenfunction is complex conjugated, the integral is over the volume of the system, and

$$N_k = \int_0^R \rho_0 \left(\xi^r(r)^2 + l(l+1)\xi^h(r)^2 \right) r^2 dr. \quad (7.7)$$

Here, $k = (n, l)$ and $k' = (n', l')$ index the tuple of radial order and harmonic degree. Furthermore, ξ^r and ξ^h are the radial and horizontal eigenfunctions, respectively. The azimuthal order m is not relevant in this case, because the eigenfunctions ξ^r and ξ^h do not depend on it. The perturbation operator of a magnetic field (see Equation (8.23)) is given by

$$\mathcal{L}_B(\xi^0) = \rho_0\Delta \left(\frac{1}{4\pi\rho} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} \right), \quad (7.8)$$

where \mathbf{B} is the magnetic field. This can be added to the right-hand side of Equation (7.4) as a perturbation, yielding an eigenvalue equation of the perturbed system equivalent to Equation (7.3).

The eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies of the unperturbed star⁸ are obtained with stellar oscillation codes, e.g., the ADIPLS code (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2008), see Section 2.3. With a suitable perturbation theory, the eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies of the perturbed system are obtained from those of the unperturbed system.

There are different ways of calculating the solutions to Equation (7.3) depending on the differences of the frequencies of the unperturbed system that is under investigation: In the following, I briefly introduce non-degenerate perturbation theory and, what can be seen as a special case of this, quasi-degenerate perturbation theory.

⁵I conform to the notation of Lively and Ritzwoller (1992) and keep the factor $-\rho_0$ on the left-hand side from hereon.

⁶That is, the Lagrangian perturbation operator did not act on them. See Section 8.2 for further clarification.

⁷Throughout this chapter an index k on eigenfunctions is assumed to denote the tuple $k = (n, l, m)$ of radial order, harmonic degree, and azimuthal order.

⁸As the systems under investigation in this thesis are stars, I use the terms *star* and *system* interchangeably.

7.3 Non-Degenerate Perturbation Theory

Let the eigenfrequencies of the unperturbed system be non-degenerate, i.e., $\omega_k^2 \neq \omega_{k'}^2$ for $k \neq k'$. Then, each eigenfunction ξ_k^0 can be uniquely assigned to one eigenfrequency ω_k^2 . An element of the perturbation matrix \mathbf{H} for the perturbation operator \mathcal{L}_1 is defined as

$$H_{k',k} = \int_V \overline{\xi_{k'}} \cdot \mathcal{L}_1 \cdot \xi_k \, dV. \quad (7.9)$$

This matrix representation of the perturbation is constructed with a convenient choice for the basis, i.e., the eigenfunctions of the unperturbed system.

With this, the eigenfrequencies $\tilde{\omega}_k^2$ and eigenfunctions ξ_k of the perturbed system can be approximated in a series expansion (e.g., Sakurai and Napolitano 2014):

$$\tilde{\omega}_k^2 = \omega_k^2 + H_{kk} + \sum_{k' \neq k} \frac{H_{k'k} H_{kk'}}{\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2}, \quad (7.10)$$

$$\xi_k = \xi_k^0 + \sum_{k' \neq k} \frac{H_{k'k}}{\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2} \xi_{k'}^0 + \sum_{k'' \neq k'} \sum_{k'' \neq k} \frac{H_{k'k''} H_{k''k}}{(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2)(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k''}^2)} \xi_{k'}^0 - \sum_{k' \neq k} \frac{H_{k'k} H_{kk}}{(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2)^2} \xi_{k'}^0, \quad (7.11)$$

where the sums extend over all states except k . Here, I stop the expansions at second order, which usually is enough to obtain a good approximation for both the eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions. As can be seen from Equation (7.11), the perturbed eigenfunction ξ_k has contributions from all states $\xi_{k'}^0$ with $k' \neq k$. This *mixing* of eigenfunctions depends on the strength of the coupling between them, which is quantified by the matrix elements $H_{k'k}$, and their difference in squared angular frequency.

For the expansions (7.10) and (7.11) to converge, the necessary condition

$$\left| \frac{H_{k'k}}{\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2} \right| \ll 1, \quad (7.12)$$

i.e., the matrix element for a coupling between two eigenfunctions is smaller than the difference of their squared eigenfrequencies, must be fulfilled. Otherwise, terms of higher order contribute more to the series expansion than terms of lower order. This has two implications: First, the perturbation must not be too strong. Second, the eigenfrequencies must not be too close or even degenerate.

As the spectrum of solar-like oscillators is usually dense, i.e., $|\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2| \ll \omega_k^2$, the concepts of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory are employed in the following chapters.

7.4 Quasi-Degenerate Perturbation Theory

As can be seen from Equations (7.10) and (7.11), states k' whose eigenfrequencies are close to that of mode k contribute more to the series expansion of the perturbed frequency and eigenfunction than those whose eigenfrequencies are far away. This is where quasi-degenerate perturbation theory comes into play.

For an arbitrary reference frequency, the frequency range of influence is restricted by the quasi-degeneracy condition

$$|\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 - \omega_k^2| < \Delta\omega^2. \quad (7.13)$$

Eigenfunctions of the system with frequencies in this range are nearly degenerate. Hence, the strength of their coupling to the reference frequency is dominating over that of the eigenfunctions outside this range. The accuracy of the subsequent calculations of the perturbed quantities is determined by the choice⁹ of $\Delta\omega^2$. The sets of coupling eigenfunctions K and its complement K^\perp are defined by the quasi-degeneracy condition, by the geometrical configuration of the perturbation, which entails angular momentum selection rules, and by the considered modes, as described in detail in Chapter 8. It is convenient to choose the reference frequency ω_{ref} to be equal or close to the frequency of the eigenfunction under consideration k .¹⁰

I will now derive the *supermatrix* \mathbf{Z} , with which an eigenvalue problem can be formulated whose solutions are the perturbed eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions in the quasi-degenerate framework.¹¹

7.4.1 The Supermatrix \mathbf{Z}

Introducing the perturbations

$$\mathcal{L}_0 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_1, \quad (7.14a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}^0 \rightarrow \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^0 + \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^1, \quad (7.14b)$$

$$\omega^2 \rightarrow \omega_{\text{ref}}^2 + \omega_1^2, \quad (7.14c)$$

$$\rho_0 \rightarrow \rho_0 + \rho_1, \quad (7.14d)$$

into Equation (7.4) results in

$$-(\rho_0 + \rho_1) (\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 + \omega_1^2) (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^0 + \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^1) = (\mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_1) (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^0 + \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^1). \quad (7.15)$$

A subscript 1 denotes departures from the respective unperturbed quantity. The expansion of the squared eigenfrequency (7.14c) respects the underlying idea of the quasi-degeneracy ansatz: The strength of the coupling of states depends on their distance to the reference frequency and they are thus shifted with respect to this frequency. The notation of the perturbed eigenfunctions will be motivated shortly.

Retaining only terms linear in the perturbations¹² in Equation (7.15) yields

$$(\mathcal{L}_0 + \rho_0\omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^1 + (\mathcal{L}_1 + \rho_1\omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^0 + \rho_0\omega_1^2 \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^0 + (\mathcal{L}_0 + \rho_0\omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^0 \approx 0. \quad (7.16)$$

⁹It must be chosen in such a way to adequately compromise between computational effort and accuracy.

¹⁰For solar oscillations the central frequency of a multiplet is usually chosen as ω_{ref} . As we will see in the next chapters, couplings within a degenerate multiplet, i.e., components of a multiplet with different azimuthal order but the same frequency, are forbidden for the perturbations I consider in this thesis. Thus, the degeneracy of the multiplet does in no way affect the following derivations.

¹¹The following derivations can also be found in Lavelly and Ritzwoller (1992), who introduced the notation and terminology that is used here to astrophysical literature.

¹²That is, linear in the second terms of the expansions (7.14).

The perturbed eigenfunctions to zeroth and first orders, i.e., $\tilde{\xi}^0$ and $\tilde{\xi}^1$, can be described as a weighted sum over the unperturbed eigenfunctions ξ_k ¹³, for which the modes k are within a coupling set K or K^\perp , multiplied by a coupling coefficient:

$$\tilde{\xi}^0 = \sum_{k \in K} a_k \xi_k, \quad (7.17a)$$

$$\tilde{\xi}^1 = \sum_{k \in K^\perp} b_k \xi_k, \quad (7.17b)$$

where the coupling coefficients a_k and b_k may in general be complex valued. Inserting these two expressions into Equation (7.16), multiplying with $\overline{\xi_{k'}}$ from the left, and integrating over the stellar volume¹⁴ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k \in K^\perp} b_k \int_V \overline{\xi_{k'}} \cdot (\mathcal{L}_0 + \rho_0 \omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \xi_k dV + \sum_{k \in K} a_k \left\{ \int_V \overline{\xi_{k'}} \cdot (\mathcal{L}_1 + \rho_1 \omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \xi_k dV \right. \\ \left. + \omega_1^2 \int_V \rho_0 \overline{\xi_{k'}} \cdot \xi_k dV + \int_V \overline{\xi_{k'}} \cdot (\mathcal{L}_0 + \rho_0 \omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \xi_k dV \right\} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (7.18)$$

By employing the orthonormality relation (7.6) and the eigenvalue equation of the unperturbed system (7.4) this can be written as

$$- \sum_{k \in K^\perp} b_k (\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 - \omega_k^2) \delta_{k'k} + \sum_{k \in K} a_k Z_{k'k} = \sum_{k \in K} a_k \omega_1^2 \delta_{k'k}, \quad (7.19)$$

where an element of the supermatrix \mathbf{Z} is defined by

$$Z_{k'k} = \frac{1}{N_k} \left\{ \int_V \overline{\xi_{k'}} \cdot (-\mathcal{L}_1 - \rho_1 \omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \xi_k dV - (\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 - \omega_k^2) N_k \delta_{k'k} \right\}. \quad (7.20)$$

The terms in the first sum of Equation (7.19) are only non-zero if $k' = k$. Now, as $k \in K^\perp$ for this sum, the terms in b_k decouple from the terms in a_k for $k \in K$. The perturbation coefficients b_k as defined in Equation (7.17b) therefore do not influence the perturbed eigenfrequencies ω_1^2 or the perturbed eigenfunctions of zeroth order $\tilde{\xi}^0$. With this, Equation (7.19) reduces to

$$\sum_{k \in K} a_k Z_{k'k} = \sum_{k \in K} a_k \omega_1^2 \delta_{k'k} \text{ for } k' \in K, \quad (7.21)$$

which can be written in matrix form:

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{\Lambda}. \quad (7.22)$$

The solutions to this equation are the eigenvector matrix \mathbf{A} and the diagonal matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda}$. An element on the diagonal of this matrix, Λ_{kk} , is a frequency perturbation $(\omega_1^2)_k$ and the corresponding eigenvector, a row of the matrix \mathbf{A} holds the expansion coefficients a_k of the perturbed eigenfunction $\tilde{\xi}^0$ as components, see Equation (7.17a). The calculation of the eigenvalues and eigenvectors introduces the complication that it is not a priori clear which eigenvector belongs to which unperturbed eigenfunction. For weak perturbations, the assignment of perturbed to

¹³The superscript 0, which so far indicated eigenfunctions of the unperturbed system, is dropped in this section. It is only used where it is necessary to avoid confusion of perturbed and unperturbed eigenfunctions.

¹⁴This corresponds to calculating the perturbation matrix via the inner product of eigenfunctions and perturbation operator as is done in Equation (7.9).

unperturbed quantities can be achieved the following way: For the k 'th unperturbed eigenfunction, the k 'th element of the corresponding eigenvector of \mathbf{Z} is closest to unity, as other states are only weakly mixed in. Hence, a simple search for that row yields the wanted eigenvector. For a detailed discussion of other approaches, e.g., if the coupling set is degenerate, see [Herzberg \(2016\)](#).

The normalization constant N_k , see Equation (7.7), is equal to unity if the radial and horizontal eigenfunctions, ξ^r and ξ^h , are normalized according to

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_{\text{norm}}^r &= \frac{\xi^r}{\sqrt{N_k}}, \\ \xi_{\text{norm}}^h &= \frac{\xi^h}{\sqrt{N_k}}.\end{aligned}\tag{7.23}$$

Also, the identification

$$H_{k'k} = \int_V \overline{\xi_{k'}} \cdot (-\mathcal{L}_1 - \rho_1 \omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \xi_k dV\tag{7.24}$$

is made in Equation (7.20) and $H_{k'k}$ is called the *general matrix element* (see Equation (7.9)). With this and the normalized eigenfunctions (7.23), an element of the supermatrix can be written as

$$Z_{k'k} = \begin{cases} H_{k'k} - (\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 - \omega_k^2) \delta_{k'k} & \text{for } k', k \in K, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}\tag{7.25}$$

As is shown in [Lavelly and Ritzwoller \(1992\)](#), the general matrix element (7.24) can be decomposed into two parts:

$$H_{k'k} = D_{k'k} - I_{k'k}.\tag{7.26}$$

The first matrix element $D_{k'k}$ accounts for the direct coupling of states due to the perturbation. I shall call this the *direct effect* in the following. It is discussed in detail in Chapter 8 and is given in Equation (8.31). The second matrix element $I_{k'k}$ accounts for the structural changes which are caused by the perturbation, henceforth called the *indirect effect*. It is calculated in Section 9.3 and given in Equation (9.22).

The coupling set K contains a number N of eigenfunctions which satisfy the quasi-degeneracy condition. I denote a single eigenfunction here with the index $k_i = (n_i, l_i)$ with $i = 1, \dots, N$. According to Equation (7.25), the supermatrix can be constructed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{Z} &= \mathbf{H} + \mathbf{Q} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{k_1, k_1} & \mathbf{H}_{k_1, k_2} & \cdots & \mathbf{H}_{k_1, k_N} \\ \mathbf{H}_{k_2, k_1} & \mathbf{H}_{k_2, k_2} & & \mathbf{H}_{k_2, k_N} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{H}_{k_N, k_1} & \mathbf{H}_{k_N, k_2} & \cdots & \mathbf{H}_{k_N, k_N} \end{pmatrix} \\ &+ \begin{pmatrix} (\omega_{k_1}^2 - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \mathbf{I}_{2l_1+1} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & (\omega_{k_2}^2 - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \mathbf{I}_{2l_2+1} & & 0 \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & (\omega_{k_N}^2 - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2) \mathbf{I}_{2l_N+1} \end{pmatrix},\end{aligned}\tag{7.27}$$

where \mathbf{I}_{2l_i+1} is the identity matrix of dimension $2l_i + 1$ and the elements of \mathbf{H} are block-matrices of the form

$$\mathbf{H}_{k',k} = \begin{pmatrix} H_{k',k}^{-l',-l} & H_{k',k}^{-l',-l+1} & \cdots & H_{k',k}^{-l',l} \\ H_{k',k}^{-l'+1,-l} & H_{k',k}^{-l'+1,-l+1} & \cdots & H_{k',k}^{-l'+1,l} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ H_{k',k}^{l',-l} & H_{k',k}^{l',-l+1} & \cdots & H_{k',k}^{l',l} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (7.28)$$

with $k = (n, l)$ and $k' = (n', l')$. The upper indices denote the azimuthal order of the eigenfunctions, taking on values from $m = -l, \dots, l$ and $m' = -l', \dots, l'$. They are ascending from left to right and from top to bottom. The matrix $\mathbf{H}_{k',k}$ is only square if $l = l'$.

7.5 Frequency Shifts

Because they are accessible and easily measurable, oscillation frequencies and their shifts due to a perturbation are of great interest to helio- and asteroseismology. The oscillation frequencies of a standard stellar model are perturbed when, e.g., a flow or a magnetic field is introduced.

In the framework of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory, the perturbed squared angular frequency is given by

$$\tilde{\omega}_k^2 = \omega_{\text{ref}}^2 + (\omega_1^2)_k, \quad (7.29)$$

where $(\omega_1^2)_k$ is the eigenvalue of the supermatrix \mathbf{Z} which is assigned to the unperturbed frequency ω_k^2 . This perturbation is with respect to the reference frequency ω_{ref}^2 . The frequency difference between the unperturbed and the perturbed state is thus given by

$$\delta\omega_k = \tilde{\omega}_k - \omega_k = \sqrt{\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 + (\omega_1^2)_k} - \omega_k, \quad (7.30)$$

where Equation (7.29) was used in the second step. We know from non-degenerate perturbation theory that the perturbed frequency can be written in a series expansion, see Equation (7.10). It can be shown (see, e.g., Section 4.5.2 in [Schad 2013](#)) that this pertains to the quasi-degenerate case, if the mode coupling is small enough compared to the frequency difference of the modes, i.e., $\left| \frac{H_{k',k} H_{kk'}}{\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2} \right| \ll 1$, so that the series converges. The series expansion for the perturbation of the squared angular frequency up to second order is then given by

$$\delta\omega_k^2 = \tilde{\omega}_k^2 - \omega_k^2 = H_{kk} + \sum_{k' \in K} \frac{H_{k'k} H_{kk'}}{\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2}, \quad (7.31)$$

where the sum extends over all modes within the coupling set K (see Section 7.4). If we choose the reference frequency to coincide with an eigenfrequency $\omega_{\text{ref}} = \omega_k$ ¹⁵ and use that the eigenvalue of the supermatrix which is assigned to the eigenfunction k , i.e., $(\omega_1^2)_k$, is well approximated by $\delta\omega_k^2$, then we obtain

$$\delta\omega_k = \sqrt{\omega_k^2 + \delta\omega_k^2} - \omega_k \quad (7.32)$$

¹⁵See footnote 10 in this chapter.

from substituting Equation (7.31) into Equation (7.30). If only self-coupling of modes is important, then this reduces to just

$$\delta\omega_k = \sqrt{\omega_k^2 + H_{kk}} - \omega_k. \quad (7.33)$$

I use Equation (7.33) in Chapter 9 to calculate the frequency shifts of solar p modes caused by a toroidal magnetic field.

7.6 Perturbation of Eigenfunctions

I do not utilize perturbed eigenfunctions in this thesis. However, I want to mention how they can be calculated. Analogously to the perturbed eigenvectors in non-degenerate perturbation theory, see Equation (7.11), the perturbed eigenfunctions can be expanded in a series. Here, the sums extend only over those modes which are within the coupling set K which is defined by the quasi-degeneracy condition (7.13) and angular momentum selection rules (see Section 8.5.1):

$$\xi_k \approx \xi_k^0 + \sum_{k' \in K \setminus k} \frac{H_{k'k}}{\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2} \xi_{k'}^0 + \sum_{k', k'' \in K \setminus k} \frac{H_{k'k''} H_{k''k}}{(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2)(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k''}^2)} \xi_{k'}^0 - \sum_{k' \in K \setminus k} \frac{H_{k'k} H_{kk}}{(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2)^2} \xi_{k'}^0, \quad (7.34)$$

where ξ_k^0 is the unperturbed eigenfunction and the series is expanded up to second order. As can be seen from this, if only self-coupling of modes is important, the eigenfunction is unchanged.

If the supermatrix is set up and the eigenvalue problem (7.22) is solved, then the eigenvector of \mathbf{Z} which is assigned to the unperturbed eigenfunction ξ_k^0 holds the expansion coefficients from which the perturbed eigenfunction can be calculated, as discussed above.

7.7 Review and Preview

In this chapter, I described two approaches for calculating perturbed eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions. For some perturbations (in the case of a magnetic field this depends on depth in the star, geometrical configuration, and strength), difficulties with the convergence of the series expansion of the perturbed quantities or the assignment of perturbed to unperturbed quantities for the eigenvector-eigenvalue ansatz can arise. The latter was studied in detail for poloidal flows in stars by Herzberg (2016). The former problem can appear for very dense spectra or strong perturbations. This can become important if, for example, strong magnetic fields in near-surface layers are investigated and cross-coupling of stellar eigenmodes cannot be neglected. I do not investigate this scenario here. Nevertheless, with the perturbation techniques at hand (series expansions of perturbed quantities; determination of the eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the supermatrix; degenerate perturbation theory in the case of degenerate coupling sets, see, e.g., Chapter 8.31 of Schiff 1968 or Herzberg 2016) the calculation of the eigenfrequency perturbation caused by these magnetic fields in stars is also feasible.

We are now equipped with the necessary theoretical tools to calculate the quantities which are needed for forward calculations of a magnetic field on stellar oscillation frequencies. For the calculation of the matrix elements, the magnetic field and all other relevant quantities are represented

in terms of generalized spherical harmonics. This representation is used to efficiently derive expressions for which angular momentum selection rules can be formulated. These selection rules help to limit the number of terms in the result of the general matrix element of the direct effect $D_{k'k}$ for a superposition of zonal¹⁶ magnetic field components in Chapter 8. Even though many terms actually can be eliminated thanks to the selection rules, the final expression for $D_{k'k}$ spans several pages (see Appendix C.7). The general matrix element of the indirect effect $I_{k'k}$ is derived in Chapter 9. For this, the perturbations of the stellar structural quantities have to be calculated. In Chapter 9, I then show forward calculations of the frequency shift caused by six models for the magnetic field in the Sun which include both the direct and the indirect effect. These forward calculations include only the self-coupling of modes, as I find that cross-coupling can be neglected for the investigated magnetic field models (see Chapter 9).

¹⁶Vector fields with azimuthal order equal to 0 are called zonal. For motivation of this term inspect the upper left spherical harmonic shown in Figure 2.1.

The General Matrix Element for the Direct Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields

This chapter and Appendix C were originally published as

“The Direct Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Stellar Oscillations:
An Analytical Expression for the General Matrix Element”,
The Astrophysical Journal, Volume 846, Number 2, Article 162, 2017,

by René Kiefer, Ariane Schad, and Markus Roth.

Abstract

Where is the solar dynamo located and what is its modus operandi? These are still open questions in solar physics. Helio- and asteroseismology can help answer them by enabling us to study solar and stellar internal structures through global oscillations. The properties of solar and stellar acoustic modes are changing with the level of magnetic activity. However, until now, the inference on subsurface magnetic fields with seismic measures has been very limited. The aim of this paper is to develop a formalism to calculate the effect of large-scale toroidal magnetic fields on solar and stellar global oscillation eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies. If the Lorentz force is added to the equilibrium equation of motion, stellar eigenmodes can couple. In quasi-degenerate perturbation theory, this coupling, also known as the direct effect, can be quantified by the general matrix element. We present the analytical expression of the matrix element for a superposition of subsurface zonal toroidal magnetic field configurations. The matrix element is important for forward calculations of perturbed solar and stellar eigenfunctions and frequency perturbations. The results presented here will help to ascertain solar and stellar large-scale subsurface magnetic fields, and their geometric configuration, strength, and their change over the course of activity cycles.

8.1 Introduction

So far, the main benchmarks for dynamo simulations are the correct cycle lengths as well as the properties and distribution of active regions over the simulated cycle (e.g., Charbonneau 2010; Charbonneau 2013). The strength and configuration of large-scale flow fields are important ingredients of modern simulations of solar and stellar flux transport dynamos Choudhuri et al. (e.g., 1995), Dikpati and Gilman (2009), and Karak et al. (2014). Seismology has contributed to

the refinement of dynamo simulations by mapping the differential rotation in the Sun (Schou et al. 1998; Howe 2009) and is beginning to do so in stars (Beck et al. 2012; Nielsen et al. 2015; Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard 2017). The meridional circulation is another crucial element in these dynamo models, which can be assessed by helioseismic investigations (Giles et al. 1997; Braun and Fan 1998; Haber et al. 2002; Schad 2013; Zhao et al. 2013). If it were made possible to measure the location, geometrical configuration, and strength of the magnetic field distribution within the Sun and stars, this would add a benchmark of supreme importance for dynamo simulation.

In the Sun, a large fraction of the total magnetic flux is assumed to be stored in the subsurface toroidal component of the magnetic field Charbonneau (2010, and references therein). The unsigned magnetic flux attributed to active regions amounts to $\sim 10^{25}$ Mx over a solar cycle, while the polar cap flux totals to just $\sim 10^{22}$ Mx (Charbonneau 2010). As the active regions are thought to originate from deep-seated toroidal flux concentrations (e.g., Caligari et al. 1995; Fan 2009), it is reasonable to concentrate on the toroidal field in a first step, as we will do in this article.

The effect of a magnetic field on stellar acoustic oscillations is twofold: the direct effect, or, as we shall also call it in the following, the coupling of oscillation modes, and the indirect effect. In this article, we focus on the direct effect. The indirect effect, which is due to additional forces – in comparison to the equilibrium stellar model without magnetic fields – perturbs stellar structural quantities, such as sound speed and density. Thus, the cavities where resonant acoustic modes exist are changed, which leads to changes in frequencies and eigenfunctions. The effect of a magnetic field on stellar structure was studied by, e.g., Mestel and Moss (1977), Mathis and Zahn (2005), Duez et al. (2008) and Duez et al. (2010).

We use an ansatz from quasi-degenerate perturbation theory to calculate the strength of the coupling between stellar oscillation modes (Lavelly and Ritzwoller 1992), which is due to a superposition of large-scale axisymmetric zonal toroidal magnetic fields. The mode coupling leads to frequency shifts, frequency splittings, and distortions of the mode eigenfunctions. The strength of the coupling is quantified by the general matrix element, which is used to construct the supermatrix (Lavelly and Ritzwoller 1992). Solving the eigenvalue problem for the supermatrix yields two essential results. First, the perturbations to the equilibrium frequencies are given by the eigenvalues. Second, the eigenvectors contain the expansion coefficients of the perturbed eigenfunction as components.

Previous studies with large-scale flows as the source of perturbation have shown that the analysis of perturbed eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions can be employed to infer the geometrical configuration and strength of that perturbation. Ritzwoller and Lavelly (1991) developed a formalism to invert global helioseismic data for differential rotation. This was expanded by Lavelly and Ritzwoller (1992) to specifically include global-scale convection and expanded in such a way that general flow fields can be taken as a source of perturbation. With their theory, the perturbation of the mode eigenfrequencies and the perturbed eigenfunctions can be computed. In that framework, the effect of the meridional circulation on solar eigenmodes was studied by, e.g., Roth and Stix (2008). Later, Schad et al. (2011) advanced the method by introducing the amplitude ratio of oscillations in the Fourier domain as a helioseismic measurement quantity. With this, Schad et al. (2013) inferred a multicellular meridional circulation in both depth and latitude by analyzing perturbed solar eigenfunctions.

Using a different perturbation approach, Gough and Thompson (1990) presented a formalism to calculate the eigenfrequencies of a stellar model with a magnetic field and rotation as perturbations. This formalism included both the direct and indirect effects of the magnetic field. Antia

et al. (2000) refined their approach by also including effects from general relativity and second-order effects of rotation. Their main results were forward calculations of helioseismic splitting coefficients. They could limit the strength of a toroidal magnetic field near the Sun's tachocline to 300 kG. Baldner et al. (2009) used the theory developed by Gough and Thompson (1990) and Antia et al. (2000) to probe the solar interior for magnetic field concentrations by comparing the calculated splitting coefficients with the observed values. Their results included two very shallow toroidal field distributions and a poloidal field. However, due to the shallowness of the inferred fields, they could not draw conclusions regarding dynamo models, which mostly rely on deeper seated field concentrations (e.g., Charbonneau 2014). Recently, Hanasoge (2017) developed a formalism to calculate the sensitivity functions of seismic measurements to the Lorentz stress tensor in the stellar interior.

A seismic investigation of the effect of magnetic fields on the oscillations in the Sun and solar-like stars within the perturbation approach developed by Lively and Ritzwoller (1992) has not been done so far. The first step of extending their analytical groundwork to fully include magnetic fields is now presented in this paper. We begin by deriving the perturbed equation of motion for a non-rotating, non-magnetic star in Section 8.2. The necessary essentials of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory are reviewed in Section 8.3. Section 8.4 is dedicated to the derivation of the general matrix element for a magnetic field, before we give its explicit analytical expression of it in spherical coordinates in Section 8.5. We discuss our findings and conclude in Section 8.6.

8.2 The Equilibrium Model

In this Section, we summarize the derivation of the perturbed equation of motion, because it will help us to trace our steps in later Sections. A detailed treatment of this can be found in, e.g., Unno et al. (1989) and Aerts et al. (2010).

The equation of motion of a parcel of gas in a non-rotating, static, and spherically symmetric star without a magnetic field reads

$$\rho \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = -\nabla p + \rho \mathbf{g}, \quad (8.1)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the velocity due to displacements from the equilibrium position, p is the pressure, \mathbf{g} is the gravitational acceleration, and ρ is the mass density. For such a star, a standard model can be computed, e.g. for the Sun Model S by Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (1996). The model supplies the eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies of adiabatic oscillations as a solution of the eigenvalue equation, which is briefly derived here.

The Lagrangian perturbation Δ of a quantity Q is given by

$$\Delta Q = \delta Q + (\boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla) Q, \quad (8.2)$$

where δQ is the Eulerian variation of Q and $(\boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla) Q$ is the term due to the advection of Q by the displacement $\boldsymbol{\xi}$. The Lagrangian perturbation commutes with the total time derivative:

$$[D/Dt, \Delta] = 0. \quad (8.3)$$

Furthermore, the following identifications of Lagrangian perturbations hold, which we need to rewrite the perturbed equation of motion:

$$\Delta \mathbf{r} = \boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad (8.4)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{v} = \frac{d\boldsymbol{\xi}}{dt}, \quad (8.5)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the position vector. Here, the material time derivative is equal to the partial time derivative

$$\frac{d}{dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t}, \quad (8.6)$$

since we consider a star without any velocity fields, such as rotation, convection, or meridional circulation.

We start by dividing Equation (8.1) by ρ , taking the Lagrangian perturbation Δ of the whole equation, and multiplying by the unperturbed density ρ_0 . From now on, unperturbed quantities are labeled with a sub- or superscript 0. These operations, together with Equations (8.3)-(8.6), yield

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial^2 \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial t^2} = -\Delta(\nabla p) + \frac{\Delta \rho}{\rho_0} \nabla p_0 + \rho_0 \Delta \mathbf{g}. \quad (8.7)$$

A change between the gravitational potential and gravitational acceleration can be done via $-\nabla \Phi = \mathbf{g}$.

By using a modal ansatz for the displacements,

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\omega t}, \quad (8.8)$$

and making use of the identification $\rho_0 \mathbf{g}_0 = \nabla p_0$, the perturbed equation of motion finally reads

$$-\rho \omega^2 \boldsymbol{\xi} = -\Delta(\nabla p) + \mathbf{g}_0 \Delta \rho + \rho_0 \Delta \mathbf{g}. \quad (8.9)$$

We identify the right-hand side with the operator $\mathcal{L}_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}^0)$:

$$\mathcal{L}_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}^0) = -\Delta(\nabla p) + \mathbf{g}_0 \Delta \rho + \rho_0 \Delta \mathbf{g}, \quad (8.10)$$

so we have

$$-\rho_0 \omega^2 \boldsymbol{\xi}^0 = \mathcal{L}_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}^0). \quad (8.11)$$

This equation describes the response of the stellar model to a displacement $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ of a parcel of gas given by the Lagrangian perturbation of Equation (8.1). This is the eigenvalue equation we sought to derive. The superscript 0 on the eigenfunctions is added here to signify that they are eigenfunctions of the equilibrium model. By adding additional forces or velocity fields to the equation of motion, we can probe the response of the model and its eigenfunctions to this perturbation. It may be noted that Equation (8.10) is equivalent to Equation B15 in [Lively and Ritzwoller \(1992\)](#) and to Equation 28 in [Lynden-Bell and Ostriker \(1967\)](#).

In this paper, all calculations are performed in spherical polar coordinates. In the following, r stands for the radial distance from the origin, θ signifies the colatitude, and ϕ is the azimuthal angle. As we are working with a spherically symmetric star, the r , θ , and ϕ components of the eigenfunctions can be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_{l,m}(r, \theta, \phi) = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_r(r, \theta, \phi) \\ \xi_\theta(r, \theta, \phi) \\ \xi_\phi(r, \theta, \phi) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \xi^r(r) Y_l^{0,m}(\theta, \phi) \\ \xi^h(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m}(\theta, \phi) \\ \xi^h(r) \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} Y_l^{0,m}(\theta, \phi) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8.12)$$

Here, $\xi^r(r)$ and $\xi^h(r)$ are the real-valued scalar radial and horizontal displacement amplitudes, respectively. The generalized spherical harmonic functions $Y_l^{N,m}$ are described in detail in Appendix C.4. The set of eigenmodes $\{\boldsymbol{\xi}_k\}$, where $k = (l, m, n)$, with eigenfrequencies ω_k , gives the solutions to Equation (8.11). The integer l is the harmonic degree, m is the azimuthal order, with $|m| \leq l$, and n is the radial order of the eigenfunction. As we are considering a non-rotating star, modes of the same radial order and harmonic degree (n, l) but of different azimuthal order m have the same frequency and form a degenerate multiplet (see, e.g., Unno et al. 1989): $\omega_k = \omega_{nl}$.

The unperturbed eigenfunctions are orthogonal,

$$\int_V \rho_0 \overline{\boldsymbol{\xi}_{k'}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}_k^0 dV = N_k \delta_{k'k} \quad (8.13)$$

and normalized with the normalization constant

$$N_k = \int_0^R \rho_0 \left[(\xi_{nl}^r(r))^2 + l(l+1) (\xi_{nl}^h(r))^2 \right] r^2 dr. \quad (8.14)$$

The integral in Equation (8.13) extends over the whole stellar volume and the integral in Equation (8.14) extends over the stellar radius.

8.3 Essentials of Quasi-Degenerate Perturbation Theory

We briefly review the required essentials of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory here. More detailed treatments can be found in, e.g., Lavelly and Ritzwoller (1992), Roth (2002), or Schad (2013). We introduce the following perturbation expansions into Equation (8.11):

$$\mathcal{L}_0 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_0 + \epsilon \mathcal{L}_1, \quad (8.15a)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}^0 \rightarrow \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^0 + \epsilon \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^1, \quad (8.15b)$$

$$\omega_j^2 \rightarrow \omega_{\text{ref}}^2 + \epsilon (\omega_1^2)_j. \quad (8.15c)$$

They express the effect on the eigenfrequencies, eigenfunctions, and equilibrium equation of motion by the operator $\epsilon \mathcal{L}_1$ that accounts for departures from the equilibrium model. The auxiliary quantity ϵ signifies a small perturbation and helps to keep track of the order of perturbation. The squared eigenfrequency perturbation in first order is given by $(\omega_1^2)_j$.

The perturbation of the equation of motion leads to a coupling of eigenmodes. The coupling due to, e.g., poloidal flow cells was studied by Herzberg (2016) and that due to a meridional flow in the Sun by Schad et al. (2011). In the framework of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory, the perturbed eigenfunctions $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_j$ to zeroth and first orders, i.e., $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_j^0$ and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_j^1$, can be described as a weighted sum over the unperturbed eigenfunctions $\boldsymbol{\xi}_k^0$, for which the modes k are within a coupling set K or K^\perp , multiplied by a coupling coefficient:

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_j^0 = \sum_{k \in K} c_{jk} \boldsymbol{\xi}_k^0, \quad (8.16a)$$

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_j^1 = \sum_{k \in K^\perp} b_{jk} \boldsymbol{\xi}_k^0. \quad (8.16b)$$

Which modes are within the coupling set K or its complement K^\perp depends on the geometrical configuration of the perturbation, which entails angular momentum selection rules, on the considered modes, as well as on the allowed difference in the frequency of the modes. When, e.g., an axisymmetric meridional poloidal flow is the source of perturbation, only modes of the same azimuthal order can couple due to selection rules Lavelly and Ritzwoller (e.g., 1992) and Roth (2002). We will discuss the selection rules for toroidal magnetic fields in Section 8.5.1. The coupling coefficients c_{jk} and b_{jk} may be complex valued. The frequency difference of modes within K is restricted by the quasi-degeneracy condition:

$$|\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 - \omega_k^2| < \Delta\omega^2. \quad (8.17)$$

Here, $\Delta\omega^2$ sets the frequency range of the coupling modes within K . The reference frequency ω_{ref} is typically chosen to be equal or close to the central frequency of a multiplet j . Increasing $\Delta\omega^2$ results in more modes within the coupling set K and therefore in a more accurate expression for the perturbed quantity. This has to be traded off against the higher computational effort necessary for the computation.

We can focus on the determination of the coefficients c_{jk} , which are needed to calculate the perturbed eigenfunction in zeroth order $\tilde{\xi}_j^0$ in Equation (8.16a). With the perturbation expansion, Equations (8.15a)-(8.15c), the following eigenvalue equation can be found (Lavelly and Ritzwoller 1992):

$$\sum_{k \in K} c_{jk} Z_{k'k} = \sum_{k \in K} c_{jk} (\omega_1^2)_j \delta_{k'k} \text{ for } k' \in K. \quad (8.18)$$

Here, it was used that a mode k is either in K or K^\perp , i.e., the equations for the coefficients c_{jk} and b_{jk} decouple. Now, the sought-for coefficients c_{jk} appear as the elements of the eigenvectors of the matrix Z . This matrix is called supermatrix, and its elements are determined from

$$Z_{k'k} = \begin{cases} H_{k'k} - (\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 - \omega_k^2) \delta_{k'k} & \text{for } k', k \in K, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (8.19)$$

It can be shown that the general matrix element $H_{k'k}$ is given by

$$H_{k'k} = - \int \tilde{\xi}_{k'}^0 \cdot \mathcal{L}_1(\xi_k^0) dV, \quad (8.20)$$

where \mathcal{L}_1 is the operator of the perturbing force that causes the coupling, introduced in Equation (8.15a).¹

The eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the supermatrix completely determine the perturbed eigenfunctions and frequencies. The squared frequency correction of a mode k is given by the eigenvalue, which belongs exactly to the eigenvector of Z that holds the expansion coefficients $\{c_{jk}\}_{k \in K}$ for the construction of the perturbed eigenfunction of the mode.

¹Here, I retain the notation $H_{k'k}$ of the general matrix element of the direct effect, which was used in the originally published paper. In the next chapter, however, the general matrix element of the direct element will be denoted by $D_{k'k}$.

8.4 The General Matrix Element for a Magnetic Field

As a perturbation to the equilibrium, we add the Lorentz force $\mathbf{F}_L = \frac{1}{c}\mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B}$, where the current is given by

$$\mathbf{j} = \frac{c}{4\pi} \nabla \times \mathbf{B}, \quad (8.21)$$

to the right-hand side of the equation of motion, Equation (8.1). We use the CGS-Gauss system for all calculations. Following the same steps as in Section 8.2 leads to

$$-\rho_0 \omega^2 \boldsymbol{\xi}^0 = \mathcal{L}_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}^0) + \mathcal{L}_B(\boldsymbol{\xi}^0), \quad (8.22)$$

where we made the identification

$$\mathcal{L}_B(\boldsymbol{\xi}^0) = \rho_0 \Delta \left(\frac{1}{4\pi\rho} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} \right). \quad (8.23)$$

This expression is the desired perturbation operator for a magnetic field, which can now be inserted into Equation (8.20) with $\mathcal{L}_B(\boldsymbol{\xi}^0) = \mathcal{L}_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}^0)$. Doing so yields the general matrix element for the Lorentz force exerted by a magnetic field of general configuration:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{k'k} = & -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int \bar{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_{k'} \cdot [((\nabla \times \delta\mathbf{B}_k) \times \mathbf{B}_0) + ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_0) \times \delta\mathbf{B}_k) \\ & + (\boldsymbol{\xi}_k \cdot \nabla)((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_0) \times \mathbf{B}_0) + (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}_k)((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_0) \times \mathbf{B}_0)] dV, \end{aligned} \quad (8.24)$$

where Equation (C.10) was used.

The Eulerian perturbation of the magnetic field $\delta\mathbf{B}_k$ can be expressed as

$$\delta\mathbf{B}_k = \nabla \times (\boldsymbol{\xi}_k \times \mathbf{B}_0). \quad (8.25)$$

The subscript k of the eigenmodes signifies that they are solutions to Equation (8.11). This is in contrast to $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ in the derivation of identity (8.25) — see Appendix C.1 — which can be any displacement. Identity (8.25) is equivalent to the induction equation of ideal magnetohydrodynamics for small perturbations in the magnetic field and the velocity field.

The unperturbed solar or stellar model has a $(2l+1)$ -fold degeneracy in each frequency multiplet (n, l) . This degeneracy can easily be lifted by introducing a differential rotation profile as a perturbation to the equilibrium model, and then applying the theory of [Lavelly and Ritzwoller \(1992\)](#) as discussed in, e.g., [Roth \(2002\)](#).

8.4.1 Modeling the Toroidal Magnetic Field

So far, \mathbf{B} has been a magnetic field of any configuration. We now restrict \mathbf{B} to a superposition of purely toroidal fields without a ϕ dependence, which is represented in generalized spherical harmonics as

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}_{\text{tor}} = \sum_s \mathbf{B}_s = \sum_s -a_s(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0}(\theta, \phi) \mathbf{e}_\phi \quad (8.26)$$

Here, $a_s(r)$ are the radial profiles of the toroidal field components and $Y_s^{0,0}(\theta, \phi)$ are the generalized spherical harmonic functions. Some useful properties of these functions are collected in Appendix C.4. The index range of s extends over those even positive integers, which are contributing to the magnetic field of the model. The restriction to even integers ensures opposite polarities in the northern and southern hemispheres.

8.4.2 The Matrix Element of a Toroidal Magnetic Field

With the specialization to a superposition of toroidal magnetic field components (Equation (8.26)), the general matrix element from Equation (8.24) is now given by

$$H_{k'k} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int \bar{\xi}_{k'} \cdot \left[\left(\left(\nabla \times \sum_s \delta \mathbf{B}_{k,s} \right) \times \sum_{s'} \mathbf{B}_{s'} \right) + \left(\left(\nabla \times \sum_s \mathbf{B}_s \right) \times \sum_{s'} \delta \mathbf{B}_{k,s'} \right) \right. \\ \left. + (\xi_k \cdot \nabla) \left(\left(\nabla \times \sum_s \mathbf{B}_s \right) \times \sum_{s'} \mathbf{B}_{s'} \right) + (\nabla \cdot \xi_k) \left(\left(\nabla \times \sum_s \mathbf{B}_s \right) \times \sum_{s'} \mathbf{B}_{s'} \right) \right] dV, \quad (8.27)$$

where s and s' extend over the same index range. Due to the distributivity of the vector product and the dot product as well as due to the sum rule for the integral, this simplifies to

$$H_{k'k} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{s,s'} \int \bar{\xi}_{k'} \cdot [((\nabla \times (\nabla \times (\xi_k \times \mathbf{B}_s))) \times \mathbf{B}_{s'}) + ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_s) \times (\nabla \times (\xi_k \times \mathbf{B}_{s'}))) \\ + (\xi_k \cdot \nabla) ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_s) \times \mathbf{B}_{s'}) + (\nabla \cdot \xi_k) ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_s) \times \mathbf{B}_{s'})] dV, \quad (8.28)$$

where we applied Equation (8.25). We will now calculate the extended form of this equation in spherical polar coordinates.

8.5 The Analytical Form of the General Matrix Element

To simplify notation and avoid indices, we consider one summand from Equation (8.28) for fixed s, s' . We omit the indices s, s' and use

$$B_\phi = a(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0}(\theta, \phi), \quad (8.29)$$

$$\hat{B}_\phi = \hat{a}(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0}(\theta, \phi), \quad (8.30)$$

where $a_s = a$ and $a_{s'} = \hat{a}$. We use the same notation for the eigenmodes, which appear twice in Equation (8.28), once due to the Lagrangian perturbation of the Lorentz force and once for the eigenmode that is multiplied from the left in Equation (8.28). The eigenmode that is multiplied from the left is assigned the hat, i.e., its radial component is written as $\hat{\xi}_r = \hat{\xi}^r(r) Y_{l'}^{0,m'}(\theta, \phi)$.

We line out the necessary calculations in Appendix C.3. As a result, we find the following expression for the general matrix element given by Equation (8.28):

$$H_{k'k} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int \left[\left(2\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \frac{\partial \xi^r}{\partial r} + \frac{2a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r}{r} \frac{\partial \xi^r}{\partial r} + a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r \frac{\partial^2 \xi^r}{\partial r^2} \right) \mathcal{T}_1 + \left(\frac{\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r \xi^h}{r} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r}{r} \frac{\partial \xi^h}{\partial r} \right) \mathcal{T}_2 \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} + \frac{\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r\xi^r}{r^2} - \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^r}{r^2} - \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r\xi^h}{r^2} - \frac{\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^r}{r} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} - \frac{\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r\xi^h}{r} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \right) \mathcal{T}_3 \\
 & + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r}{r} \frac{\partial \xi^h}{\partial r} \mathcal{T}_4 + \left(\frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h}{r} \frac{\partial \xi^r}{\partial r} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^r}{r^2} \right) \mathcal{T}_5 - \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_6 + \frac{2a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_7 \\
 & + \left(\frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^r}{r^2} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h}{r} \frac{\partial \xi^r}{\partial r} \right) \mathcal{T}_8 + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_9 + \left(\frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^r}{r^2} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h}{r} \frac{\partial \xi^r}{\partial r} \right. \\
 & + \left. \frac{\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^r}{r} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} - \frac{\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \right) \mathcal{T}_{10} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_{11} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_{12} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_{17} + \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_{18} \\
 & - \left. \frac{\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^r\xi^h}{r} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \mathcal{T}_{20} - \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_{22} - \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_{23} - \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_{24} - \frac{a\hat{a}\hat{\xi}^h\xi^h}{r^2} \mathcal{T}_{25} \right] dV \quad (8.31)
 \end{aligned}$$

The factors with a radial dependence have been separated from those factors with an angular dependence. The angular parts are contained in the symbols \mathcal{T}_i with $i = 1, \dots, 25$. They are listed in Appendix C.7. The integral in Equation (8.31) extends over the whole stellar volume. Integration over the solid angle can be carried out by utilizing Wigner $3j$ symbols, as demonstrated in Appendix (C.6). The properties of the Wigner $3j$ symbols (see Appendix (C.5)), can be used to reduce the number of terms in the angular kernels (C.36)-(C.60), which leads to Equations (C.62)-(C.86). The summation over the components of a superposition of toroidal magnetic fields as in Equation (8.25) can now easily be applied again by assigning the indices s, s' to the two magnetic fields as defined in Equations (8.29)-(8.30).

8.5.1 Selection Rules

From the properties of the integral over four generalized spherical harmonics, given by Equation (C.33), we find the following selection rules for mode coupling: two modes can only couple if their harmonic degrees satisfy

$$|l - l'| \leq s + s'. \quad (8.32)$$

This follows from property (C.30c) of the Wigner $3j$ symbol. The azimuthal order of the coupling modes must satisfy

$$m = m', \quad (8.33)$$

which is a consequence of the property (C.30a) of the Wigner $3j$ symbol and the fact that the azimuthal order was set to zero for the toroidal magnetic field.

8.6 Discussion and Conclusion

Magnetic fields in stars lead to the coupling of stellar oscillation eigenmodes. This coupling perturbs the mode frequencies and eigenfunctions of these acoustic oscillations. With an ansatz from quasi-degenerate perturbation theory, in which the magnetic field is treated as a small perturbation to the equilibrium stellar model, we presented a detailed derivation of the general matrix element. In this work, we focused on the direct effect caused by a superposition of toroidal magnetic fields. The direct effect describes the mode coupling due to the Lorentz force, whereas

the indirect effect, which we did not consider in this article, is due to the perturbation of the mode cavities by the Lorentz force. Both the direct and indirect effects have to be accounted for, if a full description of the perturbed mode frequencies and eigenfunctions is to be reached. The combination of both effects will be considered in an upcoming study.

The analytical expression of the general matrix element was obtained with the use of generalized spherical harmonics and the calculation of the angular integral over their product. The resulting general matrix element, presented in Equation (8.31), can be used to carry out forward calculations of the direct effect of arbitrary subsurface zonal toroidal field configurations on the stellar eigenmodes. From the general matrix elements, the supermatrix can be constructed. Its eigenvalues and eigenvectors hold the information on the mode frequency perturbations and the perturbed eigenfunctions, respectively.

From an inspection of the general matrix element and the selection rules for coupling of angular momenta, we find that toroidal magnetic fields couple only modes that are of equal azimuthal order (Equation (8.33)). Also, only modes whose harmonic degrees maximally differ by the sum of the harmonic degrees of the toroidal magnetic field configuration can couple (Equation (8.32)). It is noteworthy that the general matrix element and hence the supermatrix Z is not Hermitian. This is in stark contrast to the supermatrix for toroidal flows, e.g., rotation (Lavelly and Ritzwoller 1992), or poloidal flows as the meridional circulation (Roth and Stix 2008), where Z is Hermitian. The Hermiticity of the supermatrix for flows ensures that its eigenvalues and consequently the frequency perturbations are purely real. This need not be the case if the perturbation is a toroidal magnetic field. The non-Hermiticity of the supermatrix, or more precisely its asymmetry as it is completely real-valued in the case of magnetic fields, allows complex-valued eigenvalues and thus complex frequency perturbations. The asymmetry can be easily seen in Equation (8.31), considering, for example, the radially dependent part of the first term, which includes the angular factor \mathcal{T}_1 . Clearly, the terms are not symmetrical under the exchange of the modes k' and k , which renders the general matrix element asymmetrical. A complex-valued frequency perturbation is tantamount to a frequency shift and an additional damping factor for the affected mode.

The presented matrix element can be used to study the direct effect of toroidal field configurations motivated by the simulation of solar and stellar dynamos, e.g., by Miesch and Teweldebirhan (2016), in forward calculations for their effect on the solar and stellar eigenmodes. The resulting frequency and damping perturbations can then be compared with observational data for frequency shifts (e.g., Woodard and Noyes 1985; Libbrecht and Woodard 1990; Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998; Broomhall 2017) and mode damping rates (e.g., Jefferies et al. 1990; Komm et al. 2000a; Broomhall et al. 2015) over the solar cycle as well as the frequency shifts caused by changes in stellar magnetic activity (García et al. 2010; Salabert et al. 2016b; Kiefer et al. 2017a). This will provide a novel tool to calibrate and test dynamo simulations and may even help magnetic field concentrations to be located within the solar and stellar interiors. With the formalism presented here, it will also be possible to produce artificial splitting coefficients for toroidal fields. These can then also be compared to observed splitting coefficients, which may additionally help in locating subsurface magnetic field structures.

It has been shown in previous studies that the analysis of perturbed eigenfunctions can be used to infer the profile of the solar meridional flow (Schad 2013; Schad et al. 2013). The results from the present work are a first step toward such an inversion with the aim to infer the solar magnetic field from perturbed eigenfunctions analogous to the work by Schad et al. (2013). In a next step, also the indirect effect of the magnetic field also has to be accounted for, which is a work in progress.

In contrast to earlier studies, which aimed to determine the effect of subsurface magnetic fields in the Sun on global oscillations (e.g., Gough and Thompson 1990; Antia et al. 2000; Baldner et al. 2009), we present an analytical expression for the direct effect. In this way, it can readily be investigated how different modes are affected by the input magnetic field depending on the amplitudes of their radial and horizontal displacements, ξ^r and ξ^h ; their harmonic degree; frequency; and other parameters. Modes of different frequencies and harmonic degrees probe different depths of the star (e.g., Aerts et al. 2010). Depending on this lower turning point, modes are variably susceptible to perturbations by a magnetic field of a certain location and configuration. In an upcoming study, we will exploit these properties of the presented formalism by inputting different magnetic field configurations and learn how different modes are affected by different magnetic fields.

We note that the analytical expression of the general matrix element for the direct effect of a superposition of poloidal fields or general magnetic field configuration will lead to even more extensive matrix elements than the one presented here. Nonetheless, this will be a worthwhile effort and should be carried out in the future.

With the result of this paper, we contribute to a novel approach to measure subsurface magnetic field concentrations in the Sun and stars. The systematic forward modeling of frequency shifts, frequency splittings, and the distortion of mode eigenfunctions will help us to learn about the location of solar and stellar dynamos and the determination of their mode of operation.

Acknowledgments The authors wish to thank the anonymous referee and our institute’s internal referee Oskar Steiner for taking the time to review this article.

The research leading to these results received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union’s Seventh Framework Program (FP/2007-2013)/ERC Grant Agreement No. 307117.

The Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Solar Oscillation Frequencies

This chapter and Appendix D were originally published as

“The Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Solar Oscillation Frequencies”,
The Astrophysical Journal, Volume 854, Number 1, Article 74, 2018,

by René Kiefer and Markus Roth.

Abstract

Solar oscillation frequencies change with the level of magnetic activity. Localizing subsurface magnetic field concentrations in the Sun with helioseismology will help us to understand the solar dynamo. Because the magnetic fields are not considered in standard solar models, adding them to the basic equations of stellar structure changes the eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies. We use quasi-degenerate perturbation theory to calculate the effect of toroidal magnetic fields on solar oscillation mean multiplet frequencies for six field configurations. In our calculations, we consider both the direct effect of the magnetic field, which describes the coupling of modes, and the indirect effect, which accounts for changes in stellar structure due to the magnetic field. We limit our calculations to self-coupling of modes. We find that the magnetic field affects the multiplet frequencies in a way that depends on the location and the geometry of the field inside the Sun. Comparing our theoretical results with observed shifts, we find that strong tachocline fields cannot be responsible for the observed frequency shifts of p modes over the solar cycle. We also find that part of the surface effect in helioseismic oscillation frequencies might be attributed to magnetic fields in the outer layers of the Sun. The theory presented here is also applicable to models of solar-like stars and their oscillation frequencies.

9.1 Introduction

The mapping of subsurface magnetic field concentrations and with it the pinpointing of the region in the Sun, where its dynamo operates can surely be regarded as one of the outstanding open issues of solar physics. In this article, we develop the theory for the forward calculation of the effect of a superposition of zonal toroidal magnetic fields on solar oscillation frequencies in the framework of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory. The toroidal component of the global solar magnetic field

is assumed to be responsible for the bulk of phenomena associated with magnetic activity (see [Fan 2009](#); [Charbonneau 2010](#); [Hathaway 2015](#), and references therein). In simulations of flux-transport solar dynamos, the energy that is stored in the toroidal component of the large-scale magnetic field is orders of magnitude larger than the energy in the poloidal field (e.g., [Miesch and Teweldebirhan 2016](#)). Hence, the restriction to purely toroidal magnetic field configurations in the present work is adequate.

From observations, it is well known that solar p-mode frequencies vary in phase with the solar activity cycle. [Woodard and Noyes \(1985\)](#) measured these changes in frequencies for oscillation of low harmonic degree. Later, the frequency shifts over the solar cycle were confirmed and thoroughly investigated by, e.g., [Libbrecht and Woodard \(1990\)](#), [Jiménez-Reyes et al. \(1998\)](#), and [Broomhall \(2017\)](#). In the Sun, these shifts are larger for modes of higher frequency ([Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998](#)). As, e.g., [Basu et al. \(2012\)](#) showed, modes of higher frequency have their maximum sensitivity to structural changes in the solar interior in shallower layers than modes of low frequency. This can be used to study the change of subsurface solar activity as a function of time and depth ([Basu et al. 2012](#)).

It has been shown that the frequencies of acoustic oscillations of solar-like stars undergo changes similar to those observed on the Sun. The first time that such changes were reported for a star other than the Sun was done by [García et al. \(2010\)](#). They also showed that these changes are correlated with stellar magnetic activity. Since then this behavior has been observed for several more stars by [Salabert et al. \(2016b\)](#) and [Kiefer et al. \(2017a\)](#). Gaining insight about the underlying magnetic field causing these changes in stars would supplement the simulation of solar and stellar dynamos greatly.

Until now, the attempts to determine the magnetic field in the Sun with helioseismology have been rather sparse. [Gough and Thompson \(1990\)](#) calculated multiplet shifts for low degree modes for an axisymmetric buried magnetic field in a perturbational approach. Building on their framework, [Antia et al. \(2000\)](#) analyzed splitting coefficients to probe the solar acoustic asphericity and magnetic fields in the convection zone. They were able to limit the magnetic field strength at the base of the convection zone to 300 kG. [Baldner et al. \(2009\)](#) extended this work and matched simulated splitting coefficients to their observed counterparts. They found that a superposition of two very shallow toroidal magnetic fields in the upper 1% of the convection zone and a poloidal component could explain the observed even splitting coefficients best. [Dziembowski and Goode \(2005\)](#) analyzed the behavior of centroid multiplet frequencies between the minimum and maximum of cycle 23. They found that the frequency increase can be explained by a less than 2% decrease in the radial component of the turbulent velocity in the convection zone. They explain the p-mode frequency increase with rising levels of activity by the inhibiting effect of the magnetic field on convection. Recently, [Hanasoge \(2017\)](#) developed a formalism to calculate sensitivity kernels of mode coupling to Lorentz stresses in the Sun.

In this article, we describe our forward calculations of the effect of subsurface toroidal magnetic fields on solar oscillation multiplet frequencies. For this, we use an ansatz from quasi-degenerate perturbation theory to calculate the strength of the coupling between solar oscillation modes ([Lavelly and Ritzwoller 1992](#)). The coupling of initially independent modes leads to changes in mode frequencies and eigenfunctions. The distortions of the solar mode eigenfunctions by flows have previously been exploited by [Schad et al. \(2013\)](#) to infer a double cell profile of the meridional circulation. In the ansatz, we use here, the total perturbation by the magnetic field can be separated in a direct and an indirect contribution. The direct contribution couples the modes and thus changes their frequencies and eigenfunctions. An analytical derivation of the

general matrix element of this direct contribution caused by a superposition of zonal toroidal magnetic field was recently presented by [Kiefer et al. \(2017b\)](#). The indirect contribution is due to the perturbation to the equilibrium stellar structural quantities, which is caused by the magnetic field. The effect of a magnetic field on stellar structure was studied by, e.g., [Mestel and Moss \(1977\)](#), [Mathis and Zahn \(2005\)](#), [Duez et al. \(2008\)](#), and [Duez et al. \(2010\)](#).

We start by introducing the necessary theoretical background of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory in Section 9.2. The general matrix element for the indirect effect of toroidal magnetic fields is then derived in Section 9.3. We present the six magnetic field configurations we tested and the resulting multiplet shifts in Section 9.4. These results are discussed in Section 9.5 and we end the paper with our conclusions in Section 9.6. We include mathematical supplements in Appendix D.1, a detailed derivation of the projection of the Lorentz force onto spherical harmonics in Appendix D.2, the sensitivity kernels in Appendix D.3, derivations of the perturbations in stellar structural quantities in Appendix D.4, and additional figures for the modeled magnetic fields and the resulting frequency shifts in Appendix D.5.

9.2 Perturbation Theory

The equations that describe the equilibrium state of a star — without flows, rotation, or magnetic field — can be solved to give a system of eigenfunctions ([Christensen-Dalsgaard 2008](#)). These eigenfunctions, with their respective eigenfrequencies, are perturbed when flows ([Lively and Ritzwoller 1992](#)), rotation, or a magnetic field (e.g., [Gough and Thompson 1990](#)) are added to the star. If the perturbation is small enough, the perturbed eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies can be obtained from the unperturbed eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies with techniques from standard perturbation theory. As the spectrum of the eigenfrequencies of a solar-like star is dense, the techniques from quasi-degenerate perturbation theory can be adopted. The solutions to the eigenvalue problem

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{C}, \quad (9.1)$$

define the perturbed eigenvectors and eigenfrequencies of the system. Here, \mathbf{Z} is called the supermatrix with entries

$$Z_{k'k} = \begin{cases} H_{k'k} - (\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 - \omega_k^2) \delta_{k'k} & \text{for } k', k \in K, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (9.2)$$

where $H_{k'k}$ is the general matrix element, which is discussed in detail below, and the indices $k = (n, l, m)$, $k' = (n', l', m')$ define the considered eigenmodes with radial orders n, n' , harmonic degrees l, l' , and azimuthal orders m, m' . The coupling set K is made up of those modes, which satisfy the following two conditions: Firstly, their frequencies obey the quasi-degeneracy condition

$$|\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 - \omega_k^2| < \Delta\omega^2, \quad (9.3)$$

where the reference frequency ω_{ref} is typically chosen equal or close to the central frequency of a multiplet k , ω_k is the frequency of the considered mode, and $\Delta\omega^2$ is the width of this range. Second, the geometry of the modes, determined by their harmonic degree and azimuthal order, complies with angular momentum selection rules imposed by the configuration of the

perturbation. These selection rules are given in Section 8.5.1 for the magnetic field configurations considered in this work.

The eigenvector \mathbf{C} holds the expansion coefficients of the perturbed eigenfunction ξ_j :

$$\xi_j = \sum_{k \in K} c_{jk} \xi_k^0, \quad (9.4)$$

where c_{jk} is the k 'th component of \mathbf{C} and ξ_k^0 is an unperturbed eigenfunction. The matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is a diagonal matrix with the frequency perturbations $\delta\omega_k^2$ as entries.

Detailed discussions of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory with application to solar and stellar problems can be found in, e.g., Lately and Ritzwoller (1992), Roth (2002), Schad (2013), Herzberg (2016), and Herzberg and Roth (2018).

The complete general matrix element $H_{k'k}$ is calculated as

$$H_{k'k} = D_{k'k} - I_{k'k}, \quad (9.5)$$

where $D_{k'k}$ is the general matrix element, which accounts for the mode coupling due to the magnetic field.¹ An analytical expression of $D_{k'k}$ for a superposition of zonal toroidal magnetic fields was recently derived by Kiefer et al. (2017b). It is given by

$$\begin{aligned} D_{k'k} = & -\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{s,s'} \int_V \bar{\xi}_{k'} \cdot [((\nabla \times (\nabla \times (\xi_k \times \mathbf{B}_s))) \times \mathbf{B}_{s'}) + ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_s) \times (\nabla \times (\xi_k \times \mathbf{B}_{s'})))] \\ & + (\xi_k \cdot \nabla) ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_s) \times \mathbf{B}_{s'}) + (\nabla \cdot \xi_k) ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_s) \times \mathbf{B}_{s'})] dV, \quad (9.6) \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{B}_s, \mathbf{B}_{s'}$ are toroidal magnetic fields with harmonic degrees s and s' , ξ_k and $\xi_{k'}$ are eigenfunctions, and the integral extends over the stellar volume V . The sum in Equation (9.6) extends over the values of harmonic degrees s and s' of the investigated magnetic field model, see Equation (9.12). The cross-terms between configurations of unequal harmonic degree are thus included in the calculation of the matrix element. The full analytical expression of $D_{k'k}$ is given in Equations (8.31), and (C.62)–(C.86). $I_{k'k}$ in Equation (9.5) accounts for the modal interactions due to the perturbations in stellar structural quantities, which arise as a result of the magnetic field. We derive $I_{k'k}$ for the case of a superposition of zonal toroidal magnetic fields in Section 9.3.

The shift in angular frequency of a mode can be approximated by

$$\delta\omega_k = \sqrt{\omega_k^2 + \delta\omega_k^2} - \omega_k, \quad (9.7)$$

where $\delta\omega_k^2$ is the perturbation of the squared angular frequency:

$$\delta\omega_k^2 \approx H_{kk} + \sum_{k' \in K} \frac{H_{k'k} H_{kk'}}{\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2} + \dots, \quad (9.8)$$

which is expanded up to second order (Schad et al. 2011). In this article, we do not consider perturbations to the eigenfunctions but focus on the more accessible quantity – the shifts in mode frequency. However, the perturbation of the eigenfunctions by a superposition of zonal toroidal magnetic fields can be calculated with the theory presented here: To second order, the perturbed

¹In the previous chapter of this thesis, the general matrix element for the direct effect was denoted by $H_{k'k}$ to retain the notation of the originally published paper.

eigenfunction ξ_k is given by

$$\xi_k \approx \xi_k^0 + \sum_{k' \in K \setminus k} \frac{H_{k'k}}{\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2} \xi_{k'}^0 + \sum_{k', k'' \in K \setminus k} \frac{H_{k'k''} H_{k''k}}{(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2)(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k''}^2)} \xi_{k'}^0 - \sum_{k' \in K \setminus k} \frac{H_{k'k} H_{kk'}}{(\omega_k^2 - \omega_{k'}^2)^2} \xi_{k'}^0, \quad (9.9)$$

where ξ_k^0 is the unperturbed eigenfunction. Equations (9.8) and (9.9) are basic results of non- or quasi-degenerate perturbation theory, see, e.g., Sakurai and Napolitano (2014).

In the present work, we concentrate on the self-coupling of modes. This reduces the computational effort to obtain $H_{k'k}$ by a factor of $|K|^2$, i.e., from the square of the number of coupling modes to only one general matrix element H_{kk} . This approximation is justified, as the coupling strength decreases with increasing frequency difference and the radial and horizontal eigenfunction become less similar for modes of different radial order and harmonic degree. We expect the error introduced by this approximation to be of the order of a few percent. Schad (2013) found that for differential rotation, the self-coupling matrix elements are typically two orders of magnitude larger than the cross-coupling matrix elements. We expect this to be similar for a magnetic field as the perturbing agent. The eigenfunctions are not perturbed in the self-coupling limit, as can be seen from Equation (9.9). In this approximation, we find from Equations (9.7) and (9.8) that the shift in mode frequency can be calculated by

$$\delta\nu_k = \frac{\sqrt{\omega_k^2 + H_{kk}} - \omega_k}{2\pi}. \quad (9.10)$$

9.3 The Indirect Effect

If a magnetic field is present, the Lorentz force has to be added to the equation of motion. Hence, the structure of the star is slightly changed compared to the equilibrium. We treat this change as a small perturbation to the nonmagnetic star. The Lorentz force for a superposition of axisymmetric zonal toroidal magnetic fields is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{tor}}(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{4\pi} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{tor}}(r, \theta)) \times \hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{tor}}(r, \theta) \quad (9.11)$$

with the toroidal magnetic field

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{tor}}(r, \theta) = \sum_s \mathbf{B}_s(r, \theta) = \sum_s -a(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0(\theta) \mathbf{e}_\phi, \quad (9.12)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{tor}}(r, \theta) = \sum_{s'} \mathbf{B}_{s'}(r, \theta) = \sum_{s'} -\hat{a}(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0(\theta) \mathbf{e}_\phi. \quad (9.13)$$

The second magnetic field $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{tor}}$ is introduced to keep track of the individual contributions in a superposition of components of distinct harmonic degree. Here, $a(r)$ and $\hat{a}(r)$ are the radial profiles of the component of the magnetic field with harmonic degrees s and s' , respectively. $Y_s^0(\theta)$ is a spherical harmonic function of degree s and azimuthal order 0. In this article, we will be referring to relations and properties of the spherical harmonic functions and the generalized spherical harmonic functions $Y_l^{N,m}$, which can be found in Appendix C.4. Many useful relations for the spherical harmonic functions can also be found in, e.g., Dahlen and Tromp (1998). The

spherical harmonics are a special case of the generalized spherical harmonics with $Y_l^m = Y_l^{0,m}$ in the convention that is used in this work.

The Lorentz force for a magnetic field of the form presented in Equation (9.12) can be written as

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{tor}}(r, \theta) = \sum_{s,s'} \sum_{\lambda=0}^{s+s'} \left(\mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) Y_\lambda^0(\theta) \mathbf{e}_r + \mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_\lambda^0(\theta) \mathbf{e}_\theta \right), \quad (9.14)$$

where the radial functions of the radial component and the colatitudinal component are given by

$$\mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) = \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \gamma_\lambda \gamma_s \gamma_{s'} \left(\frac{a\hat{a}}{r} + \hat{a} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \right) \begin{pmatrix} s & s' & \lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} s & s' & \lambda \\ 1 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (9.15)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) = -\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \gamma_\lambda \gamma_s \gamma_{s'} \frac{a\hat{a}}{\sqrt{2}r} \begin{pmatrix} s & s' & \lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} s & s' & \lambda \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (9.16)$$

respectively. The coefficients are $\Omega_l^N = \sqrt{(l+N)(l-N+1)/2}$ and $\gamma_l = \sqrt{(2l+1)/4\pi}$. The last two factors of both equations are Wigner 3j symbols. Extensive lists of their properties can be found in, e.g., Edmonds (1960), Regge (1958) and Dahlen and Tromp (1998). We will be referring to only those properties of the Wigner 3j symbols that are listed in Appendix C.5. Equations (9.15) and (9.16) are the vector spherical harmonic expansion coefficients of the Lorentz force for a toroidal magnetic field specified in Equation (9.12). They are derived in detail in Appendix D.2.

We expand aspherical perturbations to all stellar structural quantities in spherical harmonics (Woodhouse and Dahlen 1978; Lively and Ritzwoller 1992; Dahlen and Tromp 1998):

$$\delta Q(r, \theta) = \sum_{s,s',\lambda} \delta Q_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) Y_\lambda^0(\theta), \quad (9.17)$$

where the quantity Q can be the gravitational potential ϕ , density ρ , pressure p , or squared sound speed c^2 . We consider only zonal toroidal magnetic fields as perturbations. Hence, the azimuthal order of the spherical harmonic in the expansion (9.17) is set to 0. The ranges of the summation indices are determined by the configuration of the considered magnetic field: the indices s and s' take the values of the model magnetic field. The index λ extends over all even values between 0 and $s+s'$. This can be seen from properties of the Wigner 3j symbols (C.29) and (C.30c) and the fact that we only consider magnetic fields with even harmonic degree. Restricting the magnetic field to even harmonic degrees ensures antisymmetry about the equator which is generally observed for the Sun (Hathaway 2015).

The aspherical perturbation to the gravitational potential $\delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)$ can be calculated by solving

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{d\delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{dr} \right) - \left[\frac{\lambda(\lambda+1)}{r^2} + \frac{4\pi G}{g_0} \frac{d\rho_0}{dr} \right] \delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) = \frac{4\pi G}{g_0} \left[\mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) + \frac{d}{dr} (r \mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r)) \right]. \quad (9.18)$$

where G is the constant of gravitation, g_0 is the unperturbed gravitational acceleration, ρ_0 is unperturbed density, and $\mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}$ and $\mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}$ are the vector spherical harmonic coefficients of the radial and colatitudinal component of the Lorentz force. This equation is derived in Sweet

Table 9.1: Computed models of the toroidal magnetic field.

Model	Degree	μ (R_\odot)	σ (R_\odot)	B_{\max} (kG)	$\beta(B_{\max})$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$\beta(\text{photosphere})$
A	2	0.9	0.04	50	21.3	0.39
B	2	0.9	0.04	40	33.3	0.62
C	2	0.72	0.05	300	14.5	9×10^8
D	4	0.9	0.04	50	21.3	0.39
E	2	0.9	0.04	50	15.5	0.29
	4	0.9	0.04	-30		
F	2	0.97	0.01	10	16.0	154

(1950). Having obtained $\delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda$ by numerically integrating Equation (9.18), we can calculate the perturbations in density, pressure, and squared sound speed:

$$\delta\rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) = \frac{1}{g_0} \left[\frac{d\rho_0}{dr} \delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) + \mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) + \frac{d}{dr} (r\mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r)) \right], \quad (9.19)$$

$$\delta p_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) = -\rho_0 \delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) - r\mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r), \quad (9.20)$$

$$\delta c_{s,s'}^{2\lambda}(r) = \left[\left(\frac{\partial \ln \Gamma_1}{\partial \ln p} \right)_\rho + 1 \right] \frac{\delta p_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{p_0} c_0^2 + \left[\left(\frac{\partial \ln \Gamma_1}{\partial \ln \rho} \right)_p - 1 \right] \frac{\delta \rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{\rho_0} c_0^2, \quad (9.21)$$

where Γ_1 is the first adiabatic exponent and c_0^2 is unperturbed sound speed. The derivatives of $\ln \Gamma_1$ are supplied in the solar model that was used for this work (Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996). We present brief derivations of Equations (9.19)-(9.21) in Appendix (D.4).

The general matrix element for the indirect effect is derived in Appendix (E) of Lively and Ritzwoller (1992). We neglect terms due to rotation and ellipticity and transform the general matrix element from perturbations in bulk modulus κ_0 and density ρ_0 into perturbations in squared sound speed c_0^2 and density ρ_0 , see Equation (D.40). This yields

$$I_{k'k} = 4\pi\gamma_{l'}\gamma_l (-1)^{m'} \sum_{s,s',\lambda} \gamma_\lambda \begin{pmatrix} l' & \lambda & l \\ -m' & 0 & m \end{pmatrix} \int_0^{R_\odot} \left(\rho_0(r) \delta c_{s,s'}^{2\lambda}(r) K_\lambda(r) + c_0^2 \delta \rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) K_\lambda(r) \right. \\ \left. + \delta \rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) R_\lambda^{(2)}(r) \right) r^2 dr, \quad (9.22)$$

where K_λ is the bulk modulus perturbation kernel and $R_\lambda^{(2)}$ is the density perturbation kernel, which are listed in Appendix (D.3).

9.4 Disturbing the Sun

We modeled six different toroidal magnetic field distributions. Their radial profiles were modeled with Gaussians

$$a(r) = \frac{B_{\text{scale}}}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left(-0.5 \left(\frac{r - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^2 \right), \quad (9.23)$$

where B_{scale} is a factor to scale the distribution to the desired maximum value. In Table 9.1 the locations of the maximum of the field distribution μ and the width in terms of the Gaussian

standard deviation σ are given in the third and fourth columns.² The maximum values of the distribution are given in the fifth column. The sixth and seventh columns of Table 9.1 give the values of the plasma beta

$$\beta = \frac{8\pi p}{B^2} \quad (9.24)$$

at the location of the maximum of the field distribution and at the photospheric level above the maximum of the distribution. Here, p is the gas pressure and B is the magnetic field strength. The plasma beta is the ratio of gas pressure to magnetic pressure. It must be noted that the values for β change with latitude as the spherical harmonics, with which the radial distribution are multiplied, see Equation (9.12), have a latitudinal dependence. This latitudinal dependence of the field distributions can be appreciated in the top panel of Figure 9.1, where magnetic field model A is shown in a meridional cut. The β values in Table 9.1 can thus be seen as minimal values.

Perturbations to the gravitational potential were neglected, i.e., we applied the Cowling approximation (Cowling 1941). This affects the sensitivity kernel $R_\lambda^{(1)}$ (Equation (D.28)) and the perturbations to the structural quantities (Equations (9.18)-(9.21)).³

In our calculations, we used the standard solar model Model S by Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (1996). Included in the version of the model we used is an extended set of variables, e.g., the derivatives $\left(\frac{\partial \ln \Gamma_1}{\partial \ln p}\right)_\rho$ and $\left(\frac{\partial \ln \Gamma_1}{\partial \ln \rho}\right)_p$ which are needed for the computation of the perturbation of the squared sound speed.

Model A is of harmonic degree $s = 2$, has its maximum at $\mu = 0.90 R_\odot$ with a width of $\sigma = 0.04 R_\odot$, and has a maximum field strength of $B_{\max} = 50 \text{ kG}$, see the top panel of Figure 9.1. The maximum field strength is located at latitudes of $\pm 45^\circ$. The bottom panel of Figure 9.1 shows the resulting frequency shifts as a function of unperturbed mode frequency for modes with $4 \leq l \leq 148$. To enhance clarity, we show only every fourth harmonic degree starting at $l = 4$. The frequency shifts are averaged over the azimuthal order m and are thus the mean shift of each multiplet. This shift is usually reported in studies of solar oscillation frequencies as a function of the level of activity (e.g., Broomhall 2017).

We calculated the general matrix elements for the direct and indirect effects separately. Thus, we can also examine the shifts caused by the two effects separately. In the top panel of Figure 9.2, the mean multiplet shifts of model A are shown for only the direct effect. In the bottom panel, the same is shown for the indirect effect. Note the different orders of magnitude of the shifts in the two panels.

Magnetic field model C, which is a strong field in the tachocline region with $B_{\max} = 300 \text{ kG}$, is depicted in the top panel of Figure 9.3. We modeled this field with a harmonic degree of $s = 2$, at a depth of $\mu = 0.72 R_\odot$, and with a width of $\sigma = 0.04 R_\odot$. The resulting frequency shifts as a function of unperturbed mode frequency for modes of harmonic degree $4 \leq l \leq 148$ are shown in the bottom panel of Figure 9.3. Notice the small magnitude of the shifts compared to the field model A.

²To avoid confusion, the center of the Sun is at a value of $0 R_\odot$ and the photosphere is located at $1 R_\odot$. This places the tachocline around $0.72 R_\odot$.

³If the Cowling approximation is not applied, the eigenfunctions of the gravitational potential $\delta\phi$ have to be calculated because they are required in Equation (D.28). The ADIPLS code (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2008) that was used for the computation of the set of eigenmodes can provide these functions.

Figure 9.1: *Top panel:* visualization of magnetic field model A. *Bottom panel:* multiplet frequency shifts for model A as a function of unperturbed mode frequency. Every fourth harmonic degree is shown.

Figure 9.2: Multiplet frequency shifts caused by the direct (*top panel*) and indirect effect (*bottom panel*) for magnetic field model A. Notice the different magnitudes of the shifts in the top and bottom panels.

Figure 9.3: *Top panel:* visualization of magnetic field model C. *Bottom panel:* multiplet frequency shifts for model C as a function of unperturbed mode frequency. Every fourth harmonic degree is shown.

We chose the strength of this model because Antia et al. (2000) put an upper limit of 300 kG on magnetic fields in the tachocline region from analyses of mode splitting coefficients.

Model B is the same as model A, but with a lower maximum field strength. We will use this model in the next section to investigate differences between two configurations of the same geometry and depth but different strengths. Field configuration D has the same parameters for the radial function $a(r)$ as models A and B, but has a harmonic degree of $s = 4$. Model E is a superposition of two fields, one with $s = 2$ and one with $s = 4$. Both fields are located at $\mu = 0.9 R_{\odot}$ with a width of $\sigma = 0.04 R_{\odot}$. The $s = 2$ component has a maximum field strength of $B_{\max} = 50$ kG, while the $s = 4$ component has a strength of $B_{\max} = -30$ kG. The cross-terms between the two configurations are included in the calculation of the general matrix elements. As can be seen in Figure D.5 in Appendix D.5, due to the superposition of the two fields, the maximum of the field is closer to the equator compared to model A.

Model F is a shallow field located at $\mu = 0.97 R_{\odot}$ with a width of $\sigma = 0.01 R_{\odot}$, with a maximum field strength of $B_{\max} = 10$ kG, and has harmonic degree $s = 2$. The multiplet shifts for this model are only of the order of some tens of nHz as can be seen in Figure D.8 in Appendix D.5. The shifts caused by the indirect effect are much smaller still, being at the level of a few 10^{-15} Hz. The shape of the frequency shifts as a function of mode frequency is rather different compared to the other models.

Figures D.2–D.8 in Appendix D.5 show visualizations of the magnetic fields, the resulting frequency shifts as functions of mode frequency and of lower turning point, as well as the shifts as a function of mode frequency separated for the direct and indirect effect for field models D, E, and F.

In Figure 9.4 the frequency shifts for models A and C are shown as functions of lower turning point of the modes. As can be seen in the bottom panel, only modes with lower turning point below or in the magnetized region around the tachocline experience a significant shift. Modes with turning points above the magnetic field are no longer disturbed by the direct effect. They can, however, still experience a weak shift due to the indirect effect, see lower row of panels in Figure D.2 in Appendix D.5. As can be seen in the top panel of Figure 9.4, for model A, the maximum shifts are experienced by the modes of the highest degree we calculated, as they have their lower turning point in the magnetized region.

9.5 Discussion

The six magnetic field configurations we tested produce very distinct patterns in the frequency shifts as a function of unperturbed mode frequency. While models A, B, and D lead to a decrease of the multiplet frequency for a wide range of mode frequencies, the shift is generally positive for models C, E, and F.

The multiplet shifts for field model A are presented in the bottom panel of Figure 9.1. The shifts for this model decrease for mode frequencies higher than $\nu \approx 2$ mHz and have their minimum at around $\nu \approx 3.8$ mHz. For even higher frequencies they increase and become positive for modes with $\nu \gtrsim 5$ mHz. Ridges of modes with the same radial order are apparent. The pattern seen here is determined by the direct effect. As seen in Figure 9.2, the shifts caused by the indirect effect (bottom panel) are much smaller than those caused by the direct effect (top panel).

The mean multiplet shift caused by the indirect effect is negative for all models and all modes. The dependence of the shift as a function of frequency resembles the surface effect, see, e.g., [Ball and Gizon \(2014\)](#) or [Basu \(2016\)](#). For modes of low degree, as can be seen for the $l = 4$ modes, the lowest harmonic degree we considered here, the multiplet shift caused by the indirect effect is lower than for the next harmonic degrees we considered for models D and E. This peculiarity may help to rule out some field configurations if it is not observed for the Sun. We shall study the behavior of the low degree mode frequencies in a separate article as these are of special importance for asteroseismic studies of the magnetic activity of a star for which only modes up to $l = 3$ can be observed. We speculate that magnetic fields in the upper part of the solar convection zone can explain at least part of the discrepancy between model frequencies and observed frequencies.

The direct effect is the dominant contribution to the total shift for all model fields we investigated. The indirect effect is only important for more complex field configurations and when the magnetic field strength near the photosphere is so strong as to give a plasma beta $\beta < 1$. The shifts caused by the indirect effect are of the same order of magnitude as those caused by the direct effect for models D and E, as can be seen from [Figures D.4 and D.6](#) in [Appendix D.5](#). For the other models, which all have harmonic degree $s = 2$, the contribution from the indirect effect to the mean multiplet shift can well be neglected.

Generating plots for observed shifts as a function of the lower turning point of the modes, analogously to [Figure 9.4](#), might give an indication of the location of magnetic field concentrations in the Sun. For this, the shifts of modes that have their lower turning point rather close to the surface have to be determined. If the shifts begin to decrease at a certain harmonic degree, as they do for the shifts for model C, their turning point can then be interpreted as the location of maximal magnetic field strength in this region. We note that such a location is not necessarily the location of the maximum field strength in the Sun, as deeper seated magnetic fields result in a smaller frequency shift even if they are stronger than more shallow magnetic fields. This can be seen by comparison of the top and bottom panels of [Figure 9.4](#): model A, which has a maximum magnetic field strength of 50 kG located at $0.9 R_{\odot}$, produces shifts at the μHz level. Whereas model C, which has a maximum magnetic field strength of six times that of model A, produces shifts that are only at the nHz level.

In [Figure 9.5](#), the difference of the multiplet frequency shifts for model B and model A is shown as a function of unperturbed mode frequency. We show differences between the shifts of models B and A in the sense model B - model A, that is, the model with the weaker magnetic field minus the model with the stronger field. On the Sun, the frequency shifts are correlated with the level of magnetic activity. Hence, model B with a maximum field strength of 40 kG would correspond to the activity maximum and model A with $B_{\text{max}} = 50 \text{ kG}$ would correspond to the activity minimum. In this picture, the toroidal magnetic field gets weaker in the ascending part of the cycle and reaches its minimum strength at the activity maximum. It then gets built up again by the solar dynamo and reaches its maximum strength at the activity minimum. The large field strength then causes the activity to increase again as magnetic flux starts to rise to the surface.

In the top panel of [Figure 9.6](#), we show the same as in [Figure 9.5](#) but for a restricted frequency range of $1700\text{--}4000 \mu\text{Hz}$. In the bottom panel of [Figure 9.6](#), we show the results of [Broomhall \(2017, called B17 hereafter\)](#). She investigated the mean multiplet frequency shifts between the maximum of solar cycle 23 and the minimum of the same cycle from Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG) data. As can be seen, the differences between our two model magnetic fields produce shifts in the multiplet frequencies that are strikingly similar to those reported by B17.

Figure 9.4: Multiplet frequency shifts for model A (*top panel*) and model C (*bottom panel*) as a function of lower turning point. Notice the different magnitudes of the shifts in the top and bottom panels.

Figure 9.5: Difference of the multiplet frequency shifts for model B and model A (in the sense $B - A$) as a function of unperturbed mode frequency. Every fourth harmonic degree is shown.

Our results have the correct order of magnitude, while our frequency shifts are about $0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$ higher than the solar shifts. This can, however, easily be corrected by adjusting the field strength of either model A or B. We find that the shifts of modes of low harmonic degree have a maximum at mode frequencies of $\nu \approx 3800 \mu\text{Hz}$. As can be seen in Figure 9.5, they decrease for higher frequencies and even turn negative at about $5000 \mu\text{Hz}$. This behavior is not apparent in the result of B17. An extension of the measurement of the observed frequency shifts to mode frequencies above $4000 \mu\text{Hz}$ may help to discern the model fields that best reproduce the shifts.

As can be seen in the last two columns of Table 9.1, the β values of the six models we consider here, cover a wide range. The tachocline field, model C, has the smallest β at its location of maximum magnetic field strength, but the highest value in the photosphere. Overall, the multiplet shifts for model C are very small, as can be seen in Figure 9.3. The shifts of model F, for which $\beta(\text{photosphere}) = 154$, are also only of the order of nHz. The other four models have β values at the photospheric level that are < 1 . These models produce multiplet frequency shifts that are of the order of μHz . From this, we gather that the magnetic field needs to have an appreciable field strength in the near-surface layers if the mean multiplet shifts shall reach the μHz level as is observed for the Sun.

For the model field E, which is a superposition of two fields, we find that the shifts are positive for most modes, see Figure D.6 in Appendix D.5. It is noteworthy that each of the two components of this model would lead to negative shifts on their own as can be seen for model A and model D. Also, the shifts are significantly different from zero already for mode frequencies below 2 mHz .

Figure 9.6: *Top panel:* same as Figure 9.5 but for a restricted frequency range. *Bottom panel:* observed mean multiplet frequency shifts between the maximum of solar cycle 23 and the minimum of cycle 23. Figure adapted from Broomhall (2017). Note the different color coding in the two panels.

9.6 Conclusion

The search for the layers where strong magnetic fields are located in the interior of the Sun can be conducted with helioseismic forward calculations and inversions. In this article, we described our efforts to carry out forward calculations of the effect of toroidal magnetic fields on solar multiplet frequencies of acoustic oscillations. The theoretical framework we present here is also applicable to stellar models.

We investigated six models for the magnetic field. A strong tachocline field, model C, produced only small shifts of the order of a few nHz. The maximum field strength of 300 kG is already at (Antia et al. 2000) or even high above the expected limit of magnetic fields in this region of the Sun (Arlt et al. 2007). With this, we can safely state that toroidal magnetic fields in the solar tachocline are not responsible for the observed frequency shifts over the solar cycle.

Basu (1997) put an upper limit of 300 kG on the strength of toroidal magnetic fields concentrated below the convection zone base. This is the strength of magnetic field model C. Hence, the effect of fossil fields in the solar radiative zone with comparable strengths can also only be of the order of nHz. Since we did not investigate poloidal magnetic field configurations, we cannot rule out poloidal fossil fields of this strength. We note again that the effect of near-surface magnetic field concentrations on acoustic oscillations are stronger by orders of magnitude and will thus likely impede the detection of fossil fields in the frequencies of solar acoustic oscillations. An investigation of the perturbation of eigenfunctions of low harmonic degree due to fossil fields is worthwhile and might put tighter constraints on the strength of such fields.

Shifts in multiplet frequencies of the Sun are measured between two differently magnetized states of the Sun. Commonly, these shifts are reported between an activity minimum and a following or preceding activity maximum. The difference of the multiplet shifts caused by our models A and B are found to be of the same order of magnitude as the observed shifts on the Sun. Also, the behavior of the shifts as a function of frequency and harmonic degree strongly resembles the solar values reported by B17. This might indicate that there are magnetic field distributions of the geometry and depth of our models A and B in the Sun. The location of the maximum field strength is at $0.9 R_{\odot}$ and they both have a field strength in the photosphere, which gives a plasma beta β that is smaller than unity. In general, we found that the β value in the very shallow layers must be of the order of unity to produce multiplet shifts that reach the observed μHz level.

A detailed study of splitting coefficients with the theory we presented here is expedient and will be conducted shortly. This will yield further insight into the depth, shape, and strength of the magnetic field concentration necessary to produce the observed frequency shifts and splitting coefficients caused by toroidal magnetic fields. It was shown by Schad et al. (2013) that analyses of perturbed eigenfunctions can be used to infer the solar meridional circulation. For this, the cross-coupling of modes has to be included, as self-coupling alone does not change the eigenfunction. Future integrated investigations of perturbed eigenfunctions, frequency shifts, and splitting coefficients, which can all be determined with the general matrix elements presented by Kiefer et al. (2017b) and in this article, are a promising tool to shed more light on the workings of the solar dynamo.

Acknowledgments We are grateful to Jørgen Christensen-Dalsgaard for supplying the extended version of Solar Model S. We also thank Kolja Glogowski for computing the full set of solar oscillation eigenmodes as well as for helpful discussions, Vincent Böning for important comments

and fruitful discussions, and our institute's internal referee Wolfgang Schmidt for reading the initial manuscript and his remarks, which helped to improve this article. We thank the anonymous referee for taking the time to review this paper. The research leading to these results received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union's Seventh Framework Program (FP/2007-2013)/ERC Grant Agreement no. 307117.

Concluding Remarks

In the [Introduction](#), I posed three questions, which I aimed to answer with the work presented in this thesis. In the following, I will summarize the developments and results of the thesis with respect to those three science questions.

Can we detect signatures of magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters of stars?

For the Sun, it is observed that the p-mode frequencies increase with rising levels of solar activity and that the p-mode amplitudes decrease with it. With the photometric time series that have become available over the last years — largely thanks to the space-borne missions *CoRoT* and *Kepler* — it is now possible to look for analogous behavior of stellar acoustic eigenfrequencies and other parameters. In Chapter 5, I presented my investigation of the *Kepler* short cadence time series of 24 solar-like stars. The term “solar-like” is not clearly defined, and I took it to mean that the stars under investigation exhibit solar-like (i.e., acoustic) oscillations, which can be measured from their periodograms, and that they are not too different from the Sun regarding mass and radius. This resulted in a selection of stars with spectral classes from F6–K0 (see Tables A.1 and A.2). The selection of “solar-like” stars allows to assess whether the Sun is special, or whether its behavior is typical for a star of this mass and age. Another criterion on the selection of stars was the availability of long, ideally uninterrupted *Kepler* short cadence time series: the time series of the 24 stars have lengths from 960–1147 days with an overall very high duty cycle and only few missing data sets (i.e., *Kepler* quarters).

For the search for possible temporal variations of the p-mode frequencies, I split the time series into shorter segments with lengths of 100 days or 150 days depending on the signal to noise ratio of the p-mode peaks in the periodogram. These lengths ensure a reasonable frequency resolution of about $0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$, on the one hand, and allow for the detection of temporal variations of the order of a year or less, on the other hand. From one segment to the next, the start time is shifted by 50 days. Hence, the segments are not independent. Then, the periodogram of each segment is calculated and only the frequency range of the p-modes is retained. The range of the p-modes is determined by inspection of the periodogram of the complete time series. In the next step, the p-mode ranges are cross-correlated, where the first segment serves as the reference point, i.e., all other periodograms are correlated with it. The resulting cross-correlation function is then fitted with a Lorentzian profile in order to obtain the mean shift of the p-mode peaks between the two correlated segments.

The correlation structure of the cross-correlation function is complex and it is tedious to calculate an uncertainty of the values of the cross-correlation function. This is however necessary if the

error on the measured frequency shift, which is obtained from the fitting function, shall serve as the uncertainty. To avoid this, I opted to use a resampling approach of the time series with which the uncertainty of the measured frequency shift can be calculated. In this approach, new realizations of the time series are created in the following way: first, the periodogram is smoothed to get an estimate of the underlying spectrum. The width of the smoothing window is chosen according to the frequency resolution of the respective periodogram and the width of the p-mode peaks. Then, real and imaginary parts of a Fourier transform are simulated by multiplying the square root of the spectral estimator with a zero mean normal distribution. The result of this is then transformed back to the temporal domain, where the gap structure of the original time series is applied. Each new realization of the time series is then analyzed as was done before for the original time series. This is done 200 times for all segments, including the reference segment. The mean of the 200 fits to the resulting cross-correlation functions then serves as the measured frequency shift, and their standard deviation is taken as its uncertainty. The amplitudes of the p-modes are measured not individually for every p-mode peak, but from the height of the envelope of the whole p-mode region, hence called mode height. This envelope is obtained from fitting a model of the background in the periodogram and a Gaussian for the p-mode envelope. This fitting was done with an affine invariant Markov Chain Monte Carlo code ([Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013](#)). The median of the posterior probability distribution of the resulting Markov chains is taken as the value for the mode height and the credible interval is defined from the 15.9th and 84.1th percentile of the posterior probability distributions.

These methods appear to be well-suited to answer the question which sparked their inception: I find significant frequency shifts in time for 23 out of the 24 stars. Furthermore, six of the stars show strong anti-correlation between the mode frequencies and mode heights. This indicates that the parameter changes are, indeed, caused by magnetic activity on these stars.

The star with the most significant frequency shifts in the sample is KIC 8006161. This star, being a G2 V star, is very similar to the Sun. The amplitude of its observed frequency shifts is $0.95 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{Hz}$, which is about twice the value that is observed for the Sun over its complete cycle. I also show that the frequency shifts of KIC 8006161 increase with mode frequency. For this, I divided the p-mode range into three segments and determined the mean shift of the modes within these segments in the same way as is done for the complete p-mode range. This is possible because the p-mode peaks in the periodogram of KIC 8006161 are quite narrow and the high signal-to-noise of the peaks.

The other noteworthy star in the sample is the young G0 V star KIC 10644253. Its frequency shifts exhibit a cycle-like pattern, which is also seen in the temporal variation of its mode heights. This confirms the result of [Salabert et al. \(2016b\)](#), who also found this cycle-like behavior. It is not clear whether this quasi-cyclic signal is caused by the complete activity cycle of KIC 10644253, or whether it is a short period variation of activity (as, e.g., the solar quasi-biennial oscillation seen in solar activity, see [Bazilevskaya et al. 2015](#)). Thus, I do not state a cycle length for KIC 10644253.

I plotted the measured frequency shift amplitudes for the ensemble of 24 stars as functions of their effective temperatures, ages, and rotation rates (Figures 5.4–5.6). This shows that the frequency shifts decrease with increasing age and rotation period. Due to the large scatter and error bars of the shift amplitudes, and the limited sample size, I cannot draw a final conclusion for the behavior of the shift amplitude with stellar effective temperature. In all these plots, KIC 8006161 is an outlier (see Chapter 11 for a possible explanation). There is no systematic correlation between the oscillation parameters and the background parameters, which include the granulation time

scales, across the sample of stars. I could not determine lengths of activity cycles. The available time series are not long enough for this.

My work thus clearly shows that we can, indeed, detect signatures of stellar magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters of stars.

How does a large-scale magnetic field affect a star's oscillations?

Part of the answer to this question has already been given in the last section: mode frequencies are increased and mode amplitudes are decreased by the large-scale magnetic fields that are associated with stellar cycles. However, as I will outline in Chapter 12, there are still several open questions regarding the variation of parameters of stellar p modes. For example, I did not investigate the dependence of the damping width or the energy of p modes. I addressed these parameters in a dedicated study of mode parameter data from the Sun-observing GONG network (Chapter 6).

The data that I used encompasses two complete solar cycles. I obtained the mode damping widths and amplitudes for modes of harmonic degree $l=0-150$ from the standard GONG pipeline, which fits power spectra of 108-day long time series. Several unwanted effects have to be accounted for: the temporal as well as the spatial window functions, residual parameter variations due to the change of the apparent size of the Sun over the year, and spurious jumps in the mode amplitudes. I calculated products of the mode width Γ and amplitude A , namely width times amplitude $\Gamma \cdot A$ and width squared times amplitude $\Gamma^2 \cdot A$. These products are necessary for the computation of the physical mode quantities of mean squared velocity, mode energy, and mode energy supply rate.

After correction of all the nuisance effects, the mode widths are normalized to their mean value over the complete time series and averaged over all modes. The result (see Figure 6.5) clearly shows the correlation of mode widths and the anti-correlation of mode amplitudes with the solar activity cycle. The rank correlation coefficients are $\rho = 0.62$ and $\rho = -0.91$, respectively.

Owing to the high quality of the data and the length of the time series, I was able to investigate the temporal variation of mode widths and amplitudes for different ranges of mode frequencies and harmonic degrees. This revealed that the fractional variation of mode widths is largest for modes with $2400 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 3300 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $31 \leq l \leq 60$ with a min-to-max amplitude of $26.6 \pm 0.3\%$. For the mode amplitudes, I found the largest variation for modes with $2400 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 3300 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $61 \leq l \leq 100$ with a min-to-max amplitude of $27.4 \pm 0.4\%$. Also, the level of correlation between the fractional variation of mode widths and amplitudes is dependent on mode frequency and harmonic degree. I find that the damping widths of modes with $1500 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 2400 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $0 \leq l \leq 30$ have the highest correlation with the solar cycle, with a Spearman's rank correlation coefficient of $\rho = 0.84$ and a two-sided significance of $p < 10^{-10}$. For the mode amplitudes I find this for modes with $2400 \mu\text{Hz} \leq \nu \leq 3300 \mu\text{Hz}$ and $0 \leq l \leq 30$ with a rank correlation of $\rho = -0.94$ and $p < 10^{-10}$. I found that the mode amplitudes follow an asymmetric Voigt profile. The central frequency of it is $\nu_{\text{max}} = 3073.59 \pm 0.18 \mu\text{Hz}$ and its width is $\Sigma = 621.3 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{Hz}$.

With the mode width and amplitude, I calculated the physical quantities mean squared velocity, mode energy, and mode energy supply rate. Scaling them with mode inertia removes their dependence on harmonic degree. The mode damping widths follow the well-known pattern (see, e.g., Komm et al. 2000b). I find that mean velocities of the modes peak at approximately 37 cm s^{-1} . In order to obtain clearer results of the temporal variation of these parameters, I

averaged modes within certain frequency ranges (see Table 6.2). From this, I find that the mean squared velocity and the energy of the modes decrease with rising levels of magnetic activity. I do not find a correlation between the energy supply rates to the modes within the investigated frequency range and the level of solar activity.

My theoretical calculations, which I summarize in the next section, also contribute to an answer to this question: with the formalism presented in Chapters 8 and 9, I can determine the perturbation to solar and stellar p-mode eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies caused by toroidal magnetic fields.

Where in the solar interior is the location of the dynamo?

To answer this question right away: I don't know (yet). However, the theoretical part of this thesis (Chapters 7–9) is concerned with the development of a formalism that allows to carry out forward calculations of perturbed eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions. This can eventually be used to pin down the location of magnetic field concentrations in the Sun and can thus help to locate the solar dynamo.

In an approach that is known from standard perturbation theory, the magnetic field inside the Sun (or any other star) is treated as a small perturbation to the star's equilibrium state. The eigenstates and eigenvalues (eigenfunctions and their corresponding eigenfrequencies) of the equilibrium stellar model are known. The added magnetic field has two effects on the eigenstates: first, the Lorentz force in the equation of motion allows them to couple. This is known as the *direct effect*. This coupling includes both self-coupling of an eigenstate, as well as cross-coupling between different states. Angular momentum selection rules restrict the modes which can experience cross-coupling (see Sections 8.5.1 and C.6). Furthermore, the presence of the magnetic field perturbs the equilibrium stellar structural quantities, this is called the *indirect effect*. By this, in turn, the eigenfunctions, as well as the eigenfrequencies, are changed.

The strength of the coupling of modes is quantified by the general matrix element. The major result of Chapter 8 is the calculation of the general matrix element for the direct effect of a superposition of toroidal magnetic field configurations. Because the large-scale subsurface solar magnetic field is believed to be predominantly toroidal, I restricted my calculations to the purely toroidal case (see, e.g., Charbonneau 2010). All involved quantities are represented in the basis of (generalized) spherical harmonic functions. This way, dependences on the radius and on the azimuthal and latitudinal angles can be separated. The integrals that have to be calculated can, thus, also be separated in integrals over the radius and the solid angle. The radial integrals have to be carried out numerically. The angular integrals involve products of four or more generalized spherical harmonics. These can be rewritten in terms of sums over products of Wigner $3j$ symbols. I calculated the necessary equations to compute the integral over a product of four, five, and six generalized spherical harmonic functions (see Equation (C.33); the integrals over products of five and six generalized spherical harmonics are not shown here but can be derived analogously). Several useful properties of the generalized spherical harmonics are exploited to limit the number of terms in the angular kernels. In Equation (8.28) and Appendix C.7, I present the final form of the general matrix element for the direct effect of a general superposition of toroidal magnetic fields. The angular kernels, which are given in Appendix C.7, have to be integrated over the complete sphere (Equation (C.33)).

For the calculation of the matrix element of the indirect effect, I projected the Lorentz force on the vector spherical harmonics. This considerably eases the calculation of the radial and angular

components of the Lorentz force, which is finally presented in terms of generalized spherical harmonics, see Equations (9.14)–(9.16). These components are then used in the computation of the perturbed stellar structural quantities (Equations (9.18)–(9.21)). In the next step, the perturbed stellar structural quantities are inserted into a set of sensitivity functions, which was taken from Lavelly and Ritzwoller (1992) (see Appendix D.3). With all of this, the general matrix element of the indirect effect of a general superposition of toroidal magnetic fields can be calculated.

With the general matrix elements for the direct and the indirect effects now at hand, I carried out forward calculations of the mean multiplet frequency shifts for six magnetic field configurations. I neglected the cross-coupling of modes in these forward calculations because the matrix elements for cross-coupling are orders of magnitude smaller than those for the self-coupling of modes.

For magnetic field models which are located close to the surface, i.e., within the top 10% of the Sun, I find that the resulting computed frequency shifts reach the observed μHz level. I calculated the difference of the frequency shifts of two magnetic field models (models A and B) with field concentrations that are centered around $0.9 R_{\odot}$. The magnetic fields of these two models differ only in their peak magnetic field strengths, which are 50 kG for model A and 40 kG for model B. The resulting frequency shifts of the difference model B - model A have the same order of magnitude as the observed frequency shifts over the solar cycle. Also, their dependence on both the harmonic degree and mode frequency strongly resembles that of the observed solar values. I also investigated a magnetic field model that is located around the tachocline at $0.72 R_{\odot}$, model C, with harmonic degree $s = 2$ (i.e., one magnetic field concentration per hemisphere with opposite polarity). This model has a maximum magnetic field strength of 300 kG. I find that the resulting frequency shifts are only at the level of a few nHz for such a magnetic field distribution.

For all six magnetic field models, the frequency perturbation from the indirect effect is smaller than that of the direct effect. The contribution of the indirect effect to the total frequency perturbation is larger for the more complicated magnetic field distributions, which are models D and E. The former is a magnetic field with harmonic degree $s = 4$, i.e., two concentrations of magnetic field with opposite polarity in each hemisphere. The indirect effect contributes with more than 10% to the total frequency perturbation for this model. For model E, which is a superposition of two toroidal components with $s = 2$ and 4, the indirect effect contributes almost a third of the total frequency perturbation. In plots which show the frequency perturbations as functions of the lower turning point of the modes, the location of the magnetic field concentration can be identified as the position of the maximum of the absolute of the frequency perturbation. However, this identification breaks down for very shallow field concentrations: an extremum in the frequency perturbations as a function of lower turning point is not readily apparent, see Figure D.8 for the respective plots of model F. This is because, for modes of harmonic degree up to $l = 150$, the lower turning point is below the magnetic field concentration.

I will discuss the conclusions of all of these developments and findings in Chapter 11.

The newly developed techniques and formalisms, and the results that I presented in Chapters 5–9 entail a number of conclusions regarding the driving science questions.

Can we detect signatures of magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters of stars?

As I already summed up in the preceding chapter: yes, indeed, we can. The methods which I developed and employed to detect these signatures proved to be well suited to detect activity-related changes in the oscillation spectra of solar-like stars.

The cross-correlation method to measure the p-mode frequency shifts and the resampling approach to estimate the uncertainties, which I presented in Chapter 5, are robust and not strongly dependent on user input. They can be applied in an automated way, which qualifies them to be used on very large data sets. I give ideas on how to further improve this method's performance in the next chapter.

Before the detection of magnetic activity in six stars, which I presented in Chapter 5, there were only a handful of seismic measurements of this kind: The first to achieve this were [García et al. \(2010\)](#), who found evidence for an activity cycle with $P_{\text{cyc}} > 120$ d in the F5 V star HD 49933 by analyzing the star's photometric data of the *CoRoT* satellite. Two more detections of this kind were made by [Régulo et al. \(2016\)](#) and [Salabert et al. \(2016a\)](#). Widespread detection, however, was missing. Measuring the activity-related changes of oscillation parameters of an increasingly larger number of stars opens the possibility of studying the dependencies of length, strength, and properties of stellar activity cycles on fundamental stellar parameters with seismic measures.

The Sun's activity-related frequency shifts and mode height variation appears unexceptional compared to the solar-like stars from the sample that I investigated. From plotting the measured frequency shifts as a function of stellar effective temperature, rotation period, and age, I find that the solar frequency shifts are in line with those of solar-like stars with similar fundamental parameters. Overall, I find that the frequency shift amplitude, which is connected to the intensity of a star's activity cycle, decreases with stellar age and rotation period. This is expected from dynamo theories, for which rotation is essential in the build-up of the magnetic field. That the overall level of stellar activity and the rotational frequency decrease with stellar age was already determined by [Skumanich \(1972\)](#). These findings can be used to supplement future studies of the activity-rotation-age relation, see, e.g., [Brun and Browning \(2017\)](#) and references therein.

I was not able to decide between opposing scaling relation for the p-mode frequency shifts with effective temperature. It will, however, be possible to decide between the scalings of [Chaplin et al. \(2007a\)](#) and [Metcalf et al. \(2007\)](#) with an investigation of a sample of stars, which covers a

broader range of effective temperatures which will soon become available with the launch of the TESS mission.

Recently, [Karoff et al. \(2018\)](#) have investigated the star KIC 8006161 for its frequency shifts and a possible explanation of its high levels of activity. They conclude that the reason is probably found in the star's high metallicity. KIC 8006161 has a metallicity which is about twice the solar value. The depth of the convection zone and thus the maximum possible strength of the magnetic field which can be stored and amplified in it increases with a star's metallicity. With the high signal-to-noise of its p-modes and its similarity to the Sun, KIC 8006161 is an excellent candidate for modeling the observed frequency shifts with the formalism that I presented in [Chapter 9](#). A direct comparison of modeled and observed shifts may shed more light on the reason for this star's high levels of activity (see also [Chapter 12](#)).

To conclude: signatures of seismic activity are detectable in photometric stellar time series and can be utilized to learn more about the solar-stellar connection, as well as about solar and stellar dynamos.

How does a large-scale magnetic field affect a star's oscillations?

The assessment of the variation of parameters of solar p-modes over the course of two solar activity cycles' worth of data showed that they are changed in many ways. The motivating science question, specialized to the case of the Sun in the study which I presented in [Chapter 6](#), can thus be answered with: the large-scale magnetic field enhances the damping of p modes and suppresses their amplitude depending on their frequency and harmonic degree; the velocity and energy that is associated with the modes decrease due to a large-scale magnetic field; the energy supply rate to p modes of a certain frequency range is not affected by a large-scale magnetic field.

The separation of solar p-modes into distinct frequency and harmonic degree ranges showed that the fractional variation of mode widths and amplitudes over the solar cycle depends on these parameters. The exact physical reasons for this behavior lie in the mechanisms that are responsible for the driving and damping of the p modes, see [Houdek and Dupret \(2015\)](#). Theoretical calculations of the effect of magnetic fields on the driving and damping mechanisms of stellar oscillations are worthwhile but are beyond the scope of this thesis. The suppression of mode amplitudes due to a magnetic field has implications for asteroseismic studies and the target selection: stars whose oscillations are likely to be suppressed by strong magnetic field to a level at which they can no longer be detected, disqualify from dedicated asteroseismic investigations (see, e.g., [Chaplin et al. 2011](#)).

In my investigations of stellar photometric time series, I found that the amplitude of the frequency shift of the star KIC 8006161 is dependent on mode frequency. This behavior is known from the Sun and shows that the magnetic fields which are causing the changes of the oscillations in this star and in the Sun are possibly of similar depth and configuration. This result highlights again that KIC 8006161 is an excellent laboratory for connecting stellar observations with my forward calculations.

Hence, my investigation regarding this question revealed details of the change of solar p-mode parameters that have not been reported so far and led to new findings of the change of stellar oscillation parameters that are caused by magnetic activity.

Where in the solar interior is the location of the dynamo?

With the formalism that I derived, perturbed eigenfunctions and eigenfrequencies can be calculated for a general superposition of toroidal magnetic field components. It is flexible regarding the input of models and can be applied to any standard solar or stellar model. The main results of the theoretical part of this thesis are the general matrix elements for the direct and indirect effect, which I calculated in the representation of generalized spherical harmonics.

From an inspection of the general matrix elements and the selection rules for coupling of angular momenta, I find that only modes of equal azimuthal order can couple (Equation (8.33)). Also, only modes whose harmonic degrees maximally differ by the sum of the harmonic degrees of the input toroidal magnetic field configuration can couple (Equation (8.32)). If the cross-coupling of modes is included, the framework of quasi-degenerate perturbation theory can be applied (see Chapter 7). I find that the general matrix element and hence the supermatrix \mathbf{Z} , from whose eigenvalues and eigenvectors the perturbation of the eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions can be calculated, is not Hermitian. The non-Hermiticity of the supermatrix, or more precisely its asymmetry as it is completely real-valued in the case of magnetic fields, allows complex-valued eigenvalues and thus complex frequency perturbations. A complex-valued frequency perturbation is tantamount to a frequency shift and an additional damping factor for the affected mode.

The self-coupling of modes, which I focused on in Chapter 9, can significantly alter mode frequencies. As mentioned in the last chapter, the direct effect is the dominant contribution to the total frequency perturbation for all six model field configurations which I investigated. The indirect effect is only important for more complex field configurations and when the plasma beta is smaller than unity in the very shallow layers close to the photosphere. I also find that the total frequency perturbation due to a magnetic field may partly be responsible for the solar surface term.

Because of the distinctly different frequency dependence of the mode frequency perturbations which are caused by the direct and indirect effect, it may be possible to disentangle and estimate their individual contribution to the observed p-mode frequency variation over the solar cycle. I found that the location of the maximum strength of a concentration of subsurface magnetic field can immediately be identified in plots which show the computed frequency perturbation as a function of the lower turning point of the p-modes. From the calculation of the frequency perturbations of a strong magnetic field, which is centered around the tachocline, I find that such a magnetic field cannot be responsible for the observed p-mode frequency shifts over the solar cycle. The maximum field strength of the field is 300 kG. Thus, it exceeds current estimates of the magnetic field strength in this part of the Sun (Arlt et al. 2007), but produces only small frequency perturbations which are of the order of a few nHz.

The difference of the frequency shifts which are caused by two models that are located around $0.9 R_{\odot}$ are of the order of magnitude of the observed solar shifts over the complete cycle. Furthermore, the dependence on mode frequency, as well as harmonic degree, strongly resembles that of the observational values. The two models only differ by 10 kG in magnetic field strength. Their rather shallow depth is of particular interest because the near-surface shear layer is proposed as a possible region of magnetic field generation and storage (see, e.g., Brandenburg 2005).

The equations that I derived and the forward calculations which I presented offer a novel approach to measure subsurface magnetic field concentrations in the Sun and stars. Systematic forward modeling of frequency shifts, frequency splittings, and the perturbed mode eigenfunctions will

shed light on the location of the solar dynamo and, eventually, stellar dynamos, as well as help us to learn about their mode of operation.

The methods and results that I developed and that I achieved in this thesis can be used in future studies to learn about the solar dynamo and the solar-stellar connection. Some pathways for advancement and expansion of the presented methods are straightforward and will be briefly discussed in the following.

More Stars, Improved Method As I have shown, signatures of stellar magnetic activity can be detected in the acoustic parameters of stars. Using the presented cross-correlation method in a study of a larger sample of stars, which ideally have precisely determined fundamental parameters over a broad range of the parameter space, will help to answer several questions:

- Are activity related frequency shifts and changes in mode amplitudes always anti-correlated with each other? Or is there a systematic trend of the level of correlation or anti-correlation of the variation of mode frequencies and mode amplitudes with fundamental stellar parameters?
- How does the amplitude of the frequency shifts over a stellar cycle change with the star's effective temperature and what is the correct scaling model for these amplitudes ([Chaplin et al. 2007a](#), or [Metcalf et al. 2007](#), or some other model)?
- Are there any detectable signatures of magnetic activity in the time scales of granulation and if so, can these be used for an assessment of the level of magnetic activity of the star?
- How does metallicity affect the strength of magnetic activity and seismic signatures thereof?
- How are strength and detectability of acoustic signatures of stellar magnetic activity related to a star's rotation rate and age?

Data that can be used for such studies is forthcoming with the launch of NASA's TESS mission which is scheduled for March 2018.

The cross-correlation method and the approach for calculating the associated uncertainties of the frequency shifts can be further optimized. One possibility is to focus the calculation of the cross-correlation function on the mode peaks. As I implemented it here, the whole p-mode range is used. Neglecting the frequency bins between the p-mode peaks, i.e., setting the values of the periodogram to zero, may yield less noisy cross-correlation functions. This may thus yield significantly reduced uncertainties. As the p-mode frequencies for solar-like stars are now cataloged (see, e.g., [Lund et al. 2017](#)), these can be used for such a task. Thus, the method can also be adapted to only measure the frequency shifts of modes of a certain harmonic degree or

even single modes. Such results can then also be directly compared with frequency shifts from forward calculations of the kind which I presented in Chapter 9.

Constancy of Energy Supply Rates In Chapter 6, I restricted my analysis of the energy supply rate to solar p modes within the frequency range of 3000–3600 μHz . Even though I found that the energy supply rates do not vary with the solar cycle in this case, there is still the question of whether this is true for all mode sets. However, the supply rates may be variable for specific mode sets, which encompass different ranges of mode frequency and harmonic degree, analogous to what I presented for mode widths and amplitudes in Section 6.2. I suspect that the averaging over the included modes, which is carried out to maintain the physical units of the energy supply rate, suppresses a temporal variation. If the analysis is done for normalized values, this may be circumvented. If a temporal variation of the energy supply rates were detected, the question “Where does the excess energy go?” would arise.

The Surface Effect Recently, [Howe et al. \(2017\)](#) investigated changes to the surface term over the solar cycle. They conclude that it is possible to assess the activity-related frequency variation in solar-like asteroseismic targets with the help of the surface term. The frequency shifts which I found for models of subsurface toroidal magnetic fields in the Sun bear resemblance to the observed surface effect of solar p modes (see Section 2.9 and compare Figure 2.12 with Figure 9.2). By scaling the computed frequency perturbations with mode inertia, as I did with the mode parameters in Section 6.3, the dependence on harmonic degree is removed. Hence, the surface effect, which is generally considered a weakness in our knowledge of the solar and stellar interior, may, in fact, hold critical information about subsurface magnetic fields.

Modeling the Frequency Shifts of Other Stars The formalism that I presented in Chapter 9 can also be applied to stellar models for forward calculations of frequency perturbations. The models can be chosen to cover broad ranges in the parameter spaces of fundamental stellar parameters as, e.g., metallicity, mass, or age. A set of magnetic field models can then be used to test for possible dependences of the resulting frequency perturbations on the fundamental parameters. Such a study would ideally be supplemented by an expanded set of detections of seismic signatures of activity, as discussed in the first paragraph of this chapter. This may yield essential information about the depth and strength of magnetic field in stars and put tight constraints on simulations of stellar dynamos.

Splitting Coefficients Magnetic fields inside stars contribute to the splitting of multiplets in the even order splitting coefficients (see, e.g., [Baldner et al. 2009](#)). In Chapter 9, I concentrated on mean multiplet shifts. The splitting coefficients that are caused by a certain magnetic field configuration can however readily be obtained with the presented formalism. Therefore, it is the next natural step to match not only the mean multiplet shifts to their observed counterparts but to do this for even order splitting coefficients as well. This will yield further insight into the configuration of the solar subsurface magnetic field.

It is also worthwhile to investigate acoustic glitches (see Section 2.8), which can be caused by tightly confined magnetic fields (see [Gough and Thompson 1990](#)). As the signals of glitches are measured from the differences of mean multiplet frequencies, this work may also be expanded to stars, for which the splitting coefficients are notoriously harder to measure than mean multiplet frequencies.

Extension of Formalism The framework to calculate the perturbation of eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions can be expanded to include also poloidal magnetic fields. Such a formalism can then be used to model the effect of any arbitrary axisymmetric magnetic field configuration. This will be particularly useful for stars whose large-scale magnetic field is dominated by the poloidal component, as it is, e.g., for some early M dwarfs (Donati et al. 2008).

Schad et al. (2013) have measured the solar meridional flow from the analysis of perturbed eigenfunctions. In an analogous approach, which utilizes the presented general matrix elements, the solar interior magnetic field should be measurable. The formalism presented in Chapter 9 is already able to calculate perturbed eigenfunctions for toroidal magnetic field configurations, as it includes the possibility for the cross-coupling of modes (see Section 9.2). An inversion of model data with known magnetic field configuration shall precede the analysis of real data in order to optimize the technique.

Thus, the work presented in this thesis opens many new possibilities to investigate solar and stellar magnetic fields with seismic techniques.

Appendix

Appendices to Chapter 5

A.1 Tables of Stellar Parameters

Table A.1: Radius, mass, and age of the investigated stars.

KIC	$R [R_{\odot}]$	$\sigma_R [R_{\odot}]$	$M [M_{\odot}]$	$\sigma_M [M_{\odot}]$	Age [Gyr]	$\sigma_{\text{Age}} [\text{Gyr}]$	Reference*
3632418	1.835	0.034	1.27	0.03	2.88	0.38	(2)
3656476	1.32	0.03	1.09	0.01	7.71	0.22	(1)
4914923	1.37	0.05	1.10	0.01	6.18	0.18	(1)
5184732	1.36	0.01	1.25	0.01	3.98	0.11	(1)
6106415	1.24	0.01	1.12	0.02	4.72	0.12	(1)
6116048	1.219	0.09	1.01	0.03	6.23	0.37	(2)
6603624	1.181	0.015	1.09	0.03	8.11	0.46	(2)
6933899	1.599	0.018	1.14	0.03	6.87	0.34	(2)
7680114	1.45	0.03	1.19	0.01	5.92	0.20	(1)
7976303	1.961	0.041	1.10	0.05	4.78	0.58	(2)
8006161	0.947	0.007	1.04	0.02	5.04	0.17	(2)
8228742	1.809	0.014	1.27	0.02	3.84	0.29	(2)
8379927	1.11	0.02	1.09	0.03	3.28	0.16	(1)
8760414	1.010	0.004	0.78	0.01	3.69	0.74	(2)
9025370	0.960	$^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	0.83	$^{+0.12}_{-0.06}$	11.8	$^{+3.8}_{-5.6}$	(3), (4)
9955598	0.883	0.008	0.89	0.02	6.72	0.20	(2)
10018963	1.915	0.020	1.18	0.03	4.36	0.34	(2)
10516096	1.42	0.03	1.12	0.03	6.41	0.27	(1)
10644253	1.108	0.016	1.13	0.05	1.07	0.25	(2)
10963065	1.213	0.008	1.05	0.02	4.30	0.23	(2)
11244118	1.589	0.026	1.10	0.05	6.43	0.58	(2)
11295426	1.243	0.019	1.079	0.051	7.087	0.451	(3), (5)
12009504	1.375	0.015	1.12	0.03	3.64	0.26	(2)
12258514	1.573	0.010	1.19	0.03	4.03	0.32	(2)

Notes. (*) If one reference is given, it applies to R, M, and age. If two references are given, the first one applies to R and M and the second to the age. References: (1) Mathur et al. (2012), (2) Metcalfe et al. (2014), (3) Huber et al. (2014), (4) Chaplin et al. (2014), (5) Silva Aguirre et al. (2015).

Table A.2: Spectral type, effective temperature, and rotation period of the investigated stars.

KIC	Spectral type	T_{eff} [K]	$\sigma_{T_{\text{eff}}}$ [K]	Reference*	P_{rot} [d]	$\sigma_{P_{\text{rot}}}$ [d]	Reference	Notes
3632418	F6IV	6148	111	(1)	12.591	0.036	(5)	Planet host (8)
3656476	G5IV	5586	108	(1)	31.67	3.53	(6)	High proper motion (9)
4914923	G1.5V	5808	92	(1)	20.49	2.82	(6)	—
5184732	G4V	5669	97	(1)	19.79	2.43	(6)	—
6106415	G0	6055	70	(2), (3)	—	—	—	—
6116048	F9IV-V	5991	124	(1)	17.26	1.96	(6)	—
6603624	G8IV-V	5471	128	(1)	—	—	—	—
6933899	G0.5IV	5837	97	(1)	—	—	—	—
7680114	G0V	5799	91	(1)	26.31	1.86	(6)	—
7976303	F8V	6119	106	(1)	—	—	—	—
8006161	G8V	5258	97	(1)	29.79	3.09	(6)	High proper motion (9)
8228742	F9IV-V	6061	108	(1)	20.23	2.16	(6)	—
8379927	F9IV-V	5998	108	(1)	17.259	0.026	(7)	Spectroscopic binary (10)
8760414	G0IV	5850	166	(1)	—	—	—	High proper motion (11)
9025370	F8	5659	73	(2), (4)	—	—	—	—
9955598	K0V	5264	95	(1)	34.20	5.64	(6)	Planet host (12)
10018963	F6IV	6145	112	(1)	—	—	—	—
10516096	F9IV-V	5928	95	(1)	—	—	—	—
10644253	G0V	5910	93	(1)	10.91	0.87	(6)	—
10963065	F8V	6097	130	(1)	12.444	0.172	(5)	Planet host (12)
11244118	G5IV	5605	104	(1)	23.17	3.89	(6)	—
11295426	—	5796	78	(4)	—	—	—	Planet host (13)
12009504	F9IV-V	6099	125	(1)	9.426	0.327	(7)	—
12258514	G0.5IV	5952	95	(1)	15.00	1.84	(6)	—

Notes. (*) If one reference is given, it applies to the spectral type and T_{eff} . If two references are given, the first one applies to the spectral type and the second to T_{eff} . References: (1) Molenda-Żakowicz et al. (2013), (2) SIMBAD^a entry without reference, (3) Bruntt et al. (2012), (4) Pinsonneault et al. (2012), (5) McQuillan et al. (2013), (6) García et al. (2014a), (7) McQuillan et al. (2014), (8) Howell et al. (2011), (9) Leeuwen (2007), (10) Griffin (2007), (11) Lepine and Shara (2005), (12) Marcy et al. (2014), (13) Gilliland et al. (2013).

^a<http://simbad.u-strasbg.fr/simbad/>

A.2 Plots of Frequency Shifts and Variations of the Height of the p-Mode Envelope, Correlation Coefficients of the Background Model Parameters and the Measured Frequency Shifts

Table A.3: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 3632418.

3632418	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.14	0.76						
Noise	-0.18	0.70	0.68	0.09				
τ_1	-0.21	0.64	0.25	0.59	-0.21	0.64		
τ_2	-0.68	0.09	0.68	0.09	0.75	0.05	-0.07	0.88

Figure A.1: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 3632418 as a function of time.

Table A.4: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 3656476.

3656476	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.30	0.62						
Noise	0.70	0.19	0.70	0.19				
τ_1	0.80	0.10	0.80	0.10	0.80	0.10		
τ_2	-0.80	0.10	-0.80	0.10	-0.80	0.10	-1.00	0.00

Figure A.2: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 3656476 as a function of time.

Table A.5: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 4914923.

4914923	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.49	0.33						
Noise	0.20	0.70	-0.54	0.27				
τ_1	-0.20	0.70	-0.26	0.62	0.09	0.87		
τ_2	-0.60	0.21	-0.77	0.07	-0.03	0.96	0.03	0.96

Figure A.3: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 4914923 as a function of time.**Table A.6:** Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 5184732.

5184732	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.44	0.20						
Noise	-0.43	0.21	0.25	0.49				
τ_1	0.32	0.37	-0.77	0.01	-0.35	0.33		
τ_2	-0.13	0.73	-0.08	0.83	-0.30	0.40	0.26	0.47

Figure A.4: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 5184732 as a function of time.

Table A.7: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 6106415.

6106415	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.60	0.21						
Noise	0.14	0.79	-0.26	0.62				
τ_1	-0.31	0.54	-0.83	0.04	0.14	0.79		
τ_2	-0.43	0.40	-0.60	0.21	0.31	0.54	0.09	0.87

Figure A.5: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 6106415 as a function of time.

Table A.8: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 6116048.

6116048	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.75	0.05						
Noise	-0.25	0.59	0.18	0.70				
τ_1	-0.61	0.15	-0.36	0.43	0.57	0.18		
τ_2	-0.32	0.48	-0.71	0.07	-0.14	0.76	0.32	0.48

Figure A.6: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 6116048 as a function of time.

Table A.9: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 6603624.

6603624	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.52	0.10						
Noise	0.28	0.40	0.15	0.67				
τ_1	-0.01	0.98	-0.51	0.11	0.31	0.36		
τ_2	-0.45	0.17	-0.25	0.45	0.16	0.63	0.52	0.10

Figure A.7: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 6603624 as a function of time.

Table A.10: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 6933899.

6933899	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.57	0.18						
Noise	-0.39	0.38	0.68	0.09				
τ_1	0.11	0.82	0.07	0.88	-0.36	0.43		
τ_2	0.50	0.25	-0.04	0.94	0.07	0.88	-0.57	0.18

Figure A.8: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 6933899 as a function of time.

Table A.11: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 7680114.

7680114	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.60	0.21						
Noise	0.89	0.02	0.54	0.27				
τ_1	0.31	0.54	-0.20	0.70	0.43	0.40		
τ_2	1.00	0.00	0.60	0.21	0.89	0.02	0.31	0.54

Figure A.9: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 7680114 as a function of time.

Table A.12: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 7976303.

7976303	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.29	0.53						
Noise	-0.14	0.76	-0.50	0.25				
τ_1	0.39	0.38	-0.57	0.18	0.79	0.04		
τ_2	-0.36	0.43	0.36	0.43	-0.57	0.18	-0.82	0.02

Figure A.10: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 7976303 as a function of time.

Table A.13: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 8006161.

8006161	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.93	4×10^{-5}						
Noise	0.23	0.50	-0.09	0.79				
τ_1	-0.27	0.42	0.37	0.26	-0.24	0.48		
τ_2	-0.01	0.98	0.14	0.69	0.04	0.92	0.74	0.01

Figure A.11: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 8006161 as a function of time.

Table A.14: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 8228742.

8228742	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.29	0.39						
Noise	-0.41	0.21	0.61	0.05				
τ_1	-0.07	0.83	0.04	0.92	-0.21	0.54		
τ_2	-0.02	0.96	-0.14	0.69	-0.14	0.69	-0.43	0.19

Figure A.12: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 8228742 as a function of time.

Table A.15: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 8379927.

8379927	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.43	0.34						
Noise	-0.21	0.64	0.25	0.59				
τ_1	-0.11	0.82	-0.04	0.94	-0.04	0.94		
τ_2	0.00	1.00	-0.64	0.12	-0.57	0.18	0.39	0.38

Figure A.13: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 8379927 as a function of time.**Table A.16:** Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 8760414.

8760414	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.54	0.22						
Noise	-0.43	0.34	0.39	0.38				
τ_1	-0.64	0.12	-0.11	0.82	0.07	0.88		
τ_2	0.39	0.38	-0.54	0.22	-0.86	0.01	-0.14	0.76

Figure A.14: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 8760414 as a function of time.

Table A.17: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 9025370.

9025370	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.25	0.47						
Noise	-0.55	0.08	-0.32	0.34				
τ_1	-0.02	0.96	0.29	0.39	-0.15	0.67		
τ_2	-0.13	0.71	-0.59	0.06	0.41	0.21	-0.33	0.33

Figure A.15: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 9025370 as a function of time.

Table A.18: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 9955598.

9955598	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.75	0.05						
Noise	0.71	0.07	-0.54	0.22				
τ_1	0.00	1.00	-0.14	0.76	-0.43	0.34		
τ_2	-0.21	0.64	-0.18	0.70	-0.50	0.25	0.89	0.01

Figure A.16: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 9955598 as a function of time.

Table A.19: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 10018963.

10018963	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.46	0.15						
Noise	0.15	0.65	-0.26	0.43				
τ_1	-0.13	0.71	0.23	0.50	0.06	0.85		
τ_2	-0.09	0.79	0.17	0.61	-0.31	0.36	-0.08	0.81

Figure A.17: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 10018963 as a function of time.**Table A.20:** Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 10516096.

10516096	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.26	0.47						
Noise	0.25	0.49	0.43	0.21				
τ_1	-0.75	0.01	0.38	0.28	0.05	0.88		
τ_2	0.14	0.70	-0.28	0.43	-0.56	0.09	-0.22	0.53

Figure A.18: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 10516096 as a function of time.

Table A.21: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 10644253.

10644253	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.93	3×10^{-3}						
Noise	0.50	0.25	-0.75	0.05				
τ_1	-0.71	0.07	0.68	0.09	-0.14	0.76		
τ_2	0.86	0.01	-0.82	0.02	0.43	0.34	-0.75	0.05

Figure A.19: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 10644253 as a function of time.

Table A.22: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 10963065.

10963065	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.26	0.62						
Noise	0.60	0.21	-0.83	0.04				
τ_1	0.26	0.62	-0.71	0.11	0.89	0.02		
τ_2	0.54	0.27	-0.60	0.21	0.83	0.04	0.83	0.04

Figure A.20: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 10963065 as a function of time.

Table A.23: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 11244118.

11244118	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.61	0.05						
Noise	0.25	0.47	-0.37	0.26				
τ_1	0.25	0.47	-0.12	0.73	-0.41	0.21		
τ_2	0.30	0.37	-0.65	0.03	0.15	0.67	0.50	0.12

Figure A.21: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 11244118 as a function of time.

Table A.24: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 11295426.

11295426	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	0.36	0.43						
Noise	-0.18	0.70	0.25	0.59				
τ_1	-0.14	0.76	-0.54	0.22	-0.18	0.70		
τ_2	0.29	0.53	-0.64	0.12	-0.79	0.04	0.46	0.29

Figure A.22: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 11295426 as a function of time.

Table A.25: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 12009504.

12009504	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.13	0.71						
Noise	0.17	0.61	0.63	0.04				
τ_1	-0.21	0.54	-0.08	0.81	0.00	1.00		
τ_2	-0.12	0.73	-0.45	0.17	-0.53	0.10	-0.15	0.65

Figure A.23: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 12009504 as a function of time.

Table A.26: Correlation coefficients between parameters of the background model and the frequency shifts and their associated p values for KIC 12258514.

12258514	Shifts	p	Height	p	Noise	p	τ_1	p
Height	-0.50	0.25						
Noise	0.43	0.34	-0.86	0.01				
τ_1	-0.11	0.82	0.18	0.70	-0.14	0.76		
τ_2	0.07	0.88	-0.04	0.94	-0.29	0.53	-0.61	0.15

Figure A.24: Frequency shifts (*top half*) and height of the p-mode envelope (*bottom half*) for KIC 12258514 as a function of time.

A.3 Plot of Frequency Shifts as a Function of Height of the p-Mode Envelope for KIC 5184732

Figure A.25: Frequency shifts of KIC 5184732 as a function of height of the mode envelope. The correlation between the presented quantities is negative with a tendency towards no correlation for larger heights.

Appendices to Chapter 6

B.1 Correction for Jumps in Mode Amplitudes

The correction factors that were multiplied to the mode amplitudes in the indicated time frame are

$$\begin{aligned} C &= 1 - \frac{0.03 \cdot l}{150} - \frac{0.06 \cdot \nu}{4500 \mu\text{Hz}} - 0.06 && \text{(months 1-58),} \\ C &= 1 - \frac{0.02 \cdot l}{150} - \frac{0.04 \cdot \nu}{4500 \mu\text{Hz}} - 0.04 && \text{(month 59),} \\ C &= 1 - \frac{0.01 \cdot l}{150} - \frac{0.02 \cdot \nu}{4500 \mu\text{Hz}} - 0.02 && \text{(month 60),} \\ C &= 1 && \text{(months 61-98),} \\ C &= 1 + \frac{0.0733 \cdot l}{150} && \text{(month 100),} \\ C &= 1 + \frac{0.1466 \cdot l}{150} && \text{(month 101),} \\ C &= 1 + \frac{0.22 \cdot l}{150} && \text{(months 102-223),} \end{aligned} \tag{B.1}$$

where l is the harmonic degree of the mode and ν is the frequency of the mode.

Figure B.1: Temporal variation of mode amplitudes which are not corrected for jumps in the data. Different ranges of harmonic degrees (rows, harmonic degree indicated to the right of the fourth column) and mode frequencies (columns, frequency range indicated above the first row) are shown. Amplitudes are normalized to the mean for each mode and then averaged over all modes in the respective range of frequency and degree. Months with higher than median 10.7 cm solar radio flux are highlighted by red data points. The one year average is shown by the black solid curve. Levels of 1.1 and 0.9 of the mean are indicated by grey dashed lines.

B.2 Results for Normalized Mode Parameter Variation

Table B.1: Results from the normalized and averaged variation of mode width for different parameter ranges shown in Figure 6.6.

ν_{\min}	ν_{\max}	l_{\min}	l_{\max}	#modes	min (%)	max (%)	mean error (%)	ρ	p
1500	2400	0	30	119	96.7±0.2	105.1±0.2	0.6	0.38	$6.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$
2400	3300	0	30	167	93.0±0.2	107.8±0.2	0.5	0.84	$< 10^{-10}$
3300	4500	0	30	101	97.4±0.2	103.5±0.2	0.5	0.70	$< 10^{-10}$
1500	4500	0	30	387	95.7±0.1	105.1±0.1	0.3	0.80	$< 10^{-10}$
1500	2400	31	60	122	95.0±0.1	106.7±0.2	0.4	0.31	$6.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$
2400	3300	31	60	152	86.7±0.1	113.3±0.2	0.4	0.50	$5.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$
3300	4500	31	60	123	95.8±0.2	104.0±0.2	0.4	0.50	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$
1500	4500	31	60	397	92.2±0.1	108.4±0.1	0.3	0.46	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$
1500	2400	61	100	130	96.6±0.1	104.7±0.1	0.3	0.32	$4.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
2400	3300	61	100	136	90.7±0.1	109.0±0.1	0.3	0.77	$< 10^{-10}$
3300	4500	61	100	88	94.9±0.1	104.9±0.2	0.4	0.80	$< 10^{-10}$
1500	4500	61	100	354	93.9±0.1	106.2±0.1	0.2	0.69	$< 10^{-10}$
1500	2400	101	150	124	97.6±0.1	103.1±0.1	0.3	0.39	$5.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
2400	3300	101	150	7	95.6±0.5	104.2±0.5	1.5	0.49	$6.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$
3300	4500	101	150	6	95.4±0.3	105.4±0.6	1.3	0.78	$< 10^{-10}$
1500	4500	101	150	137	97.4±0.1	103.2±0.1	0.3	0.45	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$
1500	2400	0	150	495	96.7±0.1	104.3±0.1	0.2	0.36	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
2400	3300	0	150	462	90.3±0.1	109.2±0.1	0.3	0.68	$< 10^{-10}$
3300	4500	0	150	318	96.2±0.1	103.6±0.1	0.3	0.74	$< 10^{-10}$
1500	4500	0	150	1275	94.4±0.1	105.9±0.1	0.2	0.62	$2 \cdot 10^{-9}$

Notes. *Column 1–4:* Parameters ranges of the individual panels. *Column 5:* Number of modes included. *Column 6–7:* Extrema of the one year smoothed parameter variation *Column 8:* The typical error on the individual unsmoothed data point. *Column 9–10:* Spearman’s correlation coefficient between independent data points of the unsmoothed parameter variation and the $F_{10,7}$ index and the associated p value.

Table B.2: Results from the normalized and averaged variation of mode amplitudes for different parameter ranges shown in Figure 6.7.

ν_{\min}	ν_{\max}	l_{\min}	l_{\max}	#modes	min (%)	max (%)	mean error (%)	ρ	p
1500	2400	0	30	119	94.6±0.3	106.2±0.4	1.2	-0.82	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
2400	3300	0	30	164	87.7±0.2	112.5±0.3	0.9	-0.94	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
3300	4500	0	30	101	93.5±0.2	105.1±0.3	0.8	-0.88	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	4500	0	30	384	91.4±0.2	108.5±0.2	0.6	-0.92	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	2400	31	60	122	94.4±0.2	106.9±0.2	0.7	-0.78	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
2400	3300	31	60	152	88.8±0.1	112.5±0.2	0.5	-0.88	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
3300	4500	31	60	123	93.2±0.1	107.1±0.2	0.4	-0.88	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	4500	31	60	397	91.9±0.1	109.0±0.1	0.3	-0.87	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	2400	61	100	130	94.6±0.1	107.5±0.2	0.5	-0.76	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
2400	3300	61	100	136	86.7±0.1	114.1±0.2	0.5	-0.91	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
3300	4500	61	100	88	90.3±0.1	109.9±0.2	0.5	-0.89	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	4500	61	100	354	90.6±0.1	110.6±0.1	0.3	-0.90	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	2400	101	150	124	94.0±0.1	107.4±0.2	0.5	-0.66	< 10 ⁻⁹
2400	3300	101	150	7	90.5±0.4	108.9±0.7	1.8	-0.82	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
3300	4500	101	150	6	89.1±0.4	112.2±0.7	1.7	-0.87	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	4500	101	150	137	93.8±0.1	107.7±0.2	0.5	-0.70	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	2400	0	150	495	95.0±0.1	106.9±0.1	0.4	-0.81	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
2400	3300	0	150	459	87.8±0.1	112.9±0.1	0.4	-0.92	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
3300	4500	0	150	318	92.4±0.1	107.3±0.1	0.3	-0.90	< 10 ⁻¹⁰
1500	4500	0	150	1272	91.8±0.1	109.1±0.1	0.2	-0.91	< 10 ⁻¹⁰

Notes. *Column 1–4:* Parameters ranges of the individual panels. *Column 5:* Number of modes included. *Column 6–7:* Extrema of the one year smoothed parameter variation. *Column 8:* The typical error on the individual unsmoothed data point. *Column 9–10:* Spearman’s correlation coefficient between independent data points of the unsmoothed parameter variation and the $F_{10.7}$ index and the associated p value.

B.3 Supplemental Information

Table B.3: GONG months and their corresponding starting date¹, fill factor, and $F_{10.7}$ index.

Month	Date	Fill	$F_{10.7}$	Month	Date	Fill	$F_{10.7}$
1	1995/05/07	0.803	77.2	41	1999/04/16	0.857	165.7
2	1995/06/12	0.813	76.7	42	1999/05/22	0.853	173.2
3	1995/07/18	0.847	75.3	43	1999/06/27	0.840	160.5
4	1995/08/23	0.857	74.3	44	1999/08/02	0.840	158.5
5	1995/09/28	0.877	73.4	45	1999/09/07	0.850	163.1
6	1995/11/03	0.877	71.7	46	1999/10/13	0.833	172.3
7	1995/12/09	0.887	70.9	47	1999/11/18	0.860	162.4
8	1996/01/14	0.897	70.1	48	1999/12/24	0.843	176.4
9	1996/02/19	0.913	70.5	49	2000/01/29	0.860	187.0
10	1996/03/26	0.877	71.2	50	2000/03/05	0.837	195.9
11	1996/05/01	0.817	72.5	51	2000/04/10	0.830	189.0
12	1996/06/06	0.763	73.4	52	2000/05/16	0.803	188.6
13	1996/07/12	0.797	72.8	53	2000/06/21	0.827	188.1
14	1996/08/17	0.867	72.1	54	2000/07/27	0.830	173.1
15	1996/09/22	0.920	73.1	55	2000/09/01	0.883	176.1
16	1996/10/28	0.920	73.9	56	2000/10/07	0.887	170.7
17	1996/12/03	0.907	72.2	57	2000/11/12	0.900	169.0
18	1997/01/08	0.863	71.9	58	2000/12/18	0.847	160.6
19	1997/02/13	0.823	74.7	59	2001/01/23	0.803	171.2
20	1997/03/21	0.807	75.2	60	2001/02/28	0.773	173.7
21	1997/04/26	0.827	74.7	61	2001/04/05	0.770	174.7
22	1997/06/01	0.820	76.3	62	2001/05/11	0.753	155.5
23	1997/07/07	0.830	83.9	63	2001/06/16	0.723	181.1
24	1997/08/12	0.793	87.5	64	2001/07/22	0.697	205.5
25	1997/09/17	0.813	91.7	65	2001/08/27	0.733	218.5
26	1997/10/23	0.793	93.5	66	2001/10/02	0.780	217.5
27	1997/11/28	0.850	91.5	67	2001/11/07	0.847	221.3
28	1998/01/03	0.833	96.3	68	2001/12/13	0.823	218.1
29	1998/02/08	0.820	104.6	69	2002/01/18	0.820	190.2
30	1998/03/16	0.800	112.1	70	2002/02/23	0.777	184.6
31	1998/04/21	0.780	113.0	71	2002/03/31	0.770	176.3
32	1998/05/27	0.793	124.3	72	2002/05/06	0.787	173.3
33	1998/07/02	0.793	133.5	73	2002/06/11	0.800	174.9
34	1998/08/07	0.853	133.3	74	2002/07/17	0.817	177.7
35	1998/09/12	0.897	131.1	75	2002/08/22	0.820	170.3
36	1998/10/18	0.920	139.9	76	2002/09/27	0.847	161.7
37	1998/11/23	0.913	140.7	77	2002/11/02	0.860	152.5
38	1998/12/29	0.873	132.5	78	2002/12/08	0.850	137.8
39	1999/02/03	0.853	126.1	79	2003/01/13	0.817	130.5
40	1999/03/11	0.853	130.1	80	2003/02/18	0.807	126.6

¹The data given here refers to the 108 day long GONG months as used in Chapter 6.

Table B.4: Continuation of Table B.3

Month	Date	Fill	$F_{10.7}$	Month	Date	Fill	$F_{10.7}$
81	2003/03/26	0.797	128.6	126	2007/09/01	0.927	67.6
82	2003/05/01	0.820	131.9	127	2007/10/07	0.933	70.3
83	2003/06/06	0.837	131.5	128	2007/11/12	0.910	71.8
84	2003/07/12	0.853	123.8	129	2007/12/18	0.867	71.1
85	2003/08/17	0.880	138.3	130	2008/01/23	0.820	70.8
86	2003/09/22	0.890	137.6	131	2008/02/28	0.813	70.9
87	2003/10/28	0.923	122.6	132	2008/04/04	0.817	69.5
88	2003/12/03	0.913	108.9	133	2008/05/10	0.807	68.5
89	2004/01/08	0.877	108.6	134	2008/06/15	0.787	67.8
90	2004/02/13	0.833	105.1	135	2008/07/21	0.830	67.8
91	2004/03/20	0.850	101.4	136	2008/08/26	0.883	67.5
92	2004/04/25	0.853	108.8	137	2008/10/01	0.930	67.2
93	2004/05/31	0.867	112.2	138	2008/11/06	0.903	67.1
94	2004/07/06	0.863	114.0	139	2008/12/12	0.883	67.5
95	2004/08/11	0.870	107.7	140	2009/01/17	0.863	68.9
96	2004/09/16	0.887	103.6	141	2009/02/22	0.857	70.1
97	2004/10/22	0.887	101.7	142	2009/03/30	0.823	70.9
98	2004/11/27	0.887	95.6	143	2009/05/05	0.813	71.0
99	2005/01/02	0.870	94.6	144	2009/06/10	0.840	70.1
100	2005/02/07	0.810	90.2	145	2009/07/16	0.890	70.6
101	2005/03/15	0.830	93.2	146	2009/08/21	0.917	71.6
102	2005/04/20	0.840	101.6	147	2009/09/26	0.930	72.7
103	2005/05/26	0.873	100.6	148	2009/11/01	0.937	75.1
104	2005/07/01	0.877	105.1	149	2009/12/07	0.937	78.6
105	2005/08/06	0.887	95.9	150	2010/01/12	0.927	81.2
106	2005/09/11	0.903	90.5	151	2010/02/17	0.907	77.9
107	2005/10/17	0.913	84.4	152	2010/03/25	0.907	75.4
108	2005/11/22	0.880	81.1	153	2010/04/30	0.903	77.4
109	2005/12/28	0.847	76.7	154	2010/06/05	0.890	79.3
110	2006/02/02	0.850	79.8	155	2010/07/11	0.873	81.7
111	2006/03/10	0.883	82.4	156	2010/08/16	0.853	81.2
112	2006/04/15	0.907	80.0	157	2010/09/21	0.843	81.1
113	2006/05/21	0.910	79.7	158	2010/10/27	0.823	81.0
114	2006/06/26	0.887	79.6	159	2010/12/02	0.837	84.9
115	2006/08/01	0.883	78.1	160	2011/01/07	0.870	98.6
116	2006/09/06	0.860	79.1	161	2011/02/12	0.890	111.4
117	2006/10/12	0.870	82.0	162	2011/03/20	0.887	103.4
118	2006/11/17	0.897	81.5	163	2011/04/25	0.863	98.0
119	2006/12/23	0.907	76.1	164	2011/05/31	0.867	100.2
120	2007/01/28	0.910	73.4	165	2011/07/06	0.870	112.8
121	2007/03/05	0.900	73.4	166	2011/08/11	0.883	125.8
122	2007/04/10	0.890	75.1	167	2011/09/16	0.890	141.3
123	2007/05/16	0.890	73.7	168	2011/10/22	0.897	139.3
124	2007/06/21	0.897	70.8	169	2011/11/27	0.890	123.9
125	2007/07/27	0.923	68.6	170	2012/01/02	0.860	116.4

Table B.5: Continuation of Table B.3

Month	Date	Fill	$F_{10.7}$	Month	Date	Fill	$F_{10.7}$
171	2012/02/07	0.870	111.0	216	2016/07/15	0.843	87.1
172	2012/03/14	0.893	120.8	217	2016/08/20	0.873	83.6
173	2012/04/19	0.910	130.2	218	2016/09/25	0.867	78.5
174	2012/05/25	0.890	128.4	219	2016/10/31	0.880	74.9
175	2012/06/30	0.877	128.6	220	2016/12/06	0.880	74.3
176	2012/08/05	0.890	121.9	221	2017/01/11	0.893	74.7
177	2012/09/10	0.883	121.8	222	2017/02/16	0.893	76.9
178	2012/10/16	0.867	115.4	223	2017/03/24	0.883	78.0
179	2012/11/21	0.867	109.8				
180	2012/12/27	0.887	111.6				
181	2013/02/01	0.900	112.7				
182	2013/03/09	0.897	123.5				
183	2013/04/14	0.887	122.6				
184	2013/05/20	0.883	117.1				
185	2013/06/25	0.890	113.7				
186	2013/07/31	0.887	117.9				
187	2013/09/05	0.893	127.1				
188	2013/10/11	0.887	140.3				
189	2013/11/16	0.893	155.7				
190	2013/12/22	0.890	157.5				
191	2014/01/27	0.890	153.3				
192	2014/03/04	0.907	142.3				
193	2014/04/09	0.910	134.7				
194	2014/05/15	0.900	132.1				
195	2014/06/20	0.860	139.4				
196	2014/07/26	0.830	143.2				
197	2014/08/31	0.830	151.4				
198	2014/10/06	0.870	153.4				
199	2014/11/11	0.920	147.9				
200	2014/12/17	0.913	129.6				
201	2015/01/22	0.877	127.1				
202	2015/02/27	0.840	126.1				
203	2015/04/04	0.843	128.4				
204	2015/05/10	0.817	121.9				
205	2015/06/15	0.813	107.4				
206	2015/07/21	0.760	105.0				
207	2015/08/26	0.807	104.6				
208	2015/10/01	0.833	106.5				
209	2015/11/06	0.910	105.6				
210	2015/12/12	0.913	103.5				
211	2016/01/17	0.897	95.3				
212	2016/02/22	0.880	93.4				
213	2016/03/29	0.843	91.4				
214	2016/05/04	0.827	89.7				
215	2016/06/09	0.827	87.0				

Appendices to Chapter 8

C.1 The Eulerian Perturbation of the Magnetic Field

In ideal magnetohydrodynamics, the induction equation can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}), \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where \mathbf{B} is the magnetic field and \mathbf{u} is the velocity field. We introduce the perturbations

$$\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}_0(\mathbf{r}) + \delta \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (\text{C.2})$$

$$\mathbf{u} \rightarrow \mathbf{u}_0(\mathbf{r}) + \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (\text{C.3})$$

where $\delta \mathbf{B}$ and \mathbf{v} are the Eulerian perturbation to the magnetic field and the velocity field, respectively. The unperturbed magnetic field $\mathbf{B}_0(\mathbf{r})$ is assumed to be static. We neglect large-scale velocity fields here, as we are focusing on the influence of the magnetic field. Hence, the background velocity field $\mathbf{u}_0(\mathbf{r})$ is set to zero. The Eulerian perturbation of the velocity field $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is described as a temporal change in the displacement $\boldsymbol{\xi}$:

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\xi}}{\partial t}. \quad (\text{C.4})$$

Applying Equations (C.2)-(C.4) to Equation (C.1), retaining only terms that are linear in the perturbations, and integrating over time yield the Eulerian perturbation of the magnetic field $\delta \mathbf{B}$:

$$\delta \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \nabla \times (\boldsymbol{\xi}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{B}_0(\mathbf{r})). \quad (\text{C.5})$$

C.2 Mathematical Supplements

In this appendix, we list the vector identities and formulae that were used in the calculation of the general matrix element in Section 8.5 and Appendix C.3, and help the traceability of our derivations. All calculations are done in spherical polar coordinates. In the following, r denotes the radial distance from the origin, θ signifies the colatitude, and ϕ is the azimuthal angle.

Let $\mathbf{A}(r, \theta, \phi)$ and $\mathbf{B}(r, \theta, \phi)$ denote general vector fields. A useful identity for the curl of the

cross-product of two vector fields \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} is given by

$$\nabla \times (\mathbf{A} \times \mathbf{B}) = \mathbf{A} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B}) - \mathbf{B} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A}) + (\mathbf{B} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{A} - (\mathbf{A} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{B}. \quad (\text{C.6})$$

The divergence of a vector field \mathbf{A} is

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial (r^2 A_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (A_\theta \sin \theta) + \frac{1}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial A_\phi}{\partial \phi}, \quad (\text{C.7})$$

and its curl is

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times \mathbf{A} &= \frac{1}{r \sin \theta} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (A_\phi \sin \theta) - \frac{\partial A_\theta}{\partial \phi} \right) \mathbf{e}_r \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial A_r}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r A_\phi) \right) \mathbf{e}_\theta \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r A_\theta) - \frac{\partial A_r}{\partial \theta} \right) \mathbf{e}_\phi. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.8})$$

The material derivative of the vector fields \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} is given by

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{A} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{B} &= \left(A_r \frac{\partial B_r}{\partial r} + \frac{A_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial B_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{A_\phi}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial B_r}{\partial \phi} - \frac{A_\theta B_\theta + A_\phi B_\phi}{r} \right) \mathbf{e}_r \\ &\quad + \left(A_r \frac{\partial B_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{A_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial B_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{A_\phi}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial B_\theta}{\partial \phi} + \frac{A_\theta B_r}{r} - \frac{A_\phi B_\phi \cot \theta}{r} \right) \mathbf{e}_\theta \\ &\quad + \left(A_r \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{A_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{A_\phi}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{A_\phi B_r}{r} + \frac{A_\phi B_\theta \cot \theta}{r} \right) \mathbf{e}_\phi. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.9})$$

C.3 Calculation of the General Matrix Element

In this appendix, we derive the explicit expression for the general matrix element in spherical coordinates. We start from the Lagrangian perturbation of the Lorentz force:

$$\begin{aligned} &\rho_0 \Delta \left(\frac{1}{c\rho} \mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{B} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \left(((\nabla \times \delta \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B}_0) + ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_0) \times \delta \mathbf{B}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (\boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla) ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_0) \times \mathbf{B}_0) + (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}) ((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_0) \times \mathbf{B}_0) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.10})$$

where Equations (8.2) and (8.21), in which the Lagrangian perturbation Δ and the electric current \mathbf{j} are defined, have been used, and Equation (C.5) for the Eulerian perturbation of the magnetic field $\delta \mathbf{B}$ holds. Before applying the Lagrangian perturbation to the Lorentz force, we divided by ρ only to multiply by ρ_0 afterwards. Due to the Lagrangian perturbation of $1/\rho$, a term with a factor of $-\Delta\rho/\rho_0$ appears. This term was rewritten by virtue of the Lagrangian perturbation of the density $\Delta\rho = -\rho_0 \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}$, which can be derived by linearizing the perturbed equation of mass conservation. Furthermore, c is the speed of light and $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ is an eigenfunction.

We restrict the magnetic field to be of toroidal shape but do not yet specify the exact configura-

tion:

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}_{\text{tor}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ B_\phi(r, \theta, 0) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{C.11})$$

By applying Equations (C.5), (C.6)-(C.9), and (C.11) to Equation (C.10), we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{4\pi} \left[(\nabla \times (\nabla \times (\boldsymbol{\xi} \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{tor}}))) \times \hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{tor}} + (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{tor}}) \times (\nabla \times (\boldsymbol{\xi} \times \hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{tor}})) \right. \\ & \left. + (\boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \nabla) \left((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{tor}}) \times \hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{tor}} \right) + (\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}) \left((\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_{\text{tor}}) \times \hat{\mathbf{B}}_{\text{tor}} \right) \right] \\ = & \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ \left[\left[\frac{2\hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} + 2\hat{B}_\phi \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{2\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} + \hat{B}_\phi B_\phi \frac{\partial^2 \xi_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \xi_\theta}{\partial r \partial \theta} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 \xi_r}{\partial \phi^2} + \hat{B}_\phi \xi_r \frac{\partial^2 B_\phi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial^2 B_\phi}{\partial r \partial \theta} \right] \mathbf{e}_r \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_\theta \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{2\hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi \xi_r \cot \theta}{r^2} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi \cot \theta}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \xi_r}{\partial r \partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi B_\phi}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 \xi_\theta}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r} \frac{\partial^2 B_\phi}{\partial r \partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_r \cot \theta}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_\theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 B_\phi}{\partial \theta^2} \right] \mathbf{e}_\theta \right\} \\ & + \left\{ \left[\hat{B}_\phi \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \xi_r \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\xi_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial \theta} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} + \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r^2} + \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\xi_r B_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\xi_\theta B_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial \theta} \right] \mathbf{e}_r \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} + \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta \xi_r}{r^2} + \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{B_\phi \cot \theta \xi_r}{r} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{B_\phi \xi_\theta \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial \theta} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\xi_r}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\xi_\theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial \theta} \right] \mathbf{e}_\theta \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \phi} + \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial \phi} + \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial \phi} \right] \mathbf{e}_\phi \right\} \\ & + \left\{ \left[\frac{\xi_r B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} - \frac{\xi_r B_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{\xi_r \hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} - \xi_r \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} - \xi_r \hat{B}_\phi \frac{\partial^2 B_\phi}{\partial r^2} - \frac{\xi_\theta B_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial \theta} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{\xi_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{\xi_\theta \hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial^2 B_\phi}{\partial r \partial \theta} + \frac{\xi_\theta B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2} \right] \mathbf{e}_r \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\frac{\xi_r B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2} - \frac{\xi_r B_\phi \cot \theta}{r} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{\xi_r \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\xi_r \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\xi_r}{r} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{\xi_r \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 B_\phi}{\partial r \partial \theta} - \frac{\xi_\theta B_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\xi_\theta \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\xi_\theta \hat{B}_\phi B_\phi \cot^2 \theta}{r^2} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{\xi_\theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial \hat{B}_\phi}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\xi_\theta \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 B_\phi}{\partial \theta^2} - \frac{\xi_\theta \hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} \right] \mathbf{e}_\theta \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left[-\frac{\xi_\phi B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} - \frac{\xi_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{\xi_\phi B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot^2 \theta}{r^2} - \frac{\xi_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} \right] \mathbf{e}_\phi \Big\} \\
& + \left\{ \left[-\frac{2B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r^2} - \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} - \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} - \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \xi_\theta \cot \theta}{r^2} - \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_\phi}{\partial \phi} \right. \right. \\
& - \frac{2\hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} - \hat{B}_\phi \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} - \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_\theta \cot \theta}{r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} - \left. \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r \sin \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_\phi}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial r} \right] \mathbf{e}_r \\
& + \left[-\frac{2B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \xi_r \cot \theta}{r^2} - \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} - \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} - \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \xi_\theta \cot^2 \theta}{r^2} - \frac{B_\phi \hat{B}_\phi \cot \theta}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_\phi}{\partial \phi} \right. \\
& \left. \left. - \frac{2\hat{B}_\phi \xi_r}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r} \frac{\partial \xi_r}{\partial r} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r^2} \frac{\partial \xi_\theta}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\hat{B}_\phi \xi_\theta \cot \theta}{r^2} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\hat{B}_\phi}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial \xi_\phi}{\partial \phi} \frac{\partial B_\phi}{\partial \theta} \right] \right\} \mathbf{e}_\theta. \tag{C.12}
\end{aligned}$$

In this step, we kept the four terms from Equation (C.10) separated and marked them off with curly brackets. We also applied the notation for the magnetic field from Section 8.5.

The magnetic field components B_ϕ and \hat{B}_ϕ are replaced by their representation

$$B_\phi = a(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0}(\theta, \phi), \tag{C.13}$$

$$\hat{B}_\phi = \hat{a}(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0}(\theta, \phi), \tag{C.14}$$

and the components of the eigenfunctions are expressed as given by Equation (8.12).

In the next step, the eigenfunction $\bar{\xi}_{l',m'}(r, \theta, \phi)$, where the bar denotes complex conjugation, is multiplied from the left, and the integral over the whole stellar volume is applied. As the radial and horizontal displacement amplitudes are purely real, the complex conjugation on them can be dropped: $\bar{\xi}^r(r) = \hat{\xi}^r(r)$, $\bar{\xi}^h(r) = \hat{\xi}^h(r)$. Then, terms that carry only a radial dependence are separated from those with an angular dependence. Terms with identical angular dependence can be factored out and summarized. After all of these steps, we finally arrive at Equation (8.31). The factors with an angular dependence, \mathcal{T}_i , with $i = 1, \dots, 25$, which appear in that equation, are listed in Appendix C.7.

C.4 The Generalized Spherical Harmonics and Their Properties

The generalized spherical harmonics can be used to expand tensor fields of any order. Here, they are employed in the representation of the eigenfunctions and the toroidal magnetic fields as given in Equations (8.12), (8.29), and (8.30). We follow the conventions for the generalized spherical harmonics of Dahlen and Tromp (1998), who largely build upon the notation and sign conventions from Phinney and Burridge (1973).

The scalar generalized spherical harmonics are defined by

$$Y_l^{N,m} = \gamma_l P_{lm}^N(\cos \theta) e^{im\phi}, \tag{C.15}$$

where $\gamma_l = \sqrt{(2l+1)/4\pi}$ and $P_{lm}^N(\cos \theta)$ are the generalized Legendre functions. In this convention, $Y_l^m = Y_l^{0,m}$ holds, where Y_l^m is an ordinary spherical harmonic function of degree l and azimuthal order m .

We collect all identities and relations of the generalized spherical harmonics, which are needed in the calculation of the matrix element $H_{k'k}$, especially in the calculation of volume integrals over products of these functions; see Appendix C.6 and C.7.

The generalized spherical harmonics satisfy the recursion relation

$$\frac{N \cos \theta - m}{\sin \theta} Y_l^{N,m} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\Omega_{N+1}^l Y_l^{N+1,m} + \Omega_N^l Y_l^{N-1,m} \right), \quad (\text{C.16})$$

with

$$\Omega_N^l = \sqrt{\frac{(l+N)(l-N+1)}{2}}. \quad (\text{C.17})$$

The colatitudinal derivative of $Y_l^{N,m}$ can be expressed in terms of $Y_l^{N\pm 1,m}$:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{N,m} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\Omega_N^l Y_l^{N-1,m} - \Omega_{N+1}^l Y_l^{N+1,m} \right). \quad (\text{C.18})$$

From Equation (C.15), it can be seen that the azimuthal derivative is given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} Y_l^{N,m} = im Y_l^{N,m}. \quad (\text{C.19})$$

Higher colatitudinal and azimuthal derivatives can easily be constructed by an iterative application of Equation (C.18)-(C.19). For example, the second colatitudinal derivative of $Y_l^{N,m}$ is given by

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_l^{N,m} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\Omega_N^l \Omega_{N-1}^l Y_l^{N-2,m} - \Omega_N^l \Omega_N^l Y_l^{N,m} - \Omega_{N+1}^l \Omega_{N+1}^l Y_l^{N,m} + \Omega_{N+1}^l \Omega_{N+2}^l Y_l^{N+2,m} \right). \quad (\text{C.20})$$

The complex conjugate of the $Y_l^{N,m}$ is

$$\overline{Y_l^{N,m}} = (-1)^{-N-m} Y_l^{-N,-m}. \quad (\text{C.21})$$

C.4.1 Elimination of Trigonometric Functions

Derivatives and trigonometric functions appear in the calculation of the angular integral of the angle-dependent factors of the matrix element; see Appendix C.7. The derivatives can be expressed via relations (C.18) and (C.21), and their iterative application. The trigonometric functions can be rewritten in terms of generalized spherical harmonics with the help of Equation (C.16). Setting one of the upper indices equal to zero yields a relation for eliminating a factor $\sin^{-1} \theta$ (if $N = 0$) or for eliminating a factor $\cot \theta$ (if $m = 0$).

Two more useful relations can be obtained by taking the colatitudinal derivative of the recursion relation (C.16), which yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(-\frac{N}{\sin^2 \theta} + \frac{m \cot \theta}{\sin \theta} \right) Y_l^{N,m} + \left(\frac{N \cot \theta}{\sqrt{2}} - \frac{m}{\sqrt{2} \sin \theta} \right) \left(\Omega_N^l Y_l^{N-1,m} - \Omega_{N+1}^l Y_l^{N+1,m} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\Omega_{N+1}^l \Omega_{N+1}^l Y_l^{N,m} - \Omega_{N+1}^l \Omega_{N+2}^l Y_l^{N+2,m} + \Omega_N^l \Omega_{N-1}^l Y_l^{N-2,m} - \Omega_N^l \Omega_N^l Y_l^{N,m} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.22})$$

By setting $N = 0$ in Equation (C.22) and using $Y_1^{1,0} = \gamma_1 P_1^{1,0} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4\pi}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sin \theta$, we obtain

$$m \cot \theta Y_l^{0,m} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{3}} \Omega_0^l \Omega_2^l \left(-Y_l^{2,m} Y_1^{1,0} + Y_l^{-2,m} Y_1^{1,0} \right) + \frac{m}{\sqrt{2}} \Omega_0^l \left(Y_l^{-1,m} - Y_l^{1,m} \right). \quad (\text{C.23})$$

By setting $m = 0$ in Equation (C.22) and using $Y_1^{0,0} = \gamma_1 P_1^{0,0} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{4\pi}} \cos \theta$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N}{\sin \theta} Y_l^{N,0} = & -\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{3}} \left(\Omega_{N+1}^l \Omega_{N+1}^l Y_l^{N,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_{N+1}^l \Omega_{N+2}^l Y_l^{N+2,0} Y_1^{1,0} \right. \\ & \left. + \Omega_N^l \Omega_{N-1}^l Y_l^{N-2,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_N^l \Omega_N^l Y_l^{N,0} Y_1^{1,0} \right) \\ & + N \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{3}} \left(\Omega_N^l Y_l^{N-1,0} Y_1^{0,0} - \Omega_{N+1}^l Y_l^{N+1,0} Y_1^{0,0} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.24})$$

C.5 The Wigner $3j$ Symbol

The Wigner $3j$ symbols are maximally symmetrized representations of the Clebsch-Gordon coefficients. They represent the coupling of three angular momenta to a resultant zero momentum (Racah 1942; Edmonds 1960). The most symmetrical form to calculate them is

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l_3 \\ m_1 & m_2 & m_3 \end{pmatrix} = & (-1)^{l_2+l_3+m_1} \frac{\sqrt{(l_1+l_2-l_3)! (l_1-l_2+l_3)! (-l_1+l_2+l_3)!}}{\sqrt{(l_1+l_2+l_3+1)!}} \\ & \cdot \sqrt{(l_1+m_1)! (l_1-m_1)! (l_2+m_2)! (l_2-m_2)! (l_3+m_3)! (l_3-m_3)!} \sum_k \frac{(-1)^k}{D_k}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.25})$$

where $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ runs over all values for which $D_k \neq 0$ with

$$D_k = k! (-l_1 + l_2 + l_3 - k)! (l_2 - m_2 - k)! (l_3 + m_3 - k)! (l_1 - l_2 - m_3 + k)! (l_1 - l_3 + m_2 + k)!. \quad (\text{C.26})$$

In general, l_i and m_i can be integers or half-integers. In this work, l_i are always non-negative integers and m_i are integers in the range $-l_i \leq m_i \leq l_i$.

We list only those properties of the Wigner $3j$ symbols that are useful in the calculation of the general matrix element $H_{k'k}$. More extensive lists can be found in, e.g., Dahlen and Tromp (1998), Edmonds (1960), and Regge (1958).

The numerical value of a $3j$ symbol is unchanged under an even permutation of its columns:

$$\begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l_3 \\ m_1 & m_2 & m_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} l_2 & l_3 & l_1 \\ m_2 & m_3 & m_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} l_3 & l_1 & l_2 \\ m_3 & m_1 & m_2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{C.27})$$

An odd permutation of its columns is equivalent to multiplication by $(-1)^{l_1+l_2+l_3}$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} l_2 & l_1 & l_3 \\ m_2 & m_1 & m_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_3 & l_2 \\ m_1 & m_3 & m_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} l_3 & l_2 & l_1 \\ m_3 & m_2 & m_1 \end{pmatrix} = (-1)^{l_1+l_2+l_3} \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l_3 \\ m_1 & m_2 & m_3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{C.28})$$

Selection rules for the allowed ranges of the l_i can be constructed from the following properties:

$$\begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l_3 \\ m_1 & m_2 & m_3 \end{pmatrix} = 0, \text{ if } m_1 = m_2 = m_3 = 0 \text{ and } l_1 + l_2 + l_3 \text{ is odd,} \quad (\text{C.29})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l_3 \\ m_1 & m_2 & m_3 \end{pmatrix} \neq 0, \text{ only if } \begin{cases} m_1 + m_2 + m_3 = 0, & (\text{C.30a}) \\ \text{and } |m_i| \leq l_i \text{ for } i = 1, 2, 3, & (\text{C.30b}) \\ \text{and } |l_i - l_j| \leq l_k \text{ for } i, j, k = 1, 2, 3. & (\text{C.30c}) \end{cases}$$

C.6 Integral of the Products of Generalized Spherical Harmonics on the Unit Sphere

To calculate the analytical expression of the general matrix element, it is necessary to integrate the product of four, five, and six generalized spherical harmonics. In [Dahlen and Tromp \(1998\)](#), it is shown that the integral of a product of three generalized spherical harmonics on the unit sphere can be written as

$$\int \overline{Y_l^{N,m}} Y_{l_1}^{N_1, m_1} Y_{l_2}^{N_2, m_2} d\Omega = 4\pi (-1)^{N+m} \gamma_l \gamma_{l_1} \gamma_{l_2} \begin{pmatrix} l & l_1 & l_2 \\ -N & N_1 & N_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l & l_1 & l_2 \\ -m & m_1 & m_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{C.31})$$

where $\gamma_k = \sqrt{(2k+1)/4\pi}$.

The product of two generalized spherical harmonics is given by

$$Y_{l_1}^{N_1, m_1} Y_{l_2}^{N_2, m_2} = \sum_{l, N, m} 4\pi (-1)^{N+m} \gamma_l \gamma_{l_1} \gamma_{l_2} \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l \\ N_1 & N_2 & -N \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l \\ m_1 & m_2 & -m \end{pmatrix} Y_l^{N, m}. \quad (\text{C.32})$$

We can use Equations (C.31)-(C.32) to calculate the integral over four generalized spherical harmonics:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int \overline{Y_{l_1}^{N_1, m_1}} Y_{l_2}^{N_2, m_2} Y_{l_3}^{N_3, m_3} Y_{l_4}^{N_4, m_4} d\Omega \\ &= 4\pi \gamma_{l_1} \gamma_{l_2} \gamma_{l_3} \gamma_{l_4} \sum_{l, N, m} (-1)^{N+N_1+m+m_1} (2l+1) \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l \\ -N_1 & N_2 & N \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & l_2 & l \\ -m_1 & m_2 & m \end{pmatrix} \\ & \cdot \begin{pmatrix} l_3 & l_4 & l \\ N_3 & N_4 & -N \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} l_3 & l_4 & l \\ m_3 & m_4 & -m \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.33})$$

The sum extends over all values of l , N , and m , which are allowed according to Equations (C.30a)-(C.30c).

By employing Equation (C.30a), we can deduce two useful conditions for the indices of the four generalized spherical harmonics in Equation (C.33) if the integral shall not vanish:

$$N_1 = \sum_{i>1} N_i, \quad (\text{C.34})$$

$$m_1 = \sum_{i>1} m_i. \quad (\text{C.35})$$

By iterative application of Equations (C.31)-(C.33), also integrals over products of five, six, or any

number of generalized spherical harmonics can also be calculated. Conditions (C.34) and (C.35) also hold for integrals over products with more than four generalized spherical harmonics.

C.7 The Angular Kernels for Toroidal Magnetic Fields

In the general matrix element, given by Equation (8.31), we factored out the parts that hold an angular dependence. These factors are given by the generalized spherical harmonic functions from the two eigenfunctions and the two magnetic field components, which appear in the Lorentz force. They also contain trigonometric functions, which appear due to the derivatives in spherical geometry, and derivatives acting on the generalized spherical harmonics. In this list, we include the factors \mathcal{T}_{13} - \mathcal{T}_{16} and \mathcal{T}_{21} . In our derivations, they appear for individual terms during the steps outlined in Appendix C.3 but cancel along the way to the final result. We chose to list them here, because they may be of interest for studies that focus on the Eulerian perturbation of the Lorentz force or if poloidal magnetic fields are included. The individual factors are given by

$$\mathcal{T}_1 = \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.36})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_2 = \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.37})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_3 = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.38})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_4 = \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.39})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_5 = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.40})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_6 = \cot \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.41})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_7 = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.42})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_8 = \cot \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.43})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_9 = \cot \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.44})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{10} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.45})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{11} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^3} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.46})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{12} = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.47})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{13} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial \theta^3} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.48})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{14} = \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.49})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{15} = \cot \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.50})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{16} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.51})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{17} = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta \partial \phi} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.52})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{18} = \frac{\cot \theta}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta \partial \phi} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.53})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{19} = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.54})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{20} = \cot \theta \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.55})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{21} = \cot^2 \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.56})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{22} = \frac{\cot^2 \theta}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.57})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{23} = \frac{\cot \theta}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.58})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{24} = \frac{\cot \theta}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.59})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_{25} = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m'}} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} Y_l^{0,m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \quad (\text{C.60})$$

As the integral in Equation (8.31) extends over the whole volume and we were able to separate the radial from the angular parts, we can carry out the radial and angular integrals individually. In the following, we give the explicit expressions for the angular kernels (C.36)-(C.60). In the derivation of Equations (C.62)-(C.86), Equations (C.16)-(C.20) and (C.24) are used to eliminate the derivatives of the generalized spherical harmonics and the trigonometric functions. We utilize selection rule (C.34) to eliminate terms whose angular integral is equal to zero for any combination of harmonic degrees and azimuthal orders of the eigenfunctions and the magnetic field components. To ease readability, we use that

$$\Omega_{-N}^l = \Omega_{N+1}^l, \quad (\text{C.61})$$

which can be seen from Equation (C.17). Also, we set $m' = m$, which is required by Equation (C.35). With all these, we find after considerable but straightforward algebra

$$\mathcal{T}_1 = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \right) \quad (\text{C.62})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_2 = & \frac{1}{4} \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^l \left(\Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{-2,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + 2 \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right. \\ & \left. + 2 \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{2,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.63})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_3 = & -\frac{1}{4} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \left(\overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} - \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right. \\ & - \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} - \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \\ & \left. - \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.64})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_4 = & \frac{1}{4} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \left(\Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + 2 \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right. \\ & \left. + 2 \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.65})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_5 = & -\frac{1}{4} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \left(2 \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right. \\ & \left. + \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + 2 \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.66})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_6 = \frac{1}{8} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \left(4 \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0}
\end{aligned} \tag{C.67}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_7 = & \frac{1}{8} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \left(\Omega_2^s \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-2,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-2,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right. \\
& + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{2,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-2,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& \left. + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{2,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{2,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{C.68}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_8 = & \frac{1}{4} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \left(-2\Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} + \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} \right. \\
& \left. + \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} - 2\Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{C.69}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_9 = & \frac{1}{8} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \left(2\Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} - \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{2,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} \right. \\
& + \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{2,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} + \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-2,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \\
& - 2\Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} + 2\Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{2,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} - \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-2,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} - 2\Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{2,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} + \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-2,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \\
& \left. - \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-2,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} + 2\Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{0,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{C.70}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{10} = & -\frac{1}{4} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \left(\overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \right. \\
& + \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& \left. + \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{C.71}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{11} = & \frac{1}{8} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \left(2\Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^l \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \right. \\
& + \Omega_2^l \Omega_3^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{3,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^l \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + 2\Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^l \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^l \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + 2\Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^l \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + \Omega_2^l \Omega_3^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-3,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& \left. + \Omega_2^l \Omega_2^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + 2\Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{C.72}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{12} = & \frac{-m^2}{4} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^l \left(4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \right. \\
& - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& \left. - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{1,0} Y_1^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_3^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-3,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_3^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-3,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{1,0} Y_1^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} Y_1^{0,0} \Big) \quad (C.73)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{13} = & \frac{1}{8} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^{l'} \Omega_0^l \left(2\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \right. \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_3^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{3,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_3^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-3,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} \\
& \left. + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} \right) \quad (C.74)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{14} = & \frac{1}{4} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \left(\Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} + 2\Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \right. \\
& \left. + 2\Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} + \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{0,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} \right) \quad (C.75)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{15} = & \frac{1}{8} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^{l'} \Omega_0^l \left(4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \right. \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& \left. - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \right) \quad (C.76)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{16} = & \frac{1}{8} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^{l'} \Omega_0^l \left(\Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \right. \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} \\
& \left. + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \right) \quad (C.77)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{17} = & -\frac{m}{4} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{3}} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^{l'} \\
& \times \left(-2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \right. \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{0,0} + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{3,0} Y_1^{1,0} + \Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& \left. - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0}
\end{aligned} \tag{C.83}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{23} = & \frac{1}{8} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^{l'} \left(-2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \right. \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} \\
& \left. + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{C.84}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{24} = & -\frac{m}{4} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{3}} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^{l'} \\
& \times \left(2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{0,0} \right. \\
& + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{0,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{0,0} + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} - 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{3,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& \left. - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{0,0} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{C.85}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{T}_{25} = & \frac{m}{4} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{3}} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \Omega_0^{l'} \\
& \times \left(2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \right. \\
& - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& - 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& \left. + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{-1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{0,0} + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^l \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} - 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} - 4\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-3,0} Y_1^{1,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-2,0} Y_1^{0,0} \\
& - 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_2^s \Omega_0^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{2,0} Y_{s'}^{0,0} Y_1^{0,0} - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& - \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{0,0} + \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \Omega_3^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{-2,0} Y_{s'}^{3,0} Y_1^{1,0} \\
& + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \Omega_2^{s'} \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0} Y_1^{1,0} + 2\Omega_0^s \Omega_2^s \overline{Y_{l'}^{1,m}} Y_l^{-1,m} Y_s^{0,0} Y_{s'}^{2,0} Y_1^{0,0} \Big) \tag{C.86}
\end{aligned}$$

Appendices to Chapter 9

D.1 Decomposition of a Real-Valued Vector Field

In order to expand the Lorentz force in terms of spherical harmonics, we use that every real vector field \mathbf{u} can be expanded in terms of vector spherical harmonics (Dahlen and Tromp 1998):

$$\mathbf{u} = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \mathcal{R}_l^m \mathbf{Y}_l^m + \mathcal{S}_l^m \mathbf{\Psi}_l^m - \mathcal{T}_l^m \mathbf{\Phi}_l^m. \quad (\text{D.1})$$

The vector spherical harmonics, which are complete, are defined by

$$\mathbf{Y}_l^m = Y_l^m \mathbf{e}_r, \quad (\text{D.2})$$

$$\mathbf{\Psi}_l^m = r \nabla Y_l^m = \left(\mathbf{e}_\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + \mathbf{e}_\phi \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \right) Y_l^m, \quad (\text{D.3})$$

$$\mathbf{\Phi}_l^m = \mathbf{r} \times \nabla Y_l^m = \mathbf{e}_r \times \mathbf{\Psi}_l^m = \left(-\mathbf{e}_\theta \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} + \mathbf{e}_\phi \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) Y_l^m, \quad (\text{D.4})$$

where l is the harmonic degree, m is the azimuthal order with $-m \leq l \leq m$, Y_l^m is a spherical harmonic function, and we work in spherical geometry with the coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) radius, co-latitude, and azimuth. The vector spherical harmonic coefficients in Equation (D.1) are given by

$$\mathcal{R}_l^m = \int \overline{\mathbf{Y}_l^m} \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega, \quad (\text{D.5})$$

$$\mathcal{S}_l^m = \frac{1}{l(l+1)} \int \overline{\mathbf{\Psi}_l^m} \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega, \quad (\text{D.6})$$

$$\mathcal{T}_l^m = -\frac{1}{l(l+1)} \int \overline{\mathbf{\Phi}_l^m} \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega. \quad (\text{D.7})$$

With Equations (D.1)–(D.7), the components of the vector field \mathbf{u} are calculated as

$$u_r(r, \theta, \phi) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \mathcal{R}_l^m(r) Y_l^m(\theta, \phi), \quad (\text{D.8})$$

$$u_\theta(r, \theta, \phi) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \mathcal{S}_l^m(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^m(\theta, \phi) + \mathcal{T}_l^m(r) \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} Y_l^m(\theta, \phi), \quad (\text{D.9})$$

$$u_\phi(r, \theta, \phi) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \mathcal{S}_l^m(r) \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} Y_l^m(\theta, \phi) - \mathcal{T}_l^m(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_l^m(\theta, \phi), \quad (\text{D.10})$$

D.2 Expansion of the Lorentz Force

The Lorentz force, see Equation (9.11), for the toroidal configuration defined in Equation (9.12), is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{\text{tor}} = & -\frac{1}{4\pi} \left[\frac{a\hat{a}}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 + \hat{a} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 \right] \mathbf{e}_r \\ & -\frac{1}{4\pi} \left[\frac{a\hat{a}}{r} \cot \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 + \frac{a\hat{a}}{r} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_{s'}^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \right] \mathbf{e}_\theta, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.11})$$

where a and \hat{a} are the radial profiles of the two magnetic field component, which are superposed. All dependencies were dropped. The Lorentz force (D.11) will now be projected onto the vector spherical harmonics, as defined in Equations (D.8)–(D.10). Each vector component is treated separately.

D.2.1 The Radial Component

We concentrate on one magnetic field configuration with indices s, s' , which is indicated by including the indices s, s' to the notation of the vector spherical harmonic coefficients, e.g., $\mathcal{R}_{s,s',l}^m$. Calculating the sum over different configurations in Equation (D.22) then yields the total effect of the superposition.

With Equation (D.8), the radial component of the Lorentz force can be written as

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{tor},r}(r, \theta, \phi) = \sum_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\mu=-\lambda}^{\lambda} \mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}^{\mu}(r) Y_{\lambda}^{\mu}(\theta, \phi) \mathbf{e}_r, \quad (\text{D.12})$$

where the vector spherical harmonic coefficient are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}^{\mu}(r) &= \int \overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{\lambda}^{\mu} \cdot \mathbf{F} d\Omega \\ &\stackrel{(\text{D.2})}{=} \int \overline{Y}_{\lambda}^{\mu} \mathbf{e}_r \cdot \mathbf{F} d\Omega \\ &\stackrel{(\text{D.11})}{=} \int \overline{Y}_{\lambda}^{\mu} \left(-\frac{1}{4\pi} \left[\frac{a\hat{a}}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 + \hat{a} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 \right] \right) d\Omega \\ &= -\frac{1}{4\pi} \left(\frac{a\hat{a}}{r} + \hat{a} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \right) \int \overline{Y}_{\lambda}^{\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 d\Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.13})$$

We define the angular kernel

$$\mathcal{A}_1 = \overline{Y}_{\lambda}^{0,\mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^{0,0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^{0,0}, \quad (\text{D.14})$$

where we used that $Y_l^{0,m} = Y_l^m$, see Dahlen and Tromp (1998). The relations for the generalized spherical harmonics we use here can be found in Appendix C.4. With Equation (C.18), we can

write

$$\mathcal{A}_1 = \frac{1}{2} \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \left(\overline{Y_\lambda^{0,\mu} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0}} - \overline{Y_\lambda^{0,\mu} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{-1,0}} - \overline{Y_\lambda^{0,\mu} Y_s^{-1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0}} + \overline{Y_\lambda^{0,\mu} Y_s^{1,0} Y_{s'}^{1,0}} \right). \quad (\text{D.15})$$

The angular integral over the product of three generalized spherical harmonics can be calculated with help of Equation (C.198) of [Dahlen and Tromp \(1998\)](#). Making use of the properties of the Wigner 3j symbols (C.30a)–(C.30a), we find that $\mu = 0$, as otherwise the angular integral vanishes. It can also be seen that the integrals over the first and last term in the bracket in Equation (D.15) always vanish due to Equation (C.30a). We thus find

$$\mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) = \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \gamma_\lambda \gamma_s \gamma_{s'} \left(\frac{a\hat{a}}{r} + \hat{a} \frac{\partial a}{\partial r} \right) \begin{pmatrix} s & s' & \lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} s & s' & \lambda \\ 1 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{D.16})$$

where we made use of Equations (C.27) and (C.28) and we dropped the upper index on \mathcal{R} as $\mu = 0$ always holds.

D.2.2 The Azimuthal and Colatitudinal Components

Carrying out the same procedure for the azimuthal component as for the radial part leads to $\mu = 0$. With Equations (D.4), (D.10), and (D.11), we find that $\mathcal{T}_\lambda^0 = 0$ and hence $\mathbf{F}_{\text{tor},\phi} = 0$, as can be expected from Equation (D.11). It remains to explicitly calculate the colatitudinal component of the Lorentz force:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{tor},\theta} = \sum_{\lambda=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_\lambda^0 \mathbf{e}_\theta, \quad (\text{D.17})$$

where the vector spherical harmonic coefficient is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}^0(r) &= \frac{1}{\lambda(\lambda+1)} \int \overline{\boldsymbol{\Psi}} \cdot \mathbf{F} d\Omega \\ &\stackrel{(\text{D.3})}{=} \frac{1}{\lambda(\lambda+1)} \int \left(\mathbf{e}_\theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + \mathbf{e}_\phi \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \right) \overline{Y_\lambda^0} \cdot \mathbf{F} d\Omega \\ &\stackrel{(\text{D.11})}{=} \frac{1}{\lambda(\lambda+1)} \int \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_\lambda^0} \left(-\frac{1}{4\pi} \left[\frac{a\hat{a}}{r} \cot \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 + \frac{a\hat{a}}{r} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 \right] \right) d\Omega \\ &= -\frac{a\hat{a}}{4\pi\lambda(\lambda+1)r} \int \left(\cot \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_\lambda^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 + \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_\lambda^0} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0 \right) d\Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.18})$$

We define the two angular kernels

$$\mathcal{A}_2 = \cot \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_\lambda^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0, \quad (\text{D.19})$$

$$\mathcal{A}_3 = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \overline{Y_\lambda^0} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} Y_s^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_{s'}^0. \quad (\text{D.20})$$

The following properties and equations are then used to obtain the vector spherical harmonic coefficient: Equation (C.18) to evaluate the colatitudinal derivatives; Equation (C.16) with $m = 0$ to absorb the factor $\cot \theta$ in the kernel \mathcal{A}_2 ; Equation (C.198) from [Dahlen and Tromp \(1998\)](#) to evaluate the angular integral in Equation (D.18); properties (C.27)–(C.30c) of the Wigner 3j

symbols. With all of this, we find

$$\mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) = -\Omega_0^s \Omega_0^s \Omega_0^{s'} \gamma_\lambda \gamma_s \gamma_{s'} \frac{a\hat{a}}{\sqrt{2}r} \begin{pmatrix} s & s' & \lambda \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} s & s' & \lambda \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{D.21})$$

where we dropped the upper index on \mathcal{S} as $\mu = 0$ always holds.

The complete Lorentz force vector for a superposition of toroidal magnetic fields can thus be written as

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{tor}}(r, \theta) = \sum_{s,s'} \sum_{\lambda=0}^{s+s'} \left(\mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) Y_\lambda^0(\theta) \mathbf{e}_r + \mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} Y_\lambda^0(\theta) \mathbf{e}_\theta \right), \quad (\text{D.22})$$

where the second summation extends over all even values between 0 and $s + s'$ due to properties of the Wigner $3j$ symbols (C.28) and (C.30c).

D.3 The Sensitivity Kernels

We reproduce the sensitivity kernels presented in Lively and Ritzwoller (1992), Section (6c), which appear in the general matrix element for the indirect effect given in Equation (9.22):¹

$$F(r) = r^{-1} \left(2\xi^r - l(l+1)\xi^h \right), \quad (\text{D.23})$$

$$F'(r) = r^{-1} \left(2\hat{\xi}^r - l'(l'+1)\hat{\xi}^h \right), \quad (\text{D.24})$$

$$K_\lambda(r) = \left(\frac{\partial \hat{\xi}^r}{\partial r} + F' \right) \left(\frac{\partial \xi^r}{\partial r} + F \right) B_{l'\lambda l}^{(0)+}, \quad (\text{D.25})$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_\lambda^{(1)}(r) &= \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 r^{-1} \left(\xi^r \frac{\partial \hat{\xi}^h}{\partial r} + r^{-1} \xi^r \hat{\xi}^h - \frac{\partial \xi^r}{\partial r} \hat{\xi}^h - 2F \hat{\xi}^h \right) B_{l'l\lambda}^{(1)+} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 r^{-1} \left(\hat{\xi}^r \frac{\partial \xi^h}{\partial r} + r^{-1} \hat{\xi}^r \xi^h - \frac{\partial \hat{\xi}^r}{\partial r} \xi^h - 2F' \xi^h \right) B_{l'l\lambda}^{(1)+} + \rho_0 r^{-2} \xi^r \hat{\xi}^r \lambda (\lambda + 1) B_{l'\lambda l}^{(0)+}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.26})$$

$$G_\lambda^{(2)}(r) = \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 r^{-1} \xi^r \hat{\xi}^h B_{l'l\lambda}^{(1)+} + \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 r^{-1} \hat{\xi}^r \xi^h B_{l'l\lambda}^{(1)+} - \rho_0 \left(F' \xi^r + \hat{\xi}^r F \right) B_{l'\lambda l}^{(0)+}, \quad (\text{D.27})$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_\lambda^{(1)}(r) &= \left[-\omega_{\text{ref}}^2 \xi^h \hat{\xi}^h + r^{-1} \left(\delta\varphi' \xi^h + \delta\varphi \hat{\xi}^h \right) + \frac{1}{2} g_0 r^{-1} \left(\hat{\xi}^r \xi^h + \xi^h \hat{\xi}^r \right) \right] B_{l'\lambda l}^{(1)+} \\ &\quad + \left[8\pi G \rho_0 \xi^r \hat{\xi}^r + \frac{\partial \delta\varphi'}{\partial r} \xi^r + \frac{\partial \delta\varphi}{\partial r} \hat{\xi}^r - \omega_{\text{ref}}^2 \xi^r \hat{\xi}^r - \frac{1}{2} g_0 \left(4r^{-1} \xi^r \hat{\xi}^r + \hat{\xi}^r F + \xi^r F' \right) \right] B_{l'\lambda l}^{(0)+}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.28})$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_\lambda^{(2)}(r) &= R_\lambda^{(1)}(r) + \frac{4\pi G}{2\lambda + 1} \left\{ r^\lambda \int_r^{R_\odot} r^{-\lambda} \left[(\lambda + 1) G_\lambda^{(2)}(r) - r G_\lambda^{(1)}(r) \right] dr \right. \\ &\quad \left. - r^{-\lambda-1} \int_0^r r^{\lambda+1} \left[\lambda G_\lambda^{(2)}(r) + r G_\lambda^{(1)}(r) \right] dr \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.29})$$

¹We corrected two mistakes compared to Lively and Ritzwoller (1992): In Equation (D.28) we added a factor ξ^r to the second term in the second square bracket and in Equation (D.29) we corrected the factor before the first integral from r^2 to r^λ .

where $K_\lambda(r)$ is the bulk modulus perturbation kernel and $R_\lambda^{(2)}(r)$ is the density perturbation kernel.

The Woodhouse coefficients (Woodhouse 1980) are given by

$$B_{l'l''l}^{(N)\pm} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 \pm (-1)^{l'+l''+l} \right) \left[\frac{(l'+N)!(l+N)!}{(l'-N)!(l-N)!} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (-1)^N \begin{pmatrix} l' & l'' & l \\ -N & 0 & N \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{D.30})$$

The cases, which occur in the sensitivity kernels, are

$$B_{l'sl}^{(0)\pm} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 \pm (-1)^{l'+s+l} \right) \begin{pmatrix} l' & s & l \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{D.31})$$

$$B_{l'sl}^{(1)\pm} = -\frac{1}{2} \left(1 \pm (-1)^{l'+s+l} \right) [l'(l'+1)l(l+1)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \begin{pmatrix} l' & s & l \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{D.32})$$

For useful identities of the Woodhouse coefficients, the reader is referred to the Appendix of Woodhouse (1980) and Appendix D.2.3 of Dahlen and Tromp (1998).

D.4 Perturbations in Structural Quantities

In Section 9.3 we found for the perturbations in the structural quantities:

$$\delta\rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) = \frac{1}{g_0} \left[\frac{d\rho_0}{dr} \delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) + \mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}(r) + \frac{d}{dr} (r\mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r)) \right], \quad (\text{D.33})$$

$$\delta p_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) = -\rho_0 \delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) - r\mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r), \quad (\text{D.34})$$

$$\delta c_{s,s'}^{2\lambda}(r) = \left[\left(\frac{\partial \ln \Gamma_1}{\partial \ln p} \right)_\rho + 1 \right] \frac{\delta p_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{p_0} c_0^2 + \left[\left(\frac{\partial \ln \Gamma_1}{\partial \ln \rho} \right)_p - 1 \right] \frac{\delta\rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{\rho_0} c_0^2, \quad (\text{D.35})$$

where $\delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)$ is found by integrating Equation (9.18) numerically. Equation (D.33) can be obtained from Equation (9.18) by using the Poisson equation

$$\nabla^2 \phi(r) = 4\pi G \rho(r) \quad (\text{D.36})$$

to solve for the perturbation in the density $\delta\rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)$. The derivation of Equation (D.33) can also be found in Mathis and Zahn (2004).

Introducing perturbations $Q \rightarrow Q + \delta Q$ with $Q = p, \mathbf{g}, \rho$ to the equation of hydrostatic support $dp/dr = -\mathbf{g}\rho$ yields

$$\frac{d\delta p_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{dr} = -\mathbf{g}_0 \delta\rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) - \delta g_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) \rho_0, \quad (\text{D.37})$$

where the equilibrium equation has been subtracted and only terms linear in the perturbations are retained. The gravitational acceleration is expanded, like the structural quantities, according to Equation (9.17). The expansion coefficient of the aspherical perturbation to the gravitational acceleration is given by

$$\delta g_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) = \frac{d\delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{dr} - \frac{\mathcal{R}_{s,s',\lambda}(r)}{\rho_0}, \quad (\text{D.38})$$

which is derived in [Mathis and Zahn \(2004\)](#), Section 5.2. By inserting Equation (D.33) and (D.38) into Equation (D.37), we find

$$\frac{d\delta p_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{dr} = -\frac{d\rho_0}{dr}\delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) - \frac{d}{dr}(r\mathcal{S}_{s,s',\lambda}(r)) - \frac{d\delta\phi_{s,s'}^\lambda(r)}{dr}\rho_0. \quad (\text{D.39})$$

Applying the inverse chain rule and eliminating the radial derivative yields Equation (D.34).

The kernel for the indirect effect as given in Equation (90) of [Lively and Ritzwoller \(1992\)](#) includes perturbations of the bulk modulus κ_0 and density ρ_0 . It can be transformed to perturbations in squared sound speed c_0^2 and density ρ_0 . The transformation is obtained by introducing perturbations in the defining equation of the squared sound speed $c_0^2 = \kappa_0/\rho_0$, subtracting the unperturbed equation, and linearizing in the perturbations. This yields

$$\delta\kappa_{s,s'}^\lambda(r) = \rho_0(r)\delta c_{s,s'}^{2\lambda}(r) + c_0^2\delta\rho_{s,s'}^\lambda(r), \quad (\text{D.40})$$

which was used to obtain Equation (9.22) from Equation (90) in [Lively and Ritzwoller \(1992\)](#). The aspherical perturbation to the bulk modulus can be expanded according to Equation (9.17). The perturbation in squared sound speed (Equation (D.35)) is derived in [Aerts et al. \(2010\)](#), Section 3.6. Compared to [Aerts et al. \(2010\)](#), we neglect perturbations to the chemical abundances.

D.5 Additional Figures

Figure D.1: Visualization of magnetic field model C.

Figure D.2: *Top row:* multiplet frequency shifts for model C as a function of unperturbed mode frequency (*left panel*) and as a function of lower turning point (*right panel*). *Bottom row:* multiplet frequency shifts for model C as a function of unperturbed mode frequency for the direct and indirect effect in the left and right panels, respectively. Notice the different magnitudes of the shifts in the left and right panels. Every fourth harmonic degree is shown in all plots.

Figure D.3: Visualization of magnetic field model D.

Figure D.4: *Top row:* multiplet frequency shifts for model D as a function of unperturbed mode frequency (left panel) and as a function of lower turning point (right panel). *Bottom row:* multiplet frequency shifts for model D as a function of unperturbed mode frequency for the direct and indirect effect in the left and right panels, respectively. Every fourth harmonic degree is shown in all plots.

Figure D.5: Visualization of magnetic field model E.

Figure D.6: *Top row*: multiplet frequency shifts for model E as a function of unperturbed mode frequency (left panel) and as a function of lower turning point (right panel). *Bottom row*: multiplet frequency shifts for model E as a function of unperturbed mode frequency for the direct and indirect effect in the left and right panels, respectively. Every fourth harmonic degree is shown in all plots.

Figure D.7: Visualization of magnetic field model F.

Figure D.8: *Top row:* multiplet frequency shifts for model F as a function of unperturbed mode frequency (left panel) and as a function of lower turning point (right panel). *Bottom row:* multiplet frequency shifts for model F as a function of unperturbed mode frequency for the direct and indirect effect in the left and right panels, respectively. Notice the different magnitudes of the shifts in the left and right panels. Every fourth harmonic degree is shown in all plots.

References

- [Aerts et al. 2010] C. Aerts, J. Christensen-Dalsgaard, and D. W. Kurtz. **Asteroseismology**. 1st ed. Dordrecht: Springer, 2010. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 10, 12, 13, 14, 16, 20, 25, 87, 90, 105, 113, and 196.
- [Ando and Osaki 1975] H. Ando and Y. Osaki. **Nonadiabatic Nonradial Oscillations: An Application to the Five-Minute Oscillation of the Sun**. Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan 27 (1975), pp. 581–603. [URL]. Cited on page 10.
- [Antia et al. 2000] H. M. Antia, S. M. Chitre, and M. J. Thompson. **The Sun’s acoustic asphericity and magnetic fields in the solar convection zone**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 360 (2000), pp. 335–344. [URL]. Cited on pages 7, 104, 105, 113, 116, 126, and 131.
- [Appourchaux et al. 2000] T. Appourchaux, C. Fröhlich, B. Andersen, et al. **Observational Upper Limits to Low-Degree Solar g-Modes**. The Astrophysical Journal 538.1 (2000), pp. 401–414. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 18.
- [Appourchaux et al. 2010] T. Appourchaux, K. Belkacem, A.-M. Broomhall, et al. **The quest for the solar g modes**. The Astronomy and Astrophysics Review 18.1-2 (2010), pp. 197–277. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 18, 19, and 34.
- [Appourchaux et al. 2012] T. Appourchaux, W. J. Chaplin, R. A. García, et al. **Oscillation mode frequencies of 61 main-sequence and subgiant stars observed by Kepler**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 543 (2012), A54. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 17, 33, and 55.
- [Arlt et al. 2007] R. Arlt, A. Sule, and G. Rüdiger. **Stability of toroidal magnetic fields in the solar tachocline**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 461.1 (2007), pp. 295–301. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 131 and 143.
- [Asplund et al. 2009] M. Asplund, N. Grevesse, A. J. Sauval, and P. Scott. **The chemical composition of the Sun**. Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics 47 (2009), pp. 481–522. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 27.
- [Auvergne et al. 2009] M. Auvergne, P. Bodin, L. Boissard, et al. **The CoRoT satellite in flight: description and performance**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 506.1 (2009), pp. 411–424. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 4, 9, and 54.
- [Böhm-Vitense 1969] E. Böhm-Vitense. **Über die Wasserstoffkonvektionszone in Sternen verschiedener Effektivtemperaturen und Leuchtkräfte**. Zeitschrift für Astrophysik 46 (1969), pp. 108–143. [URL]. Cited on page 31.
- [Böning 2017] V. G. A. Böning. **Inferences of the Deep Solar Meridional Flow**. PhD thesis. Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, 2017. [URL]. Cited on page 45.
- [Babcock 1961] H. W. Babcock. **The Topology of the Sun’s Magnetic Field and the 22-Year Cycle**. The Astrophysical Journal 133 (1961), pp. 572–587. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 43.
- [Baglin et al. 2006] A. Baglin, M. Auvergne, P. Barge, et al. **Scientific Objectives for a Minisat: CoRoT**. The CoRoT Mission Pre-Launch Status - Stellar Seismology and Planet Finding. Ed. by M. Fridlund, A. Baglin, J. Lochard, and L. Conroy. 1306. ESA Special Publication. Noordwijk, The Netherlands, 2006, 33. [URL]. Cited on pages 4, 9, and 54.
- [Baldner et al. 2009] C. S. Baldner, H. M. Antia, S. Basu, and T. P. Larson. **Solar Magnetic Field Signatures in Helioseismic Splitting Coefficients**. The Astrophysical Journal 705.2 (2009), pp. 1704–1713. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 7, 105, 113, 116, and 146.
- [Baliunas et al. 1995] S. L. Baliunas, R. A. Donahue, W. H. Soon, et al. **Chromospheric variations in main-sequence stars**. The Astrophysical Journal 438.1 (1995), pp. 269–287. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 40 and 54.

- [Ball and Gizon 2014] W. H. Ball and L. Gizon. **A new correction of stellar oscillation frequencies for near-surface effects**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 568 (2014), A123. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 127.
- [Balmforth and Gough 1990] N. J. Balmforth and D. O. Gough. **Effluent stellar pulsation**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 362.1 (1990), pp. 256–266. [URL]. Cited on page 17.
- [Balmforth 1992] N. J. Balmforth. **Solar pulsational stability - III. Acoustical excitation by turbulent convection**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 255.4 (1992), pp. 639–649. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 89.
- [Bartlett 1978] M. Bartlett. **An Introduction to Stochastic Processes: With Special Reference to Methods and Applications**. 3rd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1978. Cited on page 57.
- [Bastien et al. 2013] F. A. Bastien, K. G. Stassun, G. Basri, and J. Pepper. **An observational correlation between stellar brightness variations and surface gravity**. *Nature* 500.7463 (2013), pp. 427–430. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 31.
- [Basu et al. 2012] S. Basu, A.-M. Broomhall, W. J. Chaplin, and Y. Elsworth. **Thinning of the Sun’s magnetic layer: The peculiar solar minimum could have been predicted**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 758.1 (2012), 43. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 6, 54, and 116.
- [Basu 1997] S. Basu. **Seismology of the base of the solar convection zone**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 288.3 (1997), pp. 572–584. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 131.
- [Basu 2016] S. Basu. **Global Seismology of the Sun**. *Living Reviews in Solar Physics* 13 (2016), 2. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 9, 20, 31, 34, 89, and 127.
- [Bazilevskaya et al. 2015] G. Bazilevskaya, A.-M. Broomhall, Y. Elsworth, and V. M. Nakariakov. **A Combined Analysis of the Observational Aspects of the Quasi-biennial Oscillation in Solar Magnetic Activity**. *The Solar Activity Cycle. Space Sciences Series of ISSI*. Ed. by A. Balogh, H. Hudson, K. Petrovay, and R. von Steiger. 53. Springer New York, 2015, pp. 359–386. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 136.
- [Beck et al. 2012] P. G. Beck, J. Montalbán, T. Kallinger, et al. **Fast core rotation in red-giant stars revealed by gravity-dominated mixed modes**. *Nature* 481.7379 (2012), pp. 55–57. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 104.
- [Bedding and Kjeldsen 2003] T. R. Bedding and H. Kjeldsen. **Solar-like Oscillations**. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Australia* 20.2 (2003), pp. 203–212. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 25.
- [Beeck et al. 2013] B. Beeck, R. H. Cameron, A. Reiners, and M. Schüssler. **Three-dimensional simulations of near-surface convection in main-sequence stars**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 558 (2013), A49. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 62.
- [Belkacem et al. 2011] K. Belkacem, M. J. Goupil, M. A. Dupret, et al. **The underlying physical meaning of the ν_{\max} - ν_{text} relation**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 530 (2011), A142. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 27.
- [Berdyugina 2005] S. V. Berdyugina. **Starspots: A Key to the Stellar Dynamo**. *Living Reviews in Solar Physics* 2 (2005), 8. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.
- [Bogdan et al. 1988] T. J. Bogdan, P. A. Gilman, I. Lerche, and R. Howard. **Distribution of sunspot umbral areas - 1917-1982**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 327 (1988), pp. 451–456. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.
- [Bogdan et al. 1996] T. J. Bogdan, B. W. Hindman, P. S. Cally, and P. Charbonneau. **Absorption of p-Modes by Slender Magnetic Flux Tubes and p-Mode Lifetimes**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 465 (1996), pp. 406–424. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 93.
- [Bonanno and Fröhlich 2015] A. Bonanno and H.-E. Fröhlich. **A Bayesian estimation of the helioseismic solar age**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 580 (2015), A130. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 27.
- [Bonanno et al. 2002] A. Bonanno, H. Schlattl, and L. Paternò. **The age of the Sun and the relativistic corrections in the EOS**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 390.3 (2002), pp. 1115–1118. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 27.
- [Borucki et al. 2010] W. J. Borucki, D. Koch, G. Basri, et al. **Kepler Planet-Detection Mission: Introduction and First Results**. *Science* 327.5968 (2010), pp. 977–980. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 4, 9, 22, and 54.

- [Brandenburg et al. 1998] A. Brandenburg, S. H. Saar, and C. R. Turpin. **Time Evolution of the Magnetic Activity Cycle Period**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 498.1 (1998), pp. L51–L54. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 54.
- [Brandenburg 2005] A. Brandenburg. **The Case for a Distributed Solar Dynamo Shaped by Near-Surface Shear**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 625.1 (2005), pp. 539–547. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 30, 45, and 143.
- [Braun and Fan 1998] D. C. Braun and Y. Fan. **Helioseismic Measurements of the Subsurface Meridional Flow**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 508.1 (1998), pp. L105–L108. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 45 and 104.
- [Braun et al. 1987] D. C. Braun, B. J. Labonte, and J. Duvall, T. L. **Acoustic absorption by sunspots**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 319 (1987), pp. L27–L31. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 38 and 93.
- [Broomhall and Nakariakov 2015] A.-M. Broomhall and V. M. Nakariakov. **A Comparison Between Global Proxies of the Sun’s Magnetic Activity Cycle: Inferences from Helioseismology**. *Solar Physics* 290 (2015), pp. 3095–3111. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 77.
- [Broomhall et al. 2009] A.-M. Broomhall, W. J. Chaplin, G. R. Davies, et al. **Definitive Sun-as-a-star p-mode frequencies: 23 years of BiSON observations**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society: Letters* 396.1 (2009), pp. L100–L104. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 84.
- [Broomhall et al. 2014] A.-M. Broomhall, P. Chatterjee, R. Howe, et al. **The Sun’s Interior Structure and Dynamics, and the Solar Cycle**. *Space Science Reviews* 186 (2014), pp. 191–225. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 35, 38, 39, and 49.
- [Broomhall et al. 2015] A.-M. Broomhall, C. Pugh, and V. Nakariakov. **Solar cycle variations in the powers and damping rates of low-degree solar acoustic oscillations**. *Advances in Space Research* 56.12 (2015), pp. 2706–2712. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 6, 54, 61, 89, 91, and 112.
- [Broomhall 2017] A.-M. Broomhall. **A Helioseismic Perspective on the Depth of the Minimum Between Solar Cycles 23 and 24**. *Solar Physics* 292 (2017), 67. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 112, 116, 122, 127, 129, 130, and 131.
- [Brown et al. 1991] T. M. Brown, R. L. Gilliland, R. W. Noyes, and L. W. Ramsey. **Detection of possible p-mode oscillations on Procyon**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 368 (1991), pp. 599–609. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 27.
- [Brun and Browning 2017] A. S. Brun and M. K. Browning. **Magnetism, dynamo action and the solar-stellar connection**. *Living Reviews in Solar Physics* 14 (2017), 4. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 45 and 141.
- [Bruntt et al. 2012] H. Bruntt, S. Basu, B. Smalley, et al. **Accurate fundamental parameters and detailed abundance patterns from spectroscopy of 93 solar-type Kepler targets**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 423.1 (2012), pp. 122–131. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 152.
- [Caligari et al. 1995] P. Caligari, F. Moreno-Insertis, and M. Schüssler. **Emerging flux tubes in the solar convection zone. 1: Asymmetry, tilt, and emergence latitude**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 441.2 (1995), pp. 886–902. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 104.
- [Cameron and Schüssler 2015] R. Cameron and M. Schüssler. **The crucial role of surface magnetic fields for the solar dynamo**. *Science* 347.6228 (2015), pp. 1333–1335. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 43.
- [Cameron and Schüssler 2017] R. H. Cameron and M. Schüssler. **An update of Leighton’s solar dynamo model**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 599 (2017), A52. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 43.
- [Cameron et al. 2016] R. H. Cameron, M. Dikpati, and A. Brandenburg. **The Global Solar Dynamo**. *Space Science Reviews* 210 (2016), pp. 367–395. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.
- [Chaplin and Miglio 2013] W. J. Chaplin and A. Miglio. **Asteroseismology of Solar-Type and Red-Giant Stars**. *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics* 51 (2013), pp. 353–392. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 31.
- [Chaplin et al. 1998] W. J. Chaplin, Y. Elsworth, G. R. Isaak, et al. **Solar p-mode excitation: further insight from recent low-l BiSON helioseismological data**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 298.1 (1998), pp. L7–L11. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 90.

- [Chaplin et al. 2000] W. J. Chaplin, Y. Elsworth, G. R. Isaak, et al. **Variations in the excitation and damping of low- solar p modes over the solar activity cycle**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 313.1 (2000), pp. 32–42. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 49 and 91.
- [Chaplin et al. 2007a] W. J. Chaplin, Y. Elsworth, G. Houdek, and R. New. **On prospects for sounding activity cycles of Sun-like stars with acoustic modes**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 377.1 (2007), pp. 17–29. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 63, 71, 141, and 145.
- [Chaplin et al. 2007b] W. J. Chaplin, Y. Elsworth, B. A. Miller, et al. **Solar p-Mode Frequencies over Three Solar Cycles**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 659.2 (2007), pp. 1749–1760. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 48, 57, 60, and 67.
- [Chaplin et al. 2011] W. J. Chaplin, T. R. Bedding, A. Bonanno, et al. **Evidence for the impact of stellar activity on the detectability of solar-like oscillations observed by Kepler**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 732.1 (2011), L5. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 49, 91, and 142.
- [Chaplin et al. 2014] W. J. Chaplin, S. Basu, D. Huber, et al. **Asteroseismic fundamental properties of solar-type stars observed by the NASA Kepler mission**. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 210.1 (2014), 1. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 151.
- [Charbonneau 2010] P. Charbonneau. **Dynamo models of the solar cycle**. *Living Reviews in Solar Physics* 7 (2010), 3. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 35, 42, 43, 103, 104, 116, and 138.
- [Charbonneau 2013] P. Charbonneau. **Solar and Stellar Dynamos**. Ed. by O. Steiner. 1st ed. 39. Saas-Fee Advanced Courses. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2013. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 103.
- [Charbonneau 2014] P. Charbonneau. **Solar Dynamo Theory**. *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics* 52 (2014), pp. 251–290. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 7 and 105.
- [Choudhuri et al. 1995] A. R. Choudhuri, M. Schüssler, and M. Dikpati. **The solar dynamo with meridional circulation**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 303 (1995), L29. [URL]. Cited on page 103.
- [Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1985] J. Christensen-Dalsgaard, T. L. Duvall, D. O. Gough, et al. **Speed of sound in the solar interior**. *Nature* 315.6018 (1985), pp. 378–382. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 24.
- [Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1991] J. Christensen-Dalsgaard, D. O. Gough, and M. J. Thompson. **The depth of the solar convection zone**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 378 (1991), pp. 413–437. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 28.
- [Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 1996] J. Christensen-Dalsgaard, W. Däppen, S. V. Ajukov, et al. **The Current State of Solar Modeling**. *Science* 272.5266 (1996), pp. 1286–1292. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 17, 28, 31, 85, 86, 87, 105, 121, and 122.
- [Christensen-Dalsgaard 1991] J. Christensen-Dalsgaard. **Some aspects of the theory of solar oscillations**. *Geophysical & Astrophysical Fluid Dynamics* 62.1 (1991), pp. 123–152. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 15.
- [Christensen-Dalsgaard 2007] J. Christensen-Dalsgaard. **ASTEC – the Aarhus STellar Evolution Code**. *Astrophysics and Space Science* 316 (2007), pp. 13–24. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 14 and 32.
- [Christensen-Dalsgaard 2008] J. Christensen-Dalsgaard. **ADIPLS – the Aarhus adiabatic oscillation package**. *Astrophysics and Space Science* 316 (2008), pp. 113–120. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 14, 31, 95, 117, and 122.
- [Christensen-Dalsgaard 2014] J. Christensen-Dalsgaard. **Stellar oscillations - Lecture Notes**. 2014. [URL] (visited on 01/22/2018). Cited on page 19.
- [Cowling 1941] T. G. Cowling. **The Non-radial Oscillations of Polytopic Stars**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 101.8 (1941), pp. 367–375. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 15 and 122.
- [Cox 1980] J. P. Cox. **Theory of Stellar Pulsations**. 1st ed. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1980. Cited on page 15.
- [Dahlen and Tromp 1998] F. A. Dahlen and J. Tromp. **Theoretical Global Seismology**. 1st ed. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1998. Cited on pages 119, 120, 178, 180, 181, 191, 192, 193, and 195.

- [Davies et al. 2014] G. R. Davies, W. J. Chaplin, Y. Elsworth, and S. J. Hale. **BiSON data preparation: a correction for differential extinction and the weighted averaging of contemporaneous data**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 441.4 (2014), pp. 3009–3017. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 59.
- [Davies et al. 2015] G. R. Davies, W. J. Chaplin, W. M. Farr, et al. **Asteroseismic inference on rotation, gyrochronology and planetary system dynamics of 16 Cygni**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 446.3 (2015), pp. 2959–2966. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [Deheuvels and Michel 2010] S. Deheuvels and E. Michel. **New insights on the interior of solar-like pulsators thanks to CoRoT: the case of HD 49385**. *Astrophysics and Space Science* 328 (2010), pp. 259–263. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 21.
- [Deheuvels and Michel 2011] S. Deheuvels and E. Michel. **Constraints on the structure of the core of subgiants via mixed modes: the case of HD49385**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 535 (2011), A91. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 21.
- [Deheuvels et al. 2010] S. Deheuvels, H. Bruntt, E. Michel, et al. **Seismic and spectroscopic characterization of the solar-like pulsating CoRoT target HD49385**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 515 (2010), A87. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 26.
- [Dikpati and Charbonneau 1999] M. Dikpati and P. Charbonneau. **A Babcock-Leighton Flux Transport Dynamo with Solar-like Differential Rotation**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 518.1 (1999), pp. 508–520. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 45.
- [Dikpati and Gilman 2007] M. Dikpati and P. A. Gilman. **Global solar dynamo models: simulations and predictions of cyclic photospheric fields and long-term non-reversing interior fields**. *New Journal of Physics* 9 (2007), 297. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 42 and 44.
- [Dikpati and Gilman 2009] M. Dikpati and P. A. Gilman. **Flux-Transport Solar Dynamos**. *The Origin and Dynamics of Solar Magnetism*. Space Sciences Series of ISSI. Ed. by M. J. Thompson, A. Balogh, J. L. Culhane, et al. 1st ed. 32. New York: Springer, 2009, pp. 67–75. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 103.
- [Domingo et al. 1995] V. Domingo, B. Fleck, and A. I. Poland. **The SOHO Mission: An Overview**. *Solar Physics* 162 (1995), pp. 1–37. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 21.
- [Donati et al. 2008] J.-F. Donati, J. Morin, P. Petit, et al. **Large-scale magnetic topologies of early M dwarfs**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 390.2 (2008), pp. 545–560. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 147.
- [Duez et al. 2008] V. Duez, S. Mathis, A. S. Brun, and S. Turck-Chièze. **Impact of large-scale magnetic fields on stellar structure and evolution**. *Cosmic Magnetic Fields: From Planets, to Stars and Galaxies*. Ed. by K. G. Strassmeier, A. G. Kosovichev, and J. E. Beckman. 4. Proceedings of the International Astronomical Union S259. 2008, pp. 177–184. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 104 and 117.
- [Duez et al. 2010] V. Duez, S. Mathis, and S. Turck-Chièze. **Effect of a fossil magnetic field on the structure of a young Sun**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 402.1 (2010), pp. 271–281. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 104 and 117.
- [Dumusque et al. 2014] X. Dumusque, I. . Boisse, and N. C. Santos. **SOAP 2.0: A tool to estimate the photometric and radial velocity variations induced by stellar spots and plages**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 796.2 (2014), 132. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.
- [Duvall Jr. et al. 1993] T. L. Duvall Jr., S. M. Jefferies, J. W. Harvey, and M. A. Pomerantz. **Time–distance helioseismology**. *Nature* 362.6419 (1993), pp. 430–432. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 21.
- [Duvall Jr. 1979] T. L. Duvall Jr. **Large-scale solar velocity fields**. *Solar Physics* 63 (1979), pp. 3–15. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 43.
- [Duvall Jr. 1982] T. L. Duvall Jr. **A dispersion law for solar oscillations**. *Nature* 300.5889 (1982), pp. 242–243. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 24.
- [Dziembowski and Goode 2005] W. A. Dziembowski and P. R. Goode. **Sources of Oscillation Frequency Increase with Rising Solar Activity**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 625.1 (2005), pp. 548–555. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 7 and 116.

- [Eddington 1926] A. S. Eddington. **The internal constitution of the stars**. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1926. [URL]. Cited on page 3.
- [Edmonds 1960] A. R. Edmonds. **Angular momentum in quantum mechanics**. 2nd ed. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1960. [URL]. Cited on pages 120 and 180.
- [Fan 2009] Y. Fan. **Magnetic Fields in the Solar Convection Zone**. Living Reviews in Solar Physics 6 (2009), 4. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 35, 104, and 116.
- [Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013] D. Foreman-Mackey, D. W. Hogg, D. Lang, and J. Goodman. **emcee: The MCMC Hammer**. Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific 125.925 (2013), 306. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 60 and 136.
- [Fossat et al. 1992] E. Fossat, C. Régulo, T. Roca Cortés, et al. **On the acoustic cut-off frequency of the Sun**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 266 (1992), pp. 532–536. [URL]. Cited on page 17.
- [Fossat et al. 2017] E. Fossat, P. Boumier, T. Corbard, et al. **Asymptotic g modes: Evidence for a rapid rotation of the solar core**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 604 (2017), A40. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 18 and 28.
- [Fowler 1990] C. M. R. Fowler. **The Solid Earth: An Introduction to Global Geophysics**. 1st ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990. Cited on page 9.
- [García et al. 2007] R. A. García, S. Turck-Chièze, S. J. Jiménez-Reyes, et al. **Tracking Solar Gravity Modes: The Dynamics of the Solar Core**. Science 316.5831 (2007), pp. 1591–1593. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 18 and 28.
- [García et al. 2010] R. A. García, S. Mathur, D. Salabert, et al. **CoRoT reveals a magnetic activity cycle in a Sun-like star**. Science 329.5995 (2010), 1032. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 7, 42, 48, 54, 61, 62, 112, 116, and 141.
- [García et al. 2011] R. A. García, S. Hekker, D. Stello, et al. **Preparation of Kepler light curves for asteroseismic analyses**. Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society: Letters 414.1 (2011), pp. L6–L10. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 23 and 55.
- [García et al. 2014a] R. A. García, T. Ceillier, D. Salabert, et al. **Rotation and magnetism of Kepler pulsating solar-like stars - Towards asteroseismically calibrated age-rotation relations**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 572 (2014), A34. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 65, 67, 68, and 152.
- [García et al. 2014b] R. A. García, S. Mathur, S. Pires, et al. **Impact on asteroseismic analyses of regular gaps in Kepler data**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 568 (2014), A10. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 55.
- [Giles et al. 1997] P. M. Giles, T. L. Duvall, P. H. Scherrer, and R. S. Bogart. **A subsurface flow of material from the Sun’s equator to its poles**. Nature 390.6655 (1997), pp. 52–54. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 45 and 104.
- [Gilliland et al. 2013] R. L. Gilliland, G. W. Marcy, J. F. Rowe, et al. **Kepler-68: Three Planets, One With a Density Between That of Earth and Ice Giants**. The Astrophysical Journal 766.1 (2013), 40. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 152.
- [Gilman and Foukal 1979] P. A. Gilman and P. V. Foukal. **Angular velocity gradients in the solar convection zone**. The Astrophysical Journal 229 (1979), pp. 1179–1185. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 30.
- [Gizon and Birch 2005] L. Gizon and A. C. Birch. **Local Helioseismology**. Living Reviews in Solar Physics 2 (2005), 6. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 20.
- [Gizon and Solanki 2003] L. Gizon and S. K. Solanki. **Determining the Inclination of the Rotation Axis of a Sun-like Star**. The Astrophysical Journal 589.2 (2003), pp. 1009–1019. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [Gizon et al. 2013] L. Gizon, J. Ballot, E. Michel, et al. **Seismic constraints on rotation of Sun-like star and mass of exoplanet**. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences 110.33 (2013), pp. 13267–13271. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [Goldreich et al. 1994] P. Goldreich, N. Murray, and P. Kumar. **Excitation of solar p-modes**. The Astrophysical Journal 424 (1994), pp. 466–479. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 85 and 86.

- [Gough and Thompson 1990] D. O. Gough and M. J. Thompson. **The effect of rotation and a buried magnetic field on stellar oscillations**. Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society 242.1 (1990), pp. 25–55. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 7, 104, 105, 113, 116, 117, and 146.
- [Gough 2012] D. Gough. **What Have We Learned from Helioseismology, What Have We Really Learned, and What Do We Aspire to Learn?** Solar Physics 287 (2012), pp. 9–41. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 28, 33, 47, and 49.
- [Grevesse and Sauval 1998] N. Grevesse and A. Sauval. **Standard Solar Composition**. Space Science Reviews 85 (1998), pp. 161–174. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 27.
- [Griffin 2007] R. F. Griffin. **Spectroscopic binary orbits from photoelectric radial velocities - Paper 196: HR 770, HD 64207, HD 187160, and HD 212790**. The Observatory 127 (2007), pp. 313–336. [URL]. Cited on page 152.
- [Haber et al. 2002] D. A. Haber, B. W. Hindman, J. Toomre, et al. **Evolving Submerged Meridional Circulation Cells within the Upper Convection Zone Revealed by Ring-Diagram Analysis**. The Astrophysical Journal 570.2 (2002), pp. 855–864. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 104.
- [Hale et al. 1919] G. E. Hale, F. Ellerman, S. B. Nicholson, and A. H. Joy. **The Magnetic Polarity of Sun-Spots**. The Astrophysical Journal 49 (1919), pp. 153–185. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 35.
- [Hale 1908] G. E. Hale. **On the Probable Existence of a Magnetic Field in Sun-Spots**. The Astrophysical Journal 28 (1908), pp. 315–343. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 35.
- [Hall 2008] J. C. Hall. **Stellar Chromospheric Activity**. Living Reviews in Solar Physics 5 (2008), 2. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 40 and 54.
- [Hanasoge 2017] S. M. Hanasoge. **Seismic sensitivity of normal-mode coupling to Lorentz stresses in the Sun**. Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society 470.3 (2017), pp. 2780–2790. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 105 and 116.
- [Harvey et al. 1996] J. W. Harvey, F. Hill, R. P. Hubbard, et al. **The Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG) Project**. Science 272.5266 (1996), pp. 1284–1286. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 21, 23, and 24.
- [Harvey et al. 1998] J. Harvey, R. Tucker, and L. Britanik. **High Resolution Upgrade of the GONG Instruments**. Structure and Dynamics of the Interior of the Sun and Sun-like Stars. Ed. by S. Korzenik. 418. ESA Special Publication, 1998, pp. 209–211. [URL]. Cited on page 76.
- [Harvey 1985] J. Harvey. **High-resolution helioseismology**. ESA Future Missions in Solar, Heliospheric and Space Plasma Physics. Ed. by E. Rolfe and B. Battrock. 235. ESA Special Publication, 1985, pp. 199–208. [URL]. Cited on page 60.
- [Harvey 1988] J. W. Harvey. **Techniques for Observing Stellar Oscillations**. Advances in Helio- and Asteroseismology. Ed. by J. Christensen-Dalsgaard and S. Frandsen. 123. IAU Symposium. Dordrecht: D. Reidel Publishing, 1988, pp. 497–511. [URL]. Cited on pages 9 and 17.
- [Hathaway and Rightmire 2010] D. H. Hathaway and L. Rightmire. **Variations in the Sun’s Meridional Flow over a Solar Cycle**. Science 327.5971 (2010), pp. 1350–1352. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 39.
- [Hathaway 2012] D. Hathaway. **Supergranules as Probes of the Sun’s Meridional Circulation**. The Astrophysical Journal 760.1 (2012), 84. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 45.
- [Hathaway 2015] D. H. Hathaway. **The Solar Cycle**. Living Reviews in Solar Physics 12 (2015), 4. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 35, 37, 38, 116, and 120.
- [Haubois et al. 2009] X. Haubois, G. Perrin, S. Lacour, et al. **Imaging the spotty surface of Betelgeuse in the H band**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 508.2 (2009), pp. 923–932. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 40.
- [Hazra and Choudhuri 2017] G. Hazra and A. R. Choudhuri. **A theoretical model of the variation of the meridional circulation with the solar cycle**. Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society 472.3 (2017), pp. 2728–2741. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 39.

- [Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard 2017] S. Hekker and J. Christensen-Dalsgaard. **Giant star seismology**. *Astronomy and Astrophysics Review* 25 (2017), 1. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 14, 21, 22, 31, 93, and 104.
- [Herzberg and Roth 2018] W. Herzberg and M. Roth. **Effects of large-scale convective flows on stellar oscillations - General methodology and calculations for a subgiant star**. in prep. (2018). Cited on page 118.
- [Herzberg 2016] W. Herzberg. **Effects of large-scale poloidal flows on oscillation modes of subgiant stars and the sun**. PhD thesis. Albert-Ludwigs Universität Freiburg, 2016. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 94, 99, 101, 107, and 118.
- [Hill and Howe 1998] F. Hill and R. Howe. **Calculating the GONG Leakage Matrix**. Structure and Dynamics of the Interior of the Sun and Sun-like Stars. Ed. by S. G. Korzennik and A. Wilson. 418. ESA Special Publication, 1998, 225. [URL]. Cited on pages 73 and 85.
- [Hill et al. 1996] F. Hill, P. B. Stark, R. T. Stebbins, et al. **The Solar Acoustic Spectrum and Eigenmode Parameters**. *Science* 272.5266 (1996), pp. 1292–1295. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 4, 21, 24, 73, and 75.
- [Houdek and Dupret 2015] G. Houdek and M.-A. Dupret. **Interaction Between Convection and Pulsation**. *Living Reviews in Solar Physics* 12 (2015), 8. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 89 and 142.
- [Houdek et al. 1999] G. Houdek, N. J. Balmforth, J. Christensen-Dalsgaard, and D. O. Gough. **Amplitudes of stochastically excited oscillations in main-sequence stars**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 351 (1999), pp. 582–596. [URL]. Cited on pages 49 and 89.
- [Howe et al. 2005] R. Howe, J. Christensen-Dalsgaard, F. Hill, et al. **Solar Convection-Zone Dynamics, 1995–2004**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 634.2 (2005), pp. 1405–1415. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 29.
- [Howe et al. 2015] R. Howe, G. R. Davies, W. J. Chaplin, et al. **Validation of solar-cycle changes in low-degree helioseismic parameters from the Birmingham Solar-Oscillations Network**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 454.4 (2015), pp. 4120–4141. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 73.
- [Howe et al. 2017] R. Howe, S. Basu, G. R. Davies, et al. **Parametrizing the time-variation of the ‘surface term’ of stellar p-mode frequencies: application to helioseismic data**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 464.4 (2017), pp. 4777–4788. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 34 and 146.
- [Howe 2009] R. Howe. **Solar Interior Rotation and its Variation**. *Living Reviews in Solar Physics* 6 (2009), 1. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 15, 29, 30, 38, 47, and 104.
- [Howell et al. 2011] S. B. Howell, J. F. Rowe, S. T. Bryson, et al. **Kepler-21b: A 1.6 R_{Earth} Planet Transiting the Bright Oscillating F Subgiant Star HD 179070**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 746.2 (2011), 123. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 152.
- [Huber et al. 2013a] D. Huber, J. A. Carter, M. Barbieri, et al. **Stellar Spin-Orbit Misalignment in a Multiplanet System**. *Science* 342.6156 (2013), pp. 331–334. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [Huber et al. 2013b] D. Huber, W. J. Chaplin, J. Christensen-Dalsgaard, et al. **Fundamental Properties of Kepler Planet-Candidate Host Stars using Asteroseismology**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 767.2 (2013), 127. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 55.
- [Huber et al. 2014] D. Huber, V. S. Aguirre, J. M. Matthews, et al. **Revised Stellar Properties of Kepler Targets for the Quarter 1–16 Transit Detection Run**. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 211.1 (2014), 2. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 151.
- [Hughes et al. 2007] D. W. Hughes, R. Rosner, and N. O. Weiss, eds. **The Solar Tachocline**. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2007. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 29.
- [Hughes et al. 2016] A. L. H. Hughes, K. Jain, S. Kholikov, and t. N. S. I. Group. **GONG ClassicMerge: Pipeline and Product**. eprint arXiv:1603.00836 (2016). [URL]. Cited on page 76.

- [Iben 2013] I. Iben. **Stellar Evolution Physics - Volume 1: Physical Processes in Stellar Interiors**. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013. [DOI]. Cited on pages 10 and 19.
- [Iglesias and Rogers 1991] C. A. Iglesias and F. J. Rogers. **Opacities for the solar radiative interior**. The Astrophysical Journal 371 (1991), pp. 408–417. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 31.
- [Jackiewicz et al. 2007] J. Jackiewicz, L. Gizon, A. C. Birch, and T. L. Duvall Jr. **Time-Distance Helioseismology: Sensitivity of f-mode Travel Times to Flows**. The Astrophysical Journal 671.1 (2007), pp. 1051–1064. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 20.
- [Jefferies et al. 1990] S. M. Jefferies, T. L. Duvall, J. W. Harvey, and M. A. Pomerantz. **Helioseismology from the South Pole: Results from the 1987 campaign**. Progress of Seismology of the Sun and Stars. Ed. by Y. Osaki and H. Shibahashi. 367. Lecture Notes in Physics. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 1990, pp. 135–143. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 112.
- [Jiménez-Reyes et al. 1998] S. J. Jiménez-Reyes, C. Régulo, P. L. Pallé, and T. Roca Cortes. **Solar activity cycle frequency shifts of low-degree p-modes**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 329 (1998), pp. 1119–1124. [URL]. Cited on pages 6, 49, 54, 70, 71, 89, 112, and 116.
- [Jiménez-Reyes et al. 2001] S. J. Jiménez-Reyes, T. Corbard, P. L. Pallé, et al. **Analysis of the solar cycle and core rotation using 15 years of Mark-I observations: 1984–1999. I. The solar cycle**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 379.2 (2001), pp. 622–633. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 67.
- [Jiménez-Reyes et al. 2007] S. J. Jiménez-Reyes, W. J. Chaplin, Y. Elsworth, et al. **On the Variation of the Peak Asymmetry of Low-l Solar p Modes**. The Astrophysical Journal 654.2 (2007), pp. 1135–1145. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 73.
- [Kallinger et al. 2010] T. Kallinger, B. Mosser, S. Hekker, et al. **Asteroseismology of red giants from the first four months of Kepler data: Fundamental stellar parameters**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 522 (2010), A1. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 27 and 84.
- [Kallinger et al. 2014] T. Kallinger, J. De Ridder, S. Hekker, et al. **The connection between stellar granulation and oscillation as seen by the Kepler mission**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 570 (2014), A41. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 26 and 60.
- [Karak et al. 2014] B. B. Karak, J. Jiang, M. S. Miesch, et al. **Flux Transport Dynamos: From Kinematics to Dynamics**. Space Science Reviews 186.1 (2014), pp. 561–602. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 103.
- [Karoff et al. 2009] C. Karoff, T. S. Metcalfe, W. J. Chaplin, et al. **Sounding stellar cycles with Kepler - I. Strategy for selecting targets**. Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society 399.2 (2009), pp. 914–923. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 63.
- [Karoff et al. 2013] C. Karoff, T. S. Metcalfe, W. J. Chaplin, et al. **Sounding stellar cycles with Kepler - II. Ground-based observations**. Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society 433.4 (2013), pp. 3227–3238. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 54, 64, and 67.
- [Karoff et al. 2018] C. Karoff, T. S. Metcalfe, Â. R. G. Santos, et al. **The Influence of Metallicity on Stellar Differential Rotation and Magnetic Activity**. The Astrophysical Journal 852.1 (2018), 46. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 142.
- [Kiefer et al. 2015] R. Kiefer, A. Schad, W. Herzberg, and M. Roth. **Determination of fundamental asteroseismic parameters using the Hilbert transform**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 578 (2015), A56. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 25 and 33.
- [Kiefer et al. 2017a] R. Kiefer, A. Schad, G. Davies, and M. Roth. **Stellar magnetic activity and variability of oscillation parameters: An investigation of 24 solar-like stars observed by Kepler**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 598 (2017), A77. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 112 and 116.
- [Kiefer et al. 2017b] R. Kiefer, A. Schad, and M. Roth. **The Direct Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Stellar Oscillations: An Analytical Expression for the General Matrix Element**. The Astrophysical Journal 846.2 (2017), 162. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 117, 118, and 131.
- [Kiess et al. 2014] C. Kiess, R. Rezaei, and W. Schmidt. **Properties of sunspot umbrae observed in Cycle 24**. Astronomy & Astrophysics 565 (2014), A52. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.

- [Kippenhahn et al. 2012] R. Kippenhahn, A. Weigert, and A. Weiss. **Stellar Structure and Evolution**. 2nd ed. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2012. [DOI]. Cited on pages 10 and 31.
- [Kjeldsen and Bedding 1995] H. Kjeldsen and T. R. Bedding. **Amplitudes of Stellar Oscillations: The Implications for Asteroseismology**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 293 (1995), pp. 87–106. [URL]. Cited on pages 9, 27, 32, and 84.
- [Koch et al. 2010] D. G. Koch, W. J. Borucki, G. Basri, et al. **Kepler Mission Design, Realized Photometric Performance, and Early Science**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 713.2 (2010), pp. L79–L86. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 4, 9, and 54.
- [Komm et al. 2000a] R. W. Komm, R. Howe, and F. Hill. **Solar-Cycle Changes in Gong p-Mode Widths and Amplitudes 1995–1998**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 531.2 (2000), pp. 1094–1108. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 49, 89, and 112.
- [Komm et al. 2000b] R. W. Komm, R. Howe, and F. Hill. **Width and Energy of Solar p-Modes Observed by Global Oscillation Network Group**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 543.1 (2000), pp. 472–485. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 6, 9, 49, 54, 61, 75, 85, 87, 89, 90, and 137.
- [Kopp et al. 2016] G. Kopp, N. Krivova, J. Lean, and C. J. Wu. **The Impact of the Revised Sunspot Record on Solar Irradiance Reconstructions**. *Solar Physics* 291 (2016), pp. 2951–2965. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 37.
- [Kopp 2016] G. Kopp. **Magnitudes and timescales of total solar irradiance variability**. *Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate* 6 (2016), A30. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 37.
- [Korzennik et al. 2013] S. G. Korzennik, M. C. Rabello-Soares, J. Schou, and T. P. Larson. **Accurate Characterization of High-degree Modes Using MDI Observations**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 772.2 (2013), 87. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 89.
- [Korzennik 2013] S. G. Korzennik. **Mode Frequencies from GONG, MDI, and HMI Data**. *Fifty Years of Seismology of the Sun and Stars*. Ed. by K. Jain, S. C. Tripathy, F. Hill, et al. 478. *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*. San Francisco: Astronomical Society of the Pacific, 2013, pp. 137–143. [URL]. Cited on page 73.
- [Korzennik 2017] S. G. Korzennik. **Initial Results from Fitting p-Modes Using Intensity Observations from the Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager**. *Solar Physics* 292 (2017), 138. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 89.
- [Kosovichev et al. 1997] A. G. Kosovichev, J. Schou, P. H. Scherrer, et al. **Structure and Rotation of the Solar Interior: Initial Results from the MDI Medium-L Program**. *Solar Physics* 170 (1997), pp. 43–61. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 17.
- [Kuiper 1938] G. P. Kuiper. **The Empirical Mass-Luminosity Relation**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 88 (1938), pp. 472–507. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [Kumar et al. 1988] P. Kumar, J. Franklin, and P. Goldreich. **Distribution functions for the time-averaged energies of stochastically excited solar p-modes**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 328 (1988), pp. 879–887. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 86.
- [Lamb 1909] H. Lamb. **On the Theory of Waves Propagated Vertically in the Atmosphere**. *Proceedings of the London Mathematical Society* s2-7.1 (1909), pp. 122–141. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 17.
- [Lavelly and Ritzwoller 1992] E. M. Lavelly and M. H. Ritzwoller. **The effect of global-scale, steady-state convection and elastic-gravitational asphericities on helioseismic oscillations**. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* 339.1655 (1992), pp. 431–496. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 7, 50, 94, 95, 97, 99, 104, 105, 106, 107, 108, 109, 112, 116, 117, 118, 120, 121, 139, 194, and 196.
- [Leeuwen 2007] F. van Leeuwen. **Validation of the new Hipparcos reduction**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 474.2 (2007), pp. 653–664. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 152.

- [Lefebvre et al. 2008] S. Lefebvre, R. A. García, S. J. Jiménez-Reyes, et al. **Variations of the solar granulation motions with height using the GOLF/SoHO experiment**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 490.3 (2008), pp. 1143–1149. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 61.
- [Leibacher 1999] J. W. Leibacher. **The Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG) project**. *Advances in Space Research* 24.2 (1999), pp. 173–176. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 75.
- [Leighton et al. 1962] R. B. Leighton, R. W. Noyes, and G. W. Simon. **Velocity Fields in the Solar Atmosphere. I. Preliminary Report**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 135 (1962), pp. 474–499. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 9.
- [Leighton 1964] R. B. Leighton. **Transport of Magnetic Fields on the Sun**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 140 (1964), pp. 1547–1562. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 43.
- [Leighton 1969] R. B. Leighton. **A Magneto-Kinematic Model of the Solar Cycle**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 156 (1969), pp. 1–26. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 43.
- [Lepine and Shara 2005] S. Lepine and M. M. Shara. **A Catalog of Northern Stars With Annual Proper Motions Larger Than 0.15" (LSPM catalog - North)**. *The Astronomical Journal* 129.3 (2005), pp. 1483–1522. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 152.
- [Libbrecht and Woodard 1990] K. G. Libbrecht and M. F. Woodard. **Solar-cycle effects on solar oscillation frequencies**. *Nature* 345.6278 (1990), pp. 779–782. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 6, 54, 67, 112, and 116.
- [Livingston et al. 2006] W. Livingston, J. W. Harvey, O. V. Malanushenko, and L. Webster. **Sunspots with the Strongest Magnetic Fields**. *Solar Physics* 239 (2006), pp. 41–68. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 36.
- [Lomb 1976] N. R. Lomb. **Least-squares frequency analysis of unequally spaced data**. *Astrophysics and Space Science* 39 (1976), pp. 447–462. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 23 and 55.
- [Lund et al. 2017] M. N. Lund, V. S. Aguirre, G. R. Davies, et al. **Standing on the Shoulders of Dwarfs: the Kepler Asteroseismic LEGACY Sample. I. Oscillation Mode Parameters**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 835.2 (2017), 172. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 145.
- [Lynden-Bell and Ostriker 1967] D. Lynden-Bell and J. P. J. Ostriker. **On the stability of differentially rotating bodies**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 136.3 (1967), pp. 293–310. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 106.
- [Marcy et al. 2014] G. W. Marcy, H. Isaacson, A. W. Howard, et al. **Masses, Radii, and Orbits of Small Kepler Planets: The Transition from Gaseous to Rocky Planets**. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 210.2 (2014), 20. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 152.
- [Mathis and Zahn 2004] S. Mathis and J.-P. Zahn. **Transport and mixing in the radiation zones of rotating stars. I. Hydrodynamical processes**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 425.1 (2004), pp. 229–242. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 195 and 196.
- [Mathis and Zahn 2005] S. Mathis and J.-P. Zahn. **Transport and mixing in the radiation zones of rotating stars. II. Axisymmetric magnetic field**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 440.2 (2005), pp. 653–666. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 93, 104, and 117.
- [Mathur et al. 2012] S. Mathur, T. S. Metcalfe, M. Woitaszek, et al. **A uniform asteroseismic analysis of 22 solar-type stars observed by Kepler**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 749.2 (2012), 152. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 17, 32, 55, and 151.
- [Mathur et al. 2014a] S. Mathur, R. A. García, J. Ballot, et al. **Magnetic activity of F stars observed by Kepler**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 562 (2014), A124. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 62, 68, 69, and 70.
- [Mathur et al. 2014b] S. Mathur, D. Salabert, R. A. García, and T. Ceillier. **Photometric magnetic-activity metrics tested with the Sun: application to Kepler M dwarfs**. *Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate* 4 (2014), A15. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.
- [Maunder 1894] E. W. Maunder. **A Prolonged Sunspot Minimum**. *Knowledge: An Illustrated Magazine of Science* 17 (1894), pp. 173–176. [URL]. Cited on page 37.

- [Mazumdar et al. 2014] A. Mazumdar, M. J. P. F. G. Monteiro, J. Ballot, et al. **Measurement of Acoustic Glitches in Solar-Type Stars from Oscillation Frequencies Observed by Kepler**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 782.1 (2014), 18. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [McQuillan et al. 2013] A. McQuillan, T. Mazeh, and S. Aigrain. **Stellar Rotation Periods of the Kepler Objects of Interest: A Dearth of Close-in Planets around Fast Rotators**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 775.1 (2013), L11. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 152.
- [McQuillan et al. 2014] A. McQuillan, T. Mazeh, and S. Aigrain. **Rotation Periods of 34,030 Kepler Main-Sequence Stars: The Full Autocorrelation Sample**. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 211.2 (2014), 24. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 32, 41, and 152.
- [Meibom et al. 2015] S. Meibom, S. A. Barnes, I. Platais, et al. **A spin-down clock for cool stars from observations of a 2.5-billion-year-old cluster**. *Nature* 517.7536 (2015), pp. 589–591. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 41.
- [Mestel and Moss 1977] L. Mestel and D. L. Moss. **Models of rotating magnetic stars**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 178.1 (1977), pp. 27–49. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 104 and 117.
- [Metcalf and Sadlers 2017] T. S. Metcalfe and J. van Sadlers. **Magnetic Evolution and the Disappearance of Sun-Like Activity Cycles**. *Solar Physics* 292 (2017), 126. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 41 and 45.
- [Metcalf et al. 2007] T. S. Metcalfe, W. A. Dziembowski, P. G. Judge, and M. Snow. **Asteroseismic signatures of stellar magnetic activity cycles**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society: Letters* 379.1 (2007), pp. L16–L20. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 63, 64, 71, 141, and 145.
- [Metcalf et al. 2009] T. S. Metcalfe, O. L. Creevey, and J. Christensen-Dalsgaard. **A Stellar Model-fitting Pipeline for Asteroseismic Data from the Kepler Mission**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 699.1 (2009), pp. 373–382. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [Metcalf et al. 2014] T. S. Metcalfe, O. L. Creevey, G. Dogan, et al. **Properties of 42 Solar-type Kepler Targets from the Asteroseismic Modeling Portal**. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 214.2 (2014), 27. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 17, 65, 68, and 151.
- [Meunier et al. 2008] N. Meunier, T. Roudier, and M. Rieutord. **Supergranules over the solar cycle**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 488.3 (2008), pp. 1109–1115. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 62.
- [Miesch and Teweldebirhan 2016] M. Miesch and K. Teweldebirhan. **A three-dimensional Babcock–Leighton solar dynamo model: Initial results with axisymmetric flows**. *Advances in Space Research* 58.8 (2016), pp. 1571–1588. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 5, 6, 112, and 116.
- [Miesch 2005] M. S. Miesch. **Large-Scale Dynamics of the Convection Zone and Tachocline**. *Living Reviews in Solar Physics* 2 (2005), 1. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 35.
- [Mitalas and Sills 1992] R. Mitalas and K. R. Sills. **On the photon diffusion time scale for the sun**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 401.2 (1992), pp. 759–760. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 28.
- [Molenda-Żakowicz et al. 2013] J. Molenda-Żakowicz, S. G. Sousa, A. Frasca, et al. **Atmospheric parameters of 169 F-, G-, K- and M-type stars in the Kepler field**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 434.2 (2013), pp. 1422–1434. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 33, 41, 65, 68, and 152.
- [Mosser and Appourchaux 2009] B. Mosser and T. Appourchaux. **On detecting the large separation in the autocorrelation of stellar oscillation times series**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 508.2 (2009), pp. 877–887. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 33.
- [Mosser et al. 2013] B. Mosser, E. Michel, K. Belkacem, et al. **Asymptotic and measured large frequency separations**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 550 (2013), A126. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 33 and 84.
- [Mueller et al. 2012] D. Mueller, R. G. Marsden, O. C. St. Cyr, et al. **Solar Orbiter: Exploring the Sun-heliosphere connection**. *Solar Physics* 285 (2012), pp. 25–70. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 30.
- [Muller et al. 2007] R. Muller, A. Hanslmeier, and M. Saldaña-Muñoz. **Variations of the granulation related to the solar cycle and with respect to its position on the solar disk**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 475.2 (2007), pp. 717–722. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 61.

- [Muller 1988] R. Muller. **Variability of solar granulation**. *Advances in Space Research* 8.7 (1988), pp. 159–167. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 38.
- [NASA] NASA. Space Place Webpage of NASA. [URL] (visited on 01/22/2018). Cited on page 29.
- [Nielsen et al. 2015] M. B. Nielsen, H. Schunker, L. Gizon, and W. H. Ball. **Constraining differential rotation of Sun-like stars from asteroseismic and starspot rotation periods**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 582 (2015), A10. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 32 and 104.
- [Nigam et al. 1998] R. Nigam, A. G. Kosovichev, P. H. Scherrer, and J. Schou. **Asymmetry in Velocity and Intensity Helioseismic Spectra: A Solution to a Long-standing Puzzle**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 495.2 (1998), pp. L115–L118. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 21 and 73.
- [Ohnaka et al. 2017] K. Ohnaka, G. Weigelt, and K.-H. Hofmann. **Vigorous atmospheric motion in the red supergiant star Antares**. *Nature* 548.7667 (2017), pp. 310–312. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 40.
- [Olivero and Longbothum 1977] J. Olivero and R. Longbothum. **Empirical fits to the Voigt line width: A brief review**. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer* 17.2 (1977), pp. 233–236. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 84.
- [Pallé et al. 1990] P. L. Pallé, C. Régulo, and T. Roca Cortés. **The spectrum of solar p-modes and the solar activity cycle**. *Progress of Seismology of the Sun and Stars*. Ed. by Y. Osaki and H. Shibahashi. 367. *Lecture Notes in Physics*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 1990, pp. 129–134. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 6, 54, and 61.
- [Parker 1955] E. N. Parker. **Hydromagnetic Dynamo Models**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 122 (1955), pp. 293–314. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 43.
- [Paxton et al. 2011] B. Paxton, L. Bildsten, A. Dotter, et al. **Modules for Experiments in Stellar Astrophysics (MESA)**. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 192.1 (2011), 3. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 14.
- [Pesnell et al. 2012] W. D. Pesnell, B. J. Thompson, and P. C. Chamberlin. **The Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO)**. *Solar Physics* 275 (2012), pp. 3–15. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 21.
- [Phinney and Burridge 1973] R. A. Phinney and R. Burridge. **Representation of the Elastic - Gravitational Excitation of a Spherical Earth Model by Generalized Spherical Harmonics**. *Geophysical Journal International* 34.4 (1973), pp. 451–487. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 178.
- [Pinsonneault et al. 2012] M. H. Pinsonneault, D. An, J. Molenda-Żakowicz, et al. **A Revised Effective Temperature Scale for the Kepler Input Catalog**. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 199.2 (2012), 30. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 152.
- [Pires et al. 2015] S. Pires, S. Mathur, R. A. García, et al. **Gap interpolation by inpainting methods: Application to ground and space-based asteroseismic data**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 574 (2015), A18. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 55.
- [Press et al. 2007] W. H. Press, S. A. Teukolsky, W. T. Vetterling, and B. P. Flannery. **Numerical recipes: The art of scientific computing**. 3rd ed. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2007. Cited on page 55.
- [Prialnik 2009] D. Prialnik. **An Introduction to the Theory of Stellar Structure and Evolution**. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009. Cited on pages 10 and 18.
- [Priest 2014] E. Priest. **Magnetohydrodynamics of the Sun**. 1st ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 30 and 43.
- [Régulo et al. 2016] C. Régulo, R. A. García, and J. Ballot. **Magnetic activity cycles in solar-like stars: The cross-correlation technique of p-mode frequency shifts**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 589 (2016), A103. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 48, 57, 67, and 141.
- [Racah 1942] G. Racah. **Theory of Complex Spectra. II**. *Physical Review* 62.9-10 (1942), pp. 438–462. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 180.
- [Radick et al. 1998] R. R. Radick, G. W. Lockwood, B. A. Skiff, and S. L. Baliunas. **Patterns of Variation among Sun-like Stars**. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 118.1 (1998), pp. 239–258. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.

- [Rauer et al. 2013] H. Rauer, C. Catala, C. Aerts, et al. **The PLATO 2.0 Mission**. *Experimental Astronomy* 38 (2013), pp. 249–330. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 48.
- [Regge 1958] T. Regge. **Symmetry properties of Clebsch-Gordon’s coefficients**. *Il Nuovo Cimento* 10.3 (1958), pp. 544–545. [DOI]. Cited on pages 120 and 180.
- [Reinhold and Arlt 2015] T. Reinhold and R. Arlt. **A method to discriminate solar and antisolar differential rotation in high-precision light curves**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 576 (2015), A15. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.
- [Reinhold et al. 2013] T. Reinhold, A. Reiners, and G. Basri. **Rotation and differential rotation of active Kepler stars**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 560 (2013), A4. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [Rempel 2006] M. Rempel. **Flux-transport dynamos with Lorentz force feedback on differential rotation and meridional flow: Saturation mechanism and torsional oscillations**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 647.1 (2006), pp. 662–675. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 39.
- [Ricker et al. 2014] G. R. Ricker, J. N. Winn, R. Vanderspek, et al. **Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite**. *Proceedings of the SPIE* 9143 (2014), 914320. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 48.
- [Rimmele et al. 1995] T. R. Rimmele, P. R. Goode, E. Harold, and R. T. Stebbins. **Dark lanes in granulation and the excitation of solar oscillations**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 444 (1995), pp. L119–L122. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 89.
- [Ritzwoller and Lively 1991] M. H. Ritzwoller and E. M. Lively. **A unified approach to the helioseismic forward and inverse problems of differential rotation**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 369 (1991), pp. 557–566. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 104.
- [Roša et al. 1995] D. Roša, R. Brajša, B. Vršnak, and H. Wöhl. **The Relation between the Synodic and Sidereal Rotation Period of the Sun**. *Solar Physics* 159 (1995), pp. 393–398. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 29.
- [Roettenbacher et al. 2013] R. M. Roettenbacher, J. D. Monnier, R. O. Harmon, et al. **Imaging starspot evolution on Kepler target KIC 5110407 using light curve inversion**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 767.1 (2013), 60. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.
- [Rogers et al. 1996] F. J. Rogers, F. J. Swenson, and C. A. Iglesias. **OPAL Equation-of-State Tables for Astrophysical Applications**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 456 (1996), pp. 902–908. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 31.
- [Romanowicz 2008] B. Romanowicz. **Using seismic waves to image Earth’s internal structure**. *Nature* 451.7176 (2008), pp. 266–268. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 9.
- [Roth and Stix 2003] M. Roth and M. Stix. **Time-dependent coupling of solar oscillations**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 405.2 (2003), pp. 779–786. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 62.
- [Roth and Stix 2008] M. Roth and M. Stix. **Meridional circulation and global solar oscillations**. *Solar Physics* 251 (2008), pp. 77–89. [DOI]. Cited on pages 104 and 112.
- [Roth 2002] M. Roth. **Kopplung globaler Eigenschwingungen der Sonne durch Konvektion**. PhD thesis. Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, 2002. [URL]. Cited on pages 7, 10, 94, 107, 108, 109, and 118.
- [Roxburgh and Vorontsov 2003] I. W. Roxburgh and S. V. Vorontsov. **The ratio of small to large separations of acoustic oscillations as a diagnostic of the interior of solar-like stars**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 411.2 (2003), pp. 215–220. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 26.
- [Roxburgh and Vorontsov 2006] I. W. Roxburgh and S. V. Vorontsov. **The autocorrelation function of stellar p-mode measurements and its diagnostic properties**. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 369.3 (2006), pp. 1491–1496. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 33.
- [Roxburgh 2005] I. W. Roxburgh. **The ratio of small to large separations of stellar p-modes**. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 434.2 (2005), pp. 665–669. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 26.

- [Saar and Brandenburg 1999] S. H. Saar and A. Brandenburg. **Time Evolution of the Magnetic Activity Cycle Period. II. Results for an Expanded Stellar Sample.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 524.1 (1999), pp. 295–310. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 54.
- [Saders et al. 2016] J. L. van Saders, T. Ceillier, T. S. Metcalfe, et al. **Weakened magnetic braking as the origin of anomalously rapid rotation in old field stars.** *Nature* 529.7585 (2016), pp. 181–184. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 41.
- [Sakurai and Napolitano 2014] J. J. Sakurai and J. J. Napolitano. **Modern Quantum Mechanics.** 2nd ed. Harlow, UK: Pearson Education Limited, 2014. Cited on pages 94, 96, and 119.
- [Salabert et al. 2011] D. Salabert, C. Régulo, J. Ballot, et al. **About the p-mode frequency shifts in HD 49933.** *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 530 (2011), A127. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 54, 68, and 70.
- [Salabert et al. 2015] D. Salabert, R. A. García, and S. Turck-Chièze. **Seismic sensitivity to sub-surface solar activity from 18 yr of GOLF/SoHO observations.** *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 578 (2015), A137. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 6, 54, 67, and 89.
- [Salabert et al. 2016a] D. Salabert, R. A. García, P. G. Beck, et al. **Photospheric and chromospheric magnetic activity of seismic solar analogs.** *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 596 (2016), A31. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 65 and 141.
- [Salabert et al. 2016b] D. Salabert, C. Régulo, R. A. García, et al. **Magnetic variability in the young solar analog KIC 10644253.** *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 589 (2016), A118. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 54, 62, 68, 70, 112, 116, and 136.
- [Santos et al. 2016] A. R. G. Santos, M. S. Cunha, P. P. Avelino, et al. **Starspot signature on the light curve: Learning about the latitudinal distribution of spots.** *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 599 (2016), A1. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 42.
- [Scargle 1982] J. D. Scargle. **Studies in astronomical time series analysis. II - Statistical aspects of spectral analysis of unevenly spaced data.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 263 (1982), pp. 835–853. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 23, 55, and 59.
- [Schad et al. 2011] A. Schad, J. Timmer, and M. Roth. **A Unified Approach to the Helioseismic Inversion Problem of the Solar Meridional Flow from Global Oscillations.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 734.2 (2011), 97. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 7, 21, 50, 104, 107, and 118.
- [Schad et al. 2013] A. Schad, J. Timmer, and M. Roth. **Global Helioseismic Evidence for a Deeply Penetrating Solar Meridional Flow Consisting of Multiple Flow Cells.** *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 778.2 (2013), L38. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 45, 104, 112, 116, 131, and 147.
- [Schad 2013] A. Schad. **A new approach for the global helioseismic investigation of the solar meridional flow.** PhD thesis. Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, 2013. Cited on pages 94, 100, 104, 107, 112, 118, and 119.
- [Schiff 1968] L. I. Schiff. **Quantum Mechanics.** 3rd ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1968. Cited on page 101.
- [Schou et al. 1998] J. Schou, H. M. Antia, S. Basu, et al. **Helioseismic Studies of Differential Rotation in the Solar Envelope by the Solar Oscillations Investigation Using the Michelson Doppler Imager.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 505.1 (1998), pp. 390–417. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 21 and 104.
- [Schou et al. 2012] J. Schou, P. H. Scherrer, R. I. Bush, et al. **Design and Ground Calibration of the Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager (HMI) Instrument on the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO).** *Solar Physics* 275 (2012), pp. 229–259. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 21.
- [Schrijver et al. 1989] C. J. Schrijver, J. Cote, C. Zwaan, and S. H. Saar. **Relations between the photospheric magnetic field and the emission from the outer atmospheres of cool stars. I - The solar CA II K line core emission.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 337 (1989), pp. 964–976. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 40.
- [Schwabe 1844] H. Schwabe. **Sonnen-Beobachtungen im Jahre 1843.** *Astronomische Nachrichten* 21.15 (1844), pp. 234–235. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 35.

- [Silva Aguirre et al. 2015] V. Silva Aguirre, G. R. Davies, S. Basu, et al. **Ages and fundamental properties of Kepler exoplanet host stars from asteroseismology.** *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 452.2 (2015), pp. 2127–2148. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 26 and 151.
- [Skumanich et al. 1975] A. Skumanich, C. Smythe, and E. N. Frazier. **On the statistical description of inhomogeneities in the quiet solar atmosphere. I - Linear regression analysis and absolute calibration of multichannel observations of the Ca⁺ emission network.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 200.1 (1975), pp. 747–764. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 40.
- [Skumanich 1972] A. Skumanich. **Time Scales for CaII Emission Decay, Rotational Braking, and Lithium Depletion.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 171 (1972), pp. 565–567. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 41, 54, 65, and 141.
- [Solanki et al. 2006] S. K. Solanki, B. Inhester, and M. Schüssler. **The solar magnetic field.** *Reports on Progress in Physics* 69.3 (2006), pp. 563–668. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 36 and 37.
- [Spiegel and Zahn 1992] E. A. Spiegel and J.-P. Zahn. **The solar tachocline.** *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 265.1 (1992), pp. 106–114. [URL]. Cited on page 28.
- [Stello et al. 2009] D. Stello, W. J. Chaplin, H. Bruntt, et al. **Radius Determination of Solar-Type Stars Using Asteroseismology: What to Expect From the Kepler Mission.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 700.2 (2009), pp. 1589–1602. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 32.
- [Stix 2002] M. Stix. **The Sun — An Introduction.** 2nd ed. *Astronomy and Astrophysics Library.* Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2002. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 28 and 30.
- [Sweet 1950] P. A. Sweet. **The Importance of Rotation in Stellar Evolution.** *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 110.6 (1950), pp. 548–558. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 120.
- [Tapping 2013] K. F. Tapping. **The 10.7 cm solar radio flux (F10.7).** *Space Weather* 11.7 (2013), pp. 394–406. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 77.
- [Tassoul 1980] M. Tassoul. **Asymptotic approximations for stellar nonradial pulsations.** *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 43 (1980), pp. 469–490. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 25, 26, and 32.
- [Toner et al. 2003] C. G. Toner, D. Haber, T. Corbard, et al. **An image merge for GONG+.** *Proceedings of SOHO 12 / GONG+ 2002. Local and global helioseismology: the present and future.* Ed. by H. Sawaya-Lacoste. 517. ESA Special Publication. Noordwijk, Netherlands: ESA Publications Division, 2003, pp. 405–407. [URL]. Cited on page 76.
- [Townsend and Teitler 2013] R. H. D. Townsend and S. Teitler. **GYRE: An open-source stellar oscillation code based on a new Magnus Multiple Shooting Scheme.** *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 435.4 (2013), pp. 3406–3418. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 10 and 14.
- [Unno et al. 1989] W. Unno, Y. Osaki, H. Ando, et al. **Nonradial oscillations of stars.** 2nd ed. Tokyo: University of Tokyo Press, 1989. Cited on pages 10, 13, 14, 105, and 107.
- [Usoskin 2017] I. G. Usoskin. **A history of solar activity over millennia.** *Living Reviews in Solar Physics* 14 (2017), 3. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 35 and 37.
- [Van Reeth et al. 2015] T. Van Reeth, A. Tkachenko, C. Aerts, et al. **Gravity-mode period spacings as seismic diagnostic for a sample of gamma Doradus stars from Kepler space photometry and high-resolution ground-based spectroscopy.** *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series* 218.2 (2015), 27. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 19.
- [Viani et al. 2017] L. S. Viani, S. Basu, W. J. Chaplin, et al. **Changing the ν_{\max} Scaling Relation: The Need For a Mean Molecular Weight Term.** *The Astrophysical Journal* 843.1 (2017), 11. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 33 and 84.
- [Vida et al. 2014] K. Vida, K. Oláh, and R. Szabó. **Looking for activity cycles in late-type Kepler stars using time-frequency analysis.** *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 441.3 (2014), pp. 2744–2753. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 54.

- [Weigert et al. 2009] A. Weigert, H. J. Wendker, and L. Wisotzki. **Astronomie und Astrophysik: Ein Grundkurs**. 5th ed. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH, 2009. Cited on page 32.
- [Whiting 1968] E. Whiting. **An empirical approximation to the Voigt profile**. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer* 8.6 (1968), pp. 1379–1384. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 84.
- [Wiśniewska et al. 2016] A. Wiśniewska, Z. E. Musielak, J. Staiger, and M. Roth. **Observational Evidence for Variations of the Acoustic Cutoff Frequency with Height in the Solar Atmosphere**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 819.2 (2016), L23. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 18.
- [Wilson 1968] O. C. Wilson. **Flux Measurements at the Centers of Stellar H- and K-Lines**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 153 (1968), pp. 221–234. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 40.
- [Wilson 1978] O. C. Wilson. **Chromospheric variations in main-sequence stars**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 226 (1978), pp. 379–396. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 54.
- [Woodard and Noyes 1985] M. F. Woodard and R. W. Noyes. **Change of solar oscillation eigenfrequencies with the solar cycle**. *Nature* 318.6045 (1985), pp. 449–450. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 6, 54, 112, and 116.
- [Woodhouse and Dahlen 1978] J. H. Woodhouse and F. A. Dahlen. **The Effect of A General Aspherical Perturbation on the Free Oscillations of the Earth**. *Geophysical Journal International* 53.2 (1978), pp. 335–354. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 120.
- [Woodhouse 1980] J. H. Woodhouse. **The coupling and attenuation of nearly resonant multiplets in the Earth’s free oscillation spectrum**. *Geophysical Journal International* 61.2 (1980), pp. 261–283. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 195.
- [Wright et al. 2011] N. J. Wright, J. J. Drake, E. E. Mamajek, and G. W. Henry. **The stellar-activity-rotation relationship and the evolution of stellar dynamos**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 743.1 (2011), 48. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 65.
- [Yoshimura 1975] H. Yoshimura. **Solar-cycle dynamo wave propagation**. *The Astrophysical Journal* 201 (1975), pp. 740–748. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on page 43.
- [Zhao et al. 2013] J. Zhao, R. S. Bogart, A. G. Kosovichev, et al. **Detection of Equatorward Meridional Flow and Evidence of Double-Cell Meridional Circulation inside the Sun**. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 774.2 (2013), L29. [DOI]. [URL]. Cited on pages 45 and 104.

Publications and Scientific Contributions

Refereed Publications

René Kiefer and Markus Roth: *The Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Solar Oscillation Frequencies*. [The Astrophysical Journal, Volume 854, Number 1, Article 74, 2018.](#)

René Kiefer, Ariane Schad, and Markus Roth: *The Direct Effect of Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Stellar Oscillations: An Analytical Expression for the General Matrix Element*. [The Astrophysical Journal, Volume 846, Number 2, Article 162, 2017.](#)

René Kiefer, Ariane Schad, Guy Davies, and Markus Roth: *Stellar magnetic activity and variability of oscillation parameters: An investigation of 24 solar-like stars observed by Kepler*. [Astronomy & Astrophysics, Volume 598, Article A77, 2017.](#)

René Kiefer, Ariane Schad, Wiebke Herzberg, and Markus Roth: *Determination of fundamental asteroseismic parameters using the Hilbert transform*. [Astronomy & Astrophysics, Volume 578, Article A56, 2015.](#)

J. Amaya, S. Musset, V. Andersson, A. Diercke, C. Höller, S. Iliev, L. Juhász, **R. Kiefer**, et al.: *The PAC2MAN mission: a new tool to understand and predict solar energetic events*. [Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate, Volume 5, Article A5, 2015.](#)

Scientific Contributions to Conferences and Workshops

Poster: *Forward Calculation of the Effect of Large-Scale Toroidal Magnetic Fields on Solar and Stellar Oscillations*. TESSting stellar astrophysics — TASC3/KASC10 Workshop. Birmingham, UK. July 2017.

Invited talk: *Signatures of magnetic activity in the oscillation parameters of solar-like stars observed by Kepler*. Asteroseismology of stellar activity cycles: From the Sun to the stars. Workshop. December 2016, Nice France.

Oral contribution: *Investigation of the frequency shifts of 24 solar-like stars observed by Kepler*. TASC2 & KASC9 Workshop — SPACEINN & HELAS8 Conference. Seismology of the Sun and the Distant Stars 2016 — Using Today's Successes to Prepare the Future. Angra do Heroísmo, Terceira, Açores, Portugal. July 2016. [[PDF](#)]

Poster: *The Envelope Spectrum*. Solarnet III/HELAS VII/SpaceInn Conference — The Sun, the stars, and solar-stellar relations. Freiburg, Germany. September 2015. [[PDF](#)]

Poster: *p-Mode Parameters and the Solar Cycle*. Solarnet III/HELAS VII/SpaceInn Conference — The Sun, the stars, and solar-stellar relations. Freiburg, Germany. September 2015. [[PDF](#)]

Poster: *Signatures of magnetic activity in the p-mode frequencies of solar-type stars observed by Kepler*. Solarnet III/HELAS VII/SpaceInn Conference — The Sun, the stars, and solar-stellar relations. Freiburg, Germany. September 2015. [[PDF](#)]

Poster: *Magnetic Fields and Solar Oscillations*. ESPM-14 — 14th European Solar Physics Meeting. Dublin, Ireland. September 2014.

Poster: *Magnetic Fields and Solar Oscillations*. HELAS VI — Helioseismology and Applications. Göttingen, Germany. September 2014.

Participation in Workshops and Summer Schools

Workshop: T'DA1 — TESS Data for Asteroseismology — From Pixels to Lightcurves. Workshop. Birmingham, UK. November 2016.

Summer School: IVth Azores International Advanced School in Space Sciences — Asteroseismology and Exoplanets: Listening to the Stars and Searching for New Worlds. Horta, Faial, Açores, Portugal. July 2016.

Stay abroad: National Solar Observatory, Tucson, Arizona. *Mobility of Young Researchers* grant of the SOLARNET network. Worked with Rudi Komm and Frank Hill on 20 years of GONG: p-Mode parameters and the Solar Cycle. April–June 2015.

Summer School: ESA Summer School Alpbach 2013 — Space Weather: Science, Missions and Systems. Alpbach, Austria. July 2013.

The significance of our lives and our fragile planet is then determined only by our own wisdom and courage. We are the custodians of life's meaning. We long for a parent to care for us, to forgive us our errors, to save us from our childish mistakes. But knowledge is preferable to ignorance. Better by far to embrace the hard truth than a reassuring fable. If we crave some cosmic purpose, then let us find ourselves a worthy goal.

—Carl Sagan